

Crazy Running Equality Expressions With Factorial and Square-Root¹

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Abstract

*In previous works [10]-citeta14, authors wrote equality expressions in terms of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1 or 9 to 0 separated by single or double equality signs. These expressions are based on the idea of **crazy representations** of natural numbers [1]. These equality expressions are based on basic operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence and triangular numbers** values. These types of equalities, we called as **crazy running equality expressions**. This work is revised and enlarged version of author's previous works [10, 11, 12], where we considered basic operations along with **factorial, square-root**. It is not possible to write all the natural numbers in terms of **crazy running equality expressions**. Only the possible numbers are written. The work is up to 6 digits.*

Contents

1	Crazy Representations	2
2	Crazy Running Expressions	3
2.1	Using Factorial and Square-Root	3
2.2	Running Expressions with Fibonacci Sequence	4
2.3	Running Expressions with Triangular Numbers	5
3	Double Equalities Running Expressions	6
4	Single Equality Running Expressions	11
4.1	Single Digit Results	11
4.2	Two Digits Results	22
4.3	Three Digits Numbers	87
4.4	Four Digits Numbers	244
4.5	Five Digits Numbers	336
4.6	Six Digits Numbers	404

¹It is revised and enlarged version of author's previous works [10, 11, 12]

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1 Crazy Representations

In 2014, author [1] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See examples below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 100 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 101 &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 102 &:= 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 103 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\
 104 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 105 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 106 &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 107 &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 108 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 999 &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321 \\
 2535 &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
 2607 &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 = 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
 10958 &:= 12 \times 3 + \sqrt{4} + 5! \times (67 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}) = (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 65 + 4) \times 3 - 2 + 1 \\
 11807 &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 = -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1
 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that the number 10958 is the only number among 0 to 11111, where we need extra operations, such as **square-root**, **factorial**, etc. to write in increasing case. Extension of numbers from 11112 to 30000 refer [2, 3, 4].

Recently author [5, 6, 7, 8] wrote the crazy representations of natural numbers using only **factorial** up to 100.000. Below are few examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 39915 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! + 5 - 6! + 7 + 8! - 9 = 9 + 8 \times (7! - 6) + 5 - (4! + 3!)/2 + 1 \\
 39916 &:= 1 + (2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5! + (6! - 7!)/8 - 9 = 9 + 8! - 7 + (6 - 5! + 4! - 3!)/2 - 1 \\
 39917 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 + 6! \times 7/8 - 9 = (9 + 8!/7) \times 6 + 5! + (4! \times 3)^2 - 1 \\
 39918 &:= 1 + (2 + 3!)! - 4^5 + 6! \times 7/8 - 9 = 9 + 8! + 7!/6 - 5^{4!/3!} \times 2 - 1 \\
 59997 &:= (1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5!)) - 6 \times 7 - 8!/9 = 9 \times 8 \times 7!/6 - 5! - 4 - 3!!/2 + 1 \\
 59998 &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3! - 4) \times (5^6 - 7!/8) + 9) = 9 + 8! + (7! + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3!^2 + 1 \\
 59999 &:= 1 + 2 \times ((3! - 4) \times (5^6 - 7!/8) + 9) = 9 + 8! + (7 \times 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3^2 - 1 \\
 60000 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5!/6 + 7 \times 8!/9 = 9 \times (8! - 7!)/6 + 5! \times ((4! + 3!) \times 2 - 1) \\
 71051 &:= 1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7!/8 - 9) = 9 \times (8! - 7!/6)/5 + 4! - 3!^2 - 1 \\
 71052 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + (5! - 6! + 7!) \times 8) - 9 = 9 + 8! + 7! \times 6 + 5! + 4 + 3!!/2 - 1 \\
 71053 &:= 1 - 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 \times 6! - 7!/8 - 9) = 9 \times (8! - 7!/6)/5 + 4! - 3!^2 + 1 \\
 71054 &:= (1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7!/8 - 9) = 9 + 8! + 7! \times 6 + 5! + 4 + 3!!/2 + 1 \\
 99997 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3! + 4! + (5! + 6!) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) = 9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times 5! + 4 \times (3!^2 + 1) \\
 99998 &:= 1 - 2 + (3! + 4)^5 - (-6 + 7 + 8 - 9)! = (9 + 8) \times (7! - 6) + 5 \times 4 \times (3!! + 2 - 1) \\
 99999 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3! + 4)^5 + 6 + (7 - 8) \times 9 = 9 + 8! - 7! - (6 - 5! + 4!) \times (3!! - 2 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{100000} := (1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5) \times 6) \times 7 + 8! - 9 = 9 \times 8 - 7 - 6!/5 \times (4! - 3!! + 2) - 1$$

Summary of this work and videos and work done by others in this direction can be seen in author's website [9]

2 Crazy Running Expressions

Previous section give an idea how we can write natural numbers using only 9 digits from 1 to 9 or 9 to 1 with basic operations and factorial. This section extend the idea of previous section, but in little different way. The the numbers are written in such a way that there are single or double equality signs using the digits from 1 to 9 in the increasing case and 9 to 1 or 0 in the decreasing case. This section brings running expressions for crazy representations in different ways, i.e., using basic operations along with factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence values and triangular numbers. These are divided in different subsections.

2.1 Using Factorial and Square-Root

Below are few examples of running expressions, written in increasing and decreasing orders using factorial and square-root:

- **Increasing Order**

$$\mathbf{12} = 3 + 4 + (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8)/9$$

$$\mathbf{123} = 4 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 \times 9$$

$$\mathbf{1234} = -5 + 6! + 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$12 + 3 \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) = \mathbf{89}$$

$$1 + 23 + 45 + 6! = \mathbf{789}$$

... (1)

- **Decreasing Order**

$$98 - 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3) = \mathbf{21}$$

$$\sqrt{9} \times 87 + 6 + 54 = \mathbf{321}$$

$$9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! = \mathbf{4321}$$

$$9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 - 3 + 2 = \mathbf{10}$$

$$9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4^3 = \mathbf{210}$$

$$(9 - 87 + 6!) \times 5! / 4! = \mathbf{3210}$$

$$\mathbf{98} = (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times 3 + 21$$

$$\mathbf{987} = 6! + 5! + (4 + 3) \times 21$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98 &= 7 + 65 + 4 + 32 - 10 \\ 987 &= 6! + 54 + 3 + 210 \\ &\dots \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

Above examples give representations separated by equality sign having the digits in either increasing and/or decreasing orders. There are numbers that can be written in increasing as well as decreasing orders at the same time with single or double equality signs, such as

$$\begin{aligned} 16 &:= 12/3 \times 4 &= 5 + 6 + (7 + 8)/\sqrt{9} \\ &:= (9 + 87)/6 &= 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ \\ 18 &:= 12 + 3! &= \sqrt{4 + 5} \times 6 &= 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9} \\ &:= \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 &= \sqrt{6 \times 54} &= -3 + 21 &= 3! + 2 + 10 \\ \\ 120 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3)! &= 4 \times 5 \times 6 &= ((7 + 8)/\sqrt{9})! \\ &:= ((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7)! &= 6 \times 5 \times 4 &= (3 \times 2 - 1)! &= 3! \times 2 \times 10 \\ &\dots \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

The above three examples divide the numbers in two and three parts respectively with equality signs using the numbers in increasing as well as decreasing orders. From the examples (1), (2) and (3), we observe that the operations used are **addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, potentiation, factorial** and **square-root**. More details can be seen in [10, 11, 12].

2.2 Running Expressions with Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in the literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n + 1) = F(n) + F(n - 1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Similar to expressions (1) and (2), given above, below are examples of running expressions using **Fibonacci sequence** numbers. Most of the results uses basic operations, except numbers 21 and 9876, where extra operation, such as factorial is used.

- **Increasing Order**

$$\begin{aligned} 12 &= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 123 &= -4 \times 5 \times (6 - F(7)) - 8 - 9 \\ 1234 &= 5 \times F(6) \times F(7) + F(8) \times F(9) \\ \\ 1 + F(2^3 + F(4)) + (5 - 6)^7 &= 89 \\ 1 \times 2 \times 3^4 \times 5 - F(F(6)) &= 789 \\ 1 + 23 + F(4 \times 5) &= 6789. \end{aligned}$$

• **Decreasing Order**

$$9 + (-F(8)/7 + 6) \times 5 - F(4)! + 3 = \mathbf{21}$$

$$-98 - F(7) + F(6) \times 54 = \mathbf{321}$$

$$(F(9) \times F(8) + 7) \times 6 - 5 = \mathbf{4321}$$

$$\mathbf{98} = (7 - 6) \times 5 + F(4) \times (32 - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{987} = (6 - 5) \times F(4 \times (3 + 2 - 1))$$

$$\mathbf{98} = -5 - 4 - 3 + 2 \times F(10)$$

$$\mathbf{987} = (6 - 5)^4 \times F(3 \times 2 + 10)$$

$$\mathbf{9876} = (\sqrt{5+4})! + F(F(3!) \times 2) \times 10$$

More details can be seen in author's work [13].

2.3 Running Expressions with Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. These are given by

$$1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, \dots$$

The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2)$$

The letter "C" represents as "**binomial coefficient**".

In this paper our aim is to bring **running expressions** by use of **triangle numbers**. This we have done in subsequent sections. Due to high quantity of numbers, we the work is limited to 3 digits in case of single equality. As a part of results, see below some interesting examples,

• **Increasing Order**

$$\mathbf{12} = T(3) - 4 - 5 + 6 - (7 - 8) \times 9$$

$$\mathbf{123} = (-4 + 5) \times 6 + T(7) + 89$$

$$\mathbf{1234} = T(56 \times 7/8) + 9$$

$$1 + 2 + T(3) \times 4 - 5 + 67 = \mathbf{89}$$

$$1 + 2 + T(3) + T(45 - 6) = \mathbf{789}$$

$$-1 - 2 + T(3) + T(-4 + T(T(5))) = \mathbf{6789}.$$

• **Decreasing Order**

$$9 \times 8 - T(7) - T(6) + 5 - 4 - 3 = \mathbf{21}$$

$$T(9+8) - 7 \times 6 + T(5 \times 4) = \mathbf{321}$$

$$(-T(9) + T(T(8))) \times 7 - T(6) - 5 = \mathbf{4321}$$

$$\mathbf{98} = (7 - 6) \times 5^4 - T(32) + 1$$

$$\mathbf{987} = T(6) \times (5 \times T(4) - 3) \times (2 - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{9876} = T(5 \times T(4+3)) + T(2+1)$$

$$\mathbf{98} = (7 - 6) \times T(5) - 4 + 32 + T(10)$$

$$\mathbf{987} = (6 - 5) \times 4 \times (T(T(T(3)))) + 2 + T(10)$$

$$\mathbf{9876} = (-5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(3) + T(T(-2 + 10))$$

$$9 \times 8 - T(7) - T(6) - T(5) - 4 + 3 \times 2 = \mathbf{10}$$

$$T(9) + 87 \times (6 - 5) + T(4 \times 3) = \mathbf{210}$$

$$T(9) + 8 + 7 + T(6) \times T(5) \times T(4) = \mathbf{3210}$$

More details can be seen in author's work [14].

3 Double Equalities Running Expressions

In this section, we shall give equalities among the expressions divided em three parts i.e., seperated by double equality expressions in increasing as well as decreasing orders. The work is by use of factorial and square-root.

• **1**

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{23} = (4 - 5)^6 = (-7 + 8)^9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 = (6 - 5)^4 = 3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$= (3 - 2)^{10}$$

• **2**

$$\blacktriangleright 12/3! = \sqrt{4} \times (-5 + 6) = 7 - 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 = 6/\sqrt{5+4} = 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$= 3 - (21 \times 0)!$$

• **3**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 2) \times 3 = 4 + 5 - 6 = (-7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) = 6 - \sqrt{5+4} = 3 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$= 3 + 21 \times 0$$

• 4

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12/3 &= 4 \times (-5+6) = -7+8+\sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9}+8-7 &= (6-5) \times 4 = 3+2-1 \\ &= \sqrt{3 \times 2+10} \end{aligned}$$

• 5

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2+3 &= 4-5+6 = (7+8)/\sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!-8+7 &= 6-5+4 = 3 \times 2-1 \end{aligned}$$

• 6

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3 &= (4+5-6)! = 7+8-9 \\ \blacktriangleright -9+8+7 &= 6 \times (5-4) \\ &= 3 \times 2 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 7

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1+2 \times 3 &= -4+5+6 = 7 \times (-8+9) \\ \blacktriangleright (9-8) \times 7 &= 6+5-4 = 3 \times 2+1 \end{aligned}$$

• 8

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^3 &= \sqrt{4+\sqrt{5 \times 6}} = 7-8+9 \\ \blacktriangleright 9-8+7 &= \sqrt{6!/5-4} = 3^2-1 \end{aligned}$$

• 9

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12-3 &= \sqrt{4+5}+6 = \sqrt{78+\sqrt{9}} \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8-7) &= 6+\sqrt{5+4} = 3^2 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 10

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9+8-7 &= 6!/5!+4 = 3^2+1 \\ &= (3-2) \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 11

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9}+8!/7! &= 6+\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} = 3! \times 2-1 \\ &= 3-2+10 \end{aligned}$$

• 12

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3! &= (\sqrt{4+5})!+6 = 7+8-\sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9}+8+7 &= 6+(\sqrt{5+4})! = 3! \times 2 \times 1 \\ &= (3+2)!/10 \end{aligned}$$

• **13**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 3! = \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 = 78 / (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})! + 7 = 6 + 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3! \times 2 + 1 \\ = 3!/2 + 10$$

• **14**

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 = -6 + 5 \times 4 = 3! - 2 + 10$$

• **16**

$$\blacktriangleright 9!/8! + 7 = 6 + 5 \times \sqrt{4} = 3 \times 2 + 10$$

• **18**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3! = \sqrt{4+5} \times 6 = 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 = \sqrt{6 \times 54} = -3 + 21 \\ = 3! + 2 + 10$$

• **24**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 = 4 + 5!/6 = 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 = (6 - 5) \times 4! = 3 + 21$$

• **31**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 = 6 + \sqrt{5^4} = 32 - 1$$

• **35**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 = 6 + 5 + 4! = (3!)^2 - 1 \\ = 3 + \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **42**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})! \times 7 = 6 \times (5 + \sqrt{4}) = 32 + 10$$

• **48**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / (8 + 7) = -6 + 54 = 3! \times (-2 + 10)$$

• **63**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! / (8!/7) = 65 - \sqrt{4} = 3 \times 21$$

• **64**

$$\blacktriangleright (9! - 8!) / 7! = \sqrt{6! \times 5} + 4 = 32 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **72**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! = \sqrt{4! + 5!} \times 6 = 78 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7! = 6!/(5 \times \sqrt{4}) = 3! \times (2 + 10)$$

• **80**

$$\blacktriangleright (9! + 8!)/7! = 6!/(5 + 4) = (3! + 2) \times 10$$

• **90**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 87 = -6 + 5! - 4! = 3^2 \times 10$$

• **120**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 + 3)! = 4 \times 5 \times 6 = ((7 + 8)/\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7)! = 6 \times 5 \times 4 = (3 \times 2 - 1)! \\ = 3! \times 2 \times 10$$

• **240**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{(9! + 8!)/7} = 6! - 5! \times 4 = 3!!/(2 + 1)$$

• **719**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 \times 3)! = 4 - 5 + 6! = 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 = 6! - 5 + 4 = (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

• **720**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! = 4! \times 5 \times 6 = (-9 + 8 + 7)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (7 + 8 - 9)! = 6 \times 5 \times 4! = (3 \times 2)! \times 1$$

• **721**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)! = -4 + 5 + 6! = -7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7 = 6! + 5 - 4 = (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

• **727**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})!! + 7 = 6! + 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3!! + (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• **840**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 7 = 6! + 5 \times 4! = 3!! + ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• **4320**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9!/8!})!! + 7! = 6 \times (\sqrt{5 + 4})!! = 3!! \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **5040**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3)! = (-4 + 5 + 6)! = 7! \times (-8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7! = (6 + 5 - 4)! = (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

• **5046**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})! + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! = 3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$$

• **5760**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8!/7! = 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! = 3!! \times (-2 + 10)$$

• **15120**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9!/8!} \times 7! = 6! + 5!^{\sqrt{4}} = 3!! \times 21$$

• **17280**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 = 6 \times 5! \times 4! = 3!! \times (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• **30240**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9!/8!!} \times 7! = 6 \times (5 + \sqrt{4})! = 3! \times ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$$

• **40320**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! = \sqrt{4 + \sqrt{5 \times 6!!}} = (7 - 8 + 9)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)! = (\sqrt{6!/5} - 4)! = (3^2 - 1)!$$

• **279936**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!!})^7 = 6^{5+\sqrt{4}} = 3!^{(2+1)!+0!}$$

• **362880**

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3)! = (\sqrt{4 + 5} + 6)! = 7! \times 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! \times (8 - 7) = (6 + \sqrt{5 + 4})! = (3^2 \times 1)!$$

4 Single Equality Running Expressions

This work is extended and revised version of author previous works [10, 11, 12]. These results are given in following subsections.

4.1 Single Digit Results

• 0

- ▶ $1 + 2 - 3 = 4 \times (56/7 - 8) \times 9$
- ▶ $12/3 - 4 = 5 + 67 - 8 \times 9$
- ▶ $12 - 3 - 4 - 5 = 6 - 7 - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $9 - 8 - 7 + 6 = (5 - 4)^{32} - 1 = 54321 \times 0$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 - 7 - 65 = 4 - 3 - 2 + 1 = 4321 \times 0$
- ▶ $98/7 + 6 - 5 \times 4 = 3 - 2 - 1 = 321 \times 0$
- ▶ $9 \times (8 - 7 - 6 + 5) \times 43 = 21 \times 0$

• 1

- ▶ $1 = (-2 + 3)^{456789}$
- ▶ $1^2 = (-3 + 4)^{56789}$
- ▶ $1^{23} = (-4 + 5)^{6789}$
- ▶ $1^{234} = (5 + 67)/(8 \times 9)$
- ▶ $1^{2345} = (-6 + 7)^{89}$
- ▶ $1^{23456} = (-7 + 8)^9$
- ▶ $1^{234567} = (-8 + 9)$
- ▶ $9 - 8 = (7 - 6)^{54321} = (7 - 6)^{543210}$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^{7654} = 3 - 2 \times 1 = (3 - 2)^{10}$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^{76543} = 2 - 1 = (2 - 1)^0$

• 1:

- ▶ $(9 - 8)^7 = 65 - 43 - 21$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^7 = 6 - 5 \times 43 + 210$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^7 = (654321 \times 0)!$

• 1:

- ▶ $(9 - 8)^{76} = (5 - 4)^{321}$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^{76} = (5 - 4)^{3210}$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^{76} = (54321 \times 0)!$

• 1:

- ▶ $(9-8)^{765} = (4-3)^{21}$
- ▶ $(9-8)^{765} = (4-3)^{210}$
- ▶ $(9-8)^{765} = (4321 \times 0)!$

• 1:

- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) \times 7 \times 6 - 5 - (4! + 3!)/2 = 1$
- ▶ $-(9-8)^{76543} + 2 = 1$

• 2

- ▶ $1+2+3-4=5+6+(7-8) \times 9$
- ▶ $1^{234}-5+6=7-8+\sqrt{9}$

• 2:

- ▶ $1-2+3=45-6 \times 7+8-9$
- ▶ $12/3! = 45-6 \times 7+8-9$
 $= (-4-56+78)/9$

• 2:

- ▶ $1^{23}-4+5=-6+7-8+9$
- ▶ $1^{23}-4+5=6+7-8-\sqrt{9}$

• 2:

- ▶ $9-8+7-6=5 \times 4+3-21$
- ▶ $9-8+7-6=(54/3+2)/10$

• 2:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 87 - 6 - 5^4 = 98 - 76 - 5 \times 4 = 3 - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 87 - 6 - 5^4 = 98 - 76 - 5 \times 4 = -3! - 2 + 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 87 - 6 - 5^4 = 98 - 76 - 5 \times 4 = 3 - (21 \times 0)!$

• 2:

- ▶ $9 - 8 + (7 - 6)^5 = (4 - 3) \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + (7 - 6)^5 = 4 \times (3 + 2) / 10$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + (7 - 6)^5 = 4! - 32 + 10$

• 2:

- ▶ $9 + 8 + 7 - 65 + 43 = 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9} - 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^3 = 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 - 6! - 5 - 4! + 3!! = 2 \times 1$
 $1 \times 2 = 34 - 56 + 7 + 8 + 9$

• 2:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 = (6 - 5)^{432} + 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 = 6 \times 5 - 4 - 3 - 21$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 = (65 - 43 - 2) / 10$

• 3

▶ $1 \times 23 - 4 \times 5 = 6 \times (7 - 8) + 9$

▶ $12 / (34 - 5 \times 6) = \sqrt{\sqrt{78 + \sqrt{9}}}$

• 3:

- ▶ $1^2 \times 3 = 4 + (5 - 6)^{789}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{12 - 3} = 4 + (5 - 6)^{789}$
 $= 4 - (5 + 67) / (8 \times 9)$

• 3:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 3 - 4 = -5 + (-6 + 78)/9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{12 \times 3/4} = -5 + (-6 + 78)/9$$

• 3:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7) - 6 = -54/3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7) - 6 = (5 + 4)/3 + 21 \times 0$$

• 3:

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 - 6 - 5 = 4 - 3 + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 - 6 - 5 = 4 - (3 - 2)^{10}$$

• 3:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 \times 5/4 = 3 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 \times 5/4 = 3 + 21 \times 0$$

• 3:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^{7654} \times 3 = 2 + 1$$

$$1 + 2 = 3 + 4 \times (56/7 - 8) \times 9$$

• 3:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 34 - 5 - 678 = \sqrt{9}$$

$$\sqrt{9} = -8!/7! - 6! + 5 \times \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

$$\sqrt{9} = (8 - 7) \times 6 \times 54 - 321$$

$$\sqrt{9} = (8 - 7) \times \sqrt{6 \times 54} - 3 - 2 - 10$$

• 4

- ▶ $12/3 = 4 \times (-5 + 6)^{789}$
- ▶ $1^{23} \times 4 = 5 + (6 - 7)^{89}$
- ▶ $(12 + 3) \times 4 - 56 = -7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $98 - 76 - 54/3 = 2 + 1 + 0!$

• 4:

- ▶ $(9 + 8 + 7)/6 = 5 - (4 - 3)^{21}$
- ▶ $(9 + 8 + 7)/6 = 54 - (3 + 2) \times 10$

• 4:

- ▶ $(98/7 + 6)/5 = 4 \times (3 - 2 \times 1)$
- ▶ $(98/7 + 6)/5 = 4 + 321 \times 0$

• 4:

- ▶ $12 \times 3/4 - 5 = -6 - 7 + 8 + 9$
- ▶ $12 \times 3/4 - 5 = 6 - 7 + 8 - \sqrt{9}$

• 4:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 = 65 + \sqrt{4} - 3 \times 21$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 = -6! + 5 - \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 = 6 \times 54 - 32 \times 10$

• 4:

- ▶ $(9 - 8)^{765} \times 4 = 3 + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^{765} \times 4 = -3 \times 2 + 10$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^{765} \times 4 = \sqrt{3 \times 2 + 10}$

• 4:

$$\blacktriangleright 9+8-7-6=5-(4-3)^{21}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9+8-7-6=5-(4321 \times 0)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9+8-7-6=5-(4-3)^{210}$$

• 5

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3 = (45 + 67) / 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{234} \times 5 = -67 + 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{234} + 5 + 6 - 7 = 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^{765} + 4 = 3 \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 - 5 - 4 \times 3 = (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• 5:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 - 4 = 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{23} + 4 = 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 + 9$$

• 5:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 2)^{345} + 6 = (7 + 8) / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1^{2345} + 6 = (7 + 8) / \sqrt{9}$$

• 5:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 = 7 - (6 - 5)^{432} + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 = 7 - 65 + 43 + 2 \times 10$$

• 5:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 = 6 - (5 - 4)^{321}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 = 6 - (54321 \times 0)!$$

• 5:

$$\blacktriangleright -(9-8)^7 + 6 = 5 \times (4-3)^{21}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9-8)^7 + 6 = 5 + 4321 \times 0$$

• 5:

$$\blacktriangleright (9-8)^{76} \times 5 = 4 + 3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9-8)^{76} \times 5 = 4 + (3-2)^{10}$$

• 6

$$\blacktriangleright (1+23)/4 = 5 - (6-7)^{89}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + (7-6 \times 5) \times 4 = 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

• 6:

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{2345} \times 6 = 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (\sqrt{2+34})! + 5 - 6! = 7 + 8 - 9$$

• 6:

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! = -34 - 56 + 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! = 345 - 6 \times 7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 6:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3 = (45 - 6 + 7 + 8)/9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{12 \times 3} = (45 - 6 + 7 + 8)/9 \\ = 4 + 5 + 6 + (7 - 8) \times 9$$

• 6:

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{234} + 5 = (6 \times (7 - 8) + 9)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{234} + 5 = 6 \times (-7 + 8)^9$$

• 6:

$$\triangleright 1^{2345} \times 6 = 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$\triangleright 1 + (\sqrt{2+34})! + 5 - 6! = 7 + 8 - 9$$

• 6:

$$\triangleright (9 - 8 + 76 - 5) / (4 \times 3) = (2 + 1)!$$

$$\triangleright -\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) - 6! + (5 + 4)^3 = (2 + 1)!$$

• 6:

$$\triangleright -9 + 8 + 7 = 6 \times (5 - 4)^{321}$$

$$\triangleright -9 + 8 + 7 = 65 + 4 - 3 \times 21$$

$$\triangleright -9 + 8 + 7 = 6 \times (5 - 4) + 321 \times 0$$

$$\triangleright -9 + 8 + 7 = 6 + 54321 \times 0$$

• 6:

$$\triangleright (9 - 8)^{76} + 5 = (9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 + 5 = 4 \times 3 / 2 \times 1$$

$$\triangleright (9 - 8)^{76} + 5 = (9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 + 5 = \sqrt{4 + 32} \times 1$$

$$\triangleright (9 - 8)^{76} + 5 = (9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 + 5 = 4! + 3 - 21$$

$$\triangleright (9 - 8)^{76} + 5 = (9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 + 5 = 4 + 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\triangleright (9 - 8)^{76} + 5 = (9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 + 5 = 4 - 3! - 2 + 10$$

$$\triangleright (9 - 8)^{76} + 5 = (9 - 8) \times 7 - 6 + 5 = 4 + 3 - (21 \times 0)!$$

• 6:

$$\triangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 = 5 + (4 - 3)^{21}$$

$$\triangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 = (54 + 3 \times 2) / 10$$

$$\triangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 = 54 / 3 - 2 - 10$$

• 6:

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)^{3!} - 45 - 678 = (\sqrt{9})! = -876 + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3! \times 21$$

• 7

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 3 = -45 + 6 \times 78/9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{2345} + 6 = 7 \times (-8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 - 87)/6 - 5 - 4 + 3 = (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• 7:

$$\blacktriangleright (1^2 + 34)/5 = 6 + (-7 + 8)^9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{12/3 + 45} = 6 + (-7 + 8)^9$$

• 7:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 = 6 + (5 - 4)^{321}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 = 6 + (54321 \times 0)!$$

• 7:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 = 4 \times 3/2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 - (7 + 6) \times 5 = 4 \times 3/2 + 1$$

• 7:

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + 7)/(6 + 5 + 4) = 3 \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 + 6 - 54 = 3 \times 2 + 1$$

• 7:

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times 3 + 4 = 56/(7 - 8 + 9) = 56/7 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 - \sqrt{4} = 56/(7 - 8 + 9) = 56/7 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + \sqrt{2 + 34} = 56/(7 - 8 + 9) = 56/7 + 8 - 9$$

• 7:

- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7 \times (6-5) = 4 \times 3/2 + 1$
- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7 \times (6-5) = \sqrt{4+32} + 1$
- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7 \times (6-5) = 4 + 3 + 21 \times 0$

• 7:

- ▶ $(9-8)^7 + 6 = 54/3^2 + 1$
- ▶ $(9-8)^7 + 6 = 5 + 4 - 3 + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(9-8)^7 + 6 = 5 + 4! - 32 + 10$
- ▶ $(9-8)^7 + 6 = -5 \times (4-3) + 2 + 10$

• 8

- ▶ $12 - 3 + 4 - 5 = (-6 + 78)/9$
- ▶ $12 - 34 + 5 \times 6 = 7 - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! + 6! = 5!/4 - 32 + 10$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 76 - 5 - 4^3 = -2 + 10$

• 8:

- ▶ $1 \times 2^3 = (4 \times 56/7 - 8)/\sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $1 \times 2^3 = (4-5) \times (6-78)/9$

• 8:

- ▶ $12/3 + 4 = 5 + 6 \times (7-8) + 9$
- ▶ $12/3 + 4 = 56/7 \times (-8+9)$

• 8:

- ▶ $9 - (8-7)^{654} = 3^2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 - (8-7)^{654} = -\sqrt{3!} - 2 + 10$

• 8:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 \times 76 + 5^4 = 3^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 \times 76 + 5^4 = -\sqrt{3! - 2} + 10$$

• 8:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 = 654/3 - 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 = 6 \times 5 - 43 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 = 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 = 6 + (54/3 + 2)/10$$

• 8:

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 - 6 = 54/(3 \times 2) - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 - 6 = (5 - 4) \times 3^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 - 6 = 54/(3 \times 2) - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 - 6 = 5 + 4 + 3^2 - 10$$

• 8:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - (8 - 7)^{65} = 4 + 3 + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - (8 - 7)^{65} = \sqrt{43 + 21}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - (8 - 7)^{65} = 4 - 3 \times 2 + 10$$

• 9

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 - 4 \times 5 + 6 = \sqrt{78 + \sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5^4 = 3^2 \times 1$$

• 9:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12 - 3 \times (4 - 5)^{678} &= 9 \\ \blacktriangleright -12 \times 3 + 45 \times (-6 + 7)^8 &= 9 \\ \blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{12 \times 3 + 45} \right) \times (-6 + 7)^8 &= 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 - 4 \times 5 + 6 \times (-7 + 8) &= 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 12 \times 3/4 - 56/7 + 8 &= 9 \\ &9 = (8 - 7) \times 6 - 54/3 + 21 \\ &9 = (8 - 7)^6 \times 54 / (3 + 2 + 1) \\ &9 = (8 - 7)^6 \times 54 / (3 \times 2 \times 1) \\ &9 = (8 - 7)^{65} \times 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\ &9 = (8 - 7)^{654} \times 3^2 \times 1 \\ &9 = (8 - 7) \times 65 + 4 - 3 \times 2 \times 10 \\ &9 = (8 - 7) \times 65 - (4 + 3) \times (-2 + 10) \\ &9 = (8 - 7)^6 \times 5 + 4 + 321 \times 0 \\ &9 = (8 - 7)^{65} \times 4 - 3 - 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

4.2 Two Digits Results

• 10

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12 - 3! + 4 &= 5 - 67 + 8 \times 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 12 - 3 - 4 + 5 &= 6 \times (7 + 8) / 9 \\ \blacktriangleright -12 - 34 + 56 &= -7 + 8 + 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + 8 - 7 &= 6 - 5 - 4 \times 3 + 21 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + (8 - 7)^6 &= 54 / (3 \times 2) + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + (8 - 7)^{654} &= 3^2 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 10:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3 + 4 &= 5 - 67 + 8 \times 9 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{12 \times 3} + 4 &= 5 - 67 + 8 \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

• 10:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 + (8 - 7)^{65} &= 4 \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 + 65 &= 4 \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\ &= 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 10:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7 + 65 - 43 - 2 = 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - (8 - 7)^6 + 54/3 + 2 = 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - (8 - 7)^{65} + 4 \times (3 + 2) = 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8 - 7)^{654} \times (3 - 2) = 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (87 - 6) - 5! + 4 - 3!!/2 = 10$$

• 11

$$\blacktriangleright 12/3 \times 4 - 5 = 6 + (7 + 8)/\sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8!/7! = (65 - 43)/2 \times 1$$

• 11:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3! = \sqrt{45 - 6 - 7 + 89}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3! = 4! + 56 - 78 + 9$$

• 11:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 - 4 = 5 - 6 \times (7 - 8)^9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 - 4 = \sqrt{56 + 7 \times 8 + 9}$$

• 11:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 - 5 = 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 - 5 = (4 - 3)^2 + 10$$

• 11:

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 + 6 - 5 - 4 = 3! \times 2 - 1 = 3 - 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 87 + 65 + 4! = 3! \times 2 - 1 = 3 - 2 + 10$$

• 11:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 123 - 45 - 67 &= 8 + \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright 1^2 \times (34 - 5 \times 6) + 7 &= 8 + \sqrt{9} \\ \sqrt{9} + 8 &= 7 + 6 - 5 \times 4 - 3 + 21 \\ \sqrt{9} + 8 &= (7 - 6) \times 5 + \sqrt{4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)} \\ \sqrt{9} + 8 &= 7 + 6 \times 54 - 32 \times 10 \\ \sqrt{9} + 8 &= \sqrt{76 + 54 + 3 - 2 - 10} \end{aligned}$$

• 11:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 - 6 &= \sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 - 6) = 5 + 4 + 3 - 2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 - 6 &= \sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 - 6) = (5 \times 4 - 3^2) \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 - 6 &= \sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 - 6) = 5 \times 4 + 3 - 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 12

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (12 + 3) \times 4/5 &= 6 + 7 + 8 - 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 1^{234} + 5 + 6 &= 7 + 8 - \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 12:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3! &= 4 \times 5 + (6 - 78)/9 \\ \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3! &= \sqrt{4} + 5 - 67 + 8 \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 - 6 &= 54/3! + 2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 98 + 76 - 54 \times 3 &= 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 12:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12 &= 3 - 4 - 56 + 78 - 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 12 &= -3!! + 4! + 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright 12 &= (3 - 4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 - 8) + 9) \\ \blacktriangleright 12 &= 3 \times (4 + (5 + 67)/8 - 9) \\ \blacktriangleright 12 &= 3 \times (4 + 5 + 67 - 8 \times 9) \\ \blacktriangleright 12 &= 3 + (-4 + 5)^{678} \times 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 12 &= 3 + 4 + (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8)/9 \\ \blacktriangleright 12 &= (34 - 5 \times 6) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{78 + \sqrt{9}}} \end{aligned}$$

• 12:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{12-3} \times 4 &= (5 \times 6 + 78)/9 = 5 + 6 - (7-8)^9 \\ \blacktriangleright 1^2 \times 3 \times 4 &= (5 \times 6 + 78)/9 = 5 + 6 - (7-8)^9 \\ \blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 - 4! &= (5 \times 6 + 78)/9 = 5 + 6 - (7-8)^9 \end{aligned}$$

• 12:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 &= (65 - 43)/2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 &= (6 - 5 - 4) \times 3 + 21 \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 &= 6 + 5 + (4 - 3)^{210} \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 &= (6 + (54 + 3) \times 2)/10 \end{aligned}$$

• 12:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 &= -5 \times 4 + 32 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 &= 5 - 4! + 32 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 &= 54 - 32 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 12:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (9-8) \times 7 + 6 - 5 + 4 &= 3! \times 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (9-8) \times 7 + 6 - 5 + 4 &= (3+2)!/10 \\ \blacktriangleright (9-8) \times 7 + 6 - 5 + 4 &= 3 \times (2+1+0!) \end{aligned}$$

• 12:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (9-8)^7 + 6 + 5 &= 4 \times 3 \times (2-1) = 4 \times 3 + 21 \times 0 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (7-6) - 5 &= 4 \times 3 \times (2-1) = 4 \times 3 + 21 \times 0 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 \times 7 + 65 &= 4 \times 3 \times (2-1) = 4 \times 3 + 21 \times 0 \end{aligned}$$

• 13

- ▶ $1 + 2 \times 3! = (45 - 6 + 78)/9$
- ▶ $12 - 3 + 4 = -56 + 78 - 9$
- ▶ $12/3 + 4 + 5 = 6 - 7 \times (8 - 9)$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right)! + 7 = (6 - 5)^{43} + 2 + 10$

• 13:

- ▶ $98/7 - 6 + 5 = 4 + 3^2 \times 1$
- ▶ $98/7 - 6 + 5 = 4 - 3 + 2 + 10$

• 13:

- ▶ $(-9 + 87)/6 = (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 = -5 \times 4 + 32 + 1$
- ▶ $(-9 + 87)/6 = (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 = 5 - 4! + 32 \times 1$
- ▶ $(-9 + 87)/6 = (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 = 5 + \sqrt{43 + 21}$
- ▶ $(-9 + 87)/6 = (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 = -5 - 4 + 32 - 10$
- ▶ $(-9 + 87)/6 = (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 = 5 + 4 - 3 \times 2 + 10$

• 13:

- ▶ $98 - 76 - 5 - 4 = 3! \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $98 - 76 - 5 - 4 = 3!/2 + 10$
- ▶ $98 - 76 - 5 - 4 = \sqrt{3^2} + 10$

• 14

- ▶ $12 \times 3/4 + 5 = 6 + 7 - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $9 - 8 \times 7 + 65 - 4 = 3! - 2 + 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 = -7 - 6! + 5 - 4 + 3!! + 21 - 0!$

• 14:

- ▶ $1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) = 5 \times (6 - 7)^8 + 9$
- ▶ $1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) = (5 + 6) \times (-7 + 8) + \sqrt{9}$

• 14:

- ▶ $98/7 = (6-5) \times (4+3) \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $98/7 = -6 + 54/3 + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $98/7 = 6 + 5 + (4-3) \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $98/7 = 6 - 5! + 4 \times 32 \times 1$
- ▶ $98/7 = 6! + \sqrt{5! + 4!} - 3!! + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $98/7 = (6-5) \times 4 \times (3-2) + 10$
- ▶ $98/7 = 6 + 54/3! \times 2 - 10$
- ▶ $98/7 = 6 + 5 + 4 + 3^2 - 10$
- ▶ $98/7 = 65 - 43 + 2 - 10$

• 14:

- ▶ $9-8+7+6 = 5-4 \times 3 + 21$
- ▶ $9-8+7+6 = (5+43)/2 - 10$
- ▶ $9-8+7+6 = 5+4-3-2+10$

• 15

• 15:

- ▶ $1+2+3 \times 4 = 5 + (6-7)^8 + 9$
- ▶ $1+2+3 \times 4 = 5 \times (6 \times (7-8) + 9)$

• 15:

- ▶ $1 + 2^3 - 4 - 5 = 6 - (7-8) \times 9$
- ▶ $12 - 3 \times (4-5) = 6 - (7-8) \times 9$

• 15:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 87)/6 = 54/3 - 2 - 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 + 6! = 54/3 - 2 - 1$
 $= 5 \times 4 - 3 \times 2 + 1$
 $= 5 \times (4+3) - 2 \times 10$

• 15:

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 + 6 - 5 = (4 + 3) \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 + 6 - 5 = 4 + 3 - 2 + 10$$

• 15:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 - 5 + 4 = -3! + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 - 5 - \sqrt{4} = -3! + 21 \\ = 3 + 2 + 10$$

• 15:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 = 45 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 = \sqrt{4} - 56 + 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 = 4 + \sqrt{5 \times 6 \times 7 - 89}$$

• 16

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 - 4 + 5 = 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7 = 65 - 43 - (2 + 1)!$$

• 16:

$$\blacktriangleright 12/3 \times 4 = 5 \times (6 + 7 - 8) - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12/3 \times 4 = 5 + 6 + (7 + 8)/\sqrt{9}$$

• 16:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 = (5 + 43)/(2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 = 54/3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 = 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 = (54 \times 3 - 2)/10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 = 5 + 43 - \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 16:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6 \times 5 &= 4^{3-2+1} \\ \blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6 \times 5 &= 4 \times (3 + 2 - 1) \\ \blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6 \times 5 &= 4 \times 3/2 + 10 \\ \blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6 \times 5 &= \sqrt{4+32} + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 16:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4) &= 3 \times 2 + 10 \\ \blacktriangleright 98/7 + 6 / (\sqrt{5+4}) &= 3 \times 2 + 10 \\ \blacktriangleright (9 \times (8 - 7) - 6 - 5)^4 &= 3 \times 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 17

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{12-3} + 4 \times 5 - 6 &= -7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 + 5 - 4 &= -3 + 2 \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 17:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 - 2^3 + 4! &= -5 - 67 + 89 \\ \blacktriangleright 12 + 3 + \sqrt{4} &= -5 - 67 + 89 \end{aligned}$$

• 17:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 &= 6 - 5 \times 4 + 32 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 &= 6 \times 5 - 4 + 3 - 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 17:

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 34 - 5 \times (-6 + 7) = 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3 + 4 - 5 + 6 + 7 = 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1^{234} + 5 + 6 + 7 = 8 + 9$$

$$9 + 8 = 76 + 5 - 43 - 21$$

$$9 + 8 = 7 + (65 - 43)/2 - 1$$

$$9 + 8 = (7 - 6) \times (54 - 3)/(2 + 1)$$

$$9 + 8 = 7 + 65 - 43 - 2 - 10$$

$$9 + 8 = 5 - 4 + 3 \times 2 + 10$$

$$9 + 8 = 54/3! - 2 + 10$$

• 17:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 - 5 = 4 + 3! \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 - 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 - 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 - 5 = 4! + 3!/2 - 10$$

• 18

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3! = \left(\sqrt{4 \times (56 - 7)} - 8 \right) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 18:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 + (4 - 5) \times 6 = 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3! + 4! - 5! \times 6 = 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 18:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 - 6 = 54/3 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 - 6 = 54 - 3 \times (2 + 10)$$

• 18:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 - 6 - 54 = -3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 - 6 - 54 = 3! + 2 + 10$$

• 18:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23 - 4 = (5 + 67)/8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!/4 = (5 + 67)/8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3) \times \sqrt{4} = (5 + 67)/8 + 9$$

• 18:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 + 4 + 5 = 6! - 78 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 + 4 + 5 = -6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 + 4 + 5 = 6! - 78 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 + 4 + 5 = 6 + 7 + 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 18:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 = (65 + 43)/(2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 = 6^5/432 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 = 6 + 54/3! + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 = (6 + 54)/3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 = 6 + 54 - 32 - 10$$

• 18:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87 - 6)/5 = 9 - 8 \times 7 + 65 = \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87 - 6)/5 = 9 - 8 \times 7 + 65 = 4! - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87 - 6)/5 = 9 - 8 \times 7 + 65 = -4 + 32 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87 - 6)/5 = 9 - 8 \times 7 + 65 = 4 + 3! - 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87 - 6)/5 = 9 - 8 \times 7 + 65 = \sqrt{4 + 32 \times 10}$$

• 19

• 19:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 - 4 = 5 + 6 + 7 - 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 - 4 = 56/7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 19:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)! + 7 + 6 = 5 - 4 - 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)! + 7 + 6 = 54 / (3 \times 2) + 10$$

• 19:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 - 65 = 4 \times (3 + 2) - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 - 65 = 4 + 3 + 2 + 10$$

• 19:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + (7 + 65) / 4 = 3^2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 - 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3^2 + 10$$

• 19:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 = 4 \times (3 + 2) - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 = 4 - 3! + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 = 4 + 3 + 2 + 10$$

• 20

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 - 4 = 5 - 6 \times (7 - 8) + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{23} \times 4 \times 5 = -6 + 78 / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 \times 8 + 76) \times 5 = 4 \times (3 \times 2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + (7 + 65) / 4! = \sqrt{3! - 2} \times 10$$

• 20:

- ▶ $98/7 + 6 = 54/3 + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $98/7 + 6 = 5 + (4 + 3) \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $98/7 + 6 = 5 + 4 + 3 - 2 + 10$
- ▶ $98/7 + 6 = (5 - 4 + 3 - 2) \times 10$
- ▶ $98/7 + 6 = 5 \times 4 + 321 \times 0$

• 20:

- ▶ $(-9 \times 8 + 76) \times 5 \times (4 - 3) = 2 \times 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{98 + 76 - 5} + 4 + 3 = 2 \times 10$
- ▶ $-9 + 87 - 65 + 4 + 3 = 2 \times 10$

• 21

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 6) = 54 - 32 - 1$
- ▶ $(9 + 87)/6 + 5 = 4 - 3 + 2 \times 10$
- ▶ $98 - 76 - 5 + 4 = 3 \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$

• 21:

- ▶ $-1 - 23 + 45 = (6 - 7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $12/3 \times 4 + 5 = (6 - 7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$

• 21:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 = 65 - 43 - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 = \sqrt{654 - 3 - 210}$

• 21:

- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7 - 65 + 4 + 3 = 21$
- ▶ $(9 + 87)/6 + 5 \times (4 - 3) = 21$
- ▶ $98 - 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3) = 21$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9 + 8!} + 7! - 6 \times (5 + 4! + 3) = 21$

• 21:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 = 5 + 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 = \sqrt{56 \times 7/8 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) = 5 + 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 = \sqrt{56 \times 7/8 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 - \sqrt{4} = 5 + 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 = \sqrt{56 \times 7/8 \times 9}$$

• 22

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 + 4 - 5 = -67 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 \times (5 - 4)^3 = 21 + 0!$$

• 22:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23 = 4 + (5 + 67)/8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23 = -4 - 56 - 7 + 89$$

• 22:

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 34 = 5 + (-6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 34 = 5 \times 6 - 7 + 8 - 9$$

• 22:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 = 54 - 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 = (5 - 4) \times (32 - 10)$$

• 22:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (7 - 6) + 5 = 43 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8!/7! + 6 + 5 = 43 - 21$$

• 22:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 65 - 4 = 32 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 = 32 - 10$$

• 23

▶ $(1+2)^3 - 4 = -56 + 7 + 8 \times 9$

• 23:

▶ $1 \times 23 = 45 + 67 - 89$

▶ $1 \times 23 = 4 - 56 + 78 - \sqrt{9}$

• 23:

▶ $1 - 23 + 45 = 6 - 7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

▶ $-1 + 23 - 4 + 5 = 6 - 7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

• 23:

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6 = 54 - 32 + 1$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6 = 5 - 4 + 32 - 10$

• 23:

▶ $9 + \sqrt{87 - 6} + 5 = 4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1$

▶ $9 + 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 = 4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1$
 $= 43 - 2 \times 10$

• 23:

▶ $9 - 8 + 76 - 54 = (3! - 2)! - 1 = 3 + 2 \times 10$

▶ $98 - 76 + 5 - 4 = (3! - 2)! - 1 = 3 + 2 \times 10$

• 23:

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6 = 54 - 32 + 1$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6 = 5 - 4 + 32 - 10$

• 24

▶ $98 - 76 - 5 + 4 + 3 = (2 + 1 + 0)!$

• 24:

▶ $12 + 3 \times 4 = 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 + 9$

▶ $12 + 3 \times 4 = 5 + 6 + 78 / (\sqrt{9})!$

• 24:

▶ $9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5 = 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1$

▶ $9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5 = (4 + 3) \times 2 + 10$

• 24:

▶ $\sqrt{(9 + 87) \times 6} = (5 + 4) / 3 + 21$

▶ $\sqrt{(9 + 87) \times 6} = 5! - 43 \times 2 - 10$

• 24:

▶ $1 \times 2 - 34 + 56 = 7 + 8 + 9$

$9 + 8 + 7 = 65 - 43 + 2 \times 1$

$9 + 8 + 7 = 6 + 54 / 3 \times (2 - 1)$

$9 + 8 + 7 = (6 - 5) \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1$

$9 + 8 + 7 = 654 - 3 \times 210$

$9 + 8 + 7 = 6 + 5 \times (4 + 32) / 10$

$9 + 8 + 7 = (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3)! / 210$

• 24:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 - 87 + 654} = 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^{765} \times 4! = 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times (6 - 5) / 4 = 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 - 7 - 6)! \times (5 - 4) = 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! / 8 \times 7 + 654 = 3 + 21$$

$$1 + 23 = (-4 + 5)^{67} \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$1 + 23 = 4 \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 89$$

$$1 + 23 = 4 \times (5 + (-6 + 7)^{89})$$

$$1 + 23 = 4 + 5 + 6 - (7 - 8) \times 9$$

$$1 + 23 = \sqrt{4} \times (5 \times 6 + 78) / 9$$

• 24:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 \times (-4 + 5)^{67} = 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\sqrt{9} \times 8 = (7 - 6)^{54} \times 3 + 21$$

$$\sqrt{9} \times 8 = 7 \times 65 - 432 + 1$$

$$\sqrt{9} \times 8 = 7 + 6^5 / 432 - 1$$

$$\sqrt{9} \times 8 = 7 + 65 + \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times (2 - 10)$$

$$\sqrt{9} \times 8 = 7 + 6 + 5 - 4 \times (3 - 2) + 10$$

• 24:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 4 - 5) = (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 / 3 + 4 \times 5 = (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 + 4 + 5 = (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9)!$$

$$= 6 + 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$= \sqrt{6 \times (7 + 89)}$$

• 25

• 25:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (-2 + 3)! = 4 \times 5 - 67 + 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (-2 + 3)! = \sqrt{4} \times 56 - 78 - 9$$

• 25:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 = 56/7 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 + \sqrt{4} = 56/7 + 8 + 9$$

• 25:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 - 4 + 5 = (67 + 8)/\sqrt{9} = 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (123 + \sqrt{4})/5 = (67 + 8)/\sqrt{9} = 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

• 25:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 = 5 - 4 + 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 - 6 = 5 - 4 + 3 + 21$$

• 25:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 87 - 65 = 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 = 4! - 3^2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 + 6 + 5 = 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 = 4! - 3^2 + 10$$

• 25:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 + 5 + 4 = (3! - 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87)/6 + 5 + 4 = 3 + 21 + 0!$$

• 26

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23 + 4 = -56 - 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 + \sqrt{4+5} = (6+7) \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9-8)^7 \times (6 \times 5 - 4) = 3! + 2 \times 10$$

• 26:

$$\blacktriangleright (-(\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times (7 + 6) = 5 \times (4 - 3) + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-(\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times (7 + 6) = 54/3 - 2 + 10$$

• 26:

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{23} \times 4 \times 5 + 6 = 78/\sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 + 3^4 - 56 = 78/\sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! + 3!! + 4 \times 5 - 6! = 78/\sqrt{9}$$

• 26:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 65 = \sqrt{4} + 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 65 = 4! + 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 65 = 4 + 32 - 10$$

• 27

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 + 4 = 5 - 67 + 89$$

• 27:

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 34 + 5 = 6 + 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! - 45 &= 6 + 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})! \\ &= (-6 + 7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 27:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 \times 87 - 6} = 5 + 43 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 \times 87 - 6} = 54 \times (3 + 2)/10$$

• 27:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 65 - 4 = 3^{2+1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times \sqrt{76 + 5}/4! &= 3^{2+1} \\ &= 3! + 21 \end{aligned}$$

• 27:

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)^3 = -4 - 56 + 78 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)^3 = 4 + 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)^3 = 45 - 6! + 78 \times 9$$

• 27:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 + 5 = -4 + 32 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 + 5 = 4 + 3 + 2 \times 10$$

• 28

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 34 - 5 = (6 + 78) / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + 7 \times 6) / 5 = 4 + 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 / 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4 = 3! + 21 + 0!$$

• 28:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 + 4 = \sqrt{-5 + 6! + 78 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 + 4 = 56 / (7 - 8 + \sqrt{9})$$

• 28:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 / 6 = (5 + 4) \times 3 + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 / 6 = 5 + 43 - 2 \times 10$$

• 29

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 + 4 \times 5 = -6 + 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

• 29:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3 + 4! = 5 + (-6 + 78) / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)^3 + \sqrt{4} = 5 + (-6 + 78) / \sqrt{9} \\ = 5 \times 6 - (-7 + 8)^9$$

• 29:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7-6=5+4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7-6=5 \times 4-3+2+10$$

• 29:

$$\blacktriangleright -(9-8)^7+6 \times 5=-4+32+1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9}+8 \times 7-6 \times 5=-4+32+1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{(9+87)} \times 6+5 &=-4+32+1 \\ &=4!/3+21 \\ &=\sqrt{4^3}+21 \end{aligned}$$

• 30

$$\blacktriangleright -12-3+45=6+7+8+9$$

• 30:

$$\blacktriangleright 1+2+3+4! = 56-78/\sqrt{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (12+3) \times \sqrt{4} &= 56-78/\sqrt{9} \\ &= 5+6 \times 7-8-9 \end{aligned}$$

• 30:

$$\blacktriangleright 9+8+7+6=54-3-21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9+8+7+6=54/3+2+10$$

• 30:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9}-8) \times 7+65=-\sqrt{4}+32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9}-8) \times 7+65=4 \times (3+2)+10$$

• 30:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 65 + 4 = \sqrt{3^2} \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 65 + 4 = \sqrt{3^2} \times 10 \\ = 32 - 1 - 0!$$

• 30:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 \times 5 = 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 \times 5 = 4 \times (3 + 2) + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 \times 5 = (4 - 3 + 2) \times 10$$

• 31

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^3 + 4 = -56 + 78 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 34 - 5 = 6 \times 7 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{234} + 5 \times 6 = 7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \times 6 = 54 - 3 - 2 \times 10$$

• 31:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 = (654 - 3) / 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 = 6 + 5 - 4 + 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 = -6! + 5! / 4 + (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 = 6 + 54 + 3 - \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 31:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 65 = -(\sqrt{9})! / 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! = -\sqrt{4} + 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 65 = -(\sqrt{9})! / 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! = 4 + 3^{2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 65 = -(\sqrt{9})! / 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! = 43 - 2 - 10$$

• 31:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 - 6) + 5 \times 4 &= 32 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 6 - 54 & \\ \blacktriangleright 98 - 76 + 5 + 4 &= 32 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 - 4) &= 32 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 32

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 - 4 &= 56 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + 34 - 5 &= 6 + 78 / \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 32:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 \times 5 + \sqrt{4} &= 32 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 - 654 &= 32 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 32:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (-7 + 6 + 5) + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! &= \sqrt{2^{10}} \\ \blacktriangleright 98 - 76 + 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3 &= \sqrt{2^{10}} \end{aligned}$$

• 32:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7 - 6)^5 &= 4^3 / 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 \times (87 - 6)} + 5 &= 4^3 / 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 - 65 &= 4^3 / 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7 - 6)^5 &= 4^3 / 2 \times 1 \\ &= 4 + 3! + 21 \\ &= 4 \times (3^2 - 1) \\ &= 43 - 2 - 10 \\ &= 4 \times 3 + 2 \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 33

• 33:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 34 = (5 - (6 - 7)^8)! + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 34 = 5 + (6 + 78) / \sqrt{9}$$

• 33:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - (7 + 6) \times 5 = 4 \times 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times 7 - 65 = 4 \times 3 + 21$$
$$= \sqrt{43^2} - 10$$

• 33:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + (7 + 6 - 5) \times 4 = 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 87 + 6! - 54 = 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7 \times 6 \times (5 - 4) = 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 76 - 54 = 32 + 1$$

• 34

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times 34 = 5 \times (6 + 7 - 8) + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98 \times 7 + 6! = 5 - 4 + 32 + 1$$

• 34:

$$\blacktriangleright (98 - 76 - 5) \times \sqrt{4} = 32 + 1 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98/7 - 6 + 54 = 32 + 1 + 0!$$

• 34:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 = 4! + 3^2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 = \sqrt{4} + 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 = 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 10$$

• 35

• 35:

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 + 34 = 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 + 34 = 5 - 6 \times 7 + 8 \times 9$$

• 35:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 34 - 5 - 6 = 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 = 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

• 35:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 - 6 = 54/3 \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 - 6 = -5 - \sqrt{4} + 32 + 10$$

• 35:

$$\blacktriangleright ((9 - 8)^7 + 6) \times 5 = 4 + 32 - 1 = 43 + 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5 = 4 + 32 - 1 = 43 + 2 - 10$$

• 35:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 65 + 4 = 3!^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 65 + 4 = 3 + \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 35:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7 &= 6 \times 5 - 4 + 3^2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7 &= 6 + (5+4) \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7 &= 65 + \sqrt{4} - 32 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7 &= 6 \times 5 - 4 - 3 + 2 + 10 \\ \blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7 &= 65 - 4 - 3!^2 + 10 \\ \blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7 &= 6 + 5 \times 4 - 3 + 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 36

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5 = 4 + 32 \times 1$$

• 36:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (12-3) \times 4 &= 5 + 6 \times 7 - 8 - \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 34 &= 5 + 6 \times 7 - 8 - \sqrt{9} \\ &= 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 - 9 \end{aligned}$$

• 36:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -12 + 3 + 45 &= 6 \times (7 + 8 - 9) \\ \blacktriangleright 12/3 \times (4 + 5) &= 6 \times (7 + 8 - 9) \end{aligned}$$

• 36:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)! \times 7 - 6 &= 54 + 3 - 21 \\ \blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 &= 54 + 3 - 21 \\ &= 5 + 43 - 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 36:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 98 + 7 - 65 - 4 &= 3!^2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 87 - 6 - 5! \times 4 &= 3!^2 \times 1 \\ &= 3 \times (2 + 10) \end{aligned}$$

• 36:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 &= 4 + 56 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 &= 4 \times (56/7 - 8 + 9) \\ \blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 &= 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})! \end{aligned}$$

• 37

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 = 3!^2 + 1$$

• 37:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + 34 &= 5 \times 6 - 7 \times (8 - 9) \\ \blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + 34 &= 5 + 6 + 78/\sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 37:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 - 4 + 5 &= 6 \times 7 - 8 + \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 - 4 + 5 &= 6 + 7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 37:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 + 6 &= 54/3 \times 2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 + 6 &= 54 + 3 - 2 \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 37:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5 &= 4 + 32 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6 - 5) &= 4 + 32 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 38

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5 = -4 + 32 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 + 87)/6 + 54 = 3!^2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 38:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 + \sqrt{4} = 56 - 7 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 + \sqrt{4} = 5 \times 6 + 7 - 8 + 9$$

• 39

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 + 4! = 5! + 6 - 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) - 6 = 54/3 + 21$$

• 39:

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times 34 + 5 = 6!/(7 + 8) - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times 34 + 5 = -6 + (7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 39:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7!} = 6 + 5 - 4 + 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7!} = 65 - 4 - 32 + 10$$

• 39:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7) + 6 \times 5 = 4 + 3!^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98 \times 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 + 3!^2 - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -98 - 7 + 6!/5 &= 4 + 3!^2 - 1 \\ &= (4 + 3)^2 - 10 \\ &= 4! + 3 + 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 40

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 \times 3 + 45 = (6 + 7 - 8)!/\sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 87 - 6 + 5! + 4 = (3! - 2) \times 10$$

• 40:

- ▶ $12 \times 3 + 4 = -56 + 7 + 89$
- ▶ $12 \times 3 + 4 = 5 \times (-6 + 78) / 9$
- ▶ $12 \times 3 + 4 = 5 - 6 - 7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• 40:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6 = 5 \times \sqrt{43 + 21}$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6 = 5 + 43 + 2 - 10$

• 40:

- ▶ $98 + 7 - 65 = 43 - 2 - 1$
- ▶ $98 + 7 - 65 = 4 + 3 \times (2 + 10)$

• 41

- ▶ $12 + 34 - 5 = 6 \times 7 + 8 - 9$
- ▶ $-1 + 2 \times (-3 + 4!) = (5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9$
- ▶ $-9 - 8 - 7 + 65 = 43 - 2 \times 1$

• 41:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 = (6 - 5) \times (43 - 2 \times 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 = 6 - 5 - \sqrt{4} + 32 + 10$

• 41:

- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7 - 6 = 5 + 4 + 32 \times 1$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7 - 6 = -5 + 4 + 32 + 10$

• 42

- ▶ $1 + 2 + 34 + 5 = 6 \times 7 \times (-8 + 9)$
- ▶ $1^2 \times (3 + 45 - 6) = 7! / (8 - \sqrt{9})!$

• 42:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3! + 4! = 5! - 67 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3! + 4! = -5 - 6 \times 7 + 89$$

• 42:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)! \times 7 = -6! - 5 + 4! \times 32 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)! \times 7 = 6 + 54 + 3 - 21$$

• 42:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 = 5 + 4 + 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 = (5 - 4) \times 32 + 10$$

• 42:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 = 43 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 = 43 - (21 \times 0)!$$

• 42:

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 = 32 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 54 = 32 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 + 5 \times 4 = 32 + 10$$

• 43

• 43:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!) = -5 + 6 \times (7 - 8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 \times (3 - 4!) = \sqrt{5^6} + 7 - 89$$

• 43:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times 6 - 5 = 4^3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! / 5! = 4^3 - 21 \\ = 43 + 21 \times 0$$

• 43:

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 - 3 + 45 = 1 \times 23 + 4 \times 5 = -6 + 7^{(8 - (\sqrt{9}!))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 - 3 + 45 = 1 \times 23 + 4 \times 5 = 6 \times 7 - 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 - 3 + 45 = 1 \times 23 + 4 \times 5 = 67 - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 43:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 = -5 \times 4 + 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 = 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 = 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 = 5 - 4 + 32 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 = 54 - 3 + 2 - 10$$

• 44

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 - 3 + 45 = 6 \times 7 + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 44:

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 + 6 \times 5 = 43 + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 + 6 \times 5 = 43 + (21 \times 0)!$$

• 44:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 &= (-1 + 23) \times \sqrt{4} \\ \blacktriangleright (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 &= (-1 + 23) \times \sqrt{4} \\ \blacktriangleright (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 &= (-1 + 23) \times \sqrt{4} \\ &= 56 - 7 - 8 + \sqrt{9} \\ &= 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ &= 5 \times (6 - 7 + 8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

• 45

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -1 + 23 \times \sqrt{4} &= -5 + 67 - 8 - 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 1^{23} \times 45 &= (6 + 7 - 8) \times 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 12 + 34 + 5 - 6 &= (7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 45:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7)^6 \times 5 &= 43 + 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 - 8 - 76 + 5! &= 43 + 2 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 45:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) &= 65 + 4 - 3 - 21 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) &= 6 + 54/3 + 21 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) &= 6! + 54 - 3^{(2+1)!} \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) &= 6 + 54 - 3 - 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 45:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6) &= 5 + 43 - 2 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6) &= 54 - 3^2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6) &= 54 + 3 - 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 46

$$\blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6 + 54 = 3!^2 + 10$$

• 46:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + (8! - 7!)/6! = 5 + 43 - 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + (8! - 7!)/6! = 54/3 \times 2 + 10$$

• 46:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 = 43 + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5 = 43 + 2 + 1 \\ = 4 + 32 + 10$$

• 46:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 34 = 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 34 = 56 + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 34 = 5 + 6 + 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

• 47

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 234)/5 = -6 \times 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 34 - 5 + 6 = 7 \times 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 + 6 = 5 + 43 - 2 + 1$$

• 47:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 \times \sqrt{4} = 56 + (7 - 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 + 4! = 56 + (7 - 8) \times 9$$

• 47:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 = 4 \times 3! \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 = 43 + 2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 47:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 = 65 - 4 \times 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 = 6 \times (5 - 4 + 3) \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 = 65 + 4 - 32 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 = 65 \times 4 - 3 - 210$$

• 48

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 - 4 + 5) = 6 \times (7 - 8 + 9)$$

• 48:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 + 4! = 56 - 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 23) \times \sqrt{4} = 56 - 7 + 8 - 9$$

• 48:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / (8 + 7) = 65 - 4 - 3! \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / (8 + 7) = -6 \times (5 + 4) \times 3 + 210$$

• 48:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times 6 = 54 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times 6 = 5 + 43 + 21 \times 0$$

• 48:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 = 9 - 87 + 6 + 5!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 = 9 - 87 + 6 + 5!$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 &= 9 - 87 + 6 + 5! \\ &= 4! + 3 + 21 \\ &= (4 + 3)^2 - 1 \\ &= 4! - 3 \times (2 - 10) \end{aligned}$$

• 48:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 = -7 + 65 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 = 7 + 6 + 54/3 \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 = -7 + 6 + 54 + 3 + 2 - 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 = 7 + 6 - 5 - \sqrt{4} + 32 + 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 = 7 + 6 + \sqrt{5^4} \times (3 - 2) + 10$

• 49

- ▶ $12/3 + 45 = -6 + 7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 \times 5 = (4 + 3)^2 \times 1$

• 49:

- ▶ $1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4 = 56 + 7 \times (8 - 9)$
- ▶ $(1 + 2 \times 3)^{\sqrt{4}} = 56 + 7 \times (8 - 9)$

• 49:

- ▶ $1 - 23 \times 4! - 5! + 6! = 7^{8 - (\sqrt{9})!}$
- ▶ $1^2 - 3 + 45 + 6 = 7^{8 - (\sqrt{9})!}$
 $= (-7! + 8!) / (\sqrt{9})!!$

• 49:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 - 6 = 54 - (3 + 2) \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 - 6 = 54 + 3 + 2 - 10$

• 50

- ▶ $(1 + (-2 + 3)!) \times \sqrt{4} = 56 - 7 - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $1 + 23 - 4 + 5 \times 6 = 7 \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 = 65 - 4 - 3 + 2 - 10$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 - 76 + 54 = (3 + 2) \times 10$

• 50:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3 + 45 = 67 - 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23 \times \sqrt{4} + 5 = 67 - 8 - 9$$

• 50:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7!/6! = 5 + 43 + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7!/6! = 54 + 3 \times 2 - 10$$

• 50:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8!/7! \times 6 + 5 = (4 + 3)^2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + (8 - 7)^6) \times 5 = (4 + 3)^2 + 1 \\ = (4 + 3 - 2) \times 10$$

• 51

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^3 + 4! = 5!/6 \times 7 - 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 34 + 5 = 6 + (7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 51:

$$\blacktriangleright -98/7 + 65 = 4! \times 3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98/7 + 65 = 43 - 2 + 10$$

• 51:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6 = 5 + 43 + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6 = 54 - 3 + 21 \times 0$$

• 52

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 3 + 45 = 6 \times 78/9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4 = 5 - 6 \times 7 + 89$$

• 52:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5 = 4 \times (3! \times 2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 = 4 \times (3! \times 2 + 1) \\ = 4^3 - 2 - 10$$

• 52:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 = 5 + 4 \times 3! \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 = 5 + 4! + 3 + 2 \times 10$$

• 52:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 = 5 + 4 \times 3! \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 = 54 - 3 + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 = 5 + 4! + 3 + 2 \times 10$$

• 53

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2^{3!} = 4 + 5 - 6 \times (7 - 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) = 5! + 67 \times (8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^3 + 45 = 6 + 7 \times 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{2^3} - 4 + 56 = 7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 53:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 = (65 + 43)/2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 = 65 \times 4 + 3 - 210$$

• 53:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 - 6 = 54 - 3 + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 54 + 3^2 - 10$$

• 53:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 = (4! + 3) \times 2 - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 - 7 + 65 &= (4! + 3) \times 2 - 1 \\ &= \sqrt{43^2} + 10\end{aligned}$$

• 54

• 54:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 + 45 = 6 \times (-7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 + 45 = 6 \times \sqrt{78 + \sqrt{9}}$$

• 54:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4!) = 56 - 7 + 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^3 \times \sqrt{4} &= 56 - 7 + 8 - \sqrt{9} \\ &= (5 + (6 - 7)^8) \times 9\end{aligned}$$

• 54

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 - 65 = (4! + 3) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 - 65 = \sqrt{4} \times 3^{2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 - 65 = \sqrt{4} \times 32 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 - 65 = 4 + (3 + 2) \times 10$$

• 54

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 - 65 = (4! + 3) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times ((8 - 7)^6 + 5) = (4! + 3) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}\blacktriangleright 98 + 76 - 5! &= (4! + 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\ &= 4 + (3 + 2) \times 10\end{aligned}$$

• 54

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7 + 65 &= 4! + 32 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 - 5 &= 4! + 32 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 - 76 + 5! &= 4! + 32 - 1 \\ &= 43 + 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 55

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times (3 + 4!) &= 56 - (-7 + 8)^9 \\ \blacktriangleright (12 + 3 - 4) \times 5 &= 6 + 7^{(8 - (\sqrt{9})!)} \\ \blacktriangleright 12/3 + 45 + 6 &= 7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})! \end{aligned}$$

• 55:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7!/6! &= 54 + 3 - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7!/6! &= 54 - 3^2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 55:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 &= (65 + 43)/2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 &= 65 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 &= 6 + 54 - (3 + 2) \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 &= 6 + 54 + 3 + 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 55:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7 + 65 &= 4! + 32 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 - 5 &= 4! + 32 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 - 76 + 5! &= 4! + 32 - 1 \\ &= 43 + 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 56

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 + 4 \times 5 = 67 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 56:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times (8-7) + 65 = 4! + 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 + 6 - 5 = 4! + 32 \times 1 \\ = 4^3 + 2 - 10$$

• 56:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 98 - 7 \times 6 = 54 + 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 98 - 7 \times 6 = 5 + 4! \times 3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 98 - 7 \times 6 = 5 + 43 - 2 + 10$$

• 57

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (34 - 5) = 6! / (7 + 8) + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 - 7 + 65 = 4! + 32 + 1$$

• 57:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! / 7! \times 6 = (54 + 3) \times (2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! / 7! \times 6 = 5 + 4^3 - 2 - 10$$

• 58

• 58:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8! - 7!) / 6! = 54 + 3 + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8! - 7!) / 6! = 54 - 3 \times 2 + 10$$

• 58:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 65) = 4^3 - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 65) = 4 \times 3! \times 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 65) = -\sqrt{4} + 3 \times 2 \times 10$$

• 59

- ▶ $-1 + 2^{3!} - 4 = 5 - 6 \times (7 - 8) \times 9$
- ▶ $1 + 2 \times (34 - 5) = 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9$

• 59:

- ▶ $12 - \sqrt{3^4} + 56 = 7 \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $1 \times 2^3 + 45 + 6 = 7 \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$

• 59:

- ▶ $9 - 8 - 7 + 65 = -4 + 3 \times 21$
- ▶ $9 - 8 - 7 + 65 = (4 + 3)^2 + 10$

• 59:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 = 65 - 4 - 3 + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 = 6 + 5 \times 4 + 32 + 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 = (65 + 4) \times (3 - 2) - 10$

• 59:

- ▶ $9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 = 9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 = 54 + 3 + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 = 9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 = 5 + 4 + (3 + 2) \times 10$
- ▶ $9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 = 9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 = 54 - 3 - 2 + 10$

• 60

- ▶ $12 + 3 + 45 = 6 \times (-7 + 8 + 9)$
- ▶ $(9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 \times (5 - 4) = 3 \times 2 \times 10$

• 60:

- ▶ $(12 + 3) \times 4 = (5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9$
- ▶ $(12 + 3) \times 4 = 5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 - 9)$
- ▶ $(12 + 3) \times 4 = 56 - 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$

• 60:

- ▶ $(9+8-7) \times 6 = 54+3 \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(9+8-7) \times 6 = 5+43+2+10$
- ▶ $(9+8-7) \times 6 = 54/3^2 \times 10$

• 60:

- ▶ $(-9+8+7+6) \times 5 = 4 \times (-3!+21)$
- ▶ $-9-8+7 \times (6+5) = 4 \times (-3!+21)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9}+87-6 \times 5 = 4 \times (-3!+21)$
 $= 4 \times 3/2 \times 10$
 $= \sqrt{4+32} \times 10$

• 61

- ▶ $1+2^{3!}-4 = -5+67+8-9$
- ▶ $1^2+3 \times 4 \times 5 = 6+7+8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $98-7-6 \times 5 = 4^3-2-1$

• 61:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8+7+6 = 5+4!+32 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8+7+6 = 5+4^3+2-10$

• 62

- ▶ $(1+23)/4+56 = 7 \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times (8-7)+65 = 4^3-2 \times 1$
- ▶ $98/7-6+54 = 3 \times 21-0!$

• 62:

- ▶ $1 \times 2+3 \times 4 \times 5 = 67-8+\sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $12+(3!+4) \times 5 = 67-8+\sqrt{9}$
 $= (67-8) + \sqrt{9}$

• 62:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 = 6 + 54 + 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 = 6 - 54 + (3 + 2)! - 10$$

• 62:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 76 = 54 + 3^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 76 = 5 \times 4 + 32 + 10$$

• 63

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2^{3!} = 45 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 34 - 5 = -6 + 78 - 9$$

• 63:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (-3 + 4!) = 56 - 7 \times (8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2^{(3 \times \sqrt{4})} = 56 - 7 \times (8 - 9)$$

• 63:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 7 = -6! + 54 + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 7 = 65 - 4 + 3 - 2 + 1$$

• 63:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7 + 6) = (5 + 4) / 3 \times 21$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 6! &= (5 + 4) / 3 \times 21 \\ &= 54 - 3 + 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 63:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - (7 - 6)^5) = 4^3 - 2 + 1 = 43 + 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 - \sqrt{76} + 5 = 4^3 - 2 + 1 = 43 + 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right)^7 - 65 = 4^3 - 2 + 1 = 43 + 2 \times 10$$

• 63:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 \times (6 - 5 + 4) = 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 6 \times 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 - 7 + 65 + 4 = 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 + 8!} + 7! - 6 \times 5^{\sqrt{4}} = 3 \times 21$$

• 64

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{(3 \times \sqrt{4})} = 56 + 7 - 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 - 65 + 4! = 32 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 64:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \right)^6 = 5 - 4 + 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \right)^6 = 5 \times 4 \times 32 / 10$$

• 64:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{3!} = 4! - 56 + 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{3!} = \sqrt{4} + (5 - 67) \times (8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{3!} = 45 + 67 - 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 64:

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 - 8)^7 + 65 = 43 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 = 43 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 = 43 + 21$$

• 65

• 65:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + \sqrt{2^{3 \times 4}} = 56 - (7 - 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{(3 \times \sqrt{4})} = 56 - (7 - 8) \times 9$$

• 65:

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3 + 4) \times 5 = 67 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})! = 6 + 7 \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3) \times 4 + 5 = 67 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})! = 6 + 7 \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 65:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3/4 + 56 = 7 \times 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 123 - \sqrt{4} - 56 = 7 \times 8 + 9$$

• 65:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 = 6 - 5 + 43 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 = 65 + 4321 \times 0$$

• 65:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 65 = \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 65 = 4^3 + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 65 = 43 + 21 + 0!$$

• 65:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{3!} = 4 - 5 + 67 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{3!} = 4 + 5 + 67 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{3!} = 4! + (5 + 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{3!} = \sqrt{4} + 56 - 7 \times (8 - 9)$$

• 65:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 5 \times (4 + 3^2) \times 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 5 \times (4 \times 3 + 2 - 1)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6 = -54 + (3 + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 54 + 3 - 2 + 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 5 + \sqrt{4 + 32} \times 10$

• 66

▶ $98 - (7 + 6 - 5) \times 4 = 3 \times (21 + 0!)$

• 66:

- ▶ $-(1 + 2)! + 3 \times 4! = 56 - 7 + 8 + 9$
- ▶ $1 \times 2^{3!} + \sqrt{4} = 56 - 7 + 8 + 9$

• 66:

- ▶ $12 + 3! \times (4 + 5) = 67 + 8 - 9$
- ▶ $(-1 + 23) \times \sqrt{4 + 5} = 67 + 8 - 9$

• 66:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 \times 6 = 5 + 4^3 - 2 - 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 \times 6 = (5 + 4!) \times 3 - 21 \times 0!$

• 66:

- ▶ $(9 - 8)^7 + 65 = 4^3 + 2 \times 1 = 4! + 32 + 10$
- ▶ $9 + 87 - 6 \times 5 = 4^3 + 2 \times 1 = 4! + 32 + 10$

• 67

- ▶ $-1 + 23 + 45 = 67 \times (-8 + 9)$
- ▶ $-1 + 2 \times 34 + 5!/6 = 78 + 9$
- ▶ $-\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + 76 = (5 + 4!) \times 3 - 21 + 0!$

• 67:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 - 6 - 5 = 4 + 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 65 = 4 + 3 \times 21$$

• 68

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 + 45 = 67 - 8 + 9$$

• 68:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 34 = 5 - 6 + 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 34 = 56 + 7 + 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 68:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 5 + 4^3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 5 + 43 + 2 \times 10$$

• 68:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 = 4 + 3 \times 21 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) + 65 = 4 + 3 \times 21 + 0!
= 4 \times (-3 + 2 \times 10)$$

• 69

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 + 45 = -6 + 78 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 + 4 + 56 = 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) - 7 + 65 = 4! \times 3 - 2 - 1$$

• 69:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 34 = (-5 + 6) \times (78 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 34 = 5 - 6 + 7! / (8 \times 9)$$

• 69:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + (8! + 7!) / 6! = 5 + 43 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + (8! + 7!) / 6! = 54 + 3 + 2 + 10$$

• 70

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4! = -5 + 6 + 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 = 6! \times 7 / (8 \times 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 + 56 = 7! / (8 \times 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)! + 76 = 5 + 4^3 + 2 - 1$$

• 70:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 76 - 5 = 9 \times (8 + 7) - 65 = 4^3 + (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 76 - 5 = 9 \times (8 + 7) - 65 = 4 + 3 \times (21 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 76 - 5 = 9 \times (8 + 7) - 65 = (\sqrt{4} + 3 + 2) \times 10$$

• 71

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3 \times 4! = 5 + 67 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (76 - 5) = 4! \times 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5! + 4 = \sqrt{(3 \times 2 + 1)!} + 0!$$

• 71:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5 = 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! + 4 - 5 = 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9$$

• 71:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 - 8 + 7!} = 65 + 4! + 3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 - 8 + 7!} = 6 + 5 + 4! \times 3 - 2 - 10$$

• 71:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 5 + 4^3 + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 54 \times 3/2 - 10$$

• 72

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 23 \times 4! - 5!)/6 = 78 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 - 6 + 54 = 3! \times (2 + 10)$$

• 72:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 \times \sqrt{4} = 5 - 67 \times (8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3!) \times 4 = 5 - 67 \times (8 - 9)$$

• 72:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^3 + 45 = 67 + 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^3 + 45 = (-6 + 7) \times 8 \times 9$$

• 72:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7! = 65 - \sqrt{4} + 3^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7! = 65 - 4 + 3 - 2 + 10$$

• 72:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 76 - 5 = 4 \times (-3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)! \times 7 + 6 \times 5 = 4 \times (-3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 76 + 5 = 4 \times (-3 + 21)$$

$$= 4^3 - 2 + 10$$

$$= 4 \times (-3 + 21) \times 0!$$

• 72:

- ▶ $12 \times 3! = \sqrt{4} + 5! - 67 + 8 + 9$
- ▶ $12 \times 3! = (45 - 6 - 7 - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $12 \times 3! = 45 + 6 + 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $12 \times 3! = 4 \times ((5 + 67) / 8 + 9)$

• 72:

- ▶ $1^{234} \times (5 + 67) = 8 \times 9$
 - $9 \times 8 = 7 + 65 + 4 - 3 - 2 + 1$
 - $9 \times 8 = 76 + 5 + 4 \times 3 - 21$
 - $9 \times 8 = (7 - 6) \times 54 - 3 + 21$
 - $9 \times 8 = \sqrt{76 + 5} + 4^3 - 2 + 1$
 - $9 \times 8 = 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + (3 - 2) \times 10$
 - $9 \times 8 = (7 - 6) \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 + 2 + 10$
 - $9 \times 8 = (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 21 \times 0$
 - $9 \times 8 = 7 + 65 + 4321 \times 0$

• 73

- ▶ $1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 = -6 + 7 + 8 \times 9$

• 73:

- ▶ $1^2 + 3 \times 4! = 5 + 67 - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $1^2 + 3 \times 4! = 56 / 7 \times 8 + 9$

• 73:

- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7 + 65 = 4! \times 3 + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7 + 65 = 4 \times (-3 + 21) + 0!$

• 73:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 = (5 + 4) \times (3! + 2) + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 = 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 = 54 + 3^2 + 10$$

• 74

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! + \sqrt{4} = 5 - 6! + 789$$

• 74:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 76 = 5! - 43 - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 76 = 5! - 4 - 32 - 10$$

• 74:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7) + 65 = 4! \times 3 + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7) + 65 = (4!/3)^2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7) + 65 = \sqrt{4} \times 32 + 10$$

• 75

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! = 5 \times (6 - (7 - 8) \times 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 + 3 \times 4) \times 5 = 6 + 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 + 4 + 56 = 78 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 75:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 76 = (-5 + 43) \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 76 = 5 \times (4 + 3 - 2 + 10)$$

• 75:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 - 6 \times 5 = 4! \times 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 - 6 \times 5 = 43 + \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 76

• 76:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! + 4 = 5 + 6 - 7 + 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! + 4 = 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9$$

• 76:

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times 3^4 - 5 = -6 - 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3)^{\sqrt{4}} - 5 = -6 - 7 + 89$$

• 76:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 76 = (-5 + 43) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 76 = 54 + 32 - 10$$

• 76:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) - 5 = 4 \times \sqrt{3!!/2+1} = 43 \times 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 76 + 5 = 4 \times \sqrt{3!!/2+1} = 43 \times 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 = 4 \times \sqrt{3!!/2+1} = 43 \times 2 - 10$$

• 77

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (34 + 5) = 6 + \sqrt{7! - 8 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 23) \times 4 - 5 - 6 = 7 \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5) = -4 + 3^{2 \times (1 + 0!)}$$

• 77:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 = 65 + 4 \times 3 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 = 6 + 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 21 + 0!$$

• 77:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 76 = 5 - 4 \times (3 - 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 76 = 54 + 3 + 2 \times 10$$

• 78

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 3^4 = 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 123 - 45 = 6 \times 78 / (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 - 6 = 54 + 3 + 21$$

• 78:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 = 4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 / 5 = 4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)!$$
$$= 4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)! \times 0!$$

• 78:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 = 65 - 4! / 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 = 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 = 65 + (4 + 3) \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 = 6 \times (5 + \sqrt{43 + 21})$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 = 65 + 4 - 3 + 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 = 6 + 54 + 3! + 2 + 10$$

• 79

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3^4 = -5 + 67 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 = 7 + 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 / 7 + 65 = 4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• 79:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7! / 6! = 5! - 43 + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7! / 6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 32 + 10$$

• 79:

- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7 = 65 - 4 - 3 + 21$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7 = 6 + 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 21$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7 = (65 + 4) \times (3 - 2) + 10$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7 = 6 + 54 + 3^2 + 10$

• 80

- ▶ $1 - 2 + 3^4 = 5 + 6 + 78 - 9$
- ▶ $12/3 \times 4 \times 5 = (6! + 7!)/(8 \times 9)$
- ▶ $98 - (7 + 65)/4 = (3! + 2) \times 10$

• 80:

- ▶ $\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7} + 6 = 54 \times 3/2 - 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7} + 6 = 5 \times 4 + 3 \times 2 \times 10$

• 80:

- ▶ $98 - 7 - 6 - 5 = (4 + 3! - 2) \times 10$
- ▶ $(9 + 87)/6 \times 5 = (4 + 3! - 2) \times 10$
- $= \sqrt{\sqrt{4} \times 32} \times 10$

• 81

- ▶ $12 \times 3 + 45 = 6 \times (7 + 8) - 9 = 6 + 78 - \sqrt{9}$

• 81:

- ▶ $(1 + 2)^{34 - 5 \times 6} = 78 + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $(12 - 3) \times (\sqrt{4 + 5} + 6) = 78 + \sqrt{9}$

• 81:

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 87 = 6 + 5! - 43 - 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 87 = 6^5 / (43 \times 2 + 10)$

• 81:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) = 5 + 4 + 32 \times 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times \sqrt{87 - 6} &= 5 + 4 + 32 \times 1 \\ &= 54 \times 3/2 \times 1 \\ &= 5 + 43 \times 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 81:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 76 + 5 = (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 76 + 5 = (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1) \times 0!$$

• 81:

$$\blacktriangleright (98/7 - 6 - 5)^4 = (3^2)^{1+0!}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (87 - 6 - 54) &= (3^2)^{1+0!} \\ &= 3^{2 \times (1+0!)} \end{aligned}$$

• 81:

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times 3^4 = 5 - 6 - 7 + 89 = (5 + 67)/8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 2) \times 3^4 = 5 - 6 - 7 + 89 = (5 + 67)/8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3)^{\sqrt{4}} = 5 - 6 - 7 + 89 = (5 + 67)/8 \times 9$$

• 81:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) = 7 + 65 - 4 \times 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) = 76 + 5 \times (4 - 3)^{21}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) = 76 + 5 + 4321 \times 0$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) = 7 + (6 + 54 \times 3)/2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) = -7 - 6! - 5! - \sqrt{4} + 3!! + 210$$

• 82

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 + 23 \times 4 - 5 - 6 &= -7 + 89 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 76 + 5 &= (43 - 2) \times (1 + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• 82:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1^2 + 3^4 &= (5 - 6) \times 7 + 89 \\ \blacktriangleright 1^2 + 3^4 &= 56 + 78/\sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 83

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (-3 + 45) &= 5 + 67 + 8 + \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 - 7 &= -6 + 54 + 3!^2 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 65 &= 4!/3! \times 21 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 83:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3^4 &= -5 + 6 - 7 + 89 \\ \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3^4 &= 5 + 67 + 8 + \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 83:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 + 6 &= 5 \times 4 + 3 \times 21 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 + 6 &= 54 - 3 + \sqrt{2^{10}} \end{aligned}$$

• 84

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 4) &= 5 \times (6 - 7) + 89 \\ \blacktriangleright 123 - 45 + 6 &= 78 + (\sqrt{9})! \end{aligned}$$

• 84:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3^4 + 5 &= 6 \times 7 \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!) \\ \blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 \times 4 - 5) &= 6 \times 7 \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!) \\ &= 67 + 8 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

• 84:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{98 \times (7 + 65)} = 4!/3! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{98 \times (7 + 65)} = \sqrt{4} \times (32 + 10)$$

• 84:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 = 6 + 54 + 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 = 65 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 = (6 - 5) \times \sqrt{4} \times (32 + 10)$$

• 84:

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 \times 6 = (5 - 4 + 3) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 \times 6 = 5! - 4 - 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 \times 6 = 54 + 32 - 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 \times 6 = 5! - \sqrt{(4 + 32)^{1+0!}}$$

• 85

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 \times (3 - 45) = 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 6 = 54 + 32 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 6 - 5 = 43 \times 2 - 1$$

• 86

• 86:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 - 6) + 5 = 43 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times \sqrt{87 - 6} + 5 = 43 \times 2 \times 1$$

• 87

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (34 - 5) = 6 + 78 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 87:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3^4 = (-5 + 6) \times (78 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3^4 = 56 + 7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 87:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 76 = 54 + 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 87 + 6! = 54 + 32 + 1$$
$$= -5 + 4! \times 3 + 2 \times 10$$

• 87:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7 + 6 \times 5) = 43 \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 87/6! \times 5! = 43 \times 2 + 1$$

• 87:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 34 + 56 = 78 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! + 4 + 5 + 6 = 78 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 + 45 + 6 = 78 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!^3 - 4 - \sqrt{5^6} = 78 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2^{\sqrt{3^4}} - 5! + 6! = 78 + 9$$

• 88

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3^4 - 5 = 6 - 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 76 - 5 = 4 \times (32 - 10)$$

• 88:

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 23) \times 4 = (5 - 6)^7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 23) \times 4 = 5 + 6 + 7 \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

• 88:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7!/6! = \sqrt{5^4} + 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7!/6! = 54 + 32 + 1 + 0!$$

• 88:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7 = 6! - 5^4 - 3! - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7 = 6 + 54 \times 3/2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7 = 6 - 5 + 43 \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7 = 65 + 43 - 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7 = -6 + 5! - 4 - 32 + 10$$

• 89

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{3!} + 4! = 5 + 67 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!!/8 - 7 + 6 = 5! + \sqrt{4} - 32 - 1 = 54 + 3!^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 = (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 89:

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• 89:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 = 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times (-6 + 7) = 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) = 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 + \sqrt{4} + 5 + 67 = 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 + \sqrt{4} + 56 + 7 = 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 23) \times 4 + (-5 + 6)^7 = 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 23) \times (4 - 5) + 67 = 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times (-6 + 7) = 89$$

• 90

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times (34 + 56) = (7 + 8) \times \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!$$

• 90:

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2) \times (3!+4!) = 5 \times (6! - 78 \times 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2) \times (3!+4!) = (-5+6)^7 + 89$$

• 90:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!!/8 = 7 + (6 + 54 \times 3)/2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!!/8 = 7 + 6 + 54 + 3 + 2 \times 10$$

• 90:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 6 + 5 = (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 6 + 5 = (4 + 3 + 2) \times 10$$

• 90:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 = 3^2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 76 - 54) = 3^2 \times 10$$

• 90:

$$\blacktriangleright 12/3! \times 45 = -6 + 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 2 + 3) \times 45 = -6 + 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{12/3} \times 45 = -6 + 7 + 89$$

• 90:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 6 = 5 + 43 \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 6 = 54 + 3 \times (2 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 6 = 54 / (3 \times 2) \times 10$$

• 90:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 87 = 6 + 5! - 4 - 32 \times 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 87 = 65 + 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 87 = 6 \times 5 + 4 \times (-3! + 21)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 87 = (-6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2) \times 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 87 = 65 + \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 \times 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 87 = (6 - 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 2) \times 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 87 = 6 \times 5 + \sqrt{4 + 32} \times 10$

• 91

▶ $(1 + 23) \times 4 - 5 = 67 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

• 91:

- ▶ $98 - 7 = 6 + 54 + 32 - 1$
- ▶ $98 - 7 = 65 + 4 + 32 - 10$
- ▶ $98 - 7 = (6 - 5) \times (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1) + 0!$

• 92

▶ $1 \times 23 \times 4 = 5 + 6 + 78 + \sqrt{9}$

• 92:

- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7 - 6 = 5 + 43 \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7 - 6 = (54 - 3) \times 2 - 10$

• 92:

- ▶ $98 - 7 + 6 - 5 = 4 \times ((3! - 2!) - 1)$
- ▶ $98 - 7 + 6 - 5 = 4 \times (3 + 2 \times 10)$

• 93

- ▶ $(-1 + 23) \times 4 + 5 = 6 + 78 + 9$
- ▶ $98 \times (7 - 6) - 5 = 4! \times 3 + 21$

• 93:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3^4 = 5 + 6 - 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 \times 4 = 5 + 6 - 7 + 89$$

• 93:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 87 = 6 + 54 + 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 87 = 6 - 5 + 4! \times 3 + 2 \times 10$$

• 93:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 76 = 5! + 4 - 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 76 = (5 - \sqrt{4}) \times (32 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 76 = 5! - 4 - 3 - 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 76 = 5 + 4 \times (32 - 10)$$

• 94

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 - 6 - 5 = 4 + 3^2 \times 10$$

• 94:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) + 7 + 6 = -5^4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) + 7 + 6 = 5! - 4 - 32 + 10$$

• 95

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (-2 + 3!) \times 4! = 5 - 6 + 7 + 89$$

• 95:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (23 - 4) \times 5 = (6 + 7) \times 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3 + 4) \times 5 = (6 + 7) \times 8 - 9$$

• 95:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 6 + 5 = 4 \times (3! - 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 6 + 5 = 4 \times (3 + 21) - 0!$$

• 95:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) = (5 + 43) \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) = 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) = (-5 + 4!) \times (-3 - 2 + 10)$$

• 96

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 - 6 - 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3 \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 96:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3 + 45) = 6 + (7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23 \times 4 + 5 = 6 + (7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 96:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 + 4 + 56 = 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{12/3} \times 45 + 6 = 7 + 89$$

• 96:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 87 + 6 = (5 + 43) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 87 + 6 = 54 + 32 + 10$$

• 96:

- ▶ $-1 + 23 \times 4 = 56 + 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$
- ▶ $-1 + 23 \times 4 = -5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $-1 + 23 \times 4 = (-5 + 6) \times (7 + 89)$
- ▶ $-1 + 23 \times 4 = \sqrt{56 - 7} + 89$
- ▶ $-1 + 23 \times 4 = 5 + 67 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

• 96:

- ▶ $9 + 87 = 65 + 4^3 / 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 + 87 = 6 + 5 + 43 \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 + 87 = 65 + 4 + 3! + 21$
- ▶ $9 + 87 = (6 - 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 21)$
- ▶ $9 + 87 = 65 - \sqrt{4} + 32 + 1$
- ▶ $9 + 87 = 65 + 43 - 2 - 10$
- ▶ $9 + 87 = (6 - 5) \times 43 \times 2 + 10$
- ▶ $9 + 87 = 6 + 54 + 3 \times (2 + 10)$

• 97

- ▶ $1 + (-2 + 3!) \times 4! = 56/7 + 89$
- ▶ $1 \times 23 \times 4 + 5 = 6! - 7 \times 89$

• 97:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 = 65 + 4 \times (3^2 - 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 = 65 \times \sqrt{4} - 32 - 1$

• 97:

- ▶ $98 - (7 - 6)^5 = 4 \times (3! - 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $98 - (7 - 6)^5 = 4 \times (3 + 21) + 0!$

• 97:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 6 = (5 + 43) \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 6 = 5 + 4 \times ((3! - 2)! - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 6 = 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 \times 10)$$

• 98

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 34 + 5! = (6 + 7) \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 23 - 4 + 5! + 6 = 7 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• 98:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 = (4 + 3)^2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3 \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 98:

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7 = 65 + 4 \times 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7 = 6 + 5 + 43 \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7 = 6 + (54 - 3) \times 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7 = 65 + \sqrt{43^2} - 10$$

• 98:

- ▶ $98 = 7 + 6 + 54 + 32 - 1$
- ▶ $98 = (7 - 6) \times 5! - 43 + 21$
- ▶ $98 = (7 - 6) \times 5 + 4! \times 3 + 21$
- ▶ $98 = 7 \times 6 + 5! - 43 - 21$
- ▶ $98 = 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4! \times 3 - 21$
- ▶ $98 = 76 + 5 + \sqrt{4} - 3! + 21$
- ▶ $98 = 76 + 54 - 32 \times 1$
- ▶ $98 = 7 + 65 + \sqrt{4} + 3 + 21$
- ▶ $98 = 7!/6! + 5 + 43 \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $98 = 7!/6! + 54 \times 3/2 + 10$
- ▶ $98 = 7 \times 6 + 5 + 43 - 2 + 10$
- ▶ $98 = 76 + 5 + 4 + 3!/2 + 10$
- ▶ $98 = 7 + 65 + 4 + 32 - 10$
- ▶ $98 = (7 - 6) \times (5 + 43) \times 2 + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $98 = 76 \times 5/4 + 3 + 21 \times 0$
- ▶ $98 = 76 + 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2 + 10$

• 99

• 99:

- ▶ $98 + (7 - 6)^5 = (4 + 3!)^2 - 1$
- ▶ $98 + (7 - 6)^5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! - 21$

• 99:

- ▶ $98 + 7 - 6 = 5 \times 4 \times (3 + 2) - 1$
- ▶ $98 + 7 - 6 = (5 + 4) \times (3! \times 2 - 1)$
- ▶ $98 + 7 - 6 = 5 + 4 + 3^2 \times 10$

• 99:

- ▶ $-1 + (2 + 3) \times 4 \times 5 = 6 \times (7 + 8) + 9$
- ▶ $12 + 3 \times (4! + 5) = 6 \times (7 + 8) + 9$
- ▶ $-1 \times 23 + \sqrt{4} + 5! = 6 \times (7 + 8) + 9$

4.3 Three Digits Numbers

- 100

▶ $(1 + (-2 + 3)!) \times 4 = 5 + (6 + 7) \times 8 - 9$

- 100:

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 = 5 \times 4 \times (3 + 2) \times 1$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 = (5 + 4 + 3 - 2) \times 10$

- 100:

▶ $(98/7 + 6) \times 5 = (4 + 3!)^2 \times 1$

▶ $(98/7 + 6) \times 5 = (4 + 3 \times 2) \times 10$

- 101

▶ $(1 + 23) \times 4 + 5 = (6 + 7) \times 8 - \sqrt{9}$

- 101:

▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 + 6) = (54 - 3) \times 2 - 1$

▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 + 6) = 5 + 43 \times 2 + 10$

- 101:

▶ $(9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5! = (4 + 3!)^2 + 1$

▶ $\sqrt{9} + 87 + 6 + 5 = (4 + 3!)^2 + 1$
 $= (4 + 3!)^2 + 1$

- 102

- 102:

▶ $1 \times 2 \times (3! + 45) = 6 + 7 + 89$

▶ $1 - 23 + 4 + 5! = 6 + 7 + 89$

• 102:

- ▶ $(1+2) \times 34 = 5!/6 - 7 + 89$
- ▶ $(1+2) \times 34 = (5-6+7) \times (8+9)$
- ▶ $(1+2) \times 34 = 5+6! - 7 \times 89$

• 102:

- ▶ $9+87+6 = (54-3) \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9+87+6 = 5+4 \times (3! - 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9+87+6 = 5!/4 \times 3 + 2 + 10$
- ▶ $9+87+6 = 5+4 \times (3+21) + 0!$
- ▶ $9+87+6 = 54+3! \times (-2+10)$

• 103

- ▶ $98 \times (7-6) + 5 = -4! + 3! \times 21 + 0!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7 + 6 = (54-3) \times 2 + 1$

• 104

- ▶ $123 - 4! + 5 = 6 + 7 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$
- ▶ $98 + 7 - 6 + 5 = 4 \times (3! + 2 \times 10)$

• 104:

- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})!! + 8)/7 = 6 + 5! - 4 + 3 - 21$
- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})!! + 8)/7 = 6 + 5! + 4 - 3! - 2 \times 10$

• 105

- ▶ $(12+3) \times (\sqrt{4}+5) = 6! \times 7 / (8 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$
- ▶ $-12 + 3 \times (45-6) = 7! / (8 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$

• 105:

- ▶ $98 + 7!/6! = 5 \times (4-3) \times 21$
- ▶ $98 + 7!/6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3+2+10)$

• 105:

- ▶ $98 + 7 = 65 + 43 - 2 - 1$
- ▶ $98 + 7 = 6 \times 5 + 4! \times 3 + 2 + 1$
- ▶ $98 + 7 = 6 + 5 \times 4 \times (3 + 2) - 1$
- ▶ $98 + 7 = 6 + \sqrt{5 + 4} \times (32 + 1)$
- ▶ $98 + 7 = (6 - 5) \times (\sqrt{4} + 3) \times 21$
- ▶ $98 + 7 = 6 + 5 + 4 + 3^2 \times 10$
- ▶ $98 + 7 = 65 + 4 + 3 \times (2 + 10)$
- ▶ $98 + 7 = 6 \times 5 \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 10$
- ▶ $98 + 7 = 65 + \sqrt{4} + 3! + \sqrt{2^{10}}$
- ▶ $98 + 7 = (6 - 5) \times (4! - 3) \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$

• 106

- ▶ $1 + (23 - \sqrt{4}) \times 5 = (6 + 7!/8) / (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $98 + 7 + 6 - 5 = -4 + (3 + 2)! - 10$

• 107

- ▶ $(1 + 2) \times 34 + 5 = (6 + 7) \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$

• 107:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 + 6) = 5! + 4!/3 - 21$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 + 6) = 5! + \sqrt{4} + 3! - 21$

• 107:

- ▶ $9 + 87 + 6 + 5 = 4 \times 3^{2+1} - 0!$
- ▶ $98 + \sqrt{76 + 5} = 4 \times 3^{2+1} - 0!$

• 108

- ▶ $(1 + 2)^3 \times 4 = (5 + 6 - 7 + 8) \times 9$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7) \times 6 = 54 \times (3 - 2 + 1)$

• 108:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 \times \sqrt{4+5} = 6 \times (7+8+\sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3-4) + 5! = 6 \times (7+8+\sqrt{9})$$

• 108:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 + 6 \times 5 = 4 \times (3! + 21) = 4 \times 3^{2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 87) \times 6/5 = 4 \times (3! + 21) = 4 \times 3^{2+1}$$

• 109

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5 = 4 \times 3^{2+1} + 0!$$

• 110

$$\blacktriangleright (-12 + 34) \times 5 = (6+7) \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 + 6 - 5 + 4 = (3+2)! - 10$$

• 110:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7+6) = 5 \times (43-21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7+6) = 5 \times 4^3 - 210$$

• 110:

$$\blacktriangleright (98-76) \times 5 = (4+3-2)! - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (98-76) \times 5 = (\sqrt{4}+3^2) \times 10$$

• 111

$$\blacktriangleright -12 \times 3/4 + 5! = (6+7-8)! - 9$$

• 111:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 + 6 = 5! - 4 - 3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 + 6 = 5! + 4 \times 3 - 21 \times 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3)^2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 + 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 3) \times 21 + 0!$$

• 112

$$\blacktriangleright -12/3 - 4 + 5! = 6 \times 7 \times 8 / \sqrt{9}$$

• 112:

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 + 65 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + 2 - 10 \\ = (4! + 32) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 113

• 113:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^3 \times 4 + 5 = (6 + 7) \times 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 234 - 5! = (6 + 7) \times 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 123 - \sqrt{4} \times 5 = (6 + 7) \times 8 + 9$$

• 113:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) = (54 + 3) \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 - 6 = (54 + 3) \times 2 - 1$$

• 113:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 = 6 + 5! - 4 \times 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 = 6 + 5! + 4 + 3 - 2 \times 10$$

• 113:

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 - 8)^7 - 6 + 5! = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 - 8)^7 - 6 + 5! = -4 - 3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• 113:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!/5!) = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!/5!) = -4 - 3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• 114

$$\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)! + (3 + \sqrt{4})! = 5 \times 6 + 78 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 123 - 4 - 5 = 6 \times 7 + 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + (87 + 6) \times 5) / 4 = -3! + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• 114:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times (-6 + 5!) = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times (-6 + 5!) = 4 + (3 + 2)! - 10$$

• 114:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 + 6 \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 + 6 \times 5 = 4 + (3 + 2)! - 10$$

• 114:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 = (54 + 3) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 = 5 + 4 \times 3^{2+1} + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 = 54 \times 3! - 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 = 54 + 3 \times 2 \times 10$$

• 115

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 = 5! + 67 - 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 234 - 5! = 67 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 - 6 + 5! = -4 + (3 + 2)! - 1$$

• 116

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2 + 3)! - 4 = 5! / 6 + 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 + 6 + 5 = -4 + (3 + 2)! \times 1$$

• 117

- ▶ $1 + (2 + 3)! - 4 = 5 \times 6 + 78 + 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 2) \times (34 + 5) = (6 + 7 - 8)! - \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $98 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4 = -3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$

• 117:

- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times (7 + 6) = 54 + 3 \times 21$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times (7 + 6) = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + 2 - 10$

• 117:

- ▶ $9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6) + 5) = -4 + (3 + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6) + 5) = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! - 2 - 1$

• 118

• 118:

- ▶ $9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! - 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 = 4 \times 32 - 10$

• 118:

- ▶ $9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 = (3 + 2)! - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $98 + 7 + 6 + 5 + \sqrt{4} = (3 + 2)! - 1 - 0!$

• 119

- ▶ $123 - 4 = 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 \times 9$
- ▶ $-1^{234} + 5! = 6 - 7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(9 + 8) \times 7! / 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (-3 + 2 \times 10)$

• 119:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2+3)! = 4! + 5 - 6 + 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2+3)! = 4 + 5! + 67 - 8 \times 9$$

• 119:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2^3 + 4! \times 5 + 6 = 7 \times (8+9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1^{23} + 4 \times 5 \times 6 = 7 \times (8+9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 - \sqrt{3^4} + 5! + 6 = 7 \times (8+9)$$

$$(9+8) \times 7 = 6! - 5^4 + 3 + 21$$

$$(9+8) \times 7 = 6 \times (54/3 + 2) - 1$$

$$(9+8) \times 7 = 6!/5 + \sqrt{4} - 3^{2+1}$$

$$(9+8) \times 7 = (6-5) \times (4+3-2)! - 1$$

$$(9+8) \times 7 = (6-5) \times 4! \times (3+2) - 1$$

$$(9+8) \times 7 = 6!/5 + \sqrt{4} - 3^{2+1}$$

$$(9+8) \times 7 = 6 \times 5^{\sqrt{4}} - 32 + 1$$

$$(9+8) \times 7 = 6 - 5 + 4 \times 32 - 10$$

• 119:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 + 65 - 4! = (3+2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8) \times (7 - 6 \times 5) + 4 = (3+2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 54 = (3+2)! - 1$$

• 120

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3! + 4) = 5! - 6 + 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3 \times 4) \times 5 = 6! / (7 + 8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times (3+4) \times 5! - 6! = ((7+8) / \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2) \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 = (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• 120:

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \right)! = 65 + 4! + 32 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \right)! = 6 + 54 + 3 \times 2 \times 10$$

• 120:

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7)! / 6 = 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7)! / 6 = 5! + 4321 \times 0$$

• 120:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) - 76 \right)! = (54 + 3!) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) - 76 \right)! = (5 + 4321 \times 0)!$$

• 120:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 + 3)! = 45 + 6 + 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 + 3)! = 4 + 5! / 6 + 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 + 3)! = \sqrt{4} + 5 + 678 / (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 120:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^{76} \times 5! = \sqrt{9} + 87 + 6 \times 5 = 4! \times (3 \times 2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^{76} \times 5! = \sqrt{9} + 87 + 6 \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^{76} \times 5! = \sqrt{9} + 87 + 6 \times 5 = 4 \times (32 - 1 - 0!)$$

• 120:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 76 - 54 = 98 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 = (3 + 2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 76 - 54 = 98 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 = (3 \times 2 - 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 76 - 54 = 98 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 = 3! \times 2 \times 10$$

• 120:

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)! = 7+6+5! - 4 \times 3 - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)! = 76+5 \times 4+3+21$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)! = 76+54 \times (3-2) - 10$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)! = 7+6+5! + 4+3 - 2 \times 10$

• 120:

- ▶ $9 \times 8 - 7 + 65 - 4 - 3! = ((2+1)! - 0)!$
- ▶ $-9 \times 87 + 6! \times 5/4 + 3 = ((2+1)! - 0)!$
- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7 \times (6+5) + 43 = ((2+1)! - 0)!$
- ▶ $9 + 87 + \sqrt{6 \times 54} + 3! = ((2+1)! - 0)!$

• 121

▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)! + 7 - 6 = 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1$

• 121:

- ▶ $1 + (2+3) \times 4! = 56 + 7 \times 8 + 9$
- ▶ $123 - \sqrt{4} = 56 + 7 \times 8 + 9$

• 121:

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8 \times 76)/5 = (\sqrt{4}+3)! + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $98 - 7 + 6 \times 5 = 4! \times (3+2) + 1$

• 121:

- ▶ $9 + 87 + 6 - 5 + 4! = (3+2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9 \times (8 \times (7-6) + 5) + 4 = (3+2)! + 1$
- $1 + (2+3)! = 45 - 6 - 7 + 89$
- $1 + (2+3)! = 4! + 56/7 + 89$
- $1 + (2+3)! = 4 + 5 \times 6 + 78 + 9$

• 122

- ▶ $1 \times 2 + (3 + \sqrt{4})! = 5! - 6 + 7 - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8)^7 - 6 = 5! - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(98 + 7) \times 6/5 - 4 = (3 + 2)! + 1 + 0!$

• 122:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - (8 - 7)^6 + 5! = -4 + 3! \times 21$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! = -4 + 3! \times 21$

• 123

- ▶ $\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + 7 \times 6} = 5 + 4 \times 32 - 10$
- ▶ $9 \times (8 - 7) - 6 + 5! = 4! \times 3! - 21 = 4 + (3 + 2)! - 1$

• 123:

- ▶ $-1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 = 5! - 6 - (7 - 8) \times 9$
- ▶ $\sqrt{123\sqrt{4}} = 5! - 6 - (7 - 8) \times 9$

• 123:

- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 = 3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$
- ▶ $98 - 7 + 6 \times 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$
 $= 3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$

• 123:

- ▶ $123 = 4! + 5 \times 6 + 78 - 9$
- ▶ $123 = 45 + 6 + 78 - (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $123 = 45 + 67 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $123 = 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 \times 9$
- ▶ $123 = 4 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 \times 9$
- ▶ $123 = 4 + 5 - 6 + ((7 + 8) / \sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $123 = \sqrt{4} + 5 \times 6 \times 7 - 89$
- ▶ $123 = \sqrt{4} + 56 + 7 \times 8 + 9$
- ▶ $123 = \sqrt{4} + 56 - 7 + 8 \times 9$
- ▶ $123 = (4 + 5 - 6) \times (-7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$
- ▶ $123 = (-4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 - 8)! + \sqrt{9}$

• 124

• 124:

- ▶ $1 \times (2 + 3)! + 4 = 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$
- ▶ $1 \times (2 + 3)! + 4 = 5 + 6 - 7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$

• 124:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 76 = 5^4 / (3 + 2) - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 76 = 5! + 4 + 321 \times 0$

• 124:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 65 = 4 \times (32 - 1)$
- ▶ $(9 + 8) \times 7! / 6! + 5 = 4 \times (32 - 1)$
- ▶ $9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 - 5 = 4 \times (32 - 1)$

• 125

- ▶ $9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 54 = 3! \times 21 - 0!$

• 125:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 = 56 + 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 123 + \sqrt{4} = 56 + 78 - 9$$

• 125:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4) \times 5 = 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1^{23} + 4!) \times 5 = 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{23} + 4 + 5! = 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

• 125:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 = 5^4 / (3 + 2) \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 = 5^{4+3^2-10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 = 5! - 4 - 3 + 2 + 10$$

• 125:

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5 = 9 \times 8 - 7 + \sqrt{6! \times 5} = 4 + (3 + 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5 = 9 \times 8 - 7 + \sqrt{6! \times 5} = (\sqrt{4} + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5 = 9 \times 8 - 7 + \sqrt{6! \times 5} = 4 \times (32 - 1) + 0!$$

• 126

$$\blacktriangleright 123 - \sqrt{4} + 5 = (6 + 7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (-3 + 4!) = 5 \times 6 + 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 6 + 5 + 4! = 3! \times 21$$

• 126:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! / 7! + 6) = (5 + 4 - 3) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! / 7! + 6) = 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2) + 1$$

• 126:

- ▶ $9 + 87 + 6 \times 5 = (98 + 7) \times 6/5 = (4! - 3) \times (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $9 + 87 + 6 \times 5 = (98 + 7) \times 6/5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times 21$
- ▶ $9 + 87 + 6 \times 5 = (98 + 7) \times 6/5 = 4 + (3 + 2)! + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $9 + 87 + 6 \times 5 = (98 + 7) \times 6/5 = 4 \times 32 - 1 - 0!$

• 127

▶ $1^{234} + 5! + 6 = 7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$

• 127:

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7!/6! = 5 - 4 + 3! \times 21$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7!/6! = 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 - 1 - 0!$

• 127:

- ▶ $(9 - 8)^7 + 6 + 5! = 4 \times 32 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 + 65 = 4 \times 32 - 1$

• 127:

- ▶ $98 \times (7 - 6) + 5 + 4! = 3! \times 21 + 0!$
- ▶ $98 - 7 + 6 + 5!/4 = 3! \times 21 + 0!$

• 127:

- ▶ $123 + 4 = 5! + 6 - (7 - 8)^9$
- ▶ $123 + 4 = 56 + \sqrt{7! - 8 + 9}$
- ▶ $123 + 4 = 5! - 6 + 78 / (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $123 + 4 = (-5 + 6) \times 7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$

• 127:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7 = 6+5!-4+3+2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7 = 65 + \sqrt{4} \times (32-1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7 = (6+5)^{\sqrt{4}} + 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

• 128

• 128:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})!+8\right)^{7!/6!} = 5! + \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})!+8\right)^{7!/6!} = 5 \times 4^{3!-2} / 10$$

• 128:

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 - 6 + 5! = 4 \times 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} + 7 \times 6 + 5 = 4 \times 32 \times 1$$

• 128:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{3+4} = 5! + (-6 + 78) / 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{3+4} = (56 \times 7 - 8) / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{3+4} = 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 128:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})!+8\right)^7 = 6+5!-4+3+2+1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})!+8\right)^7 = 65+4^3-2+1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})!+8\right)^7 = 6-5+4 \times 32-1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})!+8\right)^7 = 65+43+2 \times 10$$

• 129

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 = 5 + 4 \times (32 - 1) = -5 + (4 \times 3)^2 - 10$$

• 129:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{3+4} = 5!/6 \times 7 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{3+4} = 5! + (6 - 7)^8 \times 9$$

• 129:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8 - 7)^6 \times 5! = 43 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 76 + 5 = 43 \times (2 + 1)$$

• 129:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{3 \times 4 - 5} = -6 + (7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3/4 + 5! = -6 + (7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 123 + (\sqrt{4 + 5})! = -6 + (7 + 8) \times 9$$

• 130

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2^{3!}) \times \sqrt{4} = 5 + 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (76 + 54) = (3 + 2)! + 10$$

• 130:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8 - 7)^6 + 5! = 4 + 3! \times 21$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 + 65 &= 4 + 3! \times 21 \\ &= (4 + 3^2) \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 131

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 - 4 + 5! = 6 \times 7 + 89$$

• 131:

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) / 5 = 4 \times (32 + 1) - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 - 6) + 5! = 4 \times (32 + 1) - 0!$$

• 132

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 65 - 4! = 3! \times (21 + 0!)$$

• 132:

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 3! \times 4! = 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + (3 + \sqrt{4})! = 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 - 9$$

• 132:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 \times 6 = 5 + 4 \times 32 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 \times 6 = 5! + 4! \times 3! / (2 + 10)$$

• 132:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! = 4 \times (32 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 - 7 + 6! / 5 = 4 \times (32 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) = 4 \times (32 + 1)$$

• 133

$$\blacktriangleright 123 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 = 6 + 7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• 133:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5!) = 4 \times (32 + 1) + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7! / 6! \times 5 = 4 \times (32 + 1) + 0!$$

• 133:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7+6=5+4 \times 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7+6=5!+4-3+2+10$$

• 134

$$\blacktriangleright 1-2+3 \times 45=67 \times (8-(\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7)-6+5=(4 \times 3)^2-10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}!) + 8)^7 + 6 = 5 + 4 \times 32 + 1$$

• 135

$$\blacktriangleright 98+7+6 \times 5=(4!+3) \times ((2+1)!-0!)$$

• 135:

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)^3 \times (4-5+6)=(7+8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12+3) \times (\sqrt{4+5}+6)=(7+8) \times 9$$

• 135:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7!/6!)=5+4+3! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7!/6!)=5^{4-3+2}+10$$

• 135:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7)=-6+54 \times 3-21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7)=6+5+4 \times (32-1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7)=65+4! \times 3-2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7)=6+5!+4+3+2-1+0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7)=-6-5-4^3+210$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7)=6+5!+4+3+2 \times 1 \times 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7)=65+(\sqrt{4}+3+2) \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7)=65 \times \sqrt{4}-3-2+10$$

• 136

▶ $(98 \times 7 - 6)/5 = 4 \times (32 + 1 + 0!)$

• 137

• 137:

▶ $9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 = 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$

▶ $(98 \times 7 - 6)/5 = 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$

• 138

▶ $-(1 + 2)! + 3! \times 4! = 56 - 7 + 89$

• 138:

▶ $9 + 8 + 7 - 6 + 5! = 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)! = 4 \times 32 + 10$

▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5 = 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)! = 4 \times 32 + 10$

▶ $-9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)! = 4 \times 32 + 10$

▶ $9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 = 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)! = 4 \times 32 + 10$

• 139

▶ $12 \times 3 \times 4 - 5 = 67 + 8 \times 9$

• 139:

▶ $(9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 - 5 = 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)! + 0!$

▶ $(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) - 7 + 65 = 4 \times (3!^2 - 1) - 0!$

• 140

• 140:

▶ $98/7 + 6 + 5! = 4 \times (3!^2 - 1)$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7/6 \times 5 = 4 \times (3!^2 - 1)$
 $= (4 + 3) \times 2 \times 10$

• 140:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times 6 = 5! + 4 \times (3 \times 2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times 6 = 5 \times (4 + 3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times 6 = 5! + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times 6 = 54 \times 3 - 21 - 0!$$

• 141

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! = 5!/6 \times 7 - 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 = 54 \times 3 - 21 = -5 - 4^3 + 210$$

• 141:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3 \times 45 = 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 - \sqrt{4} + 5! = 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9$$

• 141:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!/5! = -\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) + 6!/5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!/5! = -\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) + 6!/5 = 4! \times 3! - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6!/5! = -\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) + 6!/5 = 4 \times (3!^2 - 1) + 0!$$

• 142

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4! = 5! - 67 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 76 + 5! = 4! \times 3! - 2 \times 1 = (4 \times 3)^2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 143

$$\blacktriangleright 123 + 4 \times 5 = (6 + 7) \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

• 143:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4! = 56 + 78 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 + 3)! + 4! = 56 + 78 + 9$$

• 143:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 76 - 5 = (4 \times 3)^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 + 65 = (4 \times 3)^2 - 1$$

• 143:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7 + 6) = -5 + 4 \times (3!^2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7 + 6) = (5 + 4 + 3)^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7 + 6) = 5 + 4 \times 32 + 10$$

• 144

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 \times 4 = 5 + 67 + 8 \times 9 = (56/7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (3 + 45) = 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 = (5 + 43) \times (2 + 1) = 54 + 3^2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 + 65 = (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1 = 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 6 + 54 = 3!! \times 2/10$$

• 145

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4! = 5! + 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times 6 + 5 = (4 \times 3)^2 + 1$$

• 146

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4! = 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9$$

• 146:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 = 4! \times 3! + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 87 + 65 = 4! \times 3! + 2 \times 1$$
$$= -4^3 + 210$$

• 147

$$\blacktriangleright 123 + 4! = 56 \times 7/8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 147:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) / 6! = 5! - 4 + 32 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) / 6! = 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 10$$

• 147:

$$\blacktriangleright 987 - 6! - 5! = (4 + 3) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5) = (4 + 3) \times 21$$

• 148

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 + 6! / 5 = 4 \times (3!^2 + 1)$$

• 148:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 76 = 5! + 4 + 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 76 = 5 + (4 \times 3)^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 76 = 5! - 4 + 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 76 = (5 + 4^3) \times 2 + 10$$

• 149

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) = 4! + 3! \times 21 - 0!$$

• 150

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 = (6 \times 7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! = 4! + 3! \times 21 = (4! - 3^2) \times 10$$

• 150:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3! \times 4! = 5! + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3! \times 4! = 5 \times 6 \times (7 + 8) / \sqrt{9}$$

• 150:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 \times 6) = 5 + (4 \times 3)^2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 \times 6) = 54 \times 3 - 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 \times 6) = \sqrt{5 \times (43 + 2)} \times 10$$

• 151

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7! / (6 \times 5) = 4! + 3! \times 21 + 0!$$

• 152

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 + 6! / 5 = 4! \times 3! - 2 + 10$$

• 152:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times 76 = 5 + (4 + 3) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times 76 = 54 \times 3! / 2 - 10$$

• 153

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 + 6! = (54 - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

• 154

$$\blacktriangleright 98 / 7 \times (6 + 5) = (4 \times 3)^2 + 10$$

• 156

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3! \times 4! = 5! + 6 \times (7 + 8 - 9)$$

• 156:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 876 = 5! + 4 + 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 876 = 5! + \sqrt{(4 + 32)^{1+0!}}$$

• 156:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 65 = 4! \times 3! + 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 65 = 4! + 3! \times (21 + 0!)$$

• 156:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3^4 - 5 = 67 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 34 + 5! = 67 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + \sqrt{4} \times 5) = 67 + 89$$

• 157

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) + 76 = 5! + 4 + 32 + 1$$

• 160

$$\blacktriangleright (98/7 - 6) \times 5 \times 4 = 4 \times (3! - 2) \times 10$$

• 161

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3^4 = 5 + 67 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 + 65 = (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• 162

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) = -6 + 7 \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 162:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3^4 = 5! - 6 \times 7 \times (8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3^4 = (-5 + 67 - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 162:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 - 6 = 54 \times 3 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 - 6 = -5 - 43 + 210$$

• 162:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6/5 = (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

• 163

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 3^4 &= 5! + 6 \times 7 - 8 + 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 98 + (7 + 6) \times 5 &= 43 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• 164

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5! = 4! \times 3! + 2 \times 10$$

• 165

• 165:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6) + 5! &= 4! \times 3! + 21 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 \times 6 + 5) &= 4! \times 3! + 21 \end{aligned}$$

• 166

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! / (6 \times 5) = 4! \times 3! + 21 + 0!$$

• 166:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 76 &= 5! + 43 + 2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 76 &= 5! - 4 + (3 + 2) \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 167

• 167:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5 &= -43 + 210 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! &= -43 + 210 \end{aligned}$$

• 168

• 168:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4! &= 5! + 6 \times (7 - 8 + 9) \\ \blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4! &= (56 + 7) \times 8 / \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 168:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 - 3 \times (4 - 56) = 7 \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3!) \times (4 + 5) + 6 = 7 \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 168:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7!/6! = (5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3)^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7!/6! = 5! + 43 + (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• 168:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 = (6 + 5 - 4) \times (3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 = (6 - 5) \times 4!/3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 = 6 + 54 \times 3 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 = (6 \times 5 - 43)^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 = (6 - 5) \times 4!/3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 = (6 - 5) \times \sqrt{4^3} \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 = 6 - 5 - 43 + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 = (6 - 5) \times 4 \times (32 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 = 6 + 54 \times 3 + 21 \times 0$$

• 168:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7!/(6 \times 5) = \sqrt{4^3} \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7!/(6 \times 5) = 4!/3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7!/(6 \times 5) = 4 \times (32 + 10)$$

• 169

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{(1 + 2 \times 3!)^4} = 5! - 6 + 7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 34 \times 5 = (6 + 7)^{(8 - (\sqrt{9})!)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 76 - 5 = 4!/3 \times 21 + 0!$$

• 172

▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 + 5! = 43 \times (2 + 1 + 0!)$

• 174

▶ $(1 + 2)! \times (34 - 5) = 6 + 7 \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

• 174:

▶ $-(1 + 2)! + 3!!/4 = (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8) + 9$

▶ $-(1 + 2)! + 3!!/4 = (5 \times 6 + 7 - 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• 174:

▶ $9 \times (8 - 7) \times 6 + 5! = (-4! + 3!!)/(2 + 1 + 0!)$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (-8 \times 7 - 6 + 5!) = (-4! + 3!!)/(2 + 1 + 0!)$

• 174:

▶ $98 + 76 = 5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3^{2+1}$

▶ $98 + 76 = 54 + (3 + 2)! \times 1$

▶ $98 + 76 = 5 + (4 + 3^2)^{1+0!}$

▶ $98 + 76 = 54 \times 3 + 2 + 10$

▶ $98 + 76 = 54 + 3! \times 2 \times 10$

• 176

▶ $98 - 7 \times 6 + 5! = 4!/3 \times (21 + 0!)$

• 177

▶ $(-12 + 3!!)/4 = 5! + 6!/(7 + 8) - 9$

▶ $1 \times 2 + 3!!/4 - 5 = (67 - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$

• 178

▶ $\left((\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \right) / (-7 + 6 + 5) = -\sqrt{4} + 3!!/(2 + 1 + 0!)$

• 179

- ▶ $1 - 2 + 3!!/4 = 5! - 6 - 7 + 8 \times 9$
- ▶ $98 + 76 + 5 = (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)! - 0!$

• 180

- ▶ $12/3 \times 45 = (-6! + 7!)/\left(8 \times \sqrt{9}\right)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) \times 6!} = 54 + 3! \times 21$

• 180:

- ▶ $(1 \times 2 \times 3)!/4 = 5 \times 6 \times (7 + 8 - 9)$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{12 \times 3}\right)!/4 = 5 \times 6 \times (7 + 8 - 9)$

• 180:

- ▶ $(9 + 8) \times 7 + 65 - 4 = 3!!/(2 + 1 + 0!)$
- ▶ $-\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5! + 4 = 3!!/(2 + 1 + 0!)$
- ▶ $\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! - 8\right)/(-7 + 6 + 5) + \sqrt{4} = 3!!/(2 + 1 + 0!)$

• 180:

- ▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 = (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 = (4! - 3 \times 2) \times 10$
- ▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3^2 \times 10$

• 181

- ▶ $1 + (2 \times 3)!/4 = -5 + (6 + 7 \times 8) \times \sqrt{9}$

• 182

- ▶ $12 + 34 \times 5 = (6 + 7) \times \left(8 + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8 + 7!/(6 \times 5) = 4! \times (3! + 2) - 10$

• 182:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!!/4 = 5! + 67 - 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!!/4 = 5 + (67 - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 182:

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7 + 6) = 5! + 4^3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7 + 6) = 54 \times 3 + 2 \times 10$$

• 183

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3!!)/4 = 5! - 6 + 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 6! + 5! = -4! - 3 + 210$$

• 184

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 + 65 = 4 \times (3!^2 + 10)$$

• 186

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3!!/4 = 5! + 67 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)!/4 + 5 = (6 + 7 \times 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7 \times 6) - 5! = -4 \times 3! + 210$$

• 186:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7 + 6) = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (32 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7 + 6) = 5 + (4 + 3!!)/(2 + 1 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7 + 6) = -5 + 4! \times (3! + 2) - 1$$

• 187

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!!/4 + 5 = 67 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• 188

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) - 7 - 6 + 5! = -4 + 3! \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 189

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7+6) = \sqrt{5+4} \times 3 \times 21$$

• 189:

$$\blacktriangleright 1+2 \times 34+5! = (6+7+8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)^3 \times (\sqrt{4}+5) = (6+7+8) \times 9$$

• 189:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7+6!/5!) = -4!+3+210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}-7-6+5!} = -4!+3+210$$

• 189:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7+6) = 54/3! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7+6) = (5-\sqrt{4}) \times 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7+6) = 5!+4! \times 3-2 \times 1-0!$$

• 190

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!+8 \times (-7+6 \times 5) = 4! \times (3!+2) - 1 - 0!$$

• 191

$$\blacktriangleright -1+2^3 \times 4! = 56+(7+8) \times 9$$

• 191:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7+6) + 5 = 4! \times (3!+2) - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7+6) + 5 = 4^3 \times (2+1) - 0!$$

• 192

• 192:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^3 \times 4! = 5! - (6 - 7) \times 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^3 \times 4! = \sqrt{(5 + 67) \times 8^{\sqrt{9}}}$$

• 192:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 - 6 + 5! = 4^3 \times (2 + 1) = 4 \times 3! \times (-2 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 65) = 4^3 \times (2 + 1) = 4 \times 3! \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 192:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7 - 6 + 5! + 4} = 3! \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 + 6 \times (-5 + 4!) = 3! \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 193

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^3 \times 4! = 5 \times 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

• 193:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = 4! \times (3! + 2) + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = 4^3 \times (2 + 1) + 0!$$

• 194

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5 = 4! \times (3! + 2) + 1 + 0!$$

• 196

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 76 = 5 + 4! \times (3! + 2) - 1$$

• 196:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (76 + 5!) = (4 \times 3 + 2)^{1+0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 - 65 = (4 \times 3 + 2)^{1+0!}$$

• **198**

▶ $9 \times (87 - 65) = -4 \times 3 + 210$

• **198:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 87 \times 6 = (5! - 4! + 3) \times 2 \times 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 87 \times 6 = (5 + 4) \times (32 - 10)$

• **199**

▶ $\sqrt{-\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8! + 7 - 6} = -5! - \sqrt{4} + 321$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 76) - 5 = \sqrt{\left(\sqrt{4^3}\right)! - (2 + 1)!! + 0!}$

• **200**

▶ $9 \times (8 + 7) + 65 = 4 \times (3 + 2) \times 10$

• **201**

▶ $(12 - 3)^{\sqrt{4}} + 5! = 6! - 7 - 8^{\sqrt{9}}$

• **204**

▶ $(1 + 2)! \times 34 = 5! + 67 + 8 + 9$

▶ $12 \times (3 \times 4 + 5) = (6 \times 7 - 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$

▶ $(9 + 8) \times (7 + 6 - 5 + 4) = -3! + 210$

• **204:**

▶ $-9 + 87 + 6 + 5! = -\sqrt{4} \times 3 + 210$

▶ $\left(\sqrt{-\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8! + 7 - 6}\right) + 5 = -\sqrt{4} \times 3 + 210$
 $= 4! + 3! / (2 + 1 + 0!)$

• **204:**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 76) = 5 \times (43 - 2) - 1$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 76) = (5 \times 4 - 3) \times (2 + 10)$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 76) = 5 + \sqrt{\left(\sqrt{4^3}\right)! - (2 + 1)!! + 0!}$

• 205

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = -\sqrt{4} - 3 + 210$$

• 206

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 + 6!/5 = 4! \times 3^2 - 10$$

• 207

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9+8!+7!} - 6 = 5! + 43 \times 2 + 1 = 5 - 4!/3 + 210$$

• 207:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 - 4 = -3 + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 6!/5 \times 4 = -3 + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 - 6 \times (5+4) = -3 + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) \times 7 + 6! + 54 = -3 + 210$$

• 208

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 \times (4+5) = (-6 + 7!/8)/\sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = 4 - 3! + 210$$

• 209

• 209:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = -4 + 3 + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!/5 = -4 + 3 + 210$$

• 210

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3)!/4! = 5 \times 6 \times 7 \times (-8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3! + 4!) \times 5 = 6 \times 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 \times 3 + 4 - 5) \times 6 = 7!/ (8 \times \sqrt{9})$$

• 210:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 = (4 + 3!) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 6 + 5! = (4 + 3!) \times 21 \\ = (4 - 3) \times 210$$

• 210:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7 \times 6 = 5 \times (43 - 2 + 1) \\ &\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7 \times 6 = (5-4)^3 \times 210 \end{aligned}$$

• 210:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 - 6 + 5! \times (4 - 3) &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! / (6 \times 5) + 43 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 76 + 5 \times (4! + 3) &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4^3 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 + 8! + 7!} - 6 - 5 + 4! / 3 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright 9 \times (87 - 65) + 4 \times 3 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 6! / 5 \times 4 + 3 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times 6 + 54 \times 3 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6! / 5 + 4 + 3 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! / (7 \times 6 \times 5) + 4! + 3 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (-7 \times 6 + 54) + 3! &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7 \times 6) - 5! + 4 \times 3! &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times 7 + 6! + 54 + 3 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 5! + 43 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / (8 + 7) + 6 \times (5 + 4) \times 3 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3 &&= 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright \sqrt{- (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7 - 6 + 5 + \sqrt{4}} \times 3 = 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7) \times \sqrt{6! / 5} + \sqrt{4} \times 3 &&= 210 \end{aligned}$$

• 211

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = 4 - 3 + 210$$

• 212

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!^3 - 4 = 5! / 6 \times 7 + 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 \times 4 + 5! = (6 + 7! / 8) / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = -4 + 3! + 210$$

• 213

▶ $\sqrt{9+8!+7 \times 6!} = 5 \times 43 - 2 \times 1$

• 213:

▶ $-9+8+7 \times 6 \times 5+4 = -4+3!^{2+1}+0!$
 ▶ $(\sqrt{9}-8+76) \times (5-\sqrt{4}) = -4+3!^{2+1}+0!$
 ▶ $9+8+76+5! = -4+3!^{2+1}+0!$

• 213:

▶ $98-7+6+5!-4 = 3+210$
 ▶ $\sqrt{9+8!+7 \times 6!} \times (5-4) = 3+210$
 ▶ $9+(8+7) \times \sqrt{6!/5}+4! = 3+210$

• 213:

▶ $\sqrt{9+8!+7!} = 6+5!+43 \times 2+1$
 ▶ $\sqrt{9+8!+7!} = 6 \times (5+4!+3)+21$
 ▶ $\sqrt{9+8!+7!} = 6 \times 5^{\sqrt{4}}+3 \times 21$
 ▶ $\sqrt{9+8!+7!} = 6+5 \times 43+2-10$

• 214

▶ $-1 \times 2+3!^{\sqrt{4+5}} = (6!-78)/\sqrt{9}$
 ▶ $(-(\sqrt{9})!+8) \times (-7-6+5!) = 4!/3!+210$

• 215

▶ $-1+(2+3)!-4!+5! = 6!+7-8^{\sqrt{9}}$
 ▶ $98+(7+6) \times (5+4) = 3!^{2+1}-0!$

• 215:

- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5 = 4! \times 3^2 - 1$
- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5 = 43 \times ((2 + 1))! - 0!$
- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3 + 210$

• 216

- ▶ $(12 - 3) \times 4! = 5! \times 6 - 7 \times 8 \times 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 23) \times (4 + 5) = (-6 + 78) \times \sqrt{9} = 6! - 7 \times 8 \times 9$

• 216:

- ▶ $9 \times 8 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{76+5}} = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{2+1} = \sqrt{4} \times 3 + 210$
- ▶ $(9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) - 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{2+1} = \sqrt{4} \times 3 + 210$

• 216:

- ▶ $(1 + 2)!^3 = 4 \times (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!^3 = 4 \times 5 \times 6 + 7 + 89$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!^3 = 4 + \sqrt{5^6} + 78 + 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!^3 = \sqrt{4} - 5 + 6 + \sqrt{7! + 8!} + 9$

• 216:

- ▶ $-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = \sqrt{(-9 + 8 + 7)^6} = 54 \times (3 + 2 - 1)$
- ▶ $-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = \sqrt{(-9 + 8 + 7)^6} = 54/3 \times (2 + 10)$
- ▶ $-9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = \sqrt{(-9 + 8 + 7)^6} = 5 \times 432/10$

• 216:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{2+1} \\ \blacktriangleright (9+8) \times (7+6) - 5 &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{2+1} \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{76+5}}\right) &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{2+1} \\ \blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{2+1} \\ \blacktriangleright (9+8) \times (7+6) - 5 &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{2+1} \\ &= 4! \times 3^2 \times 1 \\ &= 432 / (1+0!) \\ &= \sqrt{4} \times 3 + 210 \end{aligned}$$

• 216:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8)! + 76 + 5 \times 4 &= 3!^{2+1} = 3! + 210 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4 &= 3!^{2+1} = 3! + 210 \\ \blacktriangleright (9-8+7 \times 6) \times 5 + \sqrt{4} &= 3!^{2+1} = 3! + 210 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + 87 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 &= 3!^{2+1} = 3! + 210 \end{aligned}$$

• 217

• 217:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 6 + 5! &= 4! \times 3^2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 6 + 5! &= 4 + 3 + 210 \end{aligned}$$

• 217:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4! &= 3!^{2+1} + 0! \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 76 + 5! + 4 &= 3!^{2+1} + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 218

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!^3 + \sqrt{4} = 5! + 6 \times 7 + 8! / (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 218:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (7 - 6) + 5! = \sqrt{4} + 3!^{2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (7 - 6) + 5! = 4!/3 + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (7 - 6) + 5! = \sqrt{4^3} + 210$$

• 219

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9+8!+7!}+6 = \sqrt{5+4}+3!^{2+1} = 54/3!+210$$

• 219:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + (7 + 6) \times 5) = 4 + 3!^{2+1} - 0!$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 98 + 7 - 6 + 5! &= 4 + 3!^{2+1} - 0! \\ &= \sqrt{4} + 3!^{2+1} + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 220

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!^3+4 = 5+6!+7-8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 + 5! = 4 + 3!^{2+1} = 4 + 3! + 210$$

• 221

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (-3! + 4!) + 5 = (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

• 221:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 + 3!^{2+1} + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = 4 + 3!^{2+1} + 0!$$

• 221:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) = 5 \times 43 + (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) = 5 + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) = 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3 + 210$$

• 222

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 + 6 + 5! = 4 \times 3 + 210$$

• 224

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9+8!+7!}+6+5=(4+3)\times\sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 225

$$\blacktriangleright (12+3)^{\sqrt{4}}=5\times(6+7-8)\times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1\times 2+3)\times 45=(67+8)\times\sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9\times(-8+7+6)\times 5=((4!+3!)/2)^{1+0!}$$

• 226

$$\blacktriangleright 1+(2+3)\times 45=678/\sqrt{9}$$

• 226:

$$\blacktriangleright (9+8)\times(7+6)+5=4!\times 3^2+10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})!+8\right)\times(-7!/6!+5!)=4!\times 3^2+10$$

• 228

$$\blacktriangleright -1+234-5=-6+78\times\sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right)\times 76=(-5+43)\times(2+1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9}\times(87-6-5)=4!-3!+210$$

• 230

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!!+8\right)/7+6+5!=\sqrt{4}\times(3+2)!-10$$

• 231

$$\blacktriangleright 98+7+6+5!=4!-3+210$$

• 232

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!!-8\times 76+5! = (-4!+3!)/(2+1)$$

• 233

$$\blacktriangleright -1+234=5-6+78\times\sqrt{9}=5!+(6+7)\times 8+9$$

• 233:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5! = (-4! + 3!!) / (2 + 1) + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 + 65 = (-4! + 3!!) / (2 + 1) + 0!$$

• 234

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5) = 4 \times 3! + 210$$

• 234:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 234 + 5 - 6 = 78 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! / 4 + 56 = 78 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 234:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8 - 7!} \times 6} = 5! \times \sqrt{4} - 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8 - 7!} \times 6} = (5 - 4 + 3)! + 210$$

• 234:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 234 = -5! - 6 + 7! / (8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 234 = (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 234 = (-5 + 6) \times 78 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 235

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 234 = 5 \times (-6 \times 7 + 89)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 \times 3 + \sqrt{4} \times 5! = (6! - 7 - 8) / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 6! / 5 = -4 + 3!! / (2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 236

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! / 3 - 4 = (\sqrt{5^6} - 7) \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + (8! - 7!) / (6! / 5) = \sqrt{4} \times ((3 + 2)! - 1 - 0!)$$

• 237

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 76 - 5) = 4! + 3 + 210$$

• 238

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (87 - 6) - 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3 + 2)! - 1 - 0!$$

• 239

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 + 3)! \times \sqrt{4} = 5 \times 6 \times (7 - 8 + 9)$$

• 239:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 \times 5 + 4) = 3!! / (2 + 1) - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 - 7 + 6! / 5 + 4 = 3!! / (2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 239:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 + 6 + 5! = \sqrt{4} \times (3 + 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 + 6 + 5! = (4 + 3)! / 21 - 0!$$

• 240

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!^3 + 4! = 5 \times 6 \times (7 - 8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 234 + 5 = 6 + 78 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 240:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / \sqrt{8 + 7 - 6} = 5! \times (4 - 3) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / \sqrt{8 + 7 - 6} = 5 \times \sqrt{4} \times 3 + 210$$

• 240:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 = (4 + 3)! / 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 + 65) = (4 + 3)! / 21 \\ = 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 10$$

• 240:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 87 + 6 \times 54 = 3!!/(2+1) = (3! - 2)! \times 10$
- ▶ $-9 + (8! - 7!)/(6!/5) + 4 = 3!!/(2+1) = (3! - 2)! \times 10$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^7 \times (6! - 5! \times 4) = 3!!/(2+1) = (3! - 2)! \times 10$
- ▶ $\left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right) \times (7 - 6 + 5!) - \sqrt{4} = 3!!/(2+1) = (3! - 2)! \times 10$

• 240:

- ▶ $(1 + 2)!!/3 = -4! + (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!!/3 = 4 + (\sqrt{5^6} - 7) \times \left(8 - (\sqrt{9})!\right)$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!!/3 = \sqrt{4} + (5! + 6 - 7) \times \left(8 - (\sqrt{9})!\right)$

• 241

▶ $1 + (2 + 3)! \times \sqrt{4} = 5 \times (-6 + 7 \times 8) - 9$

• 241:

- ▶ $\left(-\sqrt{9} + 8\right)! + 7 - 6 + 5! = \sqrt{4} \times (3 + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $\left(-\sqrt{9} + 8\right)! + 7 - 6 + 5! = (4 + 3)!/21 + 0!$
- ▶ $\left(-\sqrt{9} + 8\right)! + 7 - 6 + 5! = 4! \times (3^2 + 1) + 0!$

• 241:

- ▶ $-9 + (8 \times 7 - 6) \times 5 = 3!!/(2+1) + 0!$
- ▶ $(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 + 5! - 4 = 3!!/(2+1) + 0!$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^{76} + 5! \times \sqrt{4} = 3!!/(2+1) + 0!$

• 242

▶ $(1 + (2 + 3)!) \times \sqrt{4} = (5 + 6! - 7 + 8)/\sqrt{9}$

• 242:

- ▶ $-\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8\right) \times (7 - 6 + 5!) = \sqrt{4} \times ((3 + 2)! + 1)$
- ▶ $-\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8\right) \times (7 - 6 + 5!) = \sqrt{4} + 3!!/(2+1)$

• 243

▶ $(1+2) \times 3^4 = 5 \times 6! / (7+8) + \sqrt{9}$

• 243:

▶ $(9 \times (8-7) - 6)^5 = 4 + 3!! / (2+1) - 0!$

▶ $\sqrt{9+8!} + 7! + 6 \times 5 = 4 + 3!! / (2+1) - 0!$

• 243:

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! - 87 + 6 \times 54 = 3^{(2+1)!-0!}$

▶ $-9 + (-8 + 76 - 5) \times 4 = 3^{(2+1)!-0!}$

• 243:

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (87-6) = (5+4)^3 / (2+1)$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (87-6) = 5! + (\sqrt{4}+3)! + 2+1$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (87-6) = 54 \times 3^2 / (1+0!)$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (87-6) = 5 + \sqrt{4} \times (3+2)! - 1 - 0!$

• 244

▶ $(1+2)!! / 3+4 = \sqrt{5^6} + 7 \times (8+9)$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 76 + 5! = 4 + 3!! / (2+1)$

• 245

▶ $(1+2)!^3 + 4! + 5 = 6 \times (-7+8 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$

• 245:

▶ $(9+8) \times 7 + 6 + 5! = 4 + 3!! / (2+1) + 0!$

▶ $((\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 - 6) \times 5 = 4 + 3!! / (2+1) + 0!$

• **246**

▶ $123 \times \sqrt{4} = 5 \times 67 - 89$

▶ $\sqrt{9} + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{87-6}}\right)^5 = 4^{3!-2} - 10$

• **246:**

▶ $\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! \times 8 - 7\right) \times 6 = (5 \times 4! + 3) \times 2 \times 1$

▶ $\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! \times 8 - 7\right) \times 6 = 5! + 4 \times 32 - 1 - 0!$

• **247**

▶ $-\sqrt{9} + (8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5 = (4! + 3!)/(2 + 1) - 0!$

• **248**

• **248:**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (87 - 6) + 5 = (4! + 3!)/(2 + 1)$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (87 - 6) + 5 = 4 \times (3 \times 21 - 0!)$

• **249**

▶ $98 + 7 + 6!/5 = (4! + 3!)/(2 + 1) + 0!$

• **250**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 87 - 6 - 5 = \left(\sqrt{4} + 3\right)^2 \times 10$

• **251**

▶ $-9 + 8 + 7! \times 6/5! = 4 \times 3 \times 21 - 0!$

• **252**

▶ $12 \times (-3 + 4!) = (5 + 6 + 7) \times \left(8 + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)$

▶ $9 + \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{87-6}}\right)^5 = 4 \times 3 \times 21$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 76) = (5 + 4 + 3) \times 21$

• 252:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) = (6 + 78) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 3! \times 4! + 5! = (6 + 78) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 253

• 253:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + (8 \times 7 - 6) \times 5 = 43 + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7! \times 6 \right) / 5! = 43 + 210$$

• 254

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! \times 6 / 5! = 4^{3!-2} - 1 - 0!$$

• 255

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 - 3!)^4 = ((5 + 6) \times 7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 255:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 - 6 = 5! \times \sqrt{4} - 3! + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 - 6 = 5 \times (4 + 3)^2 + 10$$

• 255:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6) \times 5 = 4^{3!-2} - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6 \right) \times 5 = 4^{3+2-1} - 0!$$

• 256

$$\blacktriangleright (12/3)^4 = 5 \times (-6 + 7 \times 8) + (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 256:

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 \right)^{7+6-5} = 4^{3+2-1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 \right)^{7+6-5} = 4 \times (3 \times 21 + 0!)$$

• 257

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 + (-2 + 3!)^4 &= 5 + 6! - 78 \times (\sqrt{9})! \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! \times 6/5! &= 4^{3!-2} + 1 = 4^{3+2-1} + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 258

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = 43 \times (2 + 1)!$$

• 259

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8 \times 7 - 6) \times 5 = 43 \times (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• 260

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 = 5 \times 6 \times 78/9$$

• 260:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times 6 + 5! &= \sqrt{4} \times ((3 + 2)! + 10) \\ \blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times 6 + 5! &= (4 \times 3! + 2) \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 261

• 261:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 &= -6 - 54 + 321 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 &= 6 \times 5 + 4! - 3 + 210 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 &= 6 \times 54 - 3 \times 21 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 &= 6 + 5! \times \sqrt{4} - 3! + 21 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 &= 6 + 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 3)^2 \times 10 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 &= 65 + (4 \times 3 + 2)^{1+0!} \end{aligned}$$

• 263

• 263:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6!/5 &= 4! \times (3! \times 2 - 1) - 0! \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! \times 6/5! &= 4! \times (3! \times 2 - 1) - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 264

• 264:

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! = (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{1 + (2 + 3)!} \times 4! = (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

• 264:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5! = 4! \times (3! \times 2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5! = 4! \times (3 - 2 + 10)$$

• 265

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 = 4! \times (3! \times 2 - 1) + 0!$$

• 266

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4! + 5! = (6! + 78) / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7! / (6 \times 5) = 4^{3! - 2} + 10$$

• 267

$$\blacktriangleright 987 - 6 \times 5! = 4! + 3^{(2+1)! - 0!}$$

• 267:

$$\blacktriangleright 987 - 6! = -54 + 321 = 54 + 3 + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 + 6 = -54 + 321 = 54 + 3 + 210$$

• 270

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 45 = 6 \times (7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7) \times 6 \times 5 = (4! + 3! / 2) \times 10$$

• 270:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) \times 6 = 54 \times (3 + 2 \times 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) \times 6 = 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2) \times 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) \times 6 = 54 + 3! + 210$$

• 274

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (87 + 6) - 5 = 4^3 + 210$$

• 278

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 + 8! + 7!} + 65 = 4! \times 3! \times 2 - 10$$

• 279

• 279:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (87 + 6) = (5 + 4) \times (32 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (87 + 6) = 5 + 4^3 + 210$$

• 280

$$\blacktriangleright (98 - 7 \times 6) \times 5 = (-4 + 32) \times 10$$

• 282

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3! \times 45 = 6 \times (7 \times 8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 76 \times 5 = 4! \times 3 + 210$$

• 282:

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 = (5! + 4! - 3) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 = 5! + (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 = 5 \times (4! + 32) + 1 + 0!$$

• 284

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (87 + 6) + 5 = (4! \times 3! - 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 286

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + (8! - 7!)/(6 + 5!) = 4! \times 3! \times 2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 287

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! = (5 \times 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 = 4! \times 3! \times 2 - 1$$

• 288

▶ $12 \times 3! \times 4 = (5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 \times 9$

▶ $12 \times 34 - 5! = 6! / (7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• 288:

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! / (8 + 7) \times 6 = (5 + 4) \times 32 \times 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! / (8 + 7) \times 6 = (5 + 4) \times 32 - 1 + 0!$

• 288:

▶ $(9 \times 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5) = 4! \times 3! \times 2 \times 1$

▶ $(9 \times 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5) = 4! \times 3 \times (2 + 1 + 0!)$

• 289

▶ $1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! = -5 + 6 \times 7^{(8 - (\sqrt{9})!)}$

▶ $9 + 8 \times 7! / (6! / 5) = 4! \times 3! \times 2 + 1$

• 290

▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (-7 + 65) = (4! + 3 + 2) \times 10$

• 292

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7 \times \sqrt{6! \times 5} = (4! \times 3! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$

• 294

▶ $1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4! + 5 = 6 \times 7^{(8 - (\sqrt{9})!)}$

• 294:

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8! - 7!) / 6! = (5! + 4! + 3) \times 2 \times 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8! - 7!) / 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (32 + 10)$

• 296

▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 \times 6! / 5 = -4! + 32 \times 10$

• 300

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3) \times 4 \times 5 = 6 \times (7 \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• 300:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 \times 5 = (-\sqrt{4} + 32) \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 \times 5 = (4! + 3 \times 2) \times 10$$

• 300:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7 \times 6) = 5 \times (4 + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7 \times 6) = 5 \times 4^3 - 2 \times 10$$

• 301

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 = 43 \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• 306

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3! + 45) = (6 \times 7 - 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5) = \sqrt{4} - 3!! + 2^{10}$$

• 306:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7 \times 6) = (54 - 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7 \times 6) = 5! + (4! + 3!!) / (2 + 1 + 0!)$$

• 308

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 = 4 - 3!! + 2^{10}$$

• 311

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7! / (6 + 5!) = 4! \times (3! \times 2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 312

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! = -5! + 6! / (7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^3 \times 4! + 5! = (6 + 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 312:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7+6) = -5 - 4 + 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7+6) = 5 \times 4^3 + 2 - 10$$

• 312:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7+6!/5!) = 4! \times (3! \times 2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7+6!/5!) = 4! \times (3!/2 + 10)$$

• 313

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 = 4! \times (3! \times 2 + 1) + 0!$$

• 314

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! / (6 + 5!) = (-4! + 3!)^2 - 10$$

• 317

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7+6) + 5 = -4 + 321$$

• 318

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7) \times 6 = -5 + \sqrt{4} + 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 + 6! + 5! = -\sqrt{4} + 32 \times 10$$

• 319

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 = -\sqrt{4} + 321$$

• 320

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7)^6 \times 5 = 4^3 / 2 \times 10$$

• 320:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) / 6 \times 5 \times 4 = 32 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 \times 6! / 5 + 4! = 32 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 + 6! + 5! + \sqrt{4} = 32 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 = 32 \times 10$$

• 321

• 321:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 + 6 + 54 = 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times (8 + 7) + (-6 + 5!) \times 4 = 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 + \sqrt{4} = 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5 + 4 = 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times (7 + 6) - 5) + 4! = 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times \left((8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 + \sqrt{4} \right) = 321$$

• 322

• 322:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5 = (4! - 3!)^2 - 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5 = \sqrt{4} + 32 \times 10$$

• 322:

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7 \times (6 + 54) = 321 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7! / (6! / 5! \times \sqrt{4}) = 321 + 0!$$

• 323

• 323:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (7 + \sqrt{6! / 5}) = \sqrt{4} + 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 \right) \times 6 + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 321$$

• 324

• 324:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 4!) = 5 \times 67 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 4!) = (5! - 6 - 78) \times 9$$

• 324:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 - 76 + 5!) = (4! - 3!)^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 - 76 + 5!) = 4 + 32 \times 10$$

• 325

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} - 8 + 76) \times 5 = 4 + 321$$

• 326

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 + 65 = 4 + 321 + 0!$$

• 327

• 327:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = (5! - 4) \times 3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 5 + \sqrt{4} + 32 \times 10$$

• 330

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (-3! - 4 + 5!) = 6 \times (7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6) - 5! = (4! + 3^2) \times 10$$

• 330:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 5 + 4 + 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = (5 - 4 + 32) \times 10$$

• 333

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 345 = 6 \times 7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 333:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = (5 + 4) \times (3!^2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 5 + 4! - 3!! + 2^{10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 543 - 210$$

• 335

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 2 \times 34) \times 5 = 67 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

• 336

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 23)/4 \times 56 = 7 \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 336:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 = 6 + 5 + 4 + 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 = 6 \times 54 + (3 + 2)!/10$$

• 336:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7!/6! = (-5 + 4! - 3) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7!/6! = 5 \times 4! + 3! + 210$$

• 336:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + (7 - 6) \times 5!) = -4! + 3!/2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + (7 - 6) \times 5!) = 4! \times (3! - 2 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + (7 - 6) \times 5!) = 4! \times (-3! + 2 \times 10)$$

• 337

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6 - 5 = -4! + 3!/2 + 1$$

• 339

• 339:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 34 \times 5 = 6 \times 7 \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)! + 345 = 6 \times 7 \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 339:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = -5 + 43 \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 340

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 32) \times 10$$

• 342

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 345 = 6 + 7 \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! \times (7 - 6)/5! = (4 + 3)^{2+1} - 0!$$

• 342:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6 = (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 5 - 4! + 3!/2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6 = (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = (54 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6 = (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 5! + 4 \times 3 + 210$$

• 343

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 345 = (6 - 7 + 8)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 343:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + (-8 + 76) \times 5 = (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 \times (76 - 5!) = (4 + 3)^{2+1}$$

• 344

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5 = 43 \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 345

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times 345 = 6 \times 7 \times 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5! = 4! + 321$$

• 345:

- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 54 \times 3! + 21$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^3 + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = -5 + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! / 2 - 10$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 32) \times 10$

• 346

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + (-8 + 76) \times 5 = 4! + 321 + 0!$

• 347

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 = (-4! + 3!!) / 2 - 1$

• 348

▶ $-12 + 3!! / \sqrt{4} = (-5! / 6 + 78) \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• 348:

- ▶ $(-9 + 87) \times 6 - 5! = (-4! + 3!!) / 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7 + \sqrt{6! \times 5}) = (-4! + 3!!) / 2 \times 1$
 $= (-4 + 3!!) / 2 - 10$

• 349

• 349:

- ▶ $9 + (-8 + 76) \times 5 = (-4! + 3!!) / 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9 + (-8 + 76) \times 5 = (-4! + 3!! + 2) / (1 + 0!)$

• 350

- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5 = (-4! + 3!!) / 2 + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $98 + 7 \times 6! / (5 \times 4) = 3!! / 2 - 10$

• 351

▶ $9 \times (-87 + 6 + 5!) = (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) / 2 - 10$

• 352

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8! + 7!/6)/5! = \sqrt{4} + 3!/2 - 10$$

• 353

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 76 \times 5 = 4 + 3!/2 - 1$$

• 354

$$\blacktriangleright (-12 + 3!)/\sqrt{4} = (-5 + 6! - 7)/(8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 234 + 5! = 6 \times (7 \times 8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7) \times 6 = (-\sqrt{5! + 4!} + 3!)/2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7) \times 6 - 5! = 4! \times 3! + 210$$

• 355

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)!/2 - 10$$

• 355:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (76 - 5) = -4 + 3!/2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 = -4 + 3!/2 - 1$$

• 357

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 3!/\sqrt{4} = 5 \times (-6 + 78) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7 \times 65 = (-4 + 3!)/2 - 1$$

• 358

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + (7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4 = 3!/2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 358:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (-76 + 5!) = (-4 + 3!)/2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (-76 + 5!) = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)!/2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 359

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!/\sqrt{4} = 5 \times 67 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 359:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! / 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 = ((\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - 2) / (1 + 0!)$$

• 359:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 76 \times 5 - 4 = 3!! / 2 - 1 = 3!! / 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7 \times 65 + \sqrt{4} = 3!! / 2 - 1 = 3!! / 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (76 - 5) + 4 = 3!! / 2 - 1 = 3!! / 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5 + 4! = 3!! / 2 - 1 = 3!! / 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

• 360

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^3 \times 45 = (6 + 7 - 8)! \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 360:

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3) \times 4! = 5 \times (-6 + 7) \times 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3) \times 4! = 5! + 6 + 78 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 360:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 234 + 5! + 6 = 7! / (8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3 \times 4! \times 5 - 6 = 7! / (8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• 360:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7 + 6)! = 5 \times 4 \times (-3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7 + 6)! = 54 / 3 \times 2 \times 10$$

• 360:

- ▶ $(9 \times (8 - 7) - 6) \times 5! = (-9 + 87 - 6) \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! / 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(9 \times (8 - 7) - 6) \times 5! = (-9 + 87 - 6) \times 5 = 4! \times (-3! + 21)$
- ▶ $(9 \times (8 - 7) - 6) \times 5! = (-9 + 87 - 6) \times 5 = (4 + 32) \times 10$

• 360:

- ▶ $(-9 + 8 + 76) / 5 \times 4! = 3!! / 2 \times 1 = 3!^2 \times 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (-8 + (7 - 6) \times 5) + 4! = 3!! / 2 \times 1 = 3!^2 \times 10$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76 \times 5 + 4 = 3!! / 2 \times 1 = 3!^2 \times 10$

• 361

▶ $9 + (87 + 6 - 5) \times 4 = 3!! / 2 + 1$

• 361:

- ▶ $9 + 8 \times (-76 + 5!) = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! / 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times (-76 + 5!) = (4 + 3!!) / 2 - 1$

• 362

• 362:

- ▶ $98 \times 7 - 6 \times 54 = 3!! / 2 + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4! = 3!! / 2 + 1 + 0!$

• 363

- ▶ $1 + 2 + 3!! / \sqrt{4} = 5 \times (-6 + 78) + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $-9 - 8 + 76 \times 5 = 4 + 3!! / 2 - 1$

• 364

• 364:

- ▶ $\left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) / (7! / 6! - 5) = 4 + 3!! / 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $\left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) / (7! / 6! - 5) = 4 + 3!^2 \times 10$

• **365**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7 - 6) \times 5 = 4 + 3!!/2 + 1$$

• **366**

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3!!)/\sqrt{4} = 5 \times (67 + 8) - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)!/\sqrt{4} + 5 = 6 + 7!/(8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 76 \times 5 = 4 + 3!!/2 + 1 + 0!$$

• **368**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (76 - 5!) = (-4 + 3!!)/2 + 10$$

• **369**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{87 - 6} + 5!} \right) = (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!)/2 + 10$$

• **370**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)!/2 + 10$$

• **370:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 - 7) \times 6 - 5 \times 4 = 3!!/2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 87 + 6 + 5^4 = 3!!/2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (87 - 6) - 5! + 4 = 3!!/2 + 10$$

• **371**

• **371:**

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 76 \times 5 = (4! + 3!!)/2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 76 \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3!!)/2 + 10$$

• **372**

$$\blacktriangleright 123 \times 4 - 5! = (6 + 7 \times 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 372:

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \right) \times 6 = (5! + 4) \times 3 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \right) \times 6 = 54 \times 3 + 210$$

• 372:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 76) + 5! = (4! + 3!!) / 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 76) + 5! = \sqrt{4} + 3!! / 2 + 10$$

• 374

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) + 7 \times 65 = 4! + 3!! / 2 - 10$$

• 377

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7 + 6) + 5 = (4! - 3!) \times 21 - 0!$$

• 378

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 - 5! = (4! - 3!) \times 21$$

• 378:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 7 \times 6 = 5 + (4! + 3!!) / 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! + 7!) / 6! = 54 / 3 \times 21$$

• 379

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 76 \times 5 = (4! - 3!) \times 21 + 0!$$

• 380

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 76 \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3!^2) \times 10$$

• 380:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) \times 76 = 5 \times 4 + 3!! / 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) \times 76 = 5 \times (43 \times 2 - 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) \times 76 = 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3!! / 2 + 10$$

• 382

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 76 \times 5 = 4! + 3!!/2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 383

• 383:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 65 = 4! + 3!!/2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 65 = 4^3 \times (2+1)! - 0!$$

• 384

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 4! + 5) = 6! - 7 \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = (5 + 43) \times (-2 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5) = 4^3 \times (2+1)! = 4 \times 3 \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 385

• 385:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 76) \times 5 = 4! + 3!!/2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 76) \times 5 = 4^3 \times (2+1)! + 0!$$

• 386

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)! + 76 \times 5 = 4! + 3!!/2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 390

• 390:

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times 5 = 6 \times (7 \times 8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (3! + 4 + 5!) = 6 \times (7 \times 8 + 9)$$

• 390:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 = 5!/4 + 3!!/2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 = (5! + 4 + 3!) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 = \left(5 + \sqrt{4} + 32 \right) \times 10$$

• 392

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 + 3!!) / \sqrt{4} + 5 \times 6 = 7 \times 8! / (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 394

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 76 \times 5 = 4! + 3!! / 2 + 10$$

• 396

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + (87 - 6) \times 5 = (4! - 3!) \times (21 + 0!)$$

• 400

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7! / (6 + 5!) = (4 + 3!^2) \times 10$$

• 408

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 34 = (5 + 6 - 7)! \times (8 + 9)$$

• 408:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (-8 + 76) = (5! - 4! + 3!!) / 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (-8 + 76) = (54 - 3) \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 408:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! = 4! \times (-3 + 2 \times 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 87 + 6 - 5! = 4! \times (-3 + 2 \times 10)$$

• 410

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + 7 - 6} \right) \times 5 = (43 - 2) \times 10$$

• 414

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 + 3^4) \times 5 = 6 \times (78 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (87 - 6) \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (-3 + 210)$$

• 416

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! \right) / \sqrt{6! / 5} = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! - 2^{10}$$

• 420

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 4) \times 5 = 6 \times 7! / (8 \times 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 / 7 \times 6 \times 5 = (4! - 3) \times 2 \times 10$$

• 422

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! / \sqrt{6! / 5} = 432 - 10$$

• 426

$$\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)! + 3 \times (4! + 5!) = 6 \times \sqrt{7! - 8 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + (8 + 76) \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3 + 210)$$

• 430

$$\blacktriangleright \left((-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7! \right) / \sqrt{6! / 5} = \sqrt{43^2} \times 10$$

• 431

• 431:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 \times 65 = 432 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 - 8 + 7!} \times 6 + 5 = 432 - 1$$

• 432

• 432:

$$\blacktriangleright 12^3 / 4 = (-5 \times 6 + 78) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3!) \times 4! = (-5 \times 6 + 78) \times 9 \\ = (5 - 6 + 7) \times 8 \times 9$$

• 432:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 \times 4! - 5! = 6! / (7 + 8) \times 9(-6 + 78) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! + 5! = 6! / (7 + 8) \times 9(-6 + 78) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 432:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7! \times 6 = 54 \times (3^2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7! \times 6 = 5! \times (4 + 32)/10$$

• 432:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5) = 432 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times \sqrt{76 + 5} = 432 \times 1$$

• 433

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 \times (7 - \sqrt{6! \times 5}) = 432 + 1$$

• 434

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 \times \sqrt{6! \times 5} = 432 + 1 + 0!$$

• 439

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 65 = (4! - 3)^2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 440

• 440:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! / (6 + 5!) = (4! - 3)^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! / (6 + 5!) = 4 \times ((3 + 2)! - 10)$$

• 441

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 = (4! - 3) \times 21$$

• 441:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! - 7!) / 6! = 5 \times 4! + 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! - 7!) / 6! = (5 + 4 + 3! \times 2)^{1+0!}$$

• 444

• 444:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) - 7 \right) \times 6 &= 5! + (-4! + 3!)^2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) - 7 \right) \times 6 &= 5! + \sqrt{4} + 321 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 445

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2^{3!} + 4!) \times 5 = -67 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 450

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (3! + 4! + 5!) = (6 \times 7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87 - 6) \times 5 = (43 + 2) \times 10$$

• 450:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6) &= 5^{\sqrt{4}} \times 3! \times (2 + 1) \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6) &= 5 \times (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1) \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6) &= \sqrt{5^4} \times (-3 + 21) \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6) &= 5! \times 4 - \sqrt{3^2} \times 10 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6) &= 5! + (4! + 3^2) \times 10 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6) &= -5! \times 4 + 3!! + 210 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6) &= (54 - 3^2) \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 451

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 \right) \times (6 + 5) = (4! - 3)^2 + 10$$

• 455

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 65 = 4! \times \sqrt{3!!/2 + 1} - 0!$$

• 456

• 456

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)! \times 76 &= 5! \times 4 - 3 - 21 \\ \blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)! \times 76 &= (-5 + 4!) \times 3 \times (-2 + 10) \end{aligned}$$

• 456:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 \times 65 = 4! \times \sqrt{3!!/2 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (87 + 65) = 4! \times \sqrt{3!!/2 + 1}$$
$$= 4! \times (3^2 + 10)$$

• 457

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 87 - 65 = 4! \times \sqrt{3!!/2 + 1} + 0!$$

• 459

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23 \times 4 \times 5 = 6 \times 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 87 + 6! = 5! \times 4!/3! - 21$$

• 462

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (34 + 5!) = 6 \times 78 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7 \times 6 + 5!) = (4! - 3) \times (21 + 0!)$$

• 462:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 \times 6 = 5! \times 4 + 3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 \times 6 = (\sqrt{5^4} - 3) \times 21$$

• 465

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3^4) \times 5 = 6 \times 78 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 468

$$\blacktriangleright (123 - 45) \times 6 = 78 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 76 + 5!) = 4 \times (-3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!))$$

• 468:

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 87) \times 6 = 5! \times 4 - 3! \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 87) \times 6 = 5! \times 4 - 3 \times 2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 470

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) + 7 + 6 \right) \times 5 = 4 \times (3 + 2)! - 10$$

• 471

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 3 + 4 \times 5! = 6 \times 78 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 472

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 \times 65 = 4 \times ((3 + 2)! - 1 - 0!)$$

• 474

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 \times 3 + 4 \times 5! = 6 \times (7 + 8 \times 9)$$

• 474:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7) \times 6 = 5! \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7) \times 6 = 5! + (5! - 4) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7) \times 6 = \left(\sqrt{5^4} - 3 \right)^2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7) \times 6 = 5! + 4! \times 3! + 210$$

• 475

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5 = 4 \times ((3 + 2)! - 1) - 0!$$

• 476

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 = 5 + 6 \times 78 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9} \right)!! + 8 - 7! \times 6/5! = 4 \times ((3 + 2)! - 1)$$

• 477

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 2) \times 3 + 4 \times 5! = 6 \times 78 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8!/7! \times \sqrt{6! \times 5} = 4 \times ((3 + 2)! - 1) + 0!$$

• 478

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 76 \times 5 = 4 \times (3 + 2)! - 1 - 0!$$

• 479

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 = 4 \times (3 + 2)! - 1$$

• 479:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2+3)! \times 4 = 5 + 6 + 78 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2+3)! \times 4 = 5 + 6 \times (7+8 \times 9)$$

• 480

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2+3)! \times 4 = 5!/6 \times (7+8+9)$$

• 480:

$$\blacktriangleright (9+8-7-6) \times 5! = 4 \times (3+2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9+8-7-6) \times 5! = 4 \times 3! \times 2 \times 10$$

• 481

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2+3)! \times 4 = 56 \times 7 + 89$$

• 481:

$$\blacktriangleright -(9+8) \times 7 + 6! - 5! = 4 \times (3+2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (87-6) - 5 = 4 \times (3+2)! + 1 \\ = 4 \times 3! / (2+1)! + 0!$$

• 482

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 76 - 5! = \sqrt{4} \times (3! / (2+1) + 0!)$$

• 483

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8!/7! \times \sqrt{6! \times 5} = 4 \times ((3+2)! + 1) - 0!$$

• 484

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + (2+3)!) \times 4 = -5!/6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (76 - 5!) = 4 \times ((3+2)! + 1)$$

• 485

$$\blacktriangleright (98 - 7 + 6) \times 5 = 4 \times ((3+2)! + 1) + 0!$$

• 486

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! \times 3^4 = (-5+67-8) \times 9$$

• 486:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3 + 4 \times 5! = 6 \times (78 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{3^{4 \times 5}}} \right) = 6 \times (78 + \sqrt{9})$$

• 486:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (87-6) = 54 \times 3^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (87-6) = 5 + 4 \times (3+2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (87-6) = 54 \times (-3+2+10)$$

• 488

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (7+6!/5) = 4 \times ((3+2)! + 1 + 0!)$$

• 490

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (7-6) \times 5 = (4+3)^2 \times 10$$

• 492

• 492:

$$\blacktriangleright 123 \times 4 = 5! + (6+7 \times 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 123 \times 4 = \sqrt{5 \times 6!} \times 7 + 8 \times 9$$

• 492:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3! + 4 \times 5! = 6 \times (-7 + 89)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3!!/\sqrt{4} + 5! = 6 \times (-7 + 89)$$

• 492:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times (8 - 76) - 5! = 4 \times (3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!))!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 87 - 6 \times 5 = 4 \times (3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!))!$$

• 498

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3! + 4 \times 5! = -6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 = 5! \times 4 - 3 + 21$$

• 500

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 76) \times 5 = 4 \times (3! \times 21 - 0!)$$

• 502

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7 \times 6 \times 5 = \sqrt{4^{3^2}} - 10$$

• 503

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5 = 4 \times 3! \times 21 - 0!$$

• 504

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (-3 + 45) = (6 + 78) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! = 4 \times 3! \times 21$$

• 504:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 87) \times 6 = 5! \times 4 + 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 87) \times 6 = \sqrt{5! + 4!} \times (32 + 10)$$

• 504:

▶ $12 \times (3 + 45 - 6) = 7 \times 8 \times 9$

▶ $12 + 3! + 4 \times 5! + 6 = 7 \times 8 \times 9$

▶ $12 \times (3 \times 4 - 5) \times 6 = 7 \times 8 \times 9$

▶ $(-1 + 23)^{\sqrt{4}} + 5!/6 = 7 \times 8 \times 9$

$9 \times 8 \times 7 = (6 - 5) \times 4 \times 3! \times 21$

$9 \times 8 \times 7 = 6 \times (5! - 4 - 32 \times 1)$

$9 \times 8 \times 7 = 6 + 5! \times 4 - 3 + 21$

$9 \times 8 \times 7 = 6 + 5! + (4! - 3!) \times 21$

$9 \times 8 \times 7 = (6 + 54/3) \times 21$

$9 \times 8 \times 7 = (-6 + 5 \times 4) \times 3 \times (2 + 10)$

$9 \times 8 \times 7 = (6 + 5!) \times (-\sqrt{4 + 32} + 10)$

$9 \times 8 \times 7 = 6 \times (54 + 32 - 1 - 0!)$

$9 \times 8 \times 7 = 65 + (4! - 3!)^2 - 1 - 0!$

• 505

▶ $-1 + 2 + \sqrt{3^4} \times 56 = -7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$

• 505:

▶ $9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 - 5 = 4 \times 3! \times 21 + 0!$

▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times 5 = 4 \times 3! \times 21 + 0!$

• 506

▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8(\sqrt{\sqrt{76+5}}) = -4 + 3!! - 210$

• 507

▶ $-\sqrt{9 + 8! + 7!} + 6! = 5! \times 4 + 3! + 21$

• 508

▶ $-9 + 87 \times 6 - 5 = 4 \times (3! \times 21 + 0!)$

• 510

▶ $(1 + 2) \times 34 \times 5 = 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9$

▶ $(9 + 87 + 6) \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - 210$

• 510:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 = 5 \times (-4! + 3! \times 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 = (5 - 4) \times 3!! - 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 = (54 - \sqrt{3^2}) \times 10$$

• 510:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8\sqrt{\sqrt{76+5}} + 4 = 3!! - 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4) = 3!! - 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) \times (7 - 6 + 5) + 4! = 3!! - 210$$

• 511

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2^{\sqrt{3^4}} = 5 \times (6 + 7) \times 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2^{(3 \times \sqrt{4+5})} = 6 - 7 + 8\sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5 = \sqrt{4^{3^2}} - 1 = (4!/3)^{2+1} - 0!$$

• 512

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{\sqrt{3^4}} = (5 \times 6 / (7 + 8))^9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right)^{\sqrt{76+5}} = \sqrt{4^{3^2}} \times 1 = 4^3 \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 512:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2^{3!} + 4!) \times 5 + 67 = 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-12 + 3!!) / 4 + 5 \times 67 = 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{-3+4+56/7} = 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3 \times 4) \times 5 + 56 \times 7 = 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3 + 4 \times \sqrt{5^6} + 7 = 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 2 + 3)^{4+5} \times (-6 + 7) = 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{12/3})^{4+5} \times (-6 + 7) = 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 513

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{\sqrt{3^4}} = (56 - 7 + 8) \times 9$$

• 513:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 \times 6 = 5! \times 4 + 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 \times 6 = 5 + 4 \times (3! \times 21 + 0!)$$

• 513:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (87 - 6 \times 5) = \sqrt{4^{3^2}} + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (87 - 6 \times 5) = (4!/3)^{2+1} + 0!$$

• 516

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 76 - 5! = 43 \times (2 + 10)$$

• 516:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 87 - 6 = 5 + \sqrt{4^{3^2}} - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 87 - 6 = 5! \times 4 + 3 \times (2 + 10)$$

• 519

• 519:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23^{\sqrt{4}} - 5 - 6 = 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{3 \times \sqrt{4+5}} + 6 = 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 519:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 \times 6 = 5 + 4 + 3!! - 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 \times 6 = (5 + 4)^3 - 210$$

• 520

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times 65 = 4 \times ((3 + 2)! + 10)$$

• 522

▶ $(1 + 2) \times 3! \times (4! + 5) = 6 \times (78 + 9)$

▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5! + 432 \times 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 \times (6 - 5) = \sqrt{4^{3^2}} + 10$

• 522:

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 = (6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 + 21$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 = 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 - 210$

• 522:

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 = (6 + 5!) \times 4 - 3 + 21$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 = 6 + 5! \times 4 + 3!^2 \times 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 = 6 + 5 + \sqrt{4^{3^2}} - 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 = 6 \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)!)$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 = 6 + 5! \times 4 + 3 \times (2 + 10)$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 = (6 - 5) \times \sqrt{4^{3^2}} + 10$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 = 65 + 4! \times \sqrt{3!!/2 + 1} + 0!$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 = 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 - 210$

• 525

▶ $1 + 23^{\sqrt{4}} - 5 = 6 + 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$

▶ $\sqrt{9} + 87 \times 6 = 5 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3) \times 21$

• 527

▶ $-1 + 2 \times (3! \times 4! + 5!) = 67 \times 8 - 9$

• 528

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (87 + 6 - 5) = 4! \times (32 - 10)$

• 528:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (-1 + 23) \times 4! &= -5 + 67 \times 8 - \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright -1 + 23^{\sqrt{4}} &= -5 + 67 \times 8 - \sqrt{9} \\ &= -5! + (-6 + 78) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

• 528:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 87 \times 6 &= (5 \times 4 + 3)^2 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 87 \times 6 &= (5 \times 4 + 3)^2 \times 1 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 529

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 23^{\sqrt{4}} &= 5 \times (6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5 &= (4! - 3 + 2)^{1+0!} \end{aligned}$$

• 530

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23^{\sqrt{4}} = 5 + 6 + 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 531

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 87 \times 6 = 543 - 2 - 10$$

• 533

• 533:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -1 + 23^{\sqrt{4}} + 5 &= 67 \times 8 - \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright (-1 + 23) \times 4! + 5 &= 67 \times 8 - \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 534

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 23^{\sqrt{4}} + 5 &= (-6! + 7!) / 8 - (\sqrt{9})! \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 &= 4! + 3!! - 210 \end{aligned}$$

• 539

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3! \times 45 = 67 \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 540

- ▶ $(1+2) \times 3!!/4 = -5 + 67 \times 8 + 9$
- ▶ $1 \times 2 \times 3! \times 45 = 6 \times (7+8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9}+8+7) \times 6 \times 5 = (4!+3) \times 2 \times 10$

• 540:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9}+87) \times 6 = 543 - 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9}+87) \times 6 = 54 \times (3-2) \times 10$

• 543

- ▶ $-1 + 2^{3!} + 4 \times 5! = (-6! + 7!)/8 + \sqrt{9}$

• 545

- ▶ $(1+2) \times 3!!/4 + 5 = 67 \times 8 + 9$

• 546

• 546:

- ▶ $(98-7) \times 6 = 543 + 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(98-7) \times 6 = 5! + \sqrt{4} \times (3+210)$

• 551

- ▶ $-1 + 23 \times 4! = 5 + (-6! + 7!)/8 + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(98-7) \times 6 + 5 = 4! \times ((3! - 2!) - 1) - 0!$

• 552

- ▶ $12 \times 3! + 4 \times 5! = 6! - 7 \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5! + 432 \times 1$

• 552:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 + 6 \times 5 = 4! \times ((3! - 2!) - 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 87 + 6 \times 5 = 4! \times (3 + 2 \times 10)$

• 552:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 \times 4! = -5! + 678 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 \times 4! = 5! + 6! / (7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 \times 4! = 5! + 6 \times (78 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• 553

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 \times 4! = -5 + (6 + 7 \times 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times 65 = 4! \times ((3! - 2)! - 1) + 0!$$

• 558

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 \times 4! + 5 = (6 + 7 \times 8) \times 9$$

• 558:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) = (5! - 4! - 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) = (5! - 4) \times 3 + 210$$

• 560

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3)! / (4 + 5) = (6 - 7 + 8)! / 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 - 6 - 5! = (4! + 32) \times 10$$

• 561

• 561:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 - 6 = 5! \times \sqrt{4} + 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 - 6 = 5^4 - 3 \times 21 - 0!$$

• 566

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 - 6 + 5 = (4 \times 3!)^2 - 10$$

• 567

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! + 7!) / 6! = (5 + 4) \times 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times (7 + 65) = (4! + 3) \times 21$$

• 567:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 = 6! - (5! - 43) \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 = 6 + 5! \times \sqrt{4} + 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 = (65 - \sqrt{4}) \times 3^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 = 6 + 5^4 - 3 \times 21 - 0!$$

• 568

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 + 6 - 5 = (4! + 3) \times 21 + 0!$$

• 572

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 + 6 - 5! = -4 + (3! - 2)!^{1+0!}$$

• 573

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 + 6 = 5 + (4! + 3) \times 21 + 0!$$

• 574

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (76 - 5) = (4 \times 3!)^2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 575

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (-2 + 3!) \times 4! = 56 + 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 576

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 45) = 6 \times (7 + 89)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7) \times 6! / 5 = 4! \times (3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 87 + 654 = (3! - 2)!^{1+0!}$$

• 576:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 23) \times 4! = 56/7 \times 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 23)^{\sqrt{4}} = 56/7 \times 8 \times 9$$

• 576:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6 = -5! - 4 + 3!! - 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6 = (5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6 = (5 + 43) \times (2 + 10)$$

• 577

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (-2 + 3!)! \times 4! = \sqrt{-5 + 6 + 7!} \times 8 + 9$$

• 577:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (76 - 5) = (4 \times 3!)^2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (76 - 5) = 4! \times (3 + 21) + 0!$$

• 578

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 + 6 + 5 = 4! \times (3! - 2)! + 1 + 0!$$

• 579

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3 - 4! - 5! = 67 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 580

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! - 5 = 4 + (3! - 2)!^{1+0!}$$

• 582

• 582:

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 \right) \times 6 = 5 + (4 \times 3!)^2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 \right) \times 6 = (5! + 4) \times 3 + 210$$

• 585

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 45 = 6! - (7 + 8) \times 9$$

• 585:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! = 5 \times (-4 + (3 + 2)! + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times (8 + 7) + 6! = 5 + 4 + (3! - 2)!^{1+0!}$$

• 586

$$\blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6! - 5! = (4 \times 3!)^2 + 10$$

• 588

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! - 4! - 5! = 6 \times 7 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7 \times 6 = (\sqrt{5^4} + 3) \times 21$$

• 592

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! - 8)^7 + 6! = 5^4 - 32 - 1$$

• 593

• 593:

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 + 6! = 5^4 - 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 + 6! = 5^4 - 32 + 1 - 0!$$

• 594

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7 + 65) = (4! + 3) \times (21 + 0!)$$

• 596

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! - 5 = -4 + 3!! - ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• 599

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 - 8)^7 + 6! - 5! = 4! \times ((3! - 2)! + 1) - 0!$$

• 599:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 76 = 5 \times 4! \times (3 + 2) - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 76 = \sqrt{5^4} \times (3! - 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 76 = 5! + 4 \times (3 + 2 \times 1)! - 0!$$

• 600

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3! + 4) \times 5 = 6! - ((7 + 8)/\sqrt{9})!$$

• 600:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + (-2 + 3)!) \times 4! = 5! \times (-67 + 8 \times 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - (3 + \sqrt{4})! = 5! \times (-67 + 8 \times 9)$$

• 600:

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! - 8 + 7\right)! + 6! = \sqrt{5^4} \times (3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! - 8 + 7\right)! + 6! = (54 + 3 \times 2) \times 10$$

• 600:

$$\blacktriangleright (98 - 7) \times 6 + 54 = 3!! - ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(-\sqrt{9} + 8\right)! - 7 + 6! + 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3!! - ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• 600:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times (6! - 5!) = 4! \times ((3! - 2)! + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! \times (8 - 7) / 6 \times 5 &= 4! \times ((3! - 2)! + 1) \\ &= 4! \times (3 + 21 + 0!) \\ &= \left(\sqrt{4} + 3\right)! \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• 601

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 + 3)! + 4 \times 5! = 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 + 6! - 5! = 4! \times ((3! - 2)! + 1) + 0!$$

• 601:

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! = 5^4 - 3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! = 5 \times 4! \times (3 + 2) + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! = 5 - 4 + 3!! - ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• 602

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7+6!-5=\sqrt{4}+3!!-((2+1)!-0)!$$

• 602:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!+8 \times 76=-5!+(\sqrt{4} \times 3)!+2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!+8 \times 76=5^4-3-2 \times 10$$

• 604

$$\blacktriangleright -9+8 \times 76+5=4+3!!-((2+1)!-0)!$$

• 605

• 605:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9}+8 \times 76=5 \times (4! \times (3+2)+1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9}+8 \times 76=5 \times ((\sqrt{4}+3)!+2-1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9}+8 \times 76=-5^{\sqrt{4}}+3 \times 210$$

• 606

• 606:

$$\blacktriangleright -(9+8) \times 7+6!+5=-4!+3 \times 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (87-6)+5!=-4!+3 \times 210$$

• 607

• 607:

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7+6!=5^4+3-21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7+6!=5^4-3!-2-10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7+6!=5+\sqrt{4}+3!!-((2+1)!-0)!$$

• 611

• 611:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 76 = 5 \times \left((\sqrt{4} + 3)! + 2 \right) + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 76 = 5^4 + 3! - 2 \times 10$$

• 612

• 612:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 76) = -5! + 4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 76) = (54 - 3) \times (2 + 10)$$

• 614

• 614:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 76 = 5^4 - 3! \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 76 = 5^4 - 3 + 2 - 10$$

• 615

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{123\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 5 = -6 + 7! / 8 - 9$$

• 615:

$$\blacktriangleright -98 - 7 + 6! = 5^4 - 3^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98 - 7 + 6! = 5^4 \times (3 - 2) - 10$$

• 616

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times (7 + 6) = 5^4 - 3^2 \times 1$$

• 617

• 617:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 76 = 5^4 - 3^2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 76 = -5! - 4 + 3!! + 21 \times 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 76 = 5^4 + \sqrt{3!} - 2 - 10$$

• 618

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! - 3! + 4! - 5! = -6 + 7!/8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 620

$$\blacktriangleright -98 - 7 + 6! + 5 = (4^3 - 2) \times 10$$

• 621

• 621:

$$\blacktriangleright -123 + (4+5!) \times 6 = 7!/8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{123\sqrt{4}} \times 5 + 6 = 7!/8 - 9$$

• 622

• 622:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5^4 - 3! + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5^4 - 3 + 21 \times 0$$

• 623

$$\blacktriangleright -(1+2) \times 34 + 5 + 6! = 7 \times 89$$

• 623:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!!/8 - 7 + 6! = 5^4 - 3 + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!!/8 - 7 + 6! = -5 - \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 210$$

• 624

$$\blacktriangleright (1+23) \times (-4+5 \times 6) = 7!/8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7 + 6! - 5 = 4! \times (3! + 2 \times 10)$$

• 624:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2+3)^4 = 5! \times 6 - 7 - 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2+3)^4 = -5 + 6 + 7 \times 89$$

• 624:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2 \times 3)! + 4! - 5! = 6! - 7 - 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! + 4! - 5! = 6! - 7 - 89$$

• 624:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 87 + 6! = 5^4 \times (3 - 2) - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 87 + 6! = 5^4 + 3^2 - 10$$

• 625

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 + 3)^4 = 5 \times (6 + 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + 7) \times 6 - 5 = (4! + 3 - 2)^{1+0!}$$

• 626

• 626:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 + 3)^4 = (-56 + 7!)/8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 + 3)^4 = 5 + 6! \times 7/8 - 9$$

• 627

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 + 4 - 5! + 6! = 7!/8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 627:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 87 - 6 = 5^4 + 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 87 - 6 = 5^4 - 3! - 2 + 10$$

• 629

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 + 3)^4 + 5 = 6 + 7 \times 89$$

• 629:

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 3 + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7 + 6! = 5 + 4! \times (3!^2 - 10)$$

• 629:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 - 87 + 6! + 5 &= (4! + 3!) \times 21 - 0! \\ \blacktriangleright -98 + 7 + 6 \times 5! &= (4! + 3!) \times 21 - 0! \\ &= -5 + 4 + 3 \times 210 \end{aligned}$$

• 630

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2+3)^4 + 5 = 6! - (7+8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 \times 7 = 654 - 3 - 21$$

• 630:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5! &= (4! + 3!) \times 21 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5! &= (4+3)! / (-2+10) \end{aligned}$$

• 630:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (98+7) \times 6 &= 5^4 + 3 \times 2 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (98+7) \times 6 &= 5 \times \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times 21 \\ \blacktriangleright (98+7) \times 6 &= (54+3^2) \times 10 \\ \blacktriangleright (98+7) \times 6 &= (5+4)/3 \times 210 \\ \blacktriangleright (98+7) \times 6 &= 5 + (\sqrt{4}+3)^{2 \times (1+0!)} \end{aligned}$$

• 630:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 - 8 - 7 + 654 &= 3 \times 210 \\ \blacktriangleright (9+87) \times 6 + 54 &= 3 \times 210 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (87-6) + 5! + 4! &= 3 \times 210 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!!/8 - 7 + 6! + 5 + \sqrt{4} &= 3 \times 210 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 87 - 6 + 5 - \sqrt{4} &= 3 \times 210 \end{aligned}$$

• 631

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 76 - 5 = (4! + 3!) \times 21 + 0!$$

• 632

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 87 - 6 + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 210$$

• 632:

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) - 7 + 6! = 5! + \sqrt{4^{3^2}} \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) - 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 3! + 2 - 1$$

• 633

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3 \times (4! + 5) = 6! - 78 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 23 \times 4 + 5 + 6! = 7!/8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 633:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 87 = 6 + 5^4 + 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 87 = 6 + 5^4 - 3! - 2 + 10$$

• 634

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 + 3 \times 210$$

• 636

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! + 4! - 5! = 6! - 78 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 34 - 5! + 6! = 7!/8 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 636:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 87 + 6! = 5^4 + 3! \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 87 + 6! = 5! + 43 \times (2 + 10)$$

• 637

• 637:

$$\blacktriangleright - (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7 + 6! = -5 + \sqrt{4} \times 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright - (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7 + 6! = 5^4 + \sqrt{3!} - 2 + 10$$

• 638

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 23) \times (4! + 5) = 6! + 7 - 89$$

• 639

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3^4 = 567 + 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2^{3+4} \times 5 = 6! \times 7/8 + 9$$

• 639:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 87 + 6! = 5 \times 4 \times 32 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 87 + 6! = 5 + 4 + 3 \times 210$$

• 640

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7!/6 \right) \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 32 \times 10$$

• 641

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{3+4} \times 5 = 6! - 7 - 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 87 + 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 321 - 0!$$

• 641:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 \times 4 \times 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 3 \times 2 + 10$$

• 641:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 \times 4 \times 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 3 \times 2 + 10$$

• 642

$$\blacktriangleright -123 + 45 + 6! = -78 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 87 + 6! = 5 \times 4 \times 32 + 1 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 87 + 6 \times 5! = \sqrt{4} \times 321$$

• 643

• 643:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8!/7! + 6! = 5^4 - 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 + 6! = 5^4 - 3 + 21$$

$$= 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 321 + 0!$$

• 644

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 87 + 6 + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (321 + 0!)$$

• 644:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)!! - 76 = 5^4 + \sqrt{3!!/2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)!! - 76 = (5 \times 43) \times (2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 645

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2^{3+4}) \times 5 = 6 + 7!/8 + 9$$

• 646

• 646:

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7 + 6! = 5^{4!/3!} + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7 + 6! = 5 \times 43 \times (2 + 1) + 0!$$

• 647

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 87 + 6! + 5 = 4! \times 3^{2+1} - 0!$$

• 648

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8!/7! + 6! = 5^4 + 3 + 2 \times 10$$

• 648:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! \times (4 + 5) = (-6 + 78) \times 9 \\ &\blacktriangleright -1 + 23^{\sqrt{4}} + 5! = 6 - 78 + (\sqrt{9})!! \end{aligned}$$

• 648:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^3 \times 4! = (5 - 6 + 7)! - 8 \times 9 \\ &\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^3 \times 4! = (5 \times 6 + 78) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\ &\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^3 \times 4! = 5 + 6! - 7 \times (8 + \sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

• 648:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!/5 = 9 \times 8 \times \sqrt{76 + 5} = 4! \times (3! + 21) \\ &\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!/5 = 9 \times 8 \times \sqrt{76 + 5} = 4! \times 3^{2+1} \\ &\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!/5 = 9 \times 8 \times \sqrt{76 + 5} = (4! - 3!)^2 \times (1 + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• 649

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23^{\sqrt{4}} + 5! = 6! - \sqrt{7!} - 8 + 9 \\ &\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9 - 8 + 7!} + 6! = 4! \times 3^{2+1} + 0! \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5) = 5^4 + 3 + 21 \end{aligned}$$

• 650

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23^{\sqrt{4}} + 5! = 6! - 7! / (8 \times 9)$$

• 652

• 652:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 76 = 5^4 + 3^{2+1} \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 76 = 5 + 4! \times 3^{2+1} - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 654

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5) = 4! + 3 \times 210$$

• 655

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2^{3!} + (\sqrt{4+5})!! = 6! + 7 - 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 32 - 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! = -4^3 + (2+1)!! - 0!$$

• 656

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 - 6 \times 5 = -4^3 + (2+1)!!$$

• 657

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - (8! + 7!)/6! = 5^4 + 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (76 + 5) = -4^3 + (2+1)!! + 0!$$

• 658

• 658:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times 7 + 6! = -5! + 4! \times 32 + 10$$

• 660

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 = (4^3 + 2) \times 10$$

• 661

• 661:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 3!^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 3 \times (2+10)$$

• 664

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/(-7!/6 + 5!) = -4! + 3!! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 664:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7 = 654 + 3^2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7 = 654 \times (3-2) + 10$$

• 664:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7!/6! = -54 + 3!! - 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7!/6! = -5 \times 4! \times 3 + 2^{10}$$

• 665

• 665:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 + 6! = -54 + (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 + (4^3 + 2) \times 10$$

• 667

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 \times (4! + 5) = 6! - 7 \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 32 + 10$$

• 669

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3! - 45 = 678 - 9$$

• 670

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - (3! + 4) \times 5 = 6 - 7 \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times 7 + 6! = (5 + 4^3 - 2) \times 10$$

• 671

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - (8! - 7!)/6! = -5 - 4! + 3!! - 21 + 0!$$

• 671:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23 \times 4! + 5! = 6! - 7^{(8 - (\sqrt{9})!)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23 \times 4! + 5! = 6! + (7! - 8!) / (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 672

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 \times 4! + 5! = 678 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! \times 6 = (5 + 4! + 3) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times (-7 + 6) + 5!) = 4! \times (3^{2+1} + 0!)$$

• 673

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23 \times 4! + 5! = 6! - 7 \times 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 3! \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 675

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6! = \sqrt{5^4} \times 3^{2+1}$$

• 675:

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3) \times 45 = (67 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! - 45 = 678 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 675:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 - 6 - 5 = -4! + 3!! - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 = -4! + 3!! - 21$$

• 678

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 = -43 + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 \right) \times 6 + 5 \times 4 = 3!! - 21 - 0!$$

• 679

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 3!! - 4! - 5 = 6! + 7 - 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 679:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 + 6! = -5 \times 4 + 3!! - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 - 4! + 3!! - 21 - 0!$$

• 680

• 680:

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 - 6 = 5 - 4! + 3!! - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 - 6 = -5 \times 4 + 3!! - 2 \times 10$$

• 681

▶ $(1 + 2)!! + 3! - 45 = 678 + \sqrt{9}$

• 684

▶ $12 \times 3 \times (4! - 5) = 678 + (\sqrt{9})!$

• 684:

▶ $-12 + 3!! - 4! = -5 + 6! - 7 - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

▶ $-12 + 3!! - 4! = (5!/6 + 7 \times 8) \times 9$

• 684:

▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 76 = (-5 + 4!) \times 3!^2 \times 1$

▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 76 = 54 + 3 \times 210$

• 684:

▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 = -4 + 3!! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$

▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 = -4! + 3!! - 2 - 10$

• 686

▶ $(1 + 2)!! - 34 = 5 + 678 + \sqrt{9}$

▶ $98 \times 7!/6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})^3 \times 2 \times 1$

• 686:

▶ $98 \times 7 = 6 + 5 - 4! + 3!! - 21$

▶ $98 \times 7 = 654 + 32 \times 1$

▶ $98 \times 7 = 6 \times 5 - 4^3 + (2 + 1)!!$

▶ $98 \times 7 = 6 + 5! + (4! + 32) \times 10$

▶ $98 \times 7 = -(6 - 5) \times 4! + (3 \times 2)! - 10$

▶ $98 \times 7 = 6 + 5 \times 4 \times (32 + 1 + 0!)$

▶ $98 \times 7 = \sqrt{6! \times 5} - 4 + 3 \times 210$

• **687**

▶ $12 + 3!! - 45 = 678 + 9$

• **688**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times (-7 + 6 + 5) = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$

• **688:**

▶ $9 \times (87 - 6 - 5) + 4 = 3!! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! / (-7! / 6 + 5!) + 4! = 3!! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$

▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 + 4 = 3!! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$

• **689**

▶ $-1 + 2 \times 345 = 6! - 7 - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 - 4 + 3!! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$

• **690**

▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7)! - 6 \times 5$

▶ $(\sqrt{9} - 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5 = -4! + 3!! - (2 + 1)!$

• **690:**

▶ $(1 + 2)!! - 3! - 4! = 5 + 6! - 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$

▶ $(1 + 2)!! - 3! - 4! = -5! + 6 \times (7 + 8) \times 9$

• **691**

▶ $98 - 7 + 6! - 5! = -4! + 3!! - (2 + 1)! + 0!$

• **692**

• **692:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - \sqrt{-8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!} = -4 + 3!! - (2 + 1 + 0)!$

▶ $98 \times 7 + 6! / 5! = -4 + 3!! - (2 + 1 + 0)!$

$= 4 + 3!! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$

• **692:**

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 + 6 = -5 - 4! + 3!! + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 + 6 = -5 - 4! + (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 + 6 = 5! - 4 + (3! - 2)!^{1+0!}$$

• **693**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3 - 4! = (5 - 6 + 78) \times 9$$

• **693:**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 765 = -4! - 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 765 = -4! + 3!! - 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

• **694**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3!! - (\sqrt{4^5}) = 6! - 78 / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! = 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 = -4! + 3!! - 2 \times 1$$

• **695**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!! - 4! = 5 \times (67 + 8 \times 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - (-8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 = -4 + 3!! - 21$$

• **696**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 \times 3)! - 4! = 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 23) \times 4! + 5! = -6 + 78 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! = (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 21)$$

• **696:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6 + 5! = -4! + (3 \times 2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6 + 5! = -4! + 3!! + 21 \times 0$$

• 696:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (-7 + 65)/4 = (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 21) = 3!! - (2 + 1 + 0)!!$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5^4 = (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 21) = 3!! - (2 + 1 + 0)!!$
- ▶ $-9 - 8 - 7 + 6! = (5 + 4!) \times (3 + 21) = 3!! - (2 + 1 + 0)!!$

• 697

• 697:

- ▶ $98 \times 7 + 6 + 5 = -4! + (3 \times 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $98 \times 7 + 6 + 5 = -4! + (3 \times 2)! + 1 \times 0!$

• 698

• 698:

- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + 5^4 = 3!! - 21 - 0!$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 = 3!! - 21 - 0!$

• 699

- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! + 3 - 4! = 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 \times 5 = 6! - 7 - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7 - 6 = 5 - 4 + 3!! - 21 - 0!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - 21$

• 699:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + 4 = 3!! - 21$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 \times 4 = 3!! - 21$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4! = 3!! - 21$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) - 5!/4 = 3!! - 21$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 - 4 = 3!! - 21$

• 700

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + 7 \times 6) \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - 2 \times 10$$

• 700:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7 + \sqrt{6!/5} + 4! = 3!! - 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6 + 5! + 4 = 3!! - 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4 = 3!! - 2 \times 10$$

• 701

• 701:

$$\blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6! - 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6! - 5 = -4! + 3! + (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• 702

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3!! - 4! = (-5 + 6) \times 78 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (-3! + \sqrt{4} \times 5!) = 6! - 7 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 - 7 + 6! = -5 \times 4 + 3!! + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (87 + 6 \times 5) = \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 21 + 0!$$

• 702:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (345 + 6) = 78 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3!) \times (-4 + 5!) + 6 = 78 \times 9$$

• 703

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5 = 6! + 7 - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 - 4! + (3 \times 2)! + 1 + 0!$$

• 703:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)! = 4 + 3!! - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)! = 4 + 3!! - 21 \times 0!$$

• 704

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 + 3!! - 21 + 0!$$

• 704:

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) - 7 + 6! = 5 + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) - 7 + 6! = (\sqrt{5+4})! + 3!! - 21 - 0!$$

• 705

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)^{3!} - 4! = 5 \times (6 + (7+8) \times 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 \times 5 + 6 = -7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 + 6! - 5! = -4! + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7 = 6 + 5! \times \sqrt{4} \times 3 - 21$$

• 705:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7!/6! = (5! - \sqrt{4}) \times 3! - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7!/6! = 5^4 + (3! + 2) \times 10$$

• 706

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 3!! - \sqrt{4} = (5 - 6 + 7)! - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 706:

$$\blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6! = 5! + (4 \times 3!)^2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6! = -5 \times 4 + 3!! + (2+1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 21$$

• 707

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! - 3 - \sqrt{4} \times 5 = 6! - 78 / (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 = -4 \times 3 + (2+1)!! - 0!$$

• 707:

$$\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)!! - 7 - 6 = -5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 2 - 1$$

$$\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)!! - 7 - 6 = 5 + 4 + 3!! - 21 - 0!$$

• 708

• 708:

$$\triangleright (12 - 3!!) \times (4 - 5) = 6! + 7 - 8 + 9 = 6 + 78 \times 9$$

$$\triangleright -12 + 3!! + 4 \times 5 = 6! + 7 - 8 + 9 = 6 + 78 \times 9$$

• 708:

$$\triangleright 12 + 3!! - 4! = (5 - 6! + 7) \times (8 - 9)$$

$$\triangleright 12 + 3!! - 4! = 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 708:

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 - 7 + 6! = (5 + 4)^3 - 21$$

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 + 4 + 3!! - 21$$

• 708:

$$\triangleright (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6! - 5) = -4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\triangleright (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6! - 5) = -4! + 3!! + 2 + 10$$

• 708:

$$\triangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 + 4! = 3!! - 2 - 10$$

$$\triangleright (9 + 876) / 5 \times 4 = 3!! - 2 - 10$$

• 708:

- ▶ $-12 + 3!! = (-4 + 5) \times 6 + 78 \times 9$
- ▶ $-12 + 3!! = -4! + 5 + 6! - 7 \times (8 - 9)$
- ▶ $-12 + 3!! = 4! + 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $-12 + 3!! = 4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $-12 + 3!! = 4! - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $-12 + 3!! = \sqrt{4} + (5 - 6 + 7)! - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$

• 709

▶ $(9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 - 5 = -4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$

• 710

▶ $-1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5 = 6! + 7 - 8 - 9$

• 710:

- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! - 3! - 4 = 5! \times 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$
- ▶ $-12 + 3!! + \sqrt{4} = 5! \times 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$

• 710:

- ▶ $-9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! = -4 + 3!! - (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 = -4 + 3!! - (2 + 1)!$
 $= (4 \times 3/2)! - 10$

• 710:

- ▶ $-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 \times (4! \times 3! - 2) \times 1$
- ▶ $-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 \times (4 \times 3)^2 - 10$
- ▶ $-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 2 \times 10$

• 710:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 98 - 7 - 6 + 5^4 &= (3 \times 2)! - 10 \\ \blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 \times (6 - 5) + 4! &= (3 \times 2)! - 10 \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7!} + 6! + 5 + 4! &= (3 \times 2)! - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 711

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - \sqrt{3^4} &= (-5 + 6 + 78) \times 9 \\ \blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5 &= 6! + (7 - 8) \times 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 76 - 5) &= -4 - 3! + (2 + 1)!! + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 711:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 \times (8 - 7) + 6! &= -5 - 4 + (3 \times 2 \times 1)! \\ \blacktriangleright -9 \times (8 - 7) + 6! &= 5 - 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 712

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -12 + 3!! + 4 &= 56/7 \times 89 \\ \blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5 &= 6! - 7 + 8 - 9 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! &= 6! + 5 - 4 - 3^2 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 712:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 &= -7 + 6!/5 + (4 \times 3!)^2 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 &= 7 \times 6 \times 5 + \sqrt{4^{3^2}} - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 712:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! &= -\sqrt{4^3} + (2 + 1)!! \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) + 6! - 5 &= -\sqrt{4^3} + (2 + 1)!! \\ &= -4!/3 + (2 + 1)!! \\ &= 4 + 3!! - 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 712:

$$\blacktriangleright (9-8) \times (-7+6!) - 5+4 = 3!! + 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 87 - 6 + 5^4 = 3!! + 2 - 10$$

• 712:

$$\blacktriangleright -9+8-7+6! = -\sqrt{9} \times (8-7) + 6! = -5-4+(3 \times 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9+8-7+6! = -\sqrt{9} \times (8-7) + 6! = 5-4 \times 3 + (2+1)!! - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9+8-7+6! = -\sqrt{9} \times (8-7) + 6! = 5 + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! + 2 - 10$$

• 713

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 - 5 = 6! + 7 \times (8-9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9-8) \times 7 + 6! = 5 - 4 \times 3 + (2+1)!!$$

• 713:

$$\blacktriangleright -1-2+3!!-4 = 5+6+78 \times 9 = 5!+6!-7-(8-\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!!-3-4 = 5+6+78 \times 9 = 5!+6!-7-(8-\sqrt{9})!$$

• 713:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) !! - 7 = 6! - 5 - 4 + 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) !! - 7 = 6 + 5 + 4 + 3!! - 21 - 0!$$

• 713:

$$\blacktriangleright -(9-8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5! = -4 - 3 + (2+1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9-8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5! = -4 + 3!! - 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

• 713:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 - 4 = 3!! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 - 6 \times 5 + 4! = 3!! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• 714

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 = 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! - 5 = 6 \times 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

• 714:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 + 4 = 3!! - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - (8 - 7) \times 6 \times 5 + 4! = -3! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4! = 3!! - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 65 - 4 = 3!! - (2 + 1)!$$

• 714:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3! = 45 + 678 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3! = 4! + (5! - 6 - 7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 714:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 = (5 + 4 - 3)! - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 = 5 - 4 + 3!! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• 714:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 - 7) + 6 \times 5! = -4 + 3!! - 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8!/7! + 6! + 5 = -4 + 3!! - 2 \times 1 = -4 + 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\ = 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 10$$

• 715

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 = (5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 + (\sqrt{4 + 32})! - 10$$

• 715:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! - 5 + 4! = 3!! - (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 76 - 5) + 4 = 3!! - (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• 715:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times (6! - 5) = -4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times (6! - 5) = -4 + 3!! - 2 \times 1 + 0!$$

• 716

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6! = -5 + \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + 76 + 5) \times 4 = 3!! - 2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 716:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 \times 3)! - 4 = 5 + 6! + (7 - 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! - 4 = 5 + 6! + (7 - 8) \times 9$$

• 716:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times (8 - 7) + 6! + 5 = -4 + (3 \times 2 \times 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 = -4 + (3 \times 2 \times 1)!$$

$$= 4 + 3!! + 2 - 10$$

$$= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - 2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 717

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 = 5 + 6! - 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + (3 \times \sqrt{4})! - 5 = 6! + (7 - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 717:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - \sqrt{8+7-6} = 5 - \sqrt{4^3} + (2+1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times (8-7) + 6! = 5 - \sqrt{4^3} + (2+1)!! \\ = -\sqrt{5+4} + (3 \times 2 \times 1)!$$

• 717:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 = -4 + (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 + 3!! - (2+1)! - 0!$$

• 717:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 3!! = (1+2)!! - 3 = 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 3!! = (1+2)!! - 3 = \sqrt{4} \times 5! + 6 \times 78 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 3!! = (1+2)!! - 3 = 4 + 5! + 6! - 7 - (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• 717:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7 + 6 + 5! + 4! = 3!! - 2 - 1 = -3 + (2+1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 = 3!! - 2 - 1 = -3 + (2+1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 765 + 4! = 3!! - 2 - 1 = -3 + (2+1)!!$$

• 718

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 = 5 + 6! + 7 \times (8-9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 - 3!!) \times (4-5) = 6! - 7 + 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 + 6! = -5 + \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9-8) \times 7 + 6! + 5 = (\sqrt{4+32})! - 1 - 0!$$

• 718:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7!/6! + 54 &= 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! &= 45 + 6! - 7 \times 8 + 9 \\ \blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! &= 4 + 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 + 9 \\ \blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! &= 4! + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! &= (-4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 + 8 - \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! &= \sqrt{4^5} - 6 \times 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!! \end{aligned}$$

• 718:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 76 + 5^4 &= 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 &= 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times (6! - 5) + 4 &= (3 \times 2)! - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -98/7 + 6! + \sqrt{5! + 4!} &= 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 + 4! &= 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8!/7! + 6! + 5 + 4 &= 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7!/6! + 54 &= 3!! - 2 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 718:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 65 &= -4 + 3!! + 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 65 &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 65 &= (\sqrt{4 + 32})! - 1 - 0! \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 65 &= (4 \times 3/2)! - 1 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 719

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 \times 3)! + 4 - 5 &= 6! + (7 - 8)^9 \\ \blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + 3 - \sqrt{4} - 5 + 6! &= 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!! \\ \blacktriangleright -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4^3 &= (2 + 1)!! - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 719:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3 - 4 &= 5 + 6 \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ \blacktriangleright -1 + (\sqrt{2 + 34})! &= 5 + 6 \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

• 719:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8-7-6) \times 5 + 4! = (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + (7+6) \times 54 = (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

• 719:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!! = -1 + (2 \times 3)! = 4 + 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!! = -1 + (2 \times 3)! = 4 \times 5! / 6 + 7! / 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!! = -1 + (2 \times 3)! = 4 + (5+6) \times (7 \times 8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!! = -1 + (2 \times 3)! = 4! + 5 \times (67 + 8 \times 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!! = -1 + (2 \times 3)! = 4 \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!! = -1 + (2 \times 3)! = 4 \times 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!! = -1 + (2 \times 3)! = 4 + 5! \times 6 - 7 + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 719:

$$\blacktriangleright (9+8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 = (4 \times 3/2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9+8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{4+32})! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9+8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 = (4! + 3)^2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9+8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 = -4 + 3 + (2+1)!!$$

• 719:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 = 6! / 5 + (4 \times 3!)^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 = 6! - 5 + 4 + 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 = 6 \times 5 - 4! + 3!! - (2+1)! - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 = 65 + 4! + 3 \times 210$$

• 719:

- ▶ $-(9-8)^7 + 6! = (54/3^2)! - 1$
- ▶ $-(9-8)^7 + 6! = 5 \times 4 + 3!! - 21$
- ▶ $-(9-8)^7 + 6! = 5 + 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 10$
- ▶ $-(9-8)^7 + 6! = 5! - (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! - 0!$

• 720

▶ $1^{2345} \times 6! = (7 + 8 - 9)!$

• 720:

- ▶ $((1 + 23)/4)! = 5 + 6! - (7 + 8)/\sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $((1 + 23)/4)! = (5 + 67 + 8) \times 9$

• 720:

- ▶ $12 \times 3 \times 4 \times 5 = 6! \times (-7 + 8)^9$
- ▶ $(1^{234} + 5)! = 6! \times (-7 + 8)^9$

• 720:

- ▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7)! = 6 \times (54 + 3!) \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7)! = (6 + 54321 \times 0)!$

• 720:

- ▶ $(9 - 8)^7 \times 6! = (5 + (4 - 3)^{21})!$
- ▶ $(9 - 8)^7 \times 6! = 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 10)$

• 720:

- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = 3! + 45 + 678 - 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = 3^4 + 567 + 8 \times 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = 3 + 4! + (5 - 6 + 78) \times 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 \times 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = 34 + 5 + 678 + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = (3! + 4) \times 5 + 6 - 7 \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = (3 + \sqrt{4})! + 5! \times (-67 + 8 \times 9)$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = 3! + 4! + (5! - 6 - 7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = 3! + 4! + 5 + 6! - 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = 3 \times \sqrt{4} \times 5! \times (-6 + 7 + 8) / 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = 3 + \sqrt{4} \times 5 + 6! - 78 / (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! = \sqrt{3^4} + (-5 + 6 + 78) \times 9$

• 720:

- ▶ $\left((-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 \right) \times 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3! = (2 + 1)!!$
- ▶ $-9 - 8! / 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 \times 3 = (2 + 1)!!$
- ▶ $987 - (65 + 4!) \times 3 = (2 + 1)!!$

• 720:

- ▶ $-(9 - 8)^7 + 6! = (54/3^2)! - 1$
- ▶ $-(9 - 8)^7 + 6! = 5 \times 4 + 3!! - 21$
- ▶ $-(9 - 8)^7 + 6! = 5 + 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 10$
- ▶ $-(9 - 8)^7 + 6! = 5! - (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! - 0!$

• 720:

- ▶ $(98 + (7 - 6 \times 5) \times 4)! = (3 \times 2 \times 1)!$
- ▶ $98 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 = (3 \times 2 \times 1)!$
- ▶ $-9 \times (8 - 7) + 6! + 5 + 4 = (3 \times 2 \times 1)!$

• 720:

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + (7 - 6 \times 5) \times 4)! = (3 \times 2 \times 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 = (3 \times 2 \times 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times (8 - 7) + 6! + 5 + 4 = (3 \times 2 \times 1)!$$

• 720:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 \times 3)! = (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! = (1 \times 2 \times 3)! = 4! - 5! + 6! + 7 + 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 \times 3)! = (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! = (1 \times 2 \times 3)! = 4 + 5 + 6! + (7 - 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 \times 3)! = (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! = (1 \times 2 \times 3)! = 4 + (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8) - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 \times 3)! = (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! = (1 \times 2 \times 3)! = 45 + 678 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 720:

$$\blacktriangleright -123 + 45 + 6! + 78 = (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!! / 4 + 5 + 67 \times 8 = (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 720:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 \times 7 + 654 + 3^2 + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 \times 76 + 5! - 4 - 3 - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 87 + 6! - 54 - 32 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 87 + 6 + 5^4 + 3 - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = (8! + 7!)/6! + 5^4 + 32 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 \times (7 + 6) + 5^4 - 3^2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = (8 - 7) \times 6 \times 5 - 4! - 3! + (2 + 1)!!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 \times 7!/6! - 54 + 3!! - 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 + 7!/6! + (5! - \sqrt{4}) \times 3! - 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 + 7 + 6! - 5 \times 4 + 3 \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! \times \sqrt{4} \times 3 - 21$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 87 \times 6 + (5! - 4! + 3) \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = \sqrt{-8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!} - 5 - 4! + (3 \times 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = \sqrt{8 + 7 - 6} - 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = \sqrt{8 + 7 - 6} - \sqrt{5 + 4} + (3 \times 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 \times 76 + 5! - 4 - 3 - 2 + 1$

• 720:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 87 + 6 + 5^4 - 3! - 2 + 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 - 4 + 3!! - 21 - 0!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 + 76 + 5! + 43 \times (2 + 10)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 + 76 + 5 + (4! + 3!) \times 21 + 0!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 87 \times 6 + (5 + 4) \times (32 - 10)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 87 + 6 - 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3 \times 210$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = (8! - 7!)/6! - 5 - 4! + 3!! - 21 + 0!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8!/7! + 6! - 5!/4 + 32 - 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 \times 7 + 654 \times (3 - 2) + 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 \times 76 + (54 - 3) \times 2 + 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 \times 7!/(6 + 5!) + (4 + 3!^2) \times 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 \times 7!/6! - 5 \times 4! \times 3 + 2^{10}$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 + \sqrt{4}^{3^2} - 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 + 7 \times \sqrt{6! \times 5} + (4! \times 3! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! = 8 \times (-7 + 6 + 5) + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$

• 720:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) !! = 7 + 6! - 5 - 4 + 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) !! = 76 + 5^4 + \sqrt{3!!/2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) !! = 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3!! - 21 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) !! = 7 + 6 - 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) !! = 76 + (5 \times 43) \times (2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 720:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 + 65) = (4! + 3 - 21)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 + 65) = (\sqrt{4 + 32})! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 + 65) = 4 + 3!! - 2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 721

• 721:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8!/7! + 6! = (9 - 8)^7 + 6! = (54/3^2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8!/7! + 6! = (9 - 8)^7 + 6! = -5! \times (4 - 3!) \times (2 + 1) + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8!/7! + 6! = (9 - 8)^7 + 6! = 5! - (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• 721:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (\sqrt{2 + 34})! = 5! + 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 3!! + 4 = 5! + 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ = 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 721:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 + 3 - 4 + 5)! = 6! + (-7 + 8)^9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 + 3 \times \sqrt{4} \times 5! = 6! + (-7 + 8)^9$$

• 721:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7 = 6! + 5 - \sqrt{4^3} / 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7 = 6! + 5 - 4 - 321 \times 0$$

• 721:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 + 6! - 5! + 43 = (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (76 + 5) + 4^3 = (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• 721:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + (7 - 6 + 5)! = \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8 - 7)^{65} = \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 &= \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! - 1 \\ &= (4 \times 3/2)! + 1 \\ &= (\sqrt{4 + 32})! \times 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 721:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 = (3 \times 2)! + 1 = 3!! + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 + 6 + 5 + 4! = (3 \times 2)! + 1 = 3!! + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times (65 + 4!) = (3 \times 2)! + 1 = 3!! + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 54 = (3 \times 2)! + 1 = 3!! + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - \sqrt{-8 \times 7 + 6! + 5!} + 5 + 4! = (3 \times 2)! + 1 = 3!! + 2 - 1$$

• 721:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)! = -1 + 2 + 3!! = 4! \times 56 - 7 \times 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)! = -1 + 2 + 3!! = 4 + 5 + 6! - 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)! = -1 + 2 + 3!! = 4! - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 722

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)! - 4 + 5 = 6! + 7 - 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 722:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 - 4 + (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3!! + 2 - 10$$

• 722:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! = 4! - 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! = 4 + (5 + 6! - 7) \times (-8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! = 4 + 5 + 6! + 7 \times (8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! = \sqrt{4 + 5} + 6! - (-7 + 8)^9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! = 4 + 5 + 6! + 7 \times (8 - 9)$$

• 722:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 = (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + (3 \times \sqrt{4})! = (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8) - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! + \sqrt{4} &= (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8) - \sqrt{9} \\ &= 5! / 6 + 78 \times 9 \\ &= 5 + 6! + (7 - 8) \times \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 722:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright & -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 76 + 5! = 4 + 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright & (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6! - 5) = 4 + 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright & -\sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) + 6! + 5 = 4 + 3!! - 2 \times 1 \\ & = 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1 - 0! \\ & = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! + 2 \times 1 \\ & = (4 \times 3/2)! + 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 722:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright & -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 + 6! - 5 + 4! = 3!! + 2 \times 1 = (3 \times 2)! + 1 + 0! \\ \blacktriangleright & -\sqrt{9} - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 \times 4 = 3!! + 2 \times 1 = (3 \times 2)! + 1 + 0! \\ \blacktriangleright & 9 \times 87 - 65 + 4 = 3!! + 2 \times 1 = (3 \times 2)! + 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 723

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4 + 5 = 6! - (7 - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 723:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright & -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 = -5 + 6! + 7 - 8 + 9 \\ \blacktriangleright & -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4 = 5 + 6! - 7 + 8 - \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 723:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright & \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) + 6! = (5 - 4) \times (3!! + 2 + 1) \\ \blacktriangleright & \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) + 6! = (5 + 4)^3 - (2 + 1)! \end{aligned}$$

• 723:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright & -\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright & 9 - 8 + 7 + 6! - 5 = 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright & 9 \times 87 - \sqrt{6!} \times 5 = 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 723:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 6 - 54 &= 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\ \blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 &= 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 \times 4 &= 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\ &(1 + 2)!! + 3 = 4 + 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 + 9 \\ &(1 + 2)!! + 3 = 4 + 5 + 6 \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ &(1 + 2)!! + 3 = 4! + 5! + 67 + 8^{\sqrt{9}} \\ &(1 + 2)!! + 3 = 4! + 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 - (\sqrt{9})! \\ &(1 + 2)!! + 3 = 45 + 6 \times (-7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!) \end{aligned}$$

• 724

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 + 6! &= 5 - \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (87 - 6) - 5 &= 4 + (3 \times 2 \times 1)! \end{aligned}$$

• 724:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 \times 3)! + 4 &= 5 + 6! - (-7 + 8)^9 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! + 4 &= 5 + 6! - (-7 + 8)^9 \\ &= (5 - 6!) \times (7 - 8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

• 724:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 765 + 4! &= 3!! + 2 + 1 + 0! \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 + 65) + 4 &= 3!! + 2 + 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 725

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^{3!} - 4 &= (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8)^9 \\ \blacktriangleright ((1 + 23)/4)! + 5 &= 6! + (7 + 8)/\sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright 98/7 + 6! - 5 - 4 &= 3!! + (2 + 1)! - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 725:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 + 6 &= 5 \times ((4 \times 3)^2 + 1) \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 + 6 &= 5 + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - 2 + 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 725:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7!/6 - 5! &= 4 + (3 \times 2)! + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times (6! + 5) &= 4 + (3 \times 2)! + 1 \\ &= \sqrt{4} + 3!! + 2 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 726

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 = 5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 - 9$$

• 726:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! &= (5! + 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)! \\ \blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! &= (5 + 4 - 3)! + (2 + 1)! \end{aligned}$$

• 726:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7 + 65) &= 4 + 3!! + 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! &= 4 + 3!! + 2 \times 1 \\ &= -4 + (3 \times 2)! + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 726:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7)! + 6 \times (5 - 4) &= 3! + (2 + 1)!! \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (87 + 6 \times 5) + 4! &= 3! + (2 + 1)!! \end{aligned}$$

• 726:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3! &= (1 + 2)! + 3!! = 45 + 678 + \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3! &= (1 + 2)! + 3!! = (-4 + 5 - 6! - 7) \times (8 - 9) \\ \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3! &= (1 + 2)! + 3!! = 4! + (-5 + 6) \times 78 \times 9 \\ \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3! &= (1 + 2)! + 3!! = (\sqrt{4^5}) + 6! - 78/\sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3! &= (1 + 2)! + 3!! = 4 \times 5 + 6! - 7 \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!) \end{aligned}$$

• 726:

- ▶ $1 + (2 - 3 + 4)!! + 5 = 6! + 7 + 8 - 9 = 6 + (7 + 8 - 9)!$
- ▶ $-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5 = 6! + 7 + 8 - 9 = 6 + (7 + 8 - 9)!$
- ▶ $1 + (\sqrt{2 + 34})! + 5 = 6! + 7 + 8 - 9 = 6 + (7 + 8 - 9)!$
- ▶ $-1 + 2^3 + (\sqrt{4 + 5})!! = 6! + 7 + 8 - 9 = 6 + (7 + 8 - 9)!$
- ▶ $1 + (\sqrt{2 + 34})! + 5 = 6! + 7 + 8 - 9 = 6 + (7 + 8 - 9)!$

• 727

▶ $987 - 65 \times 4 = 3!! + (2 + 1)! + 0!$

• 727:

- ▶ $-1 + 2^3 + (\sqrt{4 + 5})!! = 6! - 7 \times (8 - 9)$
- ▶ $-12 + 3!! + 4 \times 5 = 6! - 7 \times (8 - 9) = 6! - 7 \times (8 - 9)$

• 727:

- ▶ $1^{2345} + 6! + 7 = 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$
- ▶ $-1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5 - 6 - 7 = 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$

• 727:

- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right)!! + 7 = 6! - 5 + 4 + 3^2 - 1$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right)!! + 7 = 6 \times 5! - 4 + 3 - 2 + 10$

• 727:

- ▶ $(9 - 8) \times (7 + 6!) = 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $(9 - 8) \times (7 + 6!) = (5 + 4)^3 - 2 \times 1$

• 727:

$$\blacktriangleright (9-8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5! = 4 + 3 + (2+1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9-8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5! = (4! + 3)^2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 727:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! - 4 = 1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 = 5! + 6! + 7 - (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! - 4 = 1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 = 56 \times 78 / (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! - 4 = 1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 = 5! \times 6 - 7 \times (8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! - 4 = 1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 = 5! \times 6 + 7 - 8 + 9$$

• 728

$$\blacktriangleright 1^{2345} + 6! + 7 = 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9-8) \times 7 + 6! + 5 - 4 = 3!! - 2 + 10$$

• 728:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! = 6! + 5 - 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! = 6! + 5 + 4 - (321 \times 0)!$$

• 728:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! = (4! + 3)^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - 2 + 10$$

• 728:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 = 76 + 5^4 + 3^{2+1}$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 = 7! \times 6/5! + 4 \times ((3+2)! - 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 = 7 + 6! + 5 - \sqrt{4^3}/2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 = 7 + 6 + 5 \times ((4 \times 3)^2 - 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 = 76 + 5 + 4! \times 3^{2+1} - 0!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 = 7 + 6 + 5^4 + 3^2 \times 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 = 7 + 6! + 5 - 4 - 321 \times 0$

• 728:

- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 + 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 \times 4 + 3!! - 2 - 10$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5! + \sqrt{4} \times (-3!! + 2^{10})$

• 729

• 729:

- ▶ $(1+2)^{(3 \times \sqrt{4})} = 5 + 6! - 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $(1+2)^{(3 \times \sqrt{4})} = ((5+67)/8)^{\sqrt{9}}$

• 729:

- ▶ $(12-3)^{\sqrt{4+5}} = 6! - (7-8) \times 9$
- ▶ $(12-3)^{\sqrt{4+5}} = (-6+7+8)^{\sqrt{9}}$

• 729:

- ▶ $9^{(8 \times (7-6)-5)} = (4! + 3)^2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9^{(8 \times (7-6)-5)} = (4! + 3)^{2+1-0!}$

• 729:

- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = 5!/4 + 3!! - 21$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = (54/3!)^{2+1}$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = (5 + 4)^3 \times (2 - 1)$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = (5 - 4) \times 3^{(2+1)!}$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = 5 + 4 + (3 \times 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = (5 + 4)^3 + 21 \times 0$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = 5 + 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1 + 0!$

• 729:

- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = 5!/4 + 3!! - 21$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = (54/3!)^{2+1}$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = (5 + 4)^3 \times (2 - 1)$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = (5 - 4) \times 3^{(2+1)!}$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = 5 + 4 + (3 \times 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = (5 + 4)^3 + 21 \times 0$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) = 5 + 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1 + 0!$

• 729:

- ▶ $-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! - 5 + 4! = 3^{(2+1)!}$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6! + 54 = 3^{(2+1)!}$
- ▶ $(98 - 76 + 5)^{\sqrt{4}} = 3^{(2+1)!}$

• 729:

- ▶ $(1 + 2)^{3!} = 4 - 5 + 6! - 7 + 8 + 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)^{3!} = 45 + 678 + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)^{3!} = \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)^{3!} = 4! + 5 \times (6 + (7 + 8) \times 9)$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)^{3!} = (-4 + 5) \times 6! - (7 - 8) \times 9$

• 730

▶ $(1+2)^{3!} - 4 + 5 = 6! - 7 + 8 + 9$

• 730:

▶ $12 + 3!! - \sqrt{4} = 5! \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$

▶ $(1+2)!! + 3! + 4 = 5! \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$
 $= 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$

• 730:

▶ $9 + 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 - 4 + 3^{(2+1)!}$

▶ $9 + 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 + 4 + (3 \times 2)! + 1$

▶ $9 + 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 \times (4 \times 3)^2 + 10$

• 730:

▶ $9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! = 4 + 3!! + (2 + 1)!$

▶ $9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! = (4! + 3)^2 + 1$

▶ $9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! = (\sqrt{4+32})! + 10$

▶ $9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! = (4 \times 3/2)! + 10$

• 730:

▶ $-9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 = (3 \times 2)! + 10$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7 + 65) + 4 = (3 \times 2)! + 10$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7 + 6 - 5 + 4! = (3 \times 2)! + 10$

• 731

▶ $(1+2)^{3!} + \sqrt{4} = 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 - 9$

• 731:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8!/7! + 6! = 5 + 4 + 3!! + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8!/7! + 6! = 5 \times \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

• 731:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 76 + 5! &= \sqrt{4} + 3^{(2+1)!} \\ &= \sqrt{4} + 3^{(2+1)!} \\ &= (4! + 3)^2 + 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 732

• 732:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + (3 \times \sqrt{4})! = 5 \times 6 + 78 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! + 3 \times 4 = 5 \times 6 + 78 \times 9$$

• 732:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 6! = (5 + 4)^3 + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 6! = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{3 \times (2 + 10)}$$

• 732:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6! + 5) = 4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 76) + 5! &= 4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\ &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! + 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 732:

- ▶ $12 + 3!! = 45 + 678 + 9$
- ▶ $12 + 3!! = 4! + 5! \times 6 - 7 - 8 + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $12 + 3!! = 4! + 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $12 + 3!! = (-4 + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 - \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $12 + 3!! = 4 + 56 \times 78 / (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $12 + 3!! = \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $12 + 3!! = 4! + 5! + 6 \times 7 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$

• 732:

- ▶ $-9 + 87 + 654 = 3!! + 2 + 10$
- ▶ $-9 - 8! / 7! + 6! + 5 + 4! = 3!! + 2 + 10$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 \times 4 = 3!! + 2 + 10$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 + 4! = 3!! + 2 + 10$

• 733

- ▶ $(1 + 2)^{3!} + 4 = 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $12 + 3!! - 4 + 5 = 6! + 78 / (\sqrt{9})!$

• 733:

- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + 7 + 6 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + 7 + 6 = (5 + 4)^3 + 2 + 1 + 0!$

• 733:

- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 + 3^{(2+1)!}$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$

• **734**

- ▶ $12 + 3!! + \sqrt{4} = (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8) + 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)^{(3 \times \sqrt{4})} + 5 = 6! + 7 \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$
- ▶ $9 \times (87 - 6) + 5 = 4 + (3 \times 2)! + 10$

• **734:**

- ▶ $98/7 + 6! = 5 \times 4 - 3! + (2 + 1)!!$
- ▶ $98/7 + 6! = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times 3! + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $98/7 + 6! = (5! + 4) \times 3 \times 2 - 10$
- ▶ $98/7 + 6! = (\sqrt{5 + 4})! + 3!! - 2 + 10$
- ▶ $98/7 + 6! = 5 + 4 + 3!! + (2 + 1)! - 0!$

• **735**

- ▶ $(12 - 3)^{\sqrt{4+5}} + 6 = 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7!/6! = (5 + 4)^3 + (2 + 1)!$

• **735:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 = 6! + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 = 6 + 5 - 4 + 3!! - 2 + 10$

• **736**

- ▶ $12 + 3!! + 4 = 5! - (6 + 7) \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + 7 + 6! = -5 + 4! + 3!! - 2 - 1$

• **737**

- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 76 + 5! = -4 + 3!! + 21$

• **737:**

- ▶ $-1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! - 5 = 67 \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$
- ▶ $1 + 23 \times \sqrt{4^5} = 67 \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$

• 737:

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 + 4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 + 4! + 3!! - 2 - 10$$

• 738

$$\triangleright 123 \times (\sqrt{4+5})! = 6! + 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! = 4! - 3! + (2 + 1)!!$$

• 738:

$$\triangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3! + 4! = 5! \times 6 + 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\triangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3! + 4! = 5! - 6 + 7! / 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 738:

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 \times 4 + 3!! - 2 \times 1$$

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 2 + 10$$

• 739

• 739:

$$\triangleright 98 / 7 + 6! + 5 = -\sqrt{4} + 3!! + 21$$

$$\triangleright 98 / 7 + 6! + 5 = (4! + 3)^2 + 10$$

• 740

$$\triangleright (9 \times 8 + 76) \times 5 = (4! \times 3 + 2) \times 10$$

• 740:

$$\triangleright 98 \times 7! / 6! + 54 = 3!! + 2 \times 10$$

$$\triangleright 98 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4) = 3!! + 2 \times 10$$

• 741

• 741:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 \times 5 &= 6 + 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!! \\ \blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! + 4 + 5 &= 6 + 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!! \end{aligned}$$

• 741:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 + 6 &= 5 \times 4 + (3 \times 2)! + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 + 6 &= 5 - 4 + 3!! + 21 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 741:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times (8) + 765 &= 4! + 3!! - 2 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7 + 6! + 5 &= 4! + 3!! - 2 - 1 \\ &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! + 21 \end{aligned}$$

• 741:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 765 - 4! &= 3!! + 21 \\ \blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 + 6! + 5 \times 4 &= 3!! + 21 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 76 + 5! + 4 &= 3!! + 21 \\ \blacktriangleright 98/7 + 6! + 5 + \sqrt{4} &= 3!! + 21 \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} - 7!} + 6! + 5!/\sqrt{4} &= 3!! + 21 \end{aligned}$$

• 742

• 742:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! &= 5! + 6! - 7 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!) \\ \blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! &= 5 + 67 \times (8 + \sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

• 742:

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7!/6 = 5^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!! - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7!/6 = 54 + 3!! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 742:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 = 4! + 3!! - 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 = 4! + (3 \times 2)! - 1 - 0!$$

• 742:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4 = 3!! + 21 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 765 - 4! = 3!! + 21 + 0!$$

• 743

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! = 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 = 4! + (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

• 744

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times (4 + 5!) = 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 + 6! = 5^4 + (3 + 2)! - 1$$

• 744:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2 \times 3)! + 4! = 5! + 6! - 7 - 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! + 4! = 5! + 6! - 7 - 89$$

• 744:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5! = 4! \times (32 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7!/6 - 5! = 4! \times (32 - 1) \\ = 4 + 3!! + 21 - 0!$$

• 744:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 765 - 4 = 3!! + (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 87 + 654 = 3!! + (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• 745

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! = 5 \times (6 + 7 - 8) + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7! / 6 - 5 = 4 + 3!! + 21$$

• 746

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! = 5! \times 6 + 78 / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 = 4! + 3!! + 2 \times 1$$

• 746:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3 + 4! + 5 = 6! + 78 / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3!! + 4 \times 5 = 6! + 78 / \sqrt{9}$$

• 747

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 876 - 5! = 4! + 3!! + 2 + 1$$

• 747:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3 + 4! = 5! + 6 + 7! / 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! = 5! + 6 + 7! / 8 - 9$$

• 748

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 765 = 4 + 3!! + (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• 749

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7 + 6! + 5! = 4! + 3! + (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• 750

• 750:

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! + 3!! + 4! = (5! + 6 + 7 - 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! + 3!! + 4! = 5 \times 6 + (7 + 8 - 9)!$$

• 750:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7!/6 = 5 + 4 + 3!! + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7!/6 = (5 + 4)^3 + 21$$

• 750:

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + 7) \times 6 + 5! = 4! + 3! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 87 + 6! + 5! = 4! + 3! + (2 + 1)!!$$

• 751

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5 = 6! + 7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 + 65 = 4! + 3!! + (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• 751:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 + 6! = 5^4 + 3! \times 21$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 + 6! &= 5^4 + 3! \times 21 \\ &= 5!/4 + (3 \times 2)! + 1 \\ &= 5 + 4 + 3!! + 21 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 752

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) - 7 + 6! + 5! = 4! + 3!! - 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8\right) \times 7 + 654 = 3!! + \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 753

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)^{3!} + 4! = 5! - 6 + 7!/8 + 9$$

• 753:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 6 \times 5 &= 4! + 3^{(2+1)!} \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 - 6 \times 5 &= 4! + 3^{(2+1)!} \times 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 754

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! + (\sqrt{4^5}) &= 6 \times 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!! \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 765 &= 4! + (3 \times 2)! + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 754:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 \times 6 &= \sqrt{5^4} + 3^{(2+1)!} \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 \times 6 &= 5! + 4 + 3 \times 210 \end{aligned}$$

• 755

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + 3!! + (\sqrt{4^5}) = 6! + 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

• 755:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9} - 8) \times 7 + 6! &= (5 + 4!) + 3! + (2 + 1)!! \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9} - 8) \times 7 + 6! &= (5!/4 + 3!) \times 21 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 756

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! + 4! &= (5! + 6) \times (7 + 8 - 9) \\ \blacktriangleright 12 + 3! \times (4 + 5!) &= (6 + 78) \times 9 \\ \blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) &= 4! + 3!! + 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 756:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 76) &= (5!/4 + 3!) \times 21 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 76) &= (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times 3! \times 21 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 76) &= 54 \times (3! - 2 + 10) \end{aligned}$$

• 758

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! + 6 \times 5 = 4! \times 32 - 10$$

• 759

• 759:

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7!/6 = 5!/4 + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7!/6 = 5 + 4! + (3 \times 2)! + 10$$

• 761

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! + 4! + 5 = 6! - 7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 761:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 \times 4 + 3!! + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 + 4! + 3!! + 2 + 10$$

• 762

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! - 3 + 45 = 6 \times \left(7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!\right)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 87 + 6! + 5! = 43 + (2+1)!! - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right)! \times 7 + 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3! + (2+1)!!$$

• 763

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 765 = 43 + (2+1)!!$$

• 764

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 765 = 4! + 3!! + 2 \times 10$$

• 765

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 45 = 6! + (7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 765 = 4! + 3!! + 21$$

• 765:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6! = (5! + 4) \times 3! + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6! = 5^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!! + 21 - 0!$$

• 766

• 766:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 765 = 4! \times 32 - 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 765 = 4! + 3!! + 21 + 0!$$

• 767

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! + 45 = 6! + 7 \times 8 - 9$$

• 767:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)! \times 7 + 6! + 5 = 4! \times 32 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 765 = 4! \times 32 - 1$$

• 767:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! = (5! - 4!) \times (3! + 2) - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5! + 4! \times 3^{2+1} - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!! + 21 + 0!$$

• 768

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3 + 45 = 6! / (7 + 8) + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 768:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! / 6 = (5! - 4!) \times (3^2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! / 6 = (5! - 4!) \times (3 \times 2 + 1 + 0!)$$

• 768:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -9 \times 8!/7! + 6! + 5! &= 4! \times 32 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 + 6! - 5! &= 4! \times 32 \times 1 \\ &= 4^3 \times (2 + 10) \end{aligned}$$

• 769

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 - 2^3 \times (4! - 5!) &= 6! + 7^{(8-(\sqrt{9})!)} \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8! - 7!)/(6 \times 5!) &= 4! \times 32 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 769:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8! - 7!)/6! &= (5! - 4!) \times (3! + 2) + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8! - 7!)/6! &= 5^4 + (3! \times 2)^{1+0!} \end{aligned}$$

• 770

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + (3! + 4) \times 5 &= 6! + 7 \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})! \\ \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 765 &= 4! \times 32 + 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 770:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 \times 6 &= 5 + 4! + 3!! + 21 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 \times 6 &= 54 + 3!! - 2 - 1 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 773

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6! = 54 + (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

• 775

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 + 6! = 5^{\sqrt{4}} \times (32 - 1)$$

• 776

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 + (2 + \sqrt{3^4}) \times 5 + 6! &= 7 \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!! \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 765 &= 4! + 3!! + \sqrt{2^{10}} \end{aligned}$$

• 776:

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7!/6! = 54 + 3!! + 2 \times 1$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7!/6! = 5!/ \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 776:

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7 = 6! + 54 + 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7 = 6! - 54 + (3 + 2)! - 10$$

• 777

$$\triangleright 9 \times 87 - 6 = 54 + 3!! + 2 + 1$$

• 778

• 778:

$$\triangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! = 4! \times 32 + 10$$

$$\triangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 = 4! \times 32 + 10$$

• 782

• 782:

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5!/ \sqrt{4} + 3!! + 2 \times 1$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5!/ \sqrt{4} + 3!! + 2 - 1 + 0!$$

• 783

$$\triangleright (1 + 2)^3 \times (4! + 5) = -6 + 789$$

• 783:

$$\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 7 + 6! = (5 + 4!) \times 3^{2+1}$$

$$\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 7 + 6! = 54 + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

• 783:

- ▶ $9 \times 87 = 6 + 54 + 3!! + 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 87 = 6! + (5 + 4) / 3 \times 21$
- ▶ $9 \times 87 = 65 \times 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 87 = 6! \times (5 - 4) + 3 \times 21$
- ▶ $9 \times 87 = 65 + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! - 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 87 = \sqrt{6! \times 5} + 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 87 = (6 - 5) \times \sqrt{4^{3!}} + (2 + 1)!! - 0!$
- ▶ $9 \times 87 = 65 - 4 + 3!! + 2 + 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9 \times 87 = 6 + 54 + 3 + (2 \times 1 + 0)!!$

• 784

• 784:

- ▶ $9 \times 87 + 6 - 5 = 4^3 + (2 + 1)!!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5 = 4^3 + (2 + 1)!!$
 $= (-4 + 32)^{1+0!}$

• 785

▶ $1 + 2^{3!} + (\sqrt{4+5})!! = 6! + 7 \times 8 + 9$

▶ $9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! = 4^3 + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$

• 785:

- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! = (\sqrt{5^4} + 3)^2 + 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5! / \sqrt{4} + 3!! + (2 + 1)! - 0!$

• 789

• 789:

- ▶ $(1 + 2)^{3!} + 4 + 56 = 789$
- ▶ $(1 + 2)^3 \times (4! + 5) + 6 = 789$
- ▶ $1 + 23 + 45 + 6! = 789$

• 789:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 + 6 = 5! / \sqrt{4} + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 + 6 = 5 + 4^3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

• 791

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9-8+7!} + 6! = (5! - 4 - 3) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - (8! - 7!) / 6! + 5! = 4! \times (32 + 1) - 0!$$

• 792

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3!! / (\sqrt{4} \times 5) = 6! + 78 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (87 + 6 - 5) = 4! \times (32 + 1)$$

• 792:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3 \times 4! = (5 + 67) \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3 \times 4! = (5 - 6 + 7)! + 8 \times 9$$

• 792:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! / 6 = (5! + 4 \times 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! / 6 = 5! + (4! - 3) \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 793

• 793:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 76 + 5 = 4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! = 4! \times (32 + 1) + 0!$$

• 794

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) - 7 + 6! = 54 + 3!! + 21 - 0!$$

• 796

$$\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + 76 = 54 + 3!! + 21 + 0!$$

• 797

$$\triangleright (1+2)!! + 3 \times 4! + 5 = 6! + 7 \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

• 797:

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 + 6! = 5! - 43 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 + 6! = 5 + 4! \times (32 + 1)$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 + 6! = (-5 + 43) \times 21 - 0!$$

• 798

$$\triangleright 123 - 45 + 6! = 78 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 798:

$$\triangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6! = (-5 + 43) \times 21$$

$$\triangleright -9 + 87 + 6! = (-5 + 43) \times 21 \\ = 5 + 4! \times (32 + 1) + 0!$$

• 799

• 799:

$$\triangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6! = \sqrt{5^4} \times 32 - 1$$

$$\triangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6! = (-5 + 43) \times 21 + 0!$$

• 801

$$\triangleright (1+2)!! + 3^4 = (5+6+78) \times 9$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 87 - 6 = 5! \times 4 + 321$$

• 804

$$\triangleright 12 \times (3 \times 4! - 5) = 6 + 78 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 76 = 5! - 4 + 3!! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **807**

▶ $(1 + 2)!! + 3 \times (4! + 5) = 6! + 78 + 9$

• **807:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 87 = 6 + 5! \times 4 + 321$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 87 = 6 \times 5 \times (4! + 3) - 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 87 = 6! + 5! - 4! - 3^2 - 1 + 0!$

• **808**

▶ $(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7 + 6! = -5! - \sqrt{4} + 3!! + 210$

• **810**

• **810:**

- ▶ $1 \times 2 \times 3^4 \times 5 = 6 \times (7 + 8) \times 9$
- ▶ $(12 + 3!) \times 45 = 6 \times (7 + 8) \times 9$

• **810:**

- ▶ $98 - 7 + 6! = 54 \times (-3! + 21)$
- ▶ $98 - 7 + 6! = 54 \times 3/2 \times 10$

• **810:**

- ▶ $9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 = 54 \times (-3! + 21)$
- ▶ $9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 = 54 \times 3/2 \times 10$

• **811**

▶ $98 - 7 + 6! = 5!/4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$

• **813**

• 813:

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 87 + 6! = 5! - 4! + 3!! - 2 - 1$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 87 + 6! = 5! - 4! + 3!! - 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

• 816

$$\triangleright 1 \times (2 \times 3)! - 4! + 5! = 6! + 7 + 89$$

$$\triangleright 98 - 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 \times (-3! + 210)$$

• 816:

$$\triangleright 9 + 87 + 6! = 5! - 4! + (3 \times 2)! \times 1$$

$$\triangleright 9 + 87 + 6! = 5! - 4 + 3!! - 21 + 0!$$

• 817

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 + 6! = 5! - 4! + (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

• 818

$$\triangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! - 4! + 5! = 6! + 7 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• 818:

$$\triangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7 + 6! = 5! - 4! + 3!! + 2 \times 1$$

$$\triangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7 + 6! = (5!/4!) + 3!! - 21 - 0!$$

• 820

• 820:

$$\triangleright (-(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7!) / 6 = (-5! + (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)!$$

$$\triangleright (-(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7!) / 6 = (5! \times \sqrt{4} / 3 + 2) \times 10$$

• 823

$$\triangleright -9 - 8 + 7! / 6 = 5! + 4 + 3!! - 21$$

• 824

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 3!! - 4 + 5! = (6 + 7) \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (7 + 6) = 5! + 4 + 3!! - 21 + 0!$$

• 825

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^{3!} - 4! + 5! = 6! + 7! / (8 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 + 6! = 5 \times (4! \times 3! + 21)$$

• 826

• 826:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7!/6 = (5! - \sqrt{4}) \times (3 \times 2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7!/6 = \sqrt{5^4} \times (32 + 1) + 0!$$

• 828

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7!/6 + 5 = 4 \times (-3 + 210)$$

• 828:

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 \times 8 + 7!) / 6 = 5! - 4 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 \times 8 + 7!) / 6 = 5! - 4! + 3!! + 2 + 10$$

• 829

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7!/6 = 5^4 - 3! + 210$$

• 831

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + 7!/6 = (5 + 4 \times 3!)^2 - 10$$

• 832

• 832:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! / 6 = 5! - (\sqrt{4}) + 3!! - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! / 6 = 5^4 - 3 + 210$$

• 833

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 3!! - 4 + 5! = 6! - 7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• 833:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 + 6! = 5! - 4 - 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 + 6! = 5 + 4 \times (-3 + 210)$$

• 834

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3! + 4! \times 5 = -6 + 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• 834:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 7 - 6 = 5! - 4 + 3!! - 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 7 - 6 = 5! - \sqrt{4} + 3!! - (2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 835

• 835:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7!/6 = 5! - 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7!/6 = 5 \times (-43 + 210)$$

• 836

• 836:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 76 = 5! - 4 + (3 \times 2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 76 = (-5 + 43) \times (21 + 0!)$$

• 837

• 837:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (87 + 6) = 5 \times 4! + 3!! - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (87 + 6) = 5! - 4 + (3 \times 2 \times 1)! + 0!$$

• **838**

• **838:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7!/6 = 5! - 4 + 3!! + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7!/6 = 5^4 + 3 + 210$$

• **839**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 \times 3)! + 4! \times 5 = 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 - 8)^7 + 6! + 5! = 4! \times (3!^2 - 1) - 0!$$

• **839:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! = 5! \times (4 + 3) - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! = 5! + \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 2 - 1$$

• **840**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + (3 + \sqrt{4})! = 5! + 6! \times (-7 + 8)^9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5! = 6! + ((7 + 8)/\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 123 - \sqrt{4 + 5} + 6! = 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• **840:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7!/6 = 5 \times 4!/3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7!/6 = (5 - 4 + 3) \times 210$$

• **840:**

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + 7 + 6! + 5! + \sqrt{4} = 3!! + ((2 + 1)! - 0)!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 \times (6 + 54) = 3!! + ((2 + 1)! - 0)!)$$

• 840:

- ▶ $98/7 \times \sqrt{6! \times 5} = (9-8)^7 \times (6!+5!) = 4! \times (3!^2 - 1)$
- ▶ $98/7 \times \sqrt{6! \times 5} = (9-8)^7 \times (6!+5!) = (4+3)!/(2+1)!$
- ▶ $98/7 \times \sqrt{6! \times 5} = (9-8)^7 \times (6!+5!) = 4!/3! \times 210$

• 840:

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)! \times 7 = 6+5! - 4+3!! - 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)! \times 7 = 6 \times 5 \times (4+3+21)$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)! \times 7 = 6+5! - \sqrt{4}+3!! - (2+1) - 0!$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)! \times 7 = (-6+5 \times 4) \times 3 \times 2 \times 10$

• 841

• 841:

- ▶ $(9-8)^7 + 6! + 5! = 4! \times (3!^2 - 1) + 0!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9}+8) \times 76 + 5 = 4! \times (3!^2 - 1) + 0!$
 $= (4! + 3 + 2)^{1+0!}$

• 841:

- ▶ $9-8+7!/6 = 5! \times (4+3) + 2-1$
- ▶ $9-8+7!/6 = 5-4+3!! + ((2+1)! - 0)!$
- ▶ $9-8+7!/6 = (5+4 \times 3!)^2 - 1 + 0!$

• 842

▶ $9 \times (87+6) + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3!! + ((2+1)! - 0)!$

• 842:

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7!/6 = 5! + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7!/6 = 5! + \sqrt{4} + 3!! + 2 - 1 - 0!$

• 843

• 843:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7!/6 = 5! + 4 + (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7!/6 = (5 + 4 \times 3!)^2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 844

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7!) / 6 = 5! + 4 + (3 \times 2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7!/6 + 5 = 4 + 3!! + ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• 845

• 845:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7!/6 = 5! + 4 + (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7!/6 = 5! + \sqrt{4} + 3!! + 2 + 1$$

• 846

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + (3 + 4) \times 5! = 6 + 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• 846:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 7 + 6 = (5! + 4! - 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 7 + 6 = 5! + \sqrt{4} + 3!! + 2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 847

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + 3!! + 4 + 5! = 6! + 7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• 847:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7 + 6! = 5! + 4 + 3!! + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7 + 6! = -5 + 4 \times (3 + 210)$$

• 848

• 848:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right)^7 + 6! = 5! + \sqrt{4} + 3!! + (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right)^7 + 6! = 5! \times (4 + 3) - 2 + 10$$

• 849

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + 7!/6 = 5 \times 4! + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

• 851

• 851:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7!/6 = 5! + \sqrt{4} + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7!/6 = 5^4 \times 3 - 2^{10}$$

• 852

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9} + 8\right)! + 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 \times (3 + 210)$$

• 852:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7)!/6 = 5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7)!/6 = 5! + 4! + 3!! - 2 - 10$$

• 854

• 854:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7!/6 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times (3 \times 2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7!/6 = 5! + 4 + (3 \times 2)! + 10$$

• 854:

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 + 6! + 5! = 4! \times 3!^2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + 7!/6 + 5 = 4! \times 3!^2 - 10$$

• **855**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! + 3 \times 45 = 6! + (7+8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7) + 6! = 5 \times (4!+3) + (2+1)!!$$

• **857**

$$\blacktriangleright 9+8+7!/6 = 5+4 \times (3+210)$$

• **860**

• **860:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((-\sqrt{9}+8)! + 7! \right) / 6 = -5 + 4! \times 3!^2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((-\sqrt{9}+8)! + 7! \right) / 6 = (54+32) \times 10$$

• **860:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8+7) + 6! + 5 = 43 \times 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((-\sqrt{9}+8)! + 7! \right) / 6! \times 5! = 43 \times 2 \times 10$$

• **862**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 876 = 5 + 4! \times 3!^2 - 1 - 0!$$

• **863**

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 765 = 4! \times 3!^2 - 1 = 4! \times 3!^2 \times 1 - 0!$$

• **864**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times (4! + 5!) = (-6! + 7!) / (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

• **864**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 \times 4! = 5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12^3 / \sqrt{4} = (5+6+7) \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 864:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (7!/6! + 5) = 4 \times 3!^{2+1} = 4 \times (3! + 210)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 + 6! + 5! = 4 \times 3!^{2+1} = 4 \times (3! + 210)$$

• 864:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7!/6 = 5! + 4! \times (32 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7!/6 = (5! + 4!) \times 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7!/6 = 5! + 4 + 3!! + 21 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7!/6 = 54 \times (3! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 865

• 865:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) = 4! \times 3!^2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7! \right) / 6 + 5 = 4! \times 3!^2 + 1$$

• 866

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + (7! - 6!) / 5 = 4! \times 3!^2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 867

• 867:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 876 = 5! + 4! + 3!! + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 876 = 5! + 4! + 3!! + 2 \times 1 + 0!$$

• 870

• 870:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 876 = 5 + 4! \times 3!^2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 876 = 5 + 4 \times 3!^{2+1} + 0!$$

• 873

• 873:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 876 = 5! + 4! + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 876 = 5 + 4 \times (3!^{2+1} + 0!)$$

• 874

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 876 - 5 = 4! \times 3!^2 + 10$$

• 879

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 876 = 5 + 4! \times 3!^2 + 10$$

• 880

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 876 = 5 - 4! \times 3! + 2^{10}$$

• 882

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times \sqrt{76+5} = (4! - 3!)^2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 882:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 876 = 54 \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 876 = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3! \times 2!$$

• 885

• 885:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 876 = 5! + 4! + 3!! + 2!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 876 = 5! + 4! + (3!! + 2!) \times 0!$$

• 887

• 887:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! = 4! \times (3!^2 + 1) - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 876 + 5 = 4! \times (3!^2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 888

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 3!!/4 \times 5 = 6! + 7 \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7!/6 + 5! = 4! \times (3!^2 + 1)$$

• 888:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5! + 4! \times 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5! + 4^3 \times (2 + 10)$$

• 889

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8! - 7!)/6! + 5! = 4! \times (3!^2 + 1) + 0!$$

• 890

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 876 + 5 = (4! + 3!)^2 - 10$$

• 898

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 \times (7!/6! - 5!) = (4! + 3!)^2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 899

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) = (4! + 3!)^2 - 1$$

• 900

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3!!/4 = 5!/6 \times (7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 900:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 + 7)/\sqrt{6!/5} = (4! + 3!)^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 + 7)/\sqrt{6!/5} = (-\sqrt{4} + 32)^{1+0!}$$

• 901

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (-7 + \sqrt{6! \times 5}) = (4! + 3!)^2 + 1$$

• 902

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! = 43 \times 21 - 0!$$

• **903**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8! + 7!)/6! + 5! = 43 \times 21$$

• **904**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 5) = 43 \times 21 + 0!$$

• **910**

$$\blacktriangleright 98/7 \times 65 = (4! + 3!)^2 + 10$$

• **912**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7!/6 = 5! + 4! \times (32 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times (-6 + 5!) = 4! \times (3!^2 + 1 + 0!)$$

• **921**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) + 7!/6 = -5 - 4 + 3!! + 210$$

• **926**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) + 7!/6 + 5 = -4 + 3!! + 210$$

• **928**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) + 7 + 6! + 5! = -\sqrt{4} + 3!! + 210$$

• **930**

$$\blacktriangleright ((1+2)! + 3!!/4) \times 5 = 6! + 7! / (8 \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7)! + (6! + 5!)/4 = 3!! + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! + 210$$

• **930:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7!/6 = 5!/4 \times (32 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7!/6 = (5 - 4) \times 3!! + 210$$

• 930:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5/4 = 3!! + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) + 4! = 3!! + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + 7! / 6 + 5 + 4} = 3!! + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + 7 + 6! + 5! + \sqrt{4}} = 3!! + 210$$

• 933

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 + 8! + 7!} + 6! = \sqrt{5 + 4} + 3!! + 210$$

• 936

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!^3 + (\sqrt{4 + 5})!! = (6 + 7) \times 8 \times 9$$

• 936:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6) = (5 - \sqrt{4})!^3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6) = (5 \times 4! - 3) \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 938

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7! / 6 = 5! \times 4! / 3 - 21 - 0!$$

• 946

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (-7 + 6 + 5!) = 43 \times (21 + 0!)$$

• 951

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! / (7 \times 6) = 5 + 43 \times (21 + 0!)$$

• 954

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! - 3! + \sqrt{4} \times 5! = 6! + 78 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8! / (7 \times 6) = (5! \times 4 - 3) \times 2 \times 1$$

• 954:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!) = 4! + 3!! + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 87 \times (6 + 5) = 4! + 3!! + 210$$

• 956

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 76 + 5! = 4 \times (3!! / (2 + 1) - 0!)$$

• 957

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8! / (7 \times 6) = 5! \times (\sqrt{4})^3 - 2 - 1$$

• 959

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! / 6 + 5! = 4 \times 3!! / (2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 959:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9})! + 8! / 7! / 6 = 5! / 4 \times 32 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9})! + 8! / 7! / 6 = 5 \times 4! \times (3! + 2) - 1$$

• 960

$$\blacktriangleright (98 / 7 - 6) \times 5! = 4 \times 3!! / (2 + 1) = 4 \times (3! - 2)! \times 10$$

• 960:

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! / 3 \times 4 = 5! \times (-6 + 78) / 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! / 3 \times 4 = 5! \times (6 + 7 - (8 - \sqrt{9}))$$

• 960:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8! / (7! \times 6) = 5! / 4 \times 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8! / (7! \times 6) = (5 + 43) \times 2 \times 10$$

• 961

• 961:

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8! / 7 \right) / 6! \times 5! = 5! / 4 \times 32 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8! / 7 \right) / 6! \times 5! = 5 \times 4! \times (3! + 2) + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8! / 7 \right) / 6! \times 5! = 4 \times 3!! / (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• 963

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9+8!}/7/6 = \sqrt{5+4} \times 321$$

• 964

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7!)/6 + 5! = 4 \times (3!/(2+1) + 0!)$$

• 966

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8!/(7 \times 6) = (5! \times 4 + 3) \times 2 \times 1$$

• 969

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! / 7 / 6 = 5! \times \sqrt{4} + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

• 972

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3^4 = (5 \times 6 + 78) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + (8+7) \times 65 = 4 \times 3^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

• 981

$$\blacktriangleright 987 - 6 = 5! \times 4! / 3 + 21$$

• 987

• 987:

$$\blacktriangleright 987 = 6! - 54 + 321$$

$$\blacktriangleright 987 = 6 + 5! \times 4! / 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 987 = 6! + 5! + (4 + 3) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 987 = ((6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 987 = 6! + 54 + 3 + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright 987 = 65 \times 4 + 3! + (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 987 = 6 \times 5! + 4! + 3^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

• 993

$$\blacktriangleright 987 + 6 = (5! + 4) \times (3! + 2) + 1$$

• 999

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 876 + 5! = (4 + 3!)^{2+1} - 0!$$

4.4 Four Digits Numbers

- **1000**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7!/6! \times 5 = (4 + 3!)^{2+1} = (4 + 3!)^2 \times 10$

- **1001**

▶ $(98 - 7) \times (6 + 5) = (4 + 3!)^{2+1} + 0!$

- **1008**

▶ $12^3 - (\sqrt{4+5})!! = 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 = (5 + 43) \times 21$

▶ $9 \times 8 \times \sqrt{76+5!} = 4! \times (32 + 10)$

- **1008:**

▶ $(123 + 45) \times 6 = 7! / (8 - \sqrt{9})$

▶ $1 - 23 + 4^5 + 6 = 7! / (8 - \sqrt{9})$

▶ $12 \times 3! \times 4 + 5! \times 6 = 7! / (8 - \sqrt{9})$

- **1014**

▶ $(1 + 2)! + (3 + 4)!/5 = 6 + 7! / (8 - \sqrt{9})$

▶ $((\sqrt{9}) \times 8 + 7! + 6) / 5 = 4^{3+2} - 10$

- **1022**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 \times 6!/5 = 4 - 3! + 2^{10}$

- **1023**

▶ $-1 + 2^{3!+4} = (5 + 6 \times 7 \times 8) \times \sqrt{9}$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) = 4^{3+2} - 1$

- **1024**

▶ $1 \times 2^{3!+4} = \sqrt{5+6-7} \times 8^{\sqrt{9}}$

▶ $(-9 \times 8 + 76)^5 = 4^{3 \times 2 - 1}$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 76) \times 5 + 4 = 32^{1+0!}$

• 1024:

- ▶ $\left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8\right) \times 7 - 6\right) / 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3 = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8\right) \times (76 - 5) + 4! + 3! = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8 + 7! + 6\right) / 5 + 4 \times 3 = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $(-9 \times 8 + 76)^5 \times (4 - 3) = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $(98 / 7 - 6) \times 5! + 4^3 = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $(-98 + 7 + 6! - 5!) \times \sqrt{4} + 3! = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5) + 4! / 3 = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $-\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 3\right)! = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5) + \sqrt{4} + 3!! = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $-\left(\sqrt{9}\right) + 8! / (7 \times 6) - 5 + 4! \times 3 = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6) + 5) + 43 = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $98 + 7 \times 6 \times 5 - 4 + 3!! = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $987 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $987 + 6 + 5^{\sqrt{4}} + 3! = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! / (7 \times 6) - 5 + 4! \times 3 = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times (7! / 6! + 5!) + \sqrt{4} + 3 = 2^{10}$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \times 6! / 5 + 4! + 3 = 2^{10}$

• 1025

▶ $9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! / 5 = 4^{3+2} + 1 = 4 - 3 + 2^{10}$

• 1026

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7! + 6!) / 5! = 4^{3+2} + 1 + 0!$

• 1027

• 1027:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) + 4 = 3 + 2^{10}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \times 6! / 5 + 4! = 3 + 2^{10}$

• 1029

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7! / 6) / 5! = \sqrt{4} + 3 + 2^{10}$

• 1030

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3 + 2^{10}$$

• 1030:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6! / 5 + 4! = 3! + 2^{10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7) \times (-6 + 5!) + 4 = 3! + 2^{10}$$

• 1032

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7! / 6 + 5! = 4! / 3 + 2^{10}$$

• 1048

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times (7 + 6) + 5 = 4 \times 3! + 2^{10}$$

• 1050

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3) \times 210$$

• 1053

• 1053:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times (7 + 6) = (5 + 4) \times (-3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!))$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times (7 + 6) = 5 + 4! + 32^{1+0!}$$

• 1054

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + (7! + 6!) / 5 = 4! + 3! + 2^{10}$$

• 1056

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5!) = 6! + 7 \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 1056:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = (5! - 4!) \times (3! \times 2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = (5 + 43) \times (21 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7 \times 6 = (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5 + 4! + 3 + 2^{10}$$

• 1064

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times 76 = 5 \times 4! / 3 + 2^{10}$$

• 1067

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 \right) \times (6 + 5) = 43 + 2^{10}$$

• 1080

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times 3!! / \sqrt{4} = 5 \times (-6 + 78) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 23) \times 45 = (6 + 7 - 8)! \times 9$$

• 1080:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6)! = 5! \times (4 + 3 + 2) \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6)! = 5 \times 432 / (1 + 0!)$$

• 1089

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 \times 7 + 65) = (4! + 3^2)^{1+0!}$$

• 1096

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) = 4! \times 3 + 2^{10}$$

• 1104

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 5) = 4! \times (3!^2 + 10)$$

• 1144

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) / 7 \times (6 + 5) = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + 2^{10}$$

• 1152

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times 4 / 5 = (6! + 7!) / (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6) + 5!) = 4!^3 / (2 + 10)$$

• 1170

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 \times (7 + 6) = (-5 + (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + 2) \times 10$$

• 1200

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4) \times 5! = 6! \times (7 + 8) / 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + (8 - 7)^6) \times 5! = (4 + 3 - 2)! \times 10$$

• 1200:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 \times 5 \times 4 = (3 + 2)! \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (7!/6! + 5) + 4! = (3 + 2)! \times 10$$

• 1202

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7 + 6!/5) = \sqrt{4} + (3 + 2)! \times 10$$

• 1224

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3! - 4! + 5!) = 6! + 7 \times 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! = (5! - 4! + 3!) \times (2 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (7 + 65) = 4! + (3 + 2)! \times 10$$

• 1234

$$\blacktriangleright 1234 = -5 + 6! + 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 1239

$$\blacktriangleright 1234 + 5 = 6! + 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 1240

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5 = (4 + (3 + 2)!) \times 10$$

• 1242

• 1242:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 87 \times 6 = 54 \times ((3! - 2!) - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 87 \times 6 = 54 \times (3 + 2 \times 10)$$

• 1260

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (-3 + 4!) \times 5 = 6 \times 7! / (8 \times \sqrt{9})$$

• 1260

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 76) \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times 210$$

• 1260:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (7 + \sqrt{6! \times 5}) + 4 = 3! \times 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) / \sqrt{6!/5} + \sqrt{4} = 3! \times 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7 \times \sqrt{6! \times 5}) + 4! = 3! \times 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 \times 5! / 4 = 3! \times 210$$

• 1262

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) / \sqrt{6!/5} = \sqrt{4} + 3! \times 210$$

• 1278

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9 + 8! + 7!}) \times 6 = 5 \times \sqrt{4^{3!+2}} - 1 - 0!$$

• 1280

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! / (7 + 65) = 4 \times 32 \times 10$$

• 1283

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 + 8! + 7!} \times 6 + 5 = 4 \times 321 - 0!$$

• 1284

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 \times \sqrt{6! \times 5}) = 4 \times 321$$

• 1287

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} \times 7 + 6!} = -5 - 4 + 3!^{2+1+0!}$$

• 1288

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (76 - 5) = 4 \times (321 + 0!)$$

• 1290

$$\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)! + 3!^4 = 5! - 6! + 7! / 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 1293

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 3!^4 = (5! + 6 \times 7) \times 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 1294

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 = -56 + 7! / 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 1295

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3!^4 = 567 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 1296

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{(12 \times 3)^4} = (5! + 6)/7 \times 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3) \times (4! + 5!) = 6^{-7+8+\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5) = (4 + 32)^{1+0!}$$

• 1296:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 + 4) = 3!^{2+1+0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (-7 + \sqrt{6! \times 5}) + 4! = 3!^{2+1+0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 = 3!^{2+1+0!}$$

• 1298

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!^4 = (\sqrt{5^6} - 7) \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

• 1299

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + 3!^4 = (5! + 6 \times 7) \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 1308

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3!^4 = 5! + 6! + 78 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 1344

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (-3! - \sqrt{4} + 5!) = 6! + 7!/8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! = 4^3 \times 21$$

• 1350

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (-3! + 456) = 7!/8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 45) = 6! \times 7/8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 1350:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 \times 7 + 6! = 5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! - 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 \times 7 + 6! = 5 + 4^3 \times 21 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 \times 7 + 6! = 54 \times ((3! - 2)! + 1)$$

• 1353

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 87 + 6! = 5^4 + 3^{(2+1)!} - 0!$$

• 1384

• 1384:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5! / \sqrt{4} \times 3! + 2^{10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5! + 4 + 3! \times 210$$

• 1392

• 1392:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (-7 + 65) = (-4! + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (-7 + 65) = (-4! + (3 \times 2)!) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 1394

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (7 + 6) + 5! = (-4! + 3!!) \times 2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 1396

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7 + 6! = 5! + 43 \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 1397

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7! / 6! + 5!) = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! - 21) - 0!$$

• 1398

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5 = 678 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 + 8! + 7!} \times 6 + 5! = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! - 21)$$

• 1404

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 3!^4 + 5! = 6 \times 78 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 1406

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 + 6! = (5 - 4! + 3!! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **1408**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right)^7 \times (6 + 5) = 4^3 \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **1416**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 = -4! + 3!! \times 2 \times 1$$

• **1422**

• **1422:**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3!^4 + 5! = 6! + 78 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5) = 6! + 78 \times 9$$

• **1424**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8\right) \times (-7!/6! + 5) = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + 2 - 10)$$

• **1425**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (3!! - \sqrt{4} - 5) = 6! - 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• **1425**

• **1425:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7 + 6! = (-5 - \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 + (4! \times 3! - 2) \times 10$$

• **1426**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right) \times (-7 + 6!) = (-5 - \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1$$

• **1428**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 \times \sqrt{6!/5} = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! - (2 + 1)!)$$

• **1429**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (-3! + (2 + 1)!!) + 0!$$

• **1430**

• 1430:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times 2 - 10 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5) &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times 2 - 10 \\ &= (-4 + 3!!) \times 2 - 1 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 1430:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 \times \sqrt{6!/5} + \sqrt{4} &= 3!! \times 2 - 10 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 + 4 &= 3!! \times 2 - 10 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} &= 3!! \times 2 - 10 \\ \blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 + 6 \times 5! + 4! &= 3!! \times 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 1431

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4) &= 5 + (6! - 7) \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!) \\ \blacktriangleright (-(\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times (-7 + 6!) + 5 &= (-4 + 3!!) \times 2 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 1432

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) = (5 - 6 + 7)! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 1432:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! + 6! &= 5 + \sqrt{4} \times (-3! + (2 + 1)!!) - 0! \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! + 6! &= 5! \times 4 \times 3 + 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 1432:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! + 6 \times 5! &= (-4 + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! + 6 \times 5! &= \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + 2 - 10 \end{aligned}$$

• 1433

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! - 7 + 6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} \times (3!! - (2 + 1)!)$$

• 1433:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! - 7 + (6!/5!)! = (-4 + 3!!) \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! - 7 + (6!/5!)! = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! - 2 - 1) - 0!$$

• 1436

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (-7 + 6! + 5) = 4 \times (3!!/2 - 1)$$

• 1436:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 76 + 5! + 4! = (3!! - 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6! + 5) \times \sqrt{4} = (3!! - 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 1437

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! + 6! + 5 + 4 = 3!! \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! + 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! - 2 \times 1) + 0!$$

• 1438

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 87 + 6 + 5^4 = 3!! \times 2 - 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times ((3 \times 2)! - 1)$$

• 1439

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3 \times 2)! - 1 = 4 \times 3!!/2 - 1$$

• 1439:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3!! = \sqrt{4} \times (-5 + 6! + 7) - 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3!! = 4 - 5 + 6! + (7 + 8 - 9)!$$

• 1439:

$$\blacktriangleright ((1+2)!! - 3) \times \sqrt{4} + 5 = 6! + 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3 \times 4 \times 5! = 6! + 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 1439:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4! = 3!! \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 + 4 = 3!! \times 2 - 1$$

• 1439:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5! \times 4 \times 3 - 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 + 4 + 3!! \times 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} \times (3!! - 2 - 1)$$

• 1440

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + \sqrt{4})! = 5! \times 6 + (7 + 8 - 9)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (-3 + 4) \times 5! = 6! \times (7 - 8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 - 7) \times 6! / 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times 2 \times 1 = (4 \times 3)^2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7 + 65) \times 4 = 3!! \times 2 \times 1$$

• 1440:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! = 4 - 5 + 6! - 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! = 4! + (-5 + 6! - 7) \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! = 4 \times (5 + 67) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! = \sqrt{4} \times (56 - 7 \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!)$$

• 1440:

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7) \times 6! = (5 - 4) \times 3!! \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7 + 6! = (5 - 4) \times 3!! \times 2 \times 1 \\ == 5! \times 4 \times 3 + 21 \times 0$$

• 1441

$$\triangleright 1 + 2 \times 3!! = 4! - 5 + 6! + 78 \times 9$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7 + 6! = 5 - 4 + 3!! \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\triangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! - 4 + 5 = 6! - 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! + 6! + 5 + 4 = 3!! \times 2 + 1$$

• 1442

$$\triangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 = 4 + 3!! \times 2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 1444

$$\triangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! + 4 = 5 + 6! + 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\triangleright (- (\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times (7 + 6! - 5) = 4 + 3!! \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\triangleright (9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5)^{\sqrt{4}} = (3!! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 1445

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8 - 7) \times (6! + 5) = 4 + 3!! \times 2 + 1$$

• 1446

$$\triangleright (1 + 2 + 3!!) \times \sqrt{4} = 5 + 6! - 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 1446:

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + 2) + 1 + 0!$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7 + 6! + 5 = 4 + 3!! \times 2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 1447

$$\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + 7 + (6!/5!) = (4 + 3!!) \times 2 - 1$$

• 1447:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + 7 + 6! = (5 - \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + 7 + 6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + 2 \times 1$$

• 1448

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4) = (5 - 6 + 7)! + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 1448:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 76 + 5! = (4 + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! + 6 \times 5! = (4 + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$= \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + 2 + 1 + 0!)$$

• 1448:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! + 6! = 5 + 4 + 3!! \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! + 6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! + 6! = 5! \times 4 \times 3 - 2 + 10$$

• 1449

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7 + 6!) = 5 + (4 + 3!!) \times 2 + 1$$

• 1450

• 1450:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 - 7 + \sqrt{6! \times 5} \times 4! = 3!! \times 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 + 6! + 5^4 = 3!! \times 2 + 10$$

• 1452

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! \times \sqrt{4} = (\sqrt{5^6} + 7) \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + 7 + 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + (2 + 1)!!)$$

• 1453

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! + 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + (2 + 1)!) + 0!$$

• 1454

• 1454:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3!! + \sqrt{4} + 5) = (6! + 7) \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4) + 5 = (6! + 7) \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• 1454:

$$\blacktriangleright (- (\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times (7 + 6!) = (5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (- (\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times (7 + 6!) = (-5 + 43)^2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (- (\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times (7 + 6 \times 5!) = 4 + 3!! \times 2 + 10$$

• 1455

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times (3!! + \sqrt{4} + 5) = 6! + 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 1455:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 + 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 + 6! = 5 + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times 2 + 10$$

• 1457

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7! - 6! \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3^{(2+1)!} - 0!$$

• **1458**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times (7 + 6 + 5) = \sqrt{4} \times 3^{(2+1)!}$$

• **1459**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7 + 6!) + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3^{(2+1)!} + 0!$$

• **1460**

• **1460:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 = 4! + (3!! - 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 + 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times ((3 \times 2)! + 10)$$

• **1461**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} - 7! - \sqrt{6! \times 5} = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + 21$$

• **1462**

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + (7 + 6) \times 5! = 4! + 3!! \times 2 - 1 - 0!$$

• **1463**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4! = 5! + 6! + 7 \times 89$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5!) = 4! + 3!! \times 2 - 1$$

• **1470**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! = (4 + 3) \times 210$$

• **1472**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}}}}} \right) - 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **1482**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)! + 7 \right) \times (-6 + 5!) = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + 21)$$

• **1486**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} - 7 \times (6! + 5) = (4! + 3!!) \times 2 - 1 - 0!$$

• **1487**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) = (5! + 67) \times 8 - 9$$

• **1488**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4!) = (-5 + 67) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **1488:**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! = (4! + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! = (4! + (3 \times 2)!) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **1496**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7 \right) + 6! = 5! \times (4! - 3) - 2^{10}$$

• **1503**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 87 + 6! = 5 + (4! + 3!!) \times 2 + 10$$

• **1504**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \times 7 + 6! + 5! = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

• **1512**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4! = 567 \times 8 / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5! = 4! \times 3 \times 21$$

• **1536**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{3!} \times 4! = 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8^{\sqrt{\sqrt{76+5}}} = 4! \times 32 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **1552**

• **1552:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7!/6 = 5! + (-4 + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7!/6 = (54 + 3!! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **1560**

- ▶ $(1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4! = 5 \times (6 + 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $(12 - 3 + 4) \times 5! = (6 + 7) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(9 + 8 + 7) \times 65 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + ((2 + 1)! - 0!)!$

• **1560:**

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times (7 + 6) = 5 \times 4! \times (3! \times 2 + 1)$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times (7 + 6) = 5! / \sqrt{4} \times (-3! + \sqrt{2^{10}})$

• **1566**

• **1566:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 87 \times 6 = 5! + \sqrt{4} \times (3 + (2 + 1)!!)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 87 \times 6 = 5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 87 \times 6 = 54 \times (-3 + \sqrt{2^{10}})$

• **1568**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + (8 + 7!/6) = 5! + (4 + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1$

• **1584**

- ▶ $9 \times (8 + 7!/(6 \times 5)) = 4! \times 3 \times (21 + 0!)$

• **1596**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 876 = 5 \times (-\sqrt{4} + 321) + 0!$

• **1608**

- ▶ $12^3 - 4! \times 5 = 67 \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

• **1620**

- ▶ $12 \times 3 \times 45 = (-6! + 7!)/8 \times \sqrt{9}$

• **1650**

- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + 210$

• 1679

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2^3)!/4! = 5 - 6 - 7! + 8! / (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 1680

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)!/4! = 5! \times (-6 + 7) \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2 + 3 \times 4) \times 5! = (6 - 7 + 8)! / \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-(\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7!/6 = 5! \times (-4 - 3 + 21)210$$

• 1680:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times (7 + 6) + 5! = (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times (7 + 6) + 5! = \sqrt{4^3} \times 210$$

• 1686

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2^3)!/4! + 5 = 6 - 7! + 8! / (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 1704

$$\blacktriangleright 12^3 - 4! = (5! - 6) \times (7 + 8) - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (76 - 5) = 4! \times \sqrt{(3! + 2 - 1)! + 0!}$$

• 1707

$$\blacktriangleright 987 + 6! = \sqrt{(5! + 4!)^3} - 21$$

• 1728

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! \times 4! = (5 + 67) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! = (4 \times 3)^{2+1}$$

• 1728:

$$\blacktriangleright 12^3 = (-4 + 5) \times 6! + 7! / (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12^3 = \sqrt{4} \times (5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12^3 = \sqrt{4 + 5} \times 6 \times (7 + 89)$$

• 1744

• 1744:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7 \times (6+5) \times 4 = 3!! + 2^{10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 \times 6! / 5 + 4! = 3!! + 2^{10}$$

• 1752

$$\blacktriangleright 12^3 + 4! + 5! = (-6 + 7!/8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 1764

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 4! + 5!) = (6 \times 7)^{8-(\sqrt{9})!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (7 + 6 + 5) = ((4! - 3) \times 2)^{1+0!}$$

• 1800

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3) \times 4! \times 5 = 6! \times (7 + 8) / (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times (8 - 7) + 6) \times 5! = (4! + 3!)^2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 1800:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 + 7) / 6 = 5! \times (4 \times 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 + 7) / 6 = 5 \times (4 + 32) \times 10$$

• 1824

• 1824:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 76 = (5! - 4!) \times \sqrt{3!!/2 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 76 = (54 + 3) \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 1839

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 76 + 5) = 43^2 - 10$$

• 1848

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) = 43^2 - 1$$

• 1860

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + 210)$$

• 1872

$$\triangleright 12^3 + 4! + 5! = (-6 + 7!/8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 1890

• 1890:

$$\triangleright (1 + 2 \times 3) \times 45 \times 6 = 7!/8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\triangleright 1 \times 234 \times 5 + 6! = 7!/8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 1899

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-87 + 6!) = 5^4 \times 3 + (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• 1920

• 1920:

$$\triangleright (9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5! = (\sqrt{4^3})!/21$$

$$\triangleright (9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5! = 4! \times (3! + 2) \times 10$$

• 1921

$$\triangleright (9 + 8) \times (-7!/6! + 5!) = (\sqrt{4^3})!/21 + 0!$$

• 1944

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 76 + 5! = 4! \times 3^{2+1+0!}$$

• 1992

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 \times 7 + 6!) = (5! + 4!^3) / ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• 2016

$$\triangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3!^4 = (5! + (6 + 7) \times 8) \times 9$$

$$\triangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4)!/5 = 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\triangleright 98/7 \times 6!/5 = (\sqrt{4^3})!/(2 \times 10)$$

• 2025

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8!/7 + 6^5 = (43 + 2)^{1+0!}$$

• 2046

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) = 4^{3!}/2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 2048

• 2048:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7)^{6+5} = 4^{3!}/2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7)^{6+5} = 4^3 \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 2058

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! + 7!/6)/5! = 4^{3!}/2 + 10$$

• 2070

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times 345 = 6! + 7!/8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 2088

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (3!! - 4!) = (-5! + 6 \times 78) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 87/(6 \times 5) = (-4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)$$

• 2096

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3!^4 = 5! + 6 + 7!/8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 2100

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 - 7 + 6! - 5) = (4 + 3!) \times 210$$

• 2136

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8!/7! + 6!) = 5! \times 4! - 3!! - (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• 2139

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \times (-7 + 6!) = \sqrt{5 + 4} \times 3!! - 21$$

• 2140

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 \times (8-7)} \times 6! = 5! + 4 \times (3!! - 210)$$

• 2148

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2) \times (3!! - 4) = (-5 + 6! - 7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 6! - 5) = (-4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)$$

• 2153

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 - 7 - 6! \times 5 = (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 2154

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2) \times (3!! - \sqrt{4}) = 5! + 678 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + (8+7) \times 6!/5 = (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)$$

• 2156

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (76 + 5!) = -4 + 3!! \times (2 + 1)$$

• 2157

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2) \times (3!! + 4 - 5) = (6! + 7 - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 - \sqrt{4}) = 3 \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• 2157:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7 + 6!) = (5 - \sqrt{4}) \times ((3 \times 2)! - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7 + 6!) = 5! \times 4! - 3!! - (2 + 1) \times 0!$$

• 2158

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times 3 - \sqrt{4} = -5 + (6! - 7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 2159

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (7!/6! + 5!) = 4 \times 3!! - (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! \times 4 = 3!! \times (2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 2160

$$\blacktriangleright 12^3/4 \times 5 = 6! \times (-7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **2160:**

- ▶ $(1+2)!! \times 3 = 4! + (5+6-7)! \times 89$
- ▶ $(1+2)!! \times 3 = 45 \times 6 \times (7-8+9)$
- ▶ $(1+2)!! \times 3 = 45 + (6! - 7 - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$

• **2160:**

- ▶ $(98 - 7 - 6 + 5) \times 4! = 3!! \times (2+1)$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7!/6 + 5! \times 4 = 3!! \times (2+1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5! + 4! = 3!! \times (2+1)$

• **2160:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8-7) \times 6! = 5 \times 432 \times 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8-7) \times 6! = 5 + (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2+1) + 0!$

• **2160:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8-7) \times 6 \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times (2+1)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8-7) \times 6 \times 5! = 4! \times 3^2 \times 10$

• **2161**

- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! \times 4$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + (8+7) \times 6!/5 + 4 = 3!! \times (2+1) + 0!$

• **2162**

- ▶ $(1+2)!! \times 3 + \sqrt{4} = 5 + (6! + 7 - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7 + 6!) + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3 \times (2+1)!!$

• **2163**

- ▶ $1 + 2 + 3 \times (\sqrt{4+5})!! = (6! - 7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + (8+7) \times 6!/5 = 4 + 3!! \times (2+1) - 0!$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \times (-7 + (6!/5)!) + 4! = 3 \times ((2+1)!! + 0!)$

• **2163:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 6!) &= 5 - \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times (2 + 1) \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 6!) &= (5 - 4) \times 3 \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!) \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 6!) &= (5 - \sqrt{4}) \times ((3 \times 2)! + 1) \end{aligned}$$

• **2165**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7) \times 6! + 5 = 4 + 3!! \times (2 + 1) + 0!$$

• **2166**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 - 6! \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)$$

• **2167**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + 7 - 6! \times 5 = 4 + 3 \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **2172**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4) &= (5 + 6! + 7 - 8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7 + 6! + 5) &= (4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

• **2184**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3 + 4! &= ((5 - 6 + 7)! + 8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 76 + 5!) &= 4! + 3!! \times (2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

• **2187**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^{8-7+6}} &= (5 + 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{87-6}} \right)^5 &= 4! + 3 \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **2187:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 \times (87 - 6) \times (5 - \sqrt{4}) &= 3^{(2+1)!+0!} \\ \blacktriangleright 987 + 6! + 5! \times 4 &= 3^{(2+1)!+0!} \end{aligned}$$

• 2187:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}}}}} \right) = 6 + \sqrt{5+4} \times 3!! + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}}}}} \right) = (6! + 5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3 + (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}}}}} \right) = 6!/5! + 4! + 3 \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}}}}} \right) = 6! + 5^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!! \times 2 + 1 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}}}}} \right) = (6! + 5) \times 4 + 3! - (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• 2189

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!/7! + 6!) + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3^{(2+1)!+0!}$$

• 2193

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}}}}} \right) + 6 = (\sqrt{5+4})! + 3^{(2+1)!+0!}$$

• 2205

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3 + 45 = (6! + 7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 + 6!) = 5 \times (4! - 3) \times 21$$

• 2231

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8!/(7 + 6 + 5) = (4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 1) - 0!$$

• 2232

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4!) = (5! - 6 + 7!/8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (-8 + 76 \times 5) = (4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)$$

• 2241

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} - 7! + 6! = (5! - \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{3!!/2 + 1} - 0!$$

• **2304**

• **2304:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!/7! + 6!) + 5! = 4!^3 / (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!/7! + 6!) + 5! = 4! \times 3 \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **2400**

$$\blacktriangleright (98/7 + 6) \times 5! = \sqrt{4} \times (3 + 2)! \times 10$$

• **2401**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 2^3)^4 = (56 - 7)^{8 - (\sqrt{9})!}$$

• **2421**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (87 + 6!) = 5!^{\sqrt{4}} / 3! + 21$$

• **2496**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!/6) = (5! - 4!) \times (3^{2+1} - 0!)$$

• **2516**

• **2516:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) / 6 = \left((5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! \right) / 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) / 6 = \left((5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! - 2 \right) / (1 + 0!)$$

• **2517**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + (-3 + 4!) \times 5! = (-6 + 7!) / \left(8 - (\sqrt{9})! \right)$$

• **2520**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3)! / \sqrt{4} = 56 \times (7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 2) \times (3 - 4!) \times 5! = 6! \times 7 / \left(8 - (\sqrt{9})! \right)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \times 7!/6 = 5 \times 4 \times 3! \times 21$$

• 2520:

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2) \times (3!! - \sqrt{4} + 5!) + 6 = 7! / (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3+4) \times 5 \times 6 = 7! / (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• 2520:

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 87) \times 6 \times 5 = (4+3)! / 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 87) \times 6 \times 5 = 4 \times 3 \times 210$$

• 2521

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) / 6 + 5 = (4+3)! / 2 + 1$$

• 2523

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + (-3 + 4!) \times 5! = (6 + 7!) / (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• 2524

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) / 6 = 5 + (4 + 3)! / 2 - 1$$

• 2526

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2) \times (3!! + \sqrt{4} + 5!) = 6 + 7! / (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• 2544

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! / 6) = 5! \times (4! - 3) + (2 + 1 + 0)! / 1$$

• 2592

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 = 5 \times 6! - 7! / (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (7! - 6!) / 5! = (4! \times 3)^2 / (1 + 0!)$$

• 2640

$$\blacktriangleright (98 - 76) \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! \times (21 + 0!)$$

• 2670

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 \times (6 + 5!)) = 4 \times 3!! - 210$$

• **2736**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8) \times 7! + 6^5 = 4! \times (-3! + ((2 + 1)! - 0!))$$

• **2760**

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 7 + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times 3!! - ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• **2784**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (-7 + 65) = 4 \times (3!! - (2 + 1 + 0)!)$$

• **2792**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 7 + 6^5 = 4 \times (3!! - 21 - 0!)$$

• **2808**

$$\blacktriangleright -12 \times 3! + 4! \times 5! = 6 \times 78 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 - 7! + 6^5 = 4! \times (-3 + ((2 + 1)! - 0!))$$

• **2832**

$$\blacktriangleright (-12 + 3!!) \times 4 = (\sqrt{5^6} - 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **2840**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! - (8!/7! - 6!) \times 5 = 4 \times ((3 \times 2)! - 10)$$

• **2856**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! = (5! + 6 - 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7! / (6 \times 5) = 4! \times ((3 + 2)! - 1)$$

• **2860**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7) \times (6! - 5) = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! \times 2 - 10)$$

• **2871**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 87 \times (6 + 5) = 4 \times (3!! - 2) - 1$$

• **2872**

• **2872:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times (3!! - 2 \times 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! - 8!/7! + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times 3!! + 2 - 10$$

• **2873**

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! - 7 + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times (3!! - 2) + 1$$

• **2874**

$$\blacktriangleright - (\sqrt{9})! + 8! / \sqrt{76 + 5!} = 4 \times 3!! - (2 + 1)!$$

• **2877**

$$\blacktriangleright - \sqrt{9} + 8! / \sqrt{76 + 5!} = 4 \times 3!! - 2 - 1$$

• **2879**

$$\blacktriangleright - 1 + (2 \times 3)! \times 4 = 5 \times 6! + 7 - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright - (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times (3 \times 2)! - 1$$

• **2880**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{12 \times 3})! \times 4 = 5 \times 6 \times (7 + 89)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3 \times 4) \times 5! = 6! \times (-7 + 8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5!) \times 4! = 3!! \times 2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **2880:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6 \times 5 = 4 \times (3 \times 2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6 \times 5 = 4! \times 3! \times 2 \times 10$$

• **2880:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! / 7 / 6 = (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7) \times 6! = 5! \times 4! + 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! / 7 / 6 = (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7) \times 6! = (5 + 4) \times 32 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! / 7 / 6 = (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7) \times 6! = 5 + 4 \times 3!! - (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• **2881**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)! \times 4 = 5 \times 6! - 7 + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright - (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

• **2883**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8!/\sqrt{76+5!} = 4 \times 3!! + 2 + 1$$

• **2885**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8!/7/6+5 = 4 \times ((3 \times 2)! + 1) + 0!$$

• **2886**

• **2886:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8!/\sqrt{76+5!} = 4 \times 3!! + (2+1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8!/\sqrt{76+5!} = 4 \times (3!! + 2) - 1 - 0!$$

• **2887**

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + 7 + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times (3!! + 2) - 1$$

• **2888**

• **2888:**

$$\blacktriangleright - (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times (3!! + 2) \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright - (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times 3!! - 2 + 10$$

• **2889**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8!/\sqrt{76+5!} = 4 \times (3!! + 2) + 1$$

• **2900**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7) \times (6! + 5) = 4 \times 3!! + 2 \times 10$$

• **2904**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! = (5! - 6 + 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **2904:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5) = 4! \times ((3 + 2)! + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5) = 4 \times 3!! + (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• 2907

• 2907:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)^7 + 6! = 5! \times 4! + 3! + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)^7 + 6! = 5 + 4 \times 3!! + 21 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)^7 + 6! = -5 + 4 \times 3!! + \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 2912

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) \times (-7 + 6 + 5) = 4 \times (3!! - 2 + 10)$$

• 2915

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + (7 + 6!) \times 5 = 4 \times 3^{(2+1)!} - 0!$$

• 2916

• 2916:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times (7! - 6!) / 5! = ((4! + 3) \times 2)^{1+0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times (7! - 6!) / 5! = 4 \times 3^{(2+1)!}$$

• 2920

$$\blacktriangleright - (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7 \times 65 = 4 \times ((3 \times 2)! + 10)$$

• 2928

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3!!) \times 4 = 5! + 6 \times 78 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 76 - 5!) = 4 \times (3!! + 2 + 10)$$

• 2960

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! / (7 + 6 + 5) = 4 \times (3!! + 21 - 0!)$$

• 2965

$$\blacktriangleright (-(-\sqrt{9}+8)!-7+6!) \times 5 = 4 \times (3!!+21)+0!$$

• 2968

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8}+7-6! \times 5 = 4 \times (3!!+21+0!)$$

• 3000

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times 8+7-6) \times 5! = 4! \times (3! \times 21-0!)$$

• 3024

$$\blacktriangleright (9+8+7) \times (6+5!) = 4! \times 3! \times 21$$

• 3024:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 5!+4! \times ((3+2)!+1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 = 5!+4!+3!! \times (2+1+0!)$$

• 3025

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8 \times 76) \times 5 = 4! \times 3! \times 21+0!$$

• 3060

$$\blacktriangleright -12+3 \times 4^5 = 6 \times 7!/8 - (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 3072

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8^{\sqrt{\sqrt{76+5}}} = 4^3! - 2^{10}$$

• 3072:

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!+8 \times 76 \right) \times 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3 \times 2^{10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9+87) \times (6 \times 5 + \sqrt{4}) = 3 \times 2^{10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7!/6!+5!)+4! = 3 \times 2^{10}$$

• 3096

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 \times 7+6! \times 5 = 4!+3 \times 2^{10}$$

• 3102

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!+8! \right) / (7+6) = 5!/4+3 \times 2^{10}$$

• **3120**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 87) + 6! \times 5 = 4! \times ((3 + 2)! + 10)$$

• **3125**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \right)^6 / 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)^{(2+1)! - 0!}$$

• **3132**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 87 \times 6 = (5! - 4) \times (3! + 21)$$

• **3168**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (-76 + 5!) = 4! \times 3! \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **3210**

• **3210:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 87 + 6!) \times 5! / 4! = 3210$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5! \times 4! = 3210$$

• **3240**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! \times 45 = 6! + 7! / (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9 \times (87 - 6)} \times 5! = (4! - 3!)^2 \times 10$$

• **3360**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 76 \times 5! = (\sqrt{4^3})! / (2 + 10)$$

• **3375**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 + 3 + 4 \times (5! + 6!) = (7 + 8)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) + 6!) \times 5 = 4^{3!} - (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• **3376**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8^{-7+6+5} = 4^{3!} - (2 + 1)!!$$

• **3402**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times 7 \times 6 = 54 \times 3 \times 21$$

• **3456**

▶ $12^3 \times \sqrt{4} = (56 \times 7 - 8) \times 9$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7 + 65) = (4!^3/2)/(1 + 0!)$

• **3560**

▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + (-7 + 6!) \times 5 = (-4 + 3!!/2) \times 10$

• **3565**

▶ $(-1 - 2 + 3!! - 4) \times 5 = (6! - 7) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$

▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (-7 + 6!) = 5 \times (-4 + 3!! - 2 - 1)$

• **3580**

▶ $(-\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 = (-4 + 3!!)/2 \times 10$

• **3584**

▶ $-1 \times 2 + (3!! - 4) \times 5 + 6 = 7 \times 8^{\sqrt{9}}$

• **3590**

▶ $-9 - 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5 = (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$

• **3590:**

▶ $(1 \times (2 \times 3)! - \sqrt{4}) \times 5 = 6 + 7 \times 8^{\sqrt{9}}$

▶ $1 \times (-2 + (3 \times \sqrt{4})!) \times 5 = 6 + 7 \times 8^{\sqrt{9}}$

• **3592**

▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7! - 6! = 5 \times (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) + 2 \times 1$

• **3595**

▶ $((\sqrt{9})!! - (8 - 7)^6) \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3) \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$

• **3599**

▶ $-(9 - 8)^7 + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times 3!! + (2 + 1)! - 0!$

• **3600**

▶ $((1 + 23)/4)! \times 5 = 6! \times (7 + 8)/\sqrt{9}$

▶ $(1 + 2)!! \times (3 + \sqrt{4}) = (56 \times 7 + 8) \times 9$

• 3600:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (-8 + 7 + 6) = (54 + 3!)^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (-8 + 7 + 6) = (5 \times 4 \times 3)^2 \times 1$$

• 3600:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 6! \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 6! \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! / 2 \times 10$$

• 3600:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + (8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4 = 3!! / 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 + 4! = 3!! / 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8! / 7!) \times 6! + 5! \times 4! = 3!! / 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + (-8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3!! / 2 \times 10$$

• 3601

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 + 6! \times 5 = 4 \times 3!! + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• 3602

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + (8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3!! / 2 \times 10$$

• 3604

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 = 4 + 3!! / 2 \times 10$$

• 3605

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3) \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• 3608

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! - 6! = 5 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) - 2 \times 1$$

• 3610

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) / 2 \times 10$$

• **3620**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 = (4 + 3!) \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• **3624**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7 + 6!/5) = 4! + 3!/2 \times 10$$

• **3635**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 = (6! + 7) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7 + 6!) = 5 \times (4 + 3!! + 2 + 1)$$

• **3640**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 = (4 + 3!/2) \times 10$$

• **3648**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 76 = (5! - 4!) \times \sqrt{(3!! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)}$$

• **3698**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 = 43^2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **3720**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 = 4 \times (3!! + 210)$$

• **3726**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + (3!! + 4!) \times 5 = 6 \times (7!/8 - 9)$$

• **3840**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 \times 8 + 7!/6) \times 5 = (4! + 3!/2) \times 10$$

• **3744**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3!! + 4! - 5!) = 6 \times (7!/8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• **3780**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times ((2 + 3)^4 + 5) \times 6 = 7!/8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 = 6! \times 7/8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **3780**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!/8 \times 7 \times 6 = 5!/4 \times 3! \times 21$$

• 3886

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + (8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 = 4^{3!} - 210$$

• 3888

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times 3!^4 = (5! + 6 \times 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 3969

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 2^{3!})^{\sqrt{4}} = (56 + 7)^{8 - (\sqrt{9})!}$$

• 3976

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7)^6 - 5! = 4^{3!} - ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• 4032

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 \times \sqrt{6!/5} = (4 + 3! - 2)!/10$$

• 4032:

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \right) \times 65 + \sqrt{4} = (3! + 2)!/10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6 \times (5 + \sqrt{4}) = (3! + 2)!/10$$

• 4050

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3!! - 45) = (6! + 7!/8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 4068

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 34 \times 5! = 678 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 4074

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + (-8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5! = 4^{3!} - 21 - 0!$$

• 4086

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + (-8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5! = 4^{3 \times 2} - 10$$

• 4089

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (-8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5! = 4^{3!} - (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• 4090

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times 7 + 6! \right) \times 5 = 4^{3!} - (2 + 1)!$$

• 4093

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8^{-7+6+5} = 4^{3!} - 2 - 1$$

• 4095

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} = 5! \times 6 + (7+8)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (-2 + 3!) \times 4^5 = 6! + (7+8)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 7 \times 65 = 4^{3 \times 2} - 1$$

• 4096

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} = 56/7 \times 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 4096:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7)^{6!/5!} = 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7)^{6!/5!} = 4^{3!} + 21 \times 0$$

• 4099

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8^{-7+6+5} = 4^{3!} + 2 + 1$$

• 4100

$$\blacktriangleright (-(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7!)/6 \times 5 = 4^{3!} + 2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 4101

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7)^6 + 5 = 4^{3!} + (2+1)! - 0!$$

• 4102

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7!/6 \times 5 = 4^{3!} + (2+1)!$$

• 4104

• 4104:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (-8 \times 7 + 6!) + 5! = 4^{3!} - 2 + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5 = 4^{3!} - 2 + 10$$

• **4116**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 \times 6!/5! &= 4^{3!} + 2 \times 10 \\ \blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 \times 6 &= (5 + \sqrt{4})^3 \times (2 + 10) \end{aligned}$$

• **4120**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \right)!! + 8 \right) / 7 + 6! \right) \times 5 = 4 \times (3! + 2^{10})$$

• **4175**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) \times (7!/6 - 5) = (-4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• **4176**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 65) = (-4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **4200**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \right) \times 7!/6 = 5! \times (4 + 32 - 1)$$

• **4216**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \right)^6 + 5! = 4^{3!} + ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• **4222**

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7! = 6! + 5! + 4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!$$

• **4225**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2^{3!})^{\sqrt{4}} = (5 \times (6 + 7))^{8 - (\sqrt{9})!}$$

• **4230**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2^{3!})^{\sqrt{4}} + 5 &= (6! - 7 - 8) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\ \blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! - 8 - 7 \right) \times 6 &= -5! + 4! + 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **4248**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! = 6! + (5! - \sqrt{4}) \times 3!^2 \times 1$$

• **4272**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! = 6! + 5! \times \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! / 10$$

• **4278**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! - 7 \right) \times 6 = (-5 - \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! \right.$$

• 4296

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1+2)! \times (3!! - 4) &= (-5 \times 6! + 7! - 8) \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! - 6! \times 5) &= (-4 + 3!!) \times (2+1)! \end{aligned}$$

• 4308

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1+2)! \times (3!! - \sqrt{4}) &= 5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ \blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 &= (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2+1)! \end{aligned}$$

• 4312

• 4312:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + (3!! - \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 6! &= 7! - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!! \\ \blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 - 5 + 6!) &= 7! - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!! \end{aligned}$$

• 4312:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + (7!/6!)! &= (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3!! + 2 - 10 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + (7!/6!)! &= (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3!! + 2 - 10 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 \times 6! &= (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3!! + 2 - 10 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 \times 6! &= (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3!! + 2 - 10 \\ &= 5 + (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2+1)! - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 4312:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7! &= (6! - 5 + 4) \times 3! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7! &= 6! \times (\sqrt{5+4})! - 3! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7! &= 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3!! - 2) - 1 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 4314

- ▶ $(1+2)! \times (3!! + 4 - 5) = 6 \times (7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!)$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times ((2+1)!! - 0!)$
- ▶ $98 \times (-76 + 5!) + \sqrt{4} = 3! \times ((2+1)!! - 0!)$

• 4314:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (-8 + 7 + 6!) = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! - (2+1)!!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (-8 + 7 + 6!) = 5 \times (4! \times 3!^2 - 1) - 0!$

• 4318

- ▶ $-1 \times 2 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4+5})!! = 6 + 7! - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!!$

• 4318:

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3!! - 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7! + 6 = 5! \times (4 + 32) - 1 - 0!$

• 4319

• 4319:

- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7! - 6! - 5 + 4 = 3! \times (2+1)!! - 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! + 4 = 3! \times (2+1)!! - 0!$

• 4320

- ▶ $12 \times 3 \times 4! \times 5 = 6 \times (7 + 8 - 9)!$

• 4320:

- ▶ $(1+2)!! \times 3! = 4 \times 5 \times (-6 + 78) \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $(1+2)!! \times 3! = \sqrt{4} - 5! \times 6 + 7! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$

• 4320:

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!! / \sqrt{4} = 5! \times 6 \times (7 + 8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3 \times \sqrt{4} = 5! \times 6 \times (7 + 8 - 9) \\ = 5 - 6! + 7! - 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• 4320:

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)!! + 7! = 6! + 5! + (-4! + 3!!) / 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)!! + 7! = (6! - 5 \times 4! \times 3) \times (2 + 10)$$

• 4320:

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! = 5! \times (4 + 32 \times 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! = 5 \times 432 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 4320:

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! = \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! = \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 = \left(\sqrt{4} \times 3 \right)! \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! = \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 = 432 \times 10$$

• 4320:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times \left(-7 + 65 + \sqrt{4} \right) = 3!! \times (2 + 1)! = 3! \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! + \sqrt{4} = 3!! \times (2 + 1)! = 3! \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 + 4 = 3!! \times (2 + 1)! = 3! \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• **4321**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5 = 4321$$

• **4321:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! - 6! - 5 + 4 = 3! \times (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (7! - 6! + 5 - 4) = 3! \times (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• **4322**

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right) + 7! - 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3! \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• **4323**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• **4324**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3! + 4 = 5 - 6! + 7! + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 = 4 + 3!! \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **4326**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3!! - 4 + 5) = (6! - 7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7\right) \times 6 = 5 + 4321$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **4326:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! - 6!/5! + 4 = 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (-8!/7! + 6! + 5) + 4! = 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **4328**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 \times 6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• **4328:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + (3!! + \sqrt{4}) \times 5 + 6! &= 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!! \\ \blacktriangleright 12 + 3!! - 4 + 5 \times 6! &= 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!! \end{aligned}$$

• **4328:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! &= 6! + 5 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! &= 6 \times (\sqrt{5+4})!! + 3^2 - 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! &= 6!/5! + 4321 + 0! \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! &= 6! + 5! + \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + 2^{10}) \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! &= (6-5) \times \sqrt{4} + 3! \times ((2+1)!! + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **4330**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5 = 4 + 3! \times ((2+1)!! + 0!)$$

• **4331**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! - 6! = 5 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) + (2+1)!! + 0!$$

• **4332**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! \times (3!! + \sqrt{4}) = 5! + 6 \times 78 \times 9$$

• **4333**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2+1)! + 0!$$

• **4338**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8!/7! + 6! - 5) = 4! + 3! \times ((2+1)!! - 0!)$$

• **4350**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 876 \times 5 = 4! + 3! \times ((2+1)!! + 0!)$$

• **4356**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 - 7 + 6! + 5) = (4^3 + 2)^{1+0!}$$

• **4362**

• 4362:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + 7 \right) \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)!! + 7 \right) \times 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3! + (2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• 4368

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! \right) \times 6 = (\sqrt{5+4})! \times (3!! - 2 + 10)$$

• 4374

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 876 \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3^{(2+1)!+0!}$$

• 4410

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7 + 6 \times 5!) = (4! - 3) \times 210$$

• 4410:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7 + 6!) = \left((5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \right)^2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 \right) \times 6 = \left((5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \right)^2 \times 10 \\ = 5! - 4! + 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• 4464

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3!! + 4!) = (-5 + 67) \times 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! = (4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

• 4500

$$\blacktriangleright ((1 + 2)!! + 3!!/4) \times 5 = 6 \times 7!/8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 4528

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times \sqrt{4^5} + 6! = 7! - 8^{\sqrt{9}}$$

• 4800

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6 \right) \times 5! = 4 \times (3 + 2)! \times 10$$

• **4824**

$$\blacktriangleright -(1+2)!^3 + (\sqrt{4}+5)! = 67 \times 8 \times 9$$

• **4830**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8! / (7 \times 6) \right) \times 5 = (4+3)! - 210$$

• **4860**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3^4 \times 5 = (-6! + 7!) / 8 \times 9$$

• **4896**

$$\blacktriangleright (9-8) \times (7! - 6! / 5) = 4! \times (-3! + 210)$$

• **4920**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1+2) \times ((3+4)! - 5!) = 6! \times 7 - (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1^2 + 34) \times 5! + 6! = 7! - (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5! = (4+3)! - ((2+1)! - 0!)$$

• **4920:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9}+8)! + 7! = 6! - 5! + (4+3)! - (2+1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9}+8)! + 7! = 6^5 - 4! \times ((3+2)! - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9}+8)! + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9}+8)! + 7! = 6! \times 5 + 4! + 3!^{2+1+0!}$$

• **4942**

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7! = 6! + 5! + 4^{3!} + (2+1)!$$

• **4950**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 \times 6! = 5! \times 43 - 210$$

• **4950:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7! = 6! \times 5 / 4! \times (32 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7! = 6 - 5! + 4! + (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7! = 6 \times 5^{\sqrt{4}} \times (32 + 1)$$

• **4956**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7! + 6 = (5! - \sqrt{4}) \times (32 + 10)$$

• **4959**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3^{2+1+0!}$$

• **4959:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7! = 6 - (5 + 4!) \times 3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7! = 6!/5 + 4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• **4965**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7! + 6 = -5^{\sqrt{4}} \times 3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **4968**

$$\blacktriangleright -12 \times 3! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6! \times 7 - 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -12 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} - 5!) + 6! = 7! - 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! \times (2 + 10)$$

• **4968:**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! = (-6 + 5! + 4!) \times 3! \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! = (6 - 5) \times 4! \times (-3 + 210)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! = (65 + 4) \times 3!^2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! = 6! + 5! + 4^{3!} + \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! = 654 + 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• **4974**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3 \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **4974:**

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})!! - 8) \times 7 = (6! - 5) \times (4 + 3) - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})!! - 8) \times 7 = 6! + 5! \times (4! + 3) + 2^{10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})!! - 8) \times 7 = 6 + (5! \times \sqrt{4} - 3) \times 21 + 0!$$

• **4986**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! = 6 - 54 + (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

• **4992**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4!) + 5 \times 6! = 7! - 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 \times 6! = 5! + (-4! + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **4992:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! = 6! \times 5 + (-4! + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! = (-6 + 54 \times 3) \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **4998**

$$\blacktriangleright ((1 + 2)!! - 3!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) = 6 + 7! - 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **4998:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3!! - (2 + 1)!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 32 - 10$$

• **5010**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7! - 6 \times 5 = -4! - 3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **5016**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 23 + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6! \times 7 - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **5016:**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3!! - 4!) + 5! + 6! = 7! - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3!) \times (-4 + 5! + 6!) = 7! - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 5016:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3 - 210$$

• 5016:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6! + 5! + (-4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6 - 5!/4 + (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6 \times (5! - 4 + (3 \times 2)! \times 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6! \times 5 + \sqrt{4} \times (3!! - 2 - 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6 \times (-5 + 43) \times (21 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6! + (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3!! - 2 - 1 - 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 32 + 1 + 0!$$

• 5019

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}\right) + 7! + \sqrt{6! \times 5} = (4 + 3)! - 21$$

• 5020

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 \times 4 = (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

• 5022

$$\blacktriangleright -12 - 3! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 + 7! - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 5022:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! \times (2 + 1)$$

• 5023

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3!! - \sqrt{4}) - 5 + 6!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 23 + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6 = 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! = 5 + (4 + 3)! - 21 - 0!$$

• 5023:

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! \times (3!! - \sqrt{4}) - 5 + 6! = 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 23 + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6 = 7! - 8 - 9$$

• 5023:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7! = 6! + (-5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2+1)! + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - (3! - 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3 - 21 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7! = 6 + 5 + (-4 + 3!!) \times ((2+1)! + 0!)$$

• 5026

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (-2 + 3!!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) = 6! \times 7 - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + (3!! - (\sqrt{4} - 5!)) \times 6 = 7! - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 5026:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3!! - 2 \times 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! - 21 + 0!$$

• 5026:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! = (6 + 5 - 4)! - 3! + 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! = 6 \times 5! + 4^3! + 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! = 6 + 5! + (-4! \times 3 + 2)^{1+0!}$$

• 5028

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + (3+4)! = 5 + 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 = (4+3)! - 2 - 10$$

• 5029

• 5029:

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 + 3! \times (-\sqrt{4} + 5! + 6!) = 7! - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (-2 + 3!!) \times (\sqrt{4+5})! + 6! = 7! - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• 5029:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3 + 2 - 10$$

• 5029:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! = 6! + (\sqrt{5+4})! \times (3!! - 2) + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! = 6 - 5 + (4+3)! - 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! = 6! - 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times ((2+1)!! - 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! = (6!/5!)! + (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2+1)! + 0!$$

• 5031

• 5031:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 - 2 - 10$$

• **5031:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = \sqrt{6!/5} + (4+3)! - 21 \\ &\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! - 21 \\ &\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3^{(2+1)!} \\ &\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6! + 5 + 4^{3!} + 210 \\ &\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6 + 5 + (4+3)! - 2 \times 10 \\ &\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6 + 5 + (4+3)! - 21 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• **5033**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 \times 8 + 7!) + 65 = (4+3) \times ((2+1)!! - 0!)$$

• **5034**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 = (4+3)! - (2+1)!$$

• **5034:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -(1+2)! + (3+4)! = 5! - 6 + 7! - (8 - \sqrt{9})! \\ &\blacktriangleright -(1+2)! + (3+4)! = 5 + 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \end{aligned}$$

• **5034:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7! = 6! \times (5 + \sqrt{4}) - 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\ &\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7! = 6! \times 5 + \sqrt{4} \times (3!! - 2 - 1) \\ &\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! \times 2 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **5035**

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 - 3! + (-4 + 5 + 6)! = 7! - 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

• **5035:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! = (6 + 5 - 4)! - 3 \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! = 6! + 5 - 4 + 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! = 6! - 5 + 432 \times 10$$

• **5037**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! = 5 + 6 + 7! - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + (8 - 7 + 6)! = 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 = (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1$$

• **5037:**

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7! = 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3) - 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7! = 6! - 5 + 4321 + 0!$$

• **5038**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times \sqrt{4} + 5 \times 6! = 7! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! = 5 - 6 + 7! + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 = (4 + 3)! - 2 \times 1$$

• **5038:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! = (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! = 6 \times 5! + 4 + 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! = 6 \times 5 + (4 + 3)! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! = \sqrt{6!75} + (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **5039**

▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 + 4!$

• **5039:**

▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5! + 4 = (3 \times 2 + 1)! - 0!$

▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5! + 4 = (3! + 2 - 1)! - 0!$

• **5039:**

▶ $(9 - 8) \times 7! - 6 + 5 = (4 + 3)! - 2 + 1$

$1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! = 5 + 6 - 7! \times (8 - 9)$

• **5039:**

▶ $-1^2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! \times 6 = 7! + 8 - 9$

▶ $-1 + 2 \times (3 \times \sqrt{4})! + 5 \times 6! = 7! + 8 - 9$

▶ $-12 + (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 = 7! + 8 - 9$

▶ $1 - 2^3 + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6 = 7! + 8 - 9$

• **5039:**

▶ $-9 + 8 + 7! = 6! + 5! \times (4 + 32) - 1$

▶ $-9 + 8 + 7! = 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3!! - 2 + 1$

▶ $-9 + 8 + 7! = 6 \times 5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!! - 0!$

▶ $-9 + 8 + 7! = 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 10$

• **5040**

▶ $1^{23} \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = (6 + (-7 + 8)^9)!$

▶ $\sqrt{12/3 + 45} \times 6! = (7 \times (-8 + 9))!$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 76) \times 5 \times 4$

▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) + 4! = (3 \times 2 + 1)!$

• 5040:

- ▶ $(1 + \sqrt{2+34})! = 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $(1 + \sqrt{2+34})! = 56 + 7 \times (-8 + (\sqrt{9})!!)$

• 5040:

- ▶ $((9-8)^7 + 6)! = 5! \times (-4 + 3!) \times 21$
- ▶ $((9-8)^7 + 6)! = (5-4+3!) \times 210$

• 5040:

- ▶ $(1 + 2 \times 3)! = 4 + 5 + (6 - 7 + 8)! - 9$
- ▶ $(1 + 2 \times 3)! = 4 - 5 + 6 + 7! - 8 + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $(1 + 2 \times 3)! = 4! + (-5 + 6) \times (7! - 8 \times \sqrt{9})$
- ▶ $(1 + 2 \times 3)! = 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 78) \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $(1 + 2 \times 3)! = 4 \times 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$

• 5040:

- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7! = (6-5) \times (\sqrt{4+32} + 1)!$
- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7! = (6-5) \times 4 \times 3! \times 210$
- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7! = (6 + 54/3) \times 210$
- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7! = 6 \times 5 \times \sqrt{4^3} \times 21$

• 5040:

- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! - 65 + 4^3 = ((2+1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! - 6 - 5 + 4 + 3! = ((2+1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $9 + 8 + 7! - \sqrt{6! \times 5} + 43 = ((2+1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7! - 6 + (5-4) \times 3! = ((2+1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (7+6) + 5! + 4^3! = ((2+1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})!! - 8) \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4+3!) = ((2+1)! + 0)!$

• 5041

- ▶ $1^{23} + (\sqrt{4+5})! = 6! \times 7 - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! + \sqrt{6!/5} = (4+3)! + 2 - 1$

• 5041:

- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! = 5 - 4 + (3 \times 2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7 \times 6! = 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 - 0!$

• 5041:

- ▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7 + 65)^{\sqrt{4}} = (3! + 2 - 1)! + 0!$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! - 6!/5! + 4! = (3! + 2 - 1)! + 0!$
 $= (3 \times 2 + 1)! + 0!$

• 5041:

- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! \times 3! - 4 + 5 + 6! = 7! - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $1^2 + (3 + 4) \times 5! \times 6 = 7! - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $1 + 2 \times (3 \times \sqrt{4})! + 5 \times 6! = 7! - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $1 - 2 \times 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6 = 7! - 8 + 9$

• 5041:

- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! = 6 \times 5! + 4321$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! = 6! + 5! \times (4 + 32) + 1$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! = 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)! \times (2 - 1)$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! = (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3)! + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! = 6! \times 5 + 4 \times 3!! / 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! = 6! + 5! \times 4! + 3!! \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! = 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3!! + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3 \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! = 6! \times 5 + \sqrt{4} \times (3 \times 2)! + 1$

• 5042

- ▶ $(1 + 2 \times 3)! + \sqrt{4} = 5 + (6 - 7 + 8)! - \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $-1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 = 6! \times 7 + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$

• 5042:

- ▶ $(1+2)!! \times 3! + \sqrt{4} + 5! \times 6 = 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(1+(2 \times 3)!) \times \sqrt{4} + 5 \times 6! = 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $1 \times 2 + (3+4)! \times (-5+6) = 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $1 - 2 - 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6 = 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $1 \times 2 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4+5})!! + 6! = 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$

• 5042:

- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 = (4+3)! + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + (8-7+6)! + 5 = (4+3)! + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + 7! + 6 + 5 = (4+3)! + 2 \times 1$

• 5042:

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! = 6 - 5 + (4+3)! + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! = 6! \times 5 + \sqrt{4} \times ((3 \times 2)! + 1)$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! = 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3!! + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! = 6 \times 5! + \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times (2+1)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! = 6 \times 5! + 4321 + 0!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! = 6! + 5! \times (4+32) + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3!! - 2) + 10$

• 5043

- ▶ $1 + 2 + (3+4)! = 5 + 6! \times 7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $-1 \times 2 + (3+4)! + 5 = (6-7+8)! + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $(9-8) \times 7! + 6 - 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3 + ((2+1)! + 0)!$

• 5043:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + (8 - 7 + 6)! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3!! + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3!! + 2 + 1$$

$$= 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 \times 1$$

• 5043:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 = (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 = 4 + (3 \times 2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• 5043:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6! + 5 - \sqrt{4} + 3! \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3!! - 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6 \times 5 - 4! - 3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6 \times 5! \times (4 + 3) + 2 \times 1 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 - (2 + 1)!! \times 0!$$

• 5044

• 5044:

$$\blacktriangleright -1^2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 = 6 + 7! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 = 6 + 7! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 5044:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! + 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{(4+3)^2})! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! + 6 = 5 + (4+3)! - 2 + 1$$

• 5044:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! + 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{(4+3)^2})! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! + 6 = 5 + (4+3)! - 2 + 1$$

• 5044:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 = 4 + (3 \times 2 + 1)! = (4+3)! + 2 + 1 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5 = 4 + (3 \times 2 + 1)! = (4+3)! + 2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 5045

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times ((3+4)! + 5) = 6 + 7! + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 3!! + 4 + 5 \times 6! = 7! + 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9-8) \times 7 \times 6! + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3 + ((2+1)! + 0)!$$

• 5045

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 = 5 + (4+3) \times (2+1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{(4+3)^2})! \times 1$$

• 5045:

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = 6 + 5 + (4+3)! - (2+1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = 6! + 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times (2+1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = (6!/5!)! + 4 + 3! \times (2+1)!! + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = 6! + 5 + 432 \times 10$$

• 5046

▶ $1^2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 = 6 - 7! \times (8 - 9)$

▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right)! + 7! = 6! + 5 + 4321$

▶ $-\left(-\sqrt{9} + 8\right)! + 7! + 6 + 5! = (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!$

• 5046

▶ $(1 + 2)! + (3 + 4)! = 5 \times 6 + 7! - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

▶ $(1 + 2)! + (3 + 4)! = 5! + 6 + 7! - (8 - \sqrt{9})!$

• 5046

▶ $9 - 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 + 4 = 3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$

▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6! / 5! + 4! = 3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$

• 5046:

▶ $(9 - 8) \times 7! + 6 = 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 - 1$

▶ $(9 - 8) \times 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! - 2 + 1 + 0!$

▶ $(9 - 8) \times 7! + 6 = 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2 + 1)! - 0!$

• 5047

▶ $9 \times 8 + 7! - 65 = (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! + 0!$

• 5047

▶ $9 - 8 + 7! + 6 = 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 \times 1$

▶ $9 - 8 + 7! + 6 = 5 \times \sqrt{4} - 3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$

• 5048

▶ $1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5 = 6 + 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$

▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! + 6! / 5! = (4 + 3)! - 2 + 10$

• 5048

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7!) / 6 = 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\ &\triangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7!) / 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 \times 2 + 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 5049

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright (1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4 + 5 = (6 - 7 + 8)! + 9 \\ &\triangleright 9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! = 5 + 4 + (3 \times 2 + 1)! \end{aligned}$$

• 5049:

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = (6 + 5^4) \times (3! + 2) + 1 \\ &\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6! + (5 + 4) + 3! \times (2 + 1)!! \\ &\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 \times 1 \\ &\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + 7! = 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 5050

$$\triangleright -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3 + 2)! + 10$$

• 5051

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (\sqrt{4 + 5})! + 6! = 7! + 8 + \sqrt{9} \\ &\triangleright -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4! \times 5) \times 6 = 7! + 8 + \sqrt{9} \\ &\triangleright (1 + 2)! + (3 + 4)! + 5 = 6 + 7! + 8 - \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 5051:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = (6!/5!)! + (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)! - 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = 6! \times 5 + \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + (2 + 1)!) - 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = 6! + (\sqrt{5+4})! \times (3!! + 2) - 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3 - 2 + 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! = 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)! \times (2 - 1)$

• 5052

- ▶ $12 + (3 + 4)! = 5 + 6 + 7! - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 = (4 + 3)! + 2 + 10$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right)! + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! \times 2 \times 1$

• 5054

- ▶ $1 \times (2 + 3!!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) = 6! \times 7 + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $1 \times 2^3 + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6 = 7! + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3!! + 2 \times 1)$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! + \sqrt{6!/5} = (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$

• 5054:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! = (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3) - 21$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! = 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! = 6! + (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3!! + 2) + 1 + 0!$

• 5055

• 5055:

- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right) + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! + 21$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right) + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 + 2 + 10$

• **5057**

▶ $(1+2)! \times (3!! + \sqrt{4}) + 5 + 6! = 7! + 8 + 9$

▶ $9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3 + 21 - 0!$

• **5057:**

▶ $12 + (3+4)! + 5 = 6 + 7! + 8 + \sqrt{9}$

▶ $12 + (3+4)! + 5 = 6! \times 7 + 8 + 9$

• **5057:**

▶ $9 + 8 + 7! = 6! + 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2+1)!$

▶ $9 + 8 + 7! = 6 + 5 + (4+3)! + (2+1)!$

▶ $9 + 8 + 7! = 6! + (5 - \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2+1)! - 0!$

• **5058**

▶ $9 + 8 + 7! + 6 - 5 = 4! - 3! + ((2+1)! + 0)!$

• **5060**

▶ $(1+2 \times 3)! + 4 \times 5 = 6 + 7! + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! + 6 = 5 \times 4 + (3 \times 2 + 1)!$

▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + 7! + 6 + 5 = (4+3)! + 2 \times 10$

• **5061**

▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + 7! + \sqrt{6!/5} = (4+3)! + 21$

• **5062**

▶ $9 + 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5$

▶ $-98 + 7 \times 6! + 5! = (4+3)! + 21 + 0!$

• **5063**

▶ $1 \times 23 + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 + 7! + 8 + 9$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! - 6 + 5 = 4! + (3! + 2 - 1)! - 0!$

• 5063:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3! - 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 + 21 - 0!$$

• 5064

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3)! + 4! = (5 + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3!! + 4 + 5!) = 6! \times 7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5! = 4! + (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

• 5064:

$$\blacktriangleright (1^2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (-5 + 6) = 7! + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3!! + 4!) - 5! + 6! = 7! + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3!! + 4) + 5! \times 6 = 7! + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)! + (3 + 4)! + 5 \times 6 = 7! + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times 3! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6 = 7! + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3!!) \times \sqrt{4} + 5 \times 6! = 7! + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 5064:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6! \times 5 + 4! + 3!! \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6! - 5! + (4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6 \times 5! + (4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6! + 543 \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 5065

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 = 4! + (3! + 2 - 1)! + 0!$$

• 5066

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3!! + 2 \times 10$$

• 5067

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}\right) + 7! + 6 \times 5 = 4! + 3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$$

• **5068**

- ▶ $9 + 8 + 7! + 6 + 5$
- ▶ $-98 + 7! + 6 + 5! = (4 + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! \times (2 + 1)$

• **5070**

- ▶ $(-9 + 87) \times 65 = 4! + 3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$

• **5070:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6 = 5!/4 + (3 \times 2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 32 - 1 - 0!$

• **5072**

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5 = (4 + 3!) + \sqrt{2^{10}}$

• **5088**

- ▶ $((1 + 2)!! + 3!) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) + 6 = 7! + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• **5088:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7 \times 6! = 5 + 43 + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7!/6) = 5 + 43 + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$
 $= (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! \times (-2 + 10)$

• **5064:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! = 6! \times 5 + (4! + 3!!) \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3! + (2 + 1)!!)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 32 + 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! = \sqrt{6! \times 5} + (4 + 3)! - 2 - 10$

• **5094**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! + 6 = 54 + (3 \times 2 + 1)!$

• **5096**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (-1 + 23 \times 4) \times 56 = 7 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!!) \\ &\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) \times 7! / 6! = 5! - \sqrt{4^{3!}} + ((2 + 1)! + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **5096:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) \times 7 = (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3) + 21 \\ &\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) \times 7 = (6 + 5 - 4) \times (3!! - 2 + 10) \\ &\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) \times 7 = 6! + 5^4 \times (3 \times 2 + 1) + 0! \\ &\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) \times 7 = 6 + 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} \times 3 + 2^{10} \right) \end{aligned}$$

• **5102**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) \times 7 + 6 = \left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 3^{(2+1)!} - 0!$$

• **5104**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! + 65 = 4^3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0!) \\ &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (-7 + 6!) + 5! = \sqrt{4^{3!}} + ((2 + 1)! + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **5112**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6! \times 7 + 8 \times 9 \\ &\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! \times (2 + 10) \end{aligned}$$

• **5112:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) + 6! = 7! + 8 \times 9 \\ &\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) + 6! = 7! + 8 \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

• **5112:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (76 - 5) = 4! \times (3 + 210) \\ &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times (8 - 7! / 6) + 5! = 4! \times (3 + 210) \end{aligned}$$

• **5112:**

- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7! = (6!/5 - \sqrt{4}) \times 3! \times (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7! = (6 + 5 - 4)! + 3! \times (2 + 10)$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7! = 6! + (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times 3!^2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7! = 6! + (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \times (2 + 10)$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 \times (21 + 0!)$

• **5118**

▶ $9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 = 5 \times 4^{3+2} - 1 - 0!$

• **5120**

▶ $\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + 7!} - 6 + 5 = \sqrt{4^{3^2}} \times 10$

• **5121**

• **5121:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7 \times 6! = 5 \times 4^{3+2} + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3^{2+1+0!}$

• **5121:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7! = 6 + 5 \times (4^{3+2} - 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7! = 6 - 5 + 4^{3!} + 2^{10}$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7! = 6 - 5 + \sqrt{4^{3^2}} \times 10$

• **5127**

▶ $(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}) + 7! + 6 = (5 + 4!) \times 3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$

• **5130**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7 \times 6! = 5 \times (4^{3+2} + 1 + 0!)$$

• **5130:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7! = (-6 + 5!) \times (43 + 2) \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7! = 6 + (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times (32 + 10)$$

• **5136**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7! + 6 = 5! - 4! + (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

• **5138**

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7 \times 6! = 5! + (4 + 3)! - 21 - 0!$$

• **5138:**

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7! = 6 + 5! + (-4 + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 + 7! = 6! - 5^4 + 3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **5160**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times (-3 + 4!)) \times 5! = 6! \times 7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5! = 43 \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7 \times 6! = 5! \times 43 \times (2 - 1)$$

• **5160:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)! + (3 + 4)! + 5! + 6 = 7! + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 + 34) \times 5! + 6! = 7! + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!!/\sqrt{4} + 5! + 6! = 7! + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• **5160:**

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7! = 6! \times (5+\sqrt{4}) + (3+2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7! = 6!+5! \times (4+32+1)$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7! = 6+5! \times 43 - (2+1)!$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7! = (6!+54)/3 \times 2 \times 10$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7! = 6!+5!+432 \times 10$

• **5166**

- ▶ $(1+2)!+(3+4)!+5! = 6+7!+(8-\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8)!+7!+6 = 5! \times 43 + (2+1)!$

• **5174**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!+8+7 \times 6!+5! = (4! \times 3)^2 - 10$

• **5182**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!-8+7!+6!/5 = (4! \times 3)^2 - 1 - 0!$

• **5183**

- ▶ $9+8+7!+6+5! = (4! \times 3)^2 - 1$

• **5184**

- ▶ $(12 \times 3!)^{\sqrt{4}} = (5+67) \times 8 \times 9$

• **5184:**

- ▶ $9 \times 8 \times (7+65) = 4! \times 3!^{2+1}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! = 4! \times 3!^{2+1}$
 $= (4! \times 3)^2 \times 1$

• **5185**

- ▶ $9-8+7!+6!/5 = (4! \times 3)^2 + 1$

• **5186**

- ▶ $\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}+7!+65} = (4! \times 3)^2 + 1 + 0!$

• **5194**

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (-7 + \sqrt{6! \times 5}) = (4! \times 3)^2 + 10$$

• **5208**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6!/5 = (4! + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **5250**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7 \times 6! + 5! = (4 + 3)! + 210$$

• **5256**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 876 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3!^{2+1}$$

• **5472**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 76 = (5! + 4!) \times (3! + \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

• **5640**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 23 + 4!) \times 5! = 6! + 7! - (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7! + 6! = 5! \times (4 \times 3! \times 2 - 1)$$

• **5662**

$$\blacktriangleright -98 + 7! + 6! = 5^4 - 3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!)$$

• **5670**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 2^{3!}) \times (4! - 5! + 6) = 7!/8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 7! + 6! = (5 + 4) \times 3 \times 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5!) = (4! + 3) \times 210$$

• **5688**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (-3! + 4 \times 5!) = 6! + 7! - 8 \times 9$$

• **5688:**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! = 5! + (-4! + 3!!) \times (-2 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! = (5! \times 4 - 3!) \times (2 + 10)$$

• **5704**

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})!! - 8) \times 7 + 6! = (5! + 4) \times (3!^2 + 10)$$

• **5710**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (-7 + 6!) = (-5 + (4 \times 3!)^2) \times 10$$

• **5712**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! + 6! = \left((5 - \sqrt{4})!! - 3! \right) \times (-2 + 10)$$

• **5720**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5) = 4 \times (3!! \times 2 - 10)$$

• **5724**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (-3 + 4 \times 5!) = (6 + 7!/8) \times 9$$

• **5736**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6! = (-5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (-2 + 10)$$

• **5747**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) = -6 - 7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• **5749**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 - 5) = 6! + 7! - 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• **5749:**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! + 6! = 5 + 4 \times (3!! - 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! + 6! = (5! \times 4! - 3!) \times 2 + 1$$

• **5751**

• **5751:**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8!/7 = (6! \times 5 - 4 - 3!!) \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8!/7 = 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 - 2 - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8!/7 = 6 - 5 + 4 \times 3!! \times 2 - 10$$

• **5752**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^3 \times (4 - 5 + 6!) = 7! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3!! + 2 - 10$$

• 5752:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7! = (6! - 5 + 4) \times (3^2 - 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7! = 6 + (5! \times 4! - 3!) \times 2 - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7! = (6! + 5! \times \sqrt{4}) \times 3! + 2 - 10$

• 5754

• 5754:

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 = 6 + (5! \times 4! - 3!) \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 = 6 \times (5! \times \sqrt{4} + 3!! - 2 \times 1 + 0!)$

• 5755

▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! = 4 \times (3!! \times 2 - 1) - 0!$

• 5755:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! + 6! = 5 + 4 \times 3!! \times 2 - 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! + 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3!! - (2 + 1)! + 0!$

• 5757

• 5757:

- ▶ $-9 + 8!/7 + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3!! - 2 - 1$
- ▶ $-9 + 8!/7 + 6 = 5 + 4 \times (3!! \times 2 - 1 - 0!)$

• 5757:

- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8!/7 = 6! - 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8!/7 = 6 + (-5 + 4 \times 3!!) \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8!/7 = 6! + 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 - 10$

• 5758

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6! + 7! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! + 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3!! - 2 \times 1$$

• 5759

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 \times 3)! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6! + 7! + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 = 5! \times 6 + 7! + 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 - 7 + 6 = 5! \times 4 \times 3! \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! = 4 \times 3!! \times 2 - 1$$

• 5760

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 23) \times \sqrt{4} \times 5! = 6! \times (7 - 8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times (6 + 54) = 3!! \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 5760:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times 4 = 5 + 6! + 7! - 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times 4 = 5! \times 6 \times (7 - 8 + 9)$$

• 5760:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times 6! = 5! \times \sqrt{4} \times (3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times 6! = 5 \times 4!^3 / (2 + 10)$$

• 5760:

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^3 \times (4 - 5 + 6!) + 7 = 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4! \times 5!) + 6 + 7 = 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 5760:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 = (7! + 6!) / 5 + 4!^3 / (2 + 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 = 7! / 6! + (5! \times 4! - 3) \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 = 7! / 6 + 5! \times (43 - 2) \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 = 7 + 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 = 7 + 6 + (5! \times 4! - 3!) \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 = 7 + 6! - 5 + (4 + 3)! - 2 + 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 = 7! / 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3!! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$

• 5760:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8! / 7! = 6 - 5 + 4 \times 3!! \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8! / 7! = 6 \times 5! / 4 \times 32 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8! / 7! = 6! / 5 \times (\sqrt{4} \times 3 - 2) \times 10$

• 5760:

- ▶ $(9 - 8) \times 7! + 6 \times 5! = 4 \times 3!! \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-\left(-\sqrt{9} + 8\right)! + 7! + 6! + 5! = 4 \times 3!! \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! + 6! - 5 = 4 \times 3!! \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 = 4 \times 3!! \times 2 \times 1$
 $= (\sqrt{4} + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!! = (4 \times 3!)^2 \times 10$

• 5761

▶ $1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 = 5! \times 6 + 7! - 8 + 9$

• 5761:

- ▶ $(-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 + 5 = 6! + 7! - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $1 + 2 \times 3! \times 4 \times 5! = 6! + 7! - 8 + 9$

• 5761:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7! + 6! &= 5! \times 4 \times 3! \times 2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7! + 6! &= 5 + 4 \times (3!! \times 2 - 1) \\ \blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5! &= 4 \times 3!! \times 2 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

• 5762

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6! + 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! / 7 - 6 + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 5762:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! + 6! &= (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3!! + 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! + 6! &= 5! \times 4 \times 3! \times 2 + 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 5763

• 5763:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! / 7 &= (6 - 5) \times 4 \times (3!! \times 2 + 1) - 0! \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! / 7 &= 6! + 5 - \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2 - 1)! \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! / 7 &= 6! + 5 - \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2 + 1)! \end{aligned}$$

• 5764

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times 4 = 5 + 6! + 7! + 8 - 9$$

• 5765

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! + 6! &= 5 + 4 \times 3!! \times 2 - 1 \times 0 \\ \blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (7! + 6! + 5) &= 4 \times (3!! \times 2 + 1) + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• 5765:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5 &= 6! + 7! + 8 - \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4! \times 5!) &= 6! + 7! + 8 - \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• 5766

• 5766:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8!/7! + 6 = 5 + 4 \times 3!! \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8!/7! + 6 = (5! \times 4! + 3) \times (2 + 1 - 0!)$$

• 5766:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 = 6! + 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 = 6 \times (5!/4 \times 32 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 = 6 \times 5 + 4! \times (3!!/(2 + 1) - 0!)$$

• 5767

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2^3 \times (-4 + 5 + 6!) = 7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 5767:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + 7 = 6! + 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + 7 = 6! - 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 10$$

• 5767:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + 7!/6! = (5! \times 4! + 3) \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + 7!/6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3!! + (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• 5768

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^3 \times (-4 + 5 + 6!) = 7! + 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! = 6! + 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 \times 6! = (5 - 4 + 3!!) \times (-2 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8!/7 - 6 + 5 = 4!/3 \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• 5769

• 5769:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8!/7 = 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8!/7 = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8!/7 = 6 + 5 - \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 5769:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8!/7 + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3^{(2+1)!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8!/7 + 6 = 5 + 4 \times (3!! \times 2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8!/7 + 6 = 5 + 4 + 3!! \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 5771

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5) = 6! + 7! + 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! + 6! = (5 + 4 \times 3!!) \times 2 + 1$$

• 5772

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 + 6 = (5! \times 4! + 3!) \times 2 \times 1$$

• 5773

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times 5!) = 6 + 7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + 7 + 6 = (5! \times 4! + 3!) \times 2 + 1$$

• 5774

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! + 6! = (5! \times 4! + 3!) \times 2 + 1 + 0!$$

• 5775

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8!/7 + 6 = 5 + 4 \times 3!! \times 2 + 10$$

• 5776

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 = 4 \times (3!! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• 5777

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + (8! - 7!)/6 = 5! + 4 \times (3!! \times 2 - 1) + 0!$$

• 5784

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 + 6 \times 5 = 4! - 3!! \times (2 - 10) \\ &\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6! = (5! + 4) \times 3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• 5800

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) = 4 \times (3!! \times 2 + 10)$$

• 5808

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! + 6! = \left((5 - \sqrt{4})!! + 3! \right) \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 5810

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7 + 6!) = (5 + (4 \times 3!)^2) \times 10$$

• 5816

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) \times 7 + 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (-2 + 10)$$

• 5832

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3!)^{-\sqrt{4}+5} = 6! + 7! + 8 \times 9$$

• 5832:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! = (4! - 3!)^{2+1} \\ &\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (76 + 5) = (4! - 3!)^{2+1} \end{aligned}$$

• 5832:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! = (54/3)^{2+1} \\ &\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! = (5 + 4)^3 \times (-2 + 10) \end{aligned}$$

• 5833

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (-7 + 6!) + 5! = (4! - 3!)^{2+1} + 0!$$

• 5836

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + 76 = 5 + (4! - 3!)^{2+1} - 0!$$

• **5877**

▶ $-\sqrt{9} + (8! - 7!)/6 = 5! + 4 \times (3!! \times 2 - 1) + 0!$

• **5879**

▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7!/6 = 5! + 4 \times 3!! \times 2 - 1$

• **5880**

▶ $1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5! = 6! + 7! + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$

▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7! + 6! = 5! \times (4 + 3)^2 \times 1$

• **5881**

▶ $((\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7!)/6 = 5! + 4 \times 3!! \times 2 + 1$

• **5883**

▶ $\sqrt{9} + (8! - 7!)/6 = 5! + 4 \times (3!! \times 2 + 1) - 0!$

• **5952**

▶ $9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5! = (4! + 3!!) \times (-2 + 10)$

• **6000**

• **6000:**

▶ $((\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7!)/6 = 5! \times ((4 + 3)^2 + 1)$

▶ $((\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7!)/6 = 5! \times (4 + 3 - 2) \times 10$

• **6048**

▶ $(-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (-4! + 5!) = 6 \times 7! / (8 - \sqrt{9})$

• **6144**

• **6144:**

▶ $(9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4! = 3! \times 2^{10}$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + 76 \times 5 + 4 = 3! \times 2^{10}$

• **6146**

▶ $98 + 7! \times 6/5 = \sqrt{4} + 3! \times 2^{10}$

• 6156

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times 76 = \sqrt{5!+4!} + 3! \times 2^{10}$$

• 6168

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9}+8\right)!+7! \times 6/5 = 4!+3! \times 2^{10}$$

• 6300

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8-7+6!-5) = (4!+3!) \times 210$$

• 6408

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8!/7!+6!) = (5+4) \times (3!!+2-10)$$

• 6417

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) \times (7-6!) = (5+4) \times (3!!-(2+1)!-0!)$$

• 6471

$$\blacktriangleright (-1+(2 \times 3)!) \times (4+5) = (6!+7-8) \times 9$$

• 6471:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8+7+6!) = (5+4) \times ((3 \times 2)!-1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8+7+6!) = (5-\sqrt{4}) \times 3 \times ((2+1)!!-0!)$$

• 6472

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!!-8+7!+6! = (5+4) \times 3!!+2-10$$

• 6473

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! \times 8-7+6! = (5+4) \times (3!!+(2+1)!+0!)$$

• 6477

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9}+8!/7+6! = (5+4) \times 3!!-2-1$$

• 6480

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times \sqrt{3^4} = 5! \times (-6+7+8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3+4!) \times 5! = 6! \times (-7+8) \times 9$$

• 6480

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7) \times 6! = 54 \times (3 + 2)! \times 1$$

• 6480:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7 = 6 \times 5! \times (-4 \times 3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7 = 6 + (5 + 4) \times 3!! - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7 = \sqrt{6! \times 5} + \sqrt{4} \times 3210$$

• 6483

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8!/7 + 6! = (5 + 4) \times 3!! + 2 + 1$$

• 6486

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 + 6! = (5 + 4) \times 3!! + (2 + 1)!$$

• 6487

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + 7 + 6! = (5 + 4) \times 3!! + (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• 6488

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! + 6! = (5 + 4) \times (3!! + 2 - 1) - 0!$$

• 6489

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times (4 + 5) = (6! - 7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7 + 6!) = (5 + 4) \times (3!! + 2 - 1)$$

• 6536

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times (7 + 6!) = 5^{\sqrt{4}} + 3^{-2+10}$$

• 6543

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times (7 + 6!) = (5 + 4) \times (3! + (2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• 6560:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} - 7 + 6 = (5 + 4) \times 3^{(2+1)!} - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} - 7 + 6 = (5 + 4)^{3!-2} - 1$$

• **6561**

▶ $9 \times (8!/7! + 6!) + 5 + 4 = 3^{-2+10}$

• **6561:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9^{8!/7!}} = (6 + 5 - \sqrt{4})^{3+2-1}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^{8!/7!}} = (6 - 5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!+2 \times 1}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^{8!/7!}} = 6! - (\sqrt{5+4})!! + 3^{-2+10}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^{8!/7!}} = 6 - 5^4 + (3!! - 2) \times 10$

• **6561:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = (7 - 6) \times (5 + 4) \times 3^{(2+1)!}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = (7 - 6) \times (5 + 4)^{3+2-1}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 7! + ((6 + 5 - 4!) \times 3)^2 \times 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 7! + 6! + 5! \times 4 + 321$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 7 - 6 + (5 + 4)^{3!-2} - 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 7!/6 + (-5! + 4! \times 3!!)/(2 + 1) + 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 7! + 65 + \sqrt{4} \times (3!! - 2 + 10)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = (-7 + 6 + 5)! - 4! + 3^{-2+10}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 7!/6! - 5 - \sqrt{4} + 3^{-2+10}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 7! + (6 + 5 - 4 + 32)^{1+0!}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 7 \times 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4} + 32)^{1+0!}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 76 + (5 + 4) \times 3!! + (2 + 1)! - 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 7 - 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4})^{3!+2 \times 1} - 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = 76 + 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} = \sqrt{-7 + 6 + 5} - \sqrt{4} + 3^{-2+10}$

• **6562**

▶ $\sqrt{9^8} + 7 - 6 = (5 + 4)^{3!-2} + 1$

• **6563**

▶ $\sqrt{9^8} + \sqrt{-7 + 6 + 5} = \sqrt{4} + 3^{-2+10}$

• 6565

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} - 7 + 6 + 5 = 4 + 3^{-2+10}$$

• 6567

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^{8!/7!}} + 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! + 3^{-2+10}$$

• 6568

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} + 7!/6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3^{-2+10}$$

• 6568:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} + 7 = 6! + 5! + (-4 + 3!!) \times (-2 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} + 7 = 6 + (5 + 4) \times 3^{(2+1)!} + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} + 7 = 6 + (5 + 4)^{3!-2} + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} + 7 = 6 + 5 - 4 + 3^{-2+10}$$

• 6585

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} + (-7 + 6 + 5)! = 4! + 3^{-2+10}$$

• 6600

• 6600:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7!/6 = 5! \times (4! + 32 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7!/6 = (-5!/ \sqrt{4} + (3 \times 2)!) \times 10$$

• 6615

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!) = 54 + 3^{-2+10}$$

• 6719

• 6719:

$$\blacktriangleright (-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7!)/6 = 5! \times (4! + 32) - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7!)/6 = 5 \times 4^3 \times 21 - 0!$$

• **6719:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! / 6 + 5 = (4!/3)! / (2+1)! - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! / 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! / (2+1)! - 0!$$

• **6720**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)! / (6! / 5!) = (\sqrt{4^3})! / (2+1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)! / 6 = 5 \times 4^3 \times 21$$

• **6721**

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8!) / (7 - 6 + 5) = (\sqrt{4^3})! / (2+1)! + 0!$$

• **6721:**

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7!) / 6 = 5! \times (4! + 32) + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7!) / 6 = 5 \times 4^3 \times 21 + 0!$$

• **6726**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! / 6 = 5 + (4!/3)! / (2+1)! + 0!$$

• **6840**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 \times 76 = (5!^{\sqrt{4}} - 3!!) / 2 \times 1 = 5! \times (4! + 32 + 1)$$

• **6912**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8! / 7! \times 6! / 5 = 4!^3 / 2 \times 1$$

• **6960**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times (-7 + 65) = (-4! + (3 \times 2)!) \times 10$$

• **7140**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 \times \sqrt{6! \times 5} = (-4 + 3!! - 2) \times 10$$

• **7160**

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})!! - 8! / 7! + 6!) \times 5 = (-4 + (3 \times 2)!) \times 10$$

• **7182**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 7 \times (-6 + 5!) = \sqrt{4} + (3!! - 2) \times 10$$

• **7200**

▶ $(1+2)!! \times (3!+4) = 5! \times 6 \times (-7+8+9)$

▶ $(12+3) \times 4 \times 5! = 6! \times (-7+8+9)$

• **7200:**

▶ $(9+8-7) \times 6! = 5 \times \sqrt{4} \times (3 \times 2)! \times 1$

▶ $(9+8-7) \times 6! = 5 \times 4 + (3!! - 2) \times 10$

• **7200:**

▶ $(9+8-7) \times 6 \times 5! = (4+3!) \times (2+1)!!$

▶ $(9+8-7) \times 6 \times 5! = (\sqrt{4+32})! \times 10$

• **7200:**

▶ $(9+8-7) \times 6 \times 5 \times 4! = (3 \times 2)! \times 10$

▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + (8! - 7!/6)/5 + 4! = (3 \times 2)! \times 10$

• **7220**

▶ $(9+8-7) \times 6! + 5 \times 4 = (3!! + 2) \times 10$

• **7240**

▶ $\left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8!/7! + 6! \right) \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3!! + 2) \times 10$

• **7268**

▶ $\sqrt{9^8} + 7 + 6! = 5! + (4+3) \times 2^{10}$

• **7274**

▶ $\sqrt{9^8} - 7 + 6! = 54 + (3!! + 2) \times 10$

• **7281**

▶ $\sqrt{9^{8!/7!}} + 6! = (\sqrt{5+4})!! + 3^{-2+10}$

• **7288**

▶ $\sqrt{9^8} + 7 + 6! = 5! + (4+3) \times 2^{10}$

• 7290

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 \times (76+5) = (4!+3)^2 \times 10$$

• 7440

$$\triangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7 + 6^5 = (4! + (3 \times 2)!) \times 10$$

• 7440:

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7!/6 = 5! \times (4^3 - 2) \times 1$$

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7!/6 = (5! + 4) \times 3 \times 2 \times 10$$

• 7488

$$\triangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7!/6) = (5! \times \sqrt{4} - 3!) \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• 7559

• 7559:

$$\triangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7!/6 = (5!^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!!)/2 - 1$$

$$\triangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7!/6 = 5 \times 4! \times 3 \times 21 - 0!$$

• 7560

• 7560:

$$\triangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times 7!/6} = 5 \times 4! \times 3 \times 21$$

$$\triangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times 7!/6} = 5 \times 4! \times 3 \times 21 \\ = 5! \times (43 + 2 \times 10)$$

• 7561

• 7561:

$$\triangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7! \right) / 6 = (5!^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!!)/2 + 1$$

$$\triangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7! \right) / 6 = 5 \times 4! \times 3 \times 21 + 0!$$

• **7569**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8! + 7!)/6 = ((5 + 4!) \times 3)^2 \times 1$$

• **7572**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7!)/6 = (5^4 + 3!) \times (2 + 10)$$

• **7680**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 87 + 6^5 = 4! \times 32 \times 10$$

• **7680:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! \right) / 6 = 5! \times (43 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! \right) / 6 = 5! \times 4 \times (3 \times 2 + 10)$$

• **7704**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (-7 - 6 + 5!) = 4! \times 321$$

• **7705**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9 - 8 + 7!} + 6^5 = 4! \times 321 + 0!$$

• **7728**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8!/7! + 6^5 = 4! \times (321 + 0!)$$

• **7776**

$$\blacktriangleright ((1 + 23)/4)^5 = 6^{(7+8)/\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times 3!^4 = (5! + 6 \times 7) \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7 \times 6^5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!^{-8+7+6} = (5 - \sqrt{4})!^{3+2} \times 1$$

• **7776:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8!/7! + 6^5 + \sqrt{4} = 3!^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7!/6) + 5! + 4! = 3!^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4! = 3!^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (76 + 5) \times 4 = 3!^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4 = 3!^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

• **7778**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) - 7 + 6^5 = \sqrt{4} + 3!^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

• **7780**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 + 6^5 = 4 + 3!^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

• **7800**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 + 7 + 6^5 = 4! + 3!^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

• **7920**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8!/7!) \times 6! = 5 \times 4! \times 3 \times (21 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) = 4 \times 3!! + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **7997**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7 + 6!) = (5 \times 4)^3 - 2 - 1$$

• **8040**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 2 \times 34) \times 5! = 67 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

• **8064**

$$\blacktriangleright (98/7 - 6)!/5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3! + 2)!/10$$

• **8100**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3!! - 45) = (6! + 7!/8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **8190**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5!) = 4^{3!} \times 2 - 1 - 0!$$

• **8192**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right)^{7+6!/5!} = 4^{3!} \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right)^{7+6} = (5!/4! + 3) \times 2^{10}$$

• **8202**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + ((8!/7!) + 6!)/5 = 4^{3!} \times 2 + 10$$

• **8280**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8! + 7!)/6 = 5! \times (4! \times 3 - 2 - 1)$$

• 8352

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + (8! + 7 \times 6!)/5 = (-4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 10)$$

• 8400

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 - 7) \times (6! + 5!) = 4! \times (3!!/2 - 10)$$

• 8592

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3!! - 4) = 5 \times 6! + 7! - 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 8592

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 = 4! \times (3!!/2 - 1 - 0!)$$

• 8616

• 8616:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8! - 7!/6)/5 = 4! \times (3!!/2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8! - 7!/6)/5 = (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 10)$$

• 8628

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 \right) \times \sqrt{6!/5} = 4 \times 3 \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• 8630

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 \right) \times (-7! + 6! + 5) = 4! \times 3!!/2 - 10$$

• 8638

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 = 4! \times 3!!/2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 8639

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 = 4! \times 3!!/2 - 1$$

• 8640

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 \times \sqrt{4})! = 5 \times 6! - 7! \times (8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8!/7)/6 = 5! \times 4 \times (-3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 87 - 6) \times 5! = 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 + 6) \times 5! \times 4 = 3!! \times (2 + 10)$$

• **8640:**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!! = (-4 + 5) \times 6! \times (7 + 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!! = 4! \times 5 \times (67 + 8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!! = 4! + 5 \times 6! + 7! - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!! = 4 \times 5 \times (-6 + 78) \times \sqrt{9}!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!! = \sqrt{4} + 5 \times 6! + 7! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **8641**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 = 4! \times 3!!/2 + 1$$

• **8642**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!! + \sqrt{4} = 5 \times 6! + 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **8642**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 = 4! \times 3!!/2 + 1 + 0!$$

• **8650**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right) \times (7! - 6! + 5) = 4! \times 3!!/2 + 10$$

• **8652**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7\right) \times \sqrt{6!/5} = 4 \times 3 \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **8664**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3!! + \sqrt{4}) = 5 \times 6! + 7! + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **8664:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 = (4! \times ((3!!/2) + 1))$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 10)$$

• **8688**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3!! + 4) = 5 \times 6! + 7! + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! + 6! \times 5 = (4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 10)$$

• **8784**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7 \times 6!/5 = 4!^3 - ((2+1)! + 0)!$$

• **8880**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 \right) \times (-7! + 6! - 5!) = 4! \times (3!!/2 + 10)$$

• **8928**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \right) \times 6!/5 = (4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 10)$$

• **9000**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 76) \times 5! = (4! + 3!)^2 \times 10$$

• **9030**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!!/8 + 76 \times 5! = 43 \times 210$$

• **9120**

• **9120:**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 76 = 5! \times 4 \times \sqrt{3!!/2 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 76 = 5! \times 4 \times (-3 + 21 + 0!)$$

• **9216**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7 \times 6! \right) / 5 = (4! - (3+2)!)^{1+0!}$$

• **9240**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7!/6) = 5 \times (43^2 - 1)$$

• **9256**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \right) \times (7+6) = 5! + 4^{3!} + ((2+1)! + 0)!$$

• **9261**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! - 8 \right) \times (7+6) + 5 = (4! - 3)^{2+1}$$

• **9360**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times 5! = 6! \times 78 / (\sqrt{9})!$$

4.5 Five Digits Numbers

- **10068**

- ▶ $1 \times 2 \times (-3! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) = (-6 + 7!) \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$
- ▶ $(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times (7! - 6) = ((5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3!) \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})! - 8) \times (-7! + 6!/5!) = \sqrt{4} \times (-3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$

- **10070**

- ▶ $(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times (7 \times 6! - 5) = (4 + 3)! \times 2 - 10$

- **10074**

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + (8 + 76) \times 5! = \sqrt{4} \times (-3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$

- **10076**

- ▶ $-9 + 8! - 7! \times 6 + 5 = ((4 + 3)! - 2) \times (1 + 0!)$

- **10079**

- ▶ $-1 + (2^3)!/4 = 5 - 6 + 7! \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$

- **10079**

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7! \times 6 + 5 = (4 + 3)! \times 2 - 1$

- **10080**

- ▶ $(1 + 2)!! \times (-3! + 4 \times 5) = 6! \times 7 \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 + 7 - 6 + 5) = (4 + 3)! \times 2 \times 1$

- **10080:**

- ▶ $(1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4 \times 5 - 6) = 7! \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$
- ▶ $1 \times 2 \times (-3 + (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) + 6 = 7! \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$

- **10080:**

- ▶ $98/7 \times 6! = (5 + 43) \times 210$
- ▶ $98/7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3!/(2 + 1)$

• **10080:**

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! = 6! \times (5 - 4 \times 3 + 21)$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! = 6! + (5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3!) \times (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! = 6! + 5! \times 4! \times 3 + (2 + 1)!!$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! = 6^5 + 4!^3 / (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! = 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)! \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! = 6^5 + (4 \times 3! \times 2)^{1+0!}$

• **10081**

- ▶ $1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)! = (-5! + 6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)$
- ▶ $(9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6! - 5!) = (4 + 3)! \times 2 + 1$

• **10082**

- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7! \times 6 + 5 = (4 + 3)! \times 2 + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7! \times 6 + 5 = (4 + 3)! \times 2 + 1 + 0!$

• **10083**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7! \times 6 = 5 + (4 + 3)! \times 2 - 1 - 0!$

• **10086**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7! \times 6 = 5 + (4 + 3)! \times 2 + 1$

• **10090**

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7 \times 6! + 5) = (4 + 3)! \times 2 + 10$

• **10092**

- ▶ $1 \times 2 \times (3! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) = (6 + 7!) \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7! + 6!/5!) = \sqrt{4} \times (3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0!))$

• **10092:**

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7! + 6) = ((5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3!) \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7! + 6) = (5 + (4 + 3)!) \times 2 + 1 + 0!$

• **10368**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7! \times 6!/5 = (4! \times 3)^2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **10440**

• **10440:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 87/6 = (5! - 4) \times 3^2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 87/6 = 5! \times (43 \times 2 + 1)$$

• **10791**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6! = 5 \times (-\sqrt{4} + 3 \times (2 + 1)!!) + 0!$$

• **10800**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (3 \times \sqrt{4})! \times 5 = 6! + 7! \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2 + 3) \times (-\sqrt{4} + 5) \times 6! = (7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 + 7) = 6 \times 5 \times (4 + 32) \times 10$$

• **10800:**

$$\blacktriangleright (- (\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7! + 6! = 6! \times 5/4 \times 3! \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (- (\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7! + 6! = \sqrt{5\sqrt{4}} \times 3!! \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (- (\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 7! + 6! = 5!/4 \times 3!! / (2 + 1 - 0!)$$

• **10809**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + (8 + 7) \times 6! = 5 \times (\sqrt{4} + 3!! \times (2 + 1)) - 0!$$

• **11520**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 23) \times 4 \times 5! = (6! + 7!) \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 87 + 6) \times 5! = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times (-2 + 10)$$

• **11520:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8 + 7) \times 6! = 5! \times 4 \times (3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8 + 7) \times 6! = 5! \times (43 \times 2 + 10)$$

• **11601**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3^{-2+10}$$

• **11601:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} + 7! = (6! + 5) \times (4 + 3! \times 2) + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} + 7! = (6 + 5 - 4)! + 3^{-2+10}$$

• **11760**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times 7! / 6 = (5! - 4^3) \times 210$$

• **12121**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6!) = 5! \times ((4 + 3!)^2 + 1) + 0!$$

• **12240**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times 34 \times 5! = 6! \times (-7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8! / 7!) \times 6 \times 5! = 4! \times (3!! - 210)$$

• **12240:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7) \times 6! = (5 + 4 \times 3) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times 8 - 7) \times 6! = 5!^{\sqrt{4}} - 3!! \times (2 + 1 \times 0!)$$

• **12288**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8^{-7+6+5} = 4^{3!} \times (2 + 1) = 4 \times 3 \times 2^{10}$$

• **12321**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} + 7! + 6! = (-5! + 4 + 3 + 2)^{1+0!}$$

• **12840**

• **12840:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \times (7! - 6!) - 5! = 4 \times 3210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! + 6^5 = 4 \times 3210$$

• **12960**

- ▶ $(1+2)!! \times (-3!+4!) = 5! \times 6 \times (7+8+\sqrt{9})$
- ▶ $12 \times 3^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5! = 6! \times (7+8+\sqrt{9})$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9}+8+7) \times 6! = 54 \times 3!!/(2+1) = 5!+4 \times 3210$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9}+8+7) \times 6 \times 5! = (4!-3!) \times (2+1)!!$

• **12984**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8+7!-6!) = -5!+4!^3 - (2+1)!!$

• **13104**

• **12840:**

- ▶ $(98-7) \times 6!/5 = 4!^3 - (2+1)!!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8+7!-6!) + 5! = 4!^3 - (2+1)!!$

• **13122**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9^8} \times \sqrt{-7+6+5} = \sqrt{4} \times 3^{-2+10}$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^{8 \times 7}}}}} \right) \times 6 = (54 \times 3)^2 / (1+0!)$

• **13439**

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8!)/\sqrt{\sqrt{76+5}} = (\sqrt{4^3})!/(2+1) - 0!$

• **13440**

• **12840:**

- ▶ $\left((\sqrt{9})!+8 \right) \times (7!/6+5!) = (\sqrt{4^3})!/(2+1)$
- ▶ $\left((\sqrt{9})!+8 \right) \times (7!/6+5!) = 4^3 \times 210$

• **13441**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9}+8!)/\sqrt{\sqrt{76+5}} = (\sqrt{4^3})!/(2+1) + 0!$

• **13824**

- ▶ $(9+87) \times 6!/5 = 4!^3 \times (2-1) = 4!^3 + 21 \times 0$

• **13832**

$$\triangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \right) \times (7 + \sqrt{6!/5}) = 4!^3 - 2 + 10$$

• **13845**

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9 + 8! + 7!} \times 65 = 4!^3 + 21$$

• **14161**

$$\triangleright (1 - (2 + 3)!)^{\sqrt{4}} = (5! + 6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

• **14280**

• **14240:**

$$\triangleright (9 + 8) \times 7!/6 = 5! \times (4! \times (3 + 2) - 1)$$

$$\triangleright (9 + 8) \times 7!/6 = 5! + (-4! + 3!! \times 2) \times 10$$

• **14399**

$$\triangleright -1 + (2 + 3)!^{\sqrt{4}} = (5! + 6! + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\triangleright (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6! + 5!) = (\sqrt{4} + 3)!^2 - 1$$

• **14400**

$$\triangleright 1 \times (2 + 3)!^{\sqrt{4}} = 5 \times 6! \times (-7 + 8 + \sqrt{9})$$

• **14400:**

$$\triangleright (9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) = (\sqrt{4} + 3)!^2 \times 1$$

$$\triangleright (9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5!) = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times 2 \times 10$$

• **14400:**

$$\triangleright 9 \times 8 \times (76 + 5! + 4) = 3!! \times 2 \times 10$$

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) - 6 \times 5! + 4! = 3!! \times 2 \times 10$$

• **14544**

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) - 6! + 5! = 4!^3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

• **14640**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right)^7 - 6 \right) \times 5! = (4! + 3!! \times 2) \times 10$$

• **14641**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 - 2 \times 3!)^4 = (5! - 6 + 7)^{8 - (\sqrt{9})!}$$

• **14880**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 76 \right) \times 5! = (4! + 3!!) \times (2 \times 10)$$

• **15078**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! - 6!/5!) = \left(-\sqrt{4} + 3!! \right) \times 21$$

• **15090**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) = 6 - 5!/4 + 3!! \times 21$$

• **15096**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 23^{\sqrt{4}} + 5^6 = (7! - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7 \times 6!) = 5!^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!! - (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• **15096:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) = 6! + 5!^{\sqrt{4}} - 3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) = \sqrt{6! \times 5} + (-4 + 3!!) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) = 6 \times (5! - 4) + 3!! \times 2 \times 10$$

• **15097**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) + 6 - 5 + 4! = 3!! \times 21 + 0!$$

• **15099**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! + 6 - 5) = (4! - 3) \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• **15102**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (-3! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) = 6 + (7! - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) + 6 = \left((5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! \right) \times (2 + 1)$$

• **15114**

$$\blacktriangleright -(1+2)! + 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = (6 + 7! - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! + 6) = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3 - (2 + 1)!$$

• **15119**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! + 6) + 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times 21 - 0!$$

• **15119:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 \right) \times 6! - 5 + 4 = 3!! \times 21 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) - 6 + 5 + 4! = 3!! \times 21 - 0!$$

• **15120**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! + 3!! \times 4 \times 5 = (6 - 7 + 8)! \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2) \times (3+4)! = 5 \times 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times 9$$

• **15120:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 6)! = 5! \times \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 6)! = (5 - 4) \times 3!! \times 21$$

• **15120:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 = 4! \times 3 \times 210$$

• **15120:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 76) \times 5 \times 4 = 3!! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) \times (6 - 5) + 4! = 3!! \times 21$$

• 15120:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \times 7! = 6! + 5!^{\sqrt{4}} / 3 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \times 7! = 6! + 5!^{\sqrt{4}} - 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \times 7! = (65 + 4 + 3) \times 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \times 7! = 6! + 5! \times 4 \times \sqrt{3^2} \times 10$$

• 15121

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 \times 6! \times 5 + 4 = 3!! \times 21 + 0!$$

• 15123

• 15123:

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \times (7! + 6 - 5) = 4 + 3!! \times 21 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 \times 6! \times 5 = 4 + 3!! \times 21 - 0!$$

$$= \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times 21 + 0!$$

• 15125

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7 \right) \times 6! + 5 = 4 + 3!! \times 21 + 0!$$

• 15126

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3 \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = (-6 + 7! + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 15126

• 15126:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! - 6) = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3 + (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! - 6) = 5! / 4! + 3!! \times 21 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! - 6) = 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times 21 - 0!$$

• **15129**

$$\blacktriangleright 123^{\sqrt{4}} = (5 + 6 + 7! - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **15138**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) - 6 = \left((5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! \right) \times (2 + 1)$$

• **15141**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! - 6 + 5) = (4! - 3) \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **15143**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) - 6 + 5 = 4! + 3!! \times 21 - 0!$$

• **15144**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times \left(3! + (\sqrt{4} + 5)! \right) + 6 = (7! + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - (2 + 3)! \times 4 + 5^6 = (7! + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + (-7! + 6) \times 5 = 4! + 3!! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7 \times 6!) = 5!^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!! + (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• **15144:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) = (6!/5!)! + 4! + 3!! \times 2 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) = (6 + 5^4) \times 3! \times (2 + 1 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) = 6!/5! \times 4 + 3!! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) = 6! + 5!^{\sqrt{4}} + 3 + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) = 65 + \left(-\sqrt{4} + 3!! \right) \times 21 + 0!$$

• **15150**

• **15150:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) + 6 = 5!/4 + 3!! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) + 6 = 5 + 4! + 3!! \times 21 + 0!$$

• **15161**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) + 65 = \left(\sqrt{4} + 3!! \right) \times 21 - 0!$$

• **15162**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! + 6!/5!) = (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times 21$$

• **15204**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) + \sqrt{6! \times 5} = (4 + 3!!) \times 21$$

• **15552**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7) \times 6^5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

• **15625**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 - 2 + 3!)^{(\sqrt{4+5})!} &= (6 + 7 - 8)^{(\sqrt{9})!} \\ \blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \right)^6 &= 5^{4+3-2+1} = 5^{-4 \times (3-2)+10} \\ \blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)^{7-6+5} &= (\sqrt{4} + 3)^{(2+1)!} \end{aligned}$$

• **15816**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7!) + 6 \times 5! = -4! + 3!! \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **15840**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7! - 6! \times 5) = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **15840:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}} \right) \times 7! + 6! = 5!^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!! \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}}} \right) \times 7! + 6! = 5! \times \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **15864**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7!) + (6!/5!)! = 4! + 3!! \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **16128**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right)^7 \times (6 + 5!) = 4 \times (3! + 2)!/10$$

• **16368**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (-8 - 7! + 6^5) = (4! + 3!!) \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **16384**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{76+5!}} = 4^{3 \times 2 + 1}$$

• **16527**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! + (3+4)^5 = 6! + 7^{8-\sqrt{9}}$$

• **16560**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! / 7 - 6! = (5 \times 4 + 3) \times (2+1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! / 7 - 6 \times 5! = 4! \times 3!! - (2+1)!!$$

• **16752**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times (-7 + 6!) - 5!) = 4! \times (3!! - 21 - 0!)$$

• **16800**

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + 7 \times 6) \times 5! = 4! \times (3!! - 2 \times 10)$$

• **16807**

$$\blacktriangleright ((9-8)^7 + 6)^5 = (4+3)^{(2+1)!-0!}$$

• **16807:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(1+2)!! + (3+4)^5 + 6! = 7^{8-\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(1+2)! + (3+4)^5 + 6 = 7^{8-\sqrt{9}}$$

• **16813**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! + (3+4)^5 = 6 + 7^{8-\sqrt{9}}$$

• **16992**

$$\blacktriangleright (-12 + 3!!) \times 4! = (-5 + 6! - 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **17088**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times (7 + 6!) - 5!) = 4! \times (3!! + 2 - 10)$$

• **17112**

$$\blacktriangleright -(12 - 3!!) \times 4! + 5! = (6! - 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 5!) = 4! \times (3!! - (2+1)! - 0!)$$

• 17112:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (-7 + 6!) = (-5 - \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (-7 + 6!) = 5! + 4! \times (3!! - 2 - 10)$$

• 17136

$$\blacktriangleright ((1 + 2)!! - 3!) \times 4! + 5! = (6! + 7! - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6!/5 = 4! \times (3!! - (2 + 1)!)$$

• 17160

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 + 7) \times (6! - 5) = 4! \times (3!! - (2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• 17232

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (-2 + 3!!) \times 4! = (5 + 6! - 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 17232:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (-7 + 6!) + 5! = 4! \times (3!! - 2) \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (-7 + 6!) + 5! = (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• 17256

$$\blacktriangleright ((1 + 2)!! - 3!) \times 4! + 5! = (6! + 7! - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4! = (5! \times 6 + 7! - 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

• 17256

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! + 6!) = 5! + 4! \times (3!! - (2 + 1)!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! + 6 \times 5!) = 4! \times ((3 \times 2)! - 1)$$

• 17262

• 17262:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!/7 - 6) = (5! \times 4! - 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!/7 - 6) = 5 + 4! \times ((3 \times 2)! - 1) + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!/7 - 6) = 5 + 4! \times (3!! - 2 + 1) + 0!$$

• **17274**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 - 6!/5! = 4! \times 3!! - (2 + 1)!$
▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 - 6 = 5! \times 4! \times 3! - (2 + 1)!$

• **17277**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8!/7 - 6 + 5) = 4! \times 3!! - 2 - 1$

• **17279**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 - 6 + 5 = 4! \times (3 \times 2)! - 1$

• **17280**

▶ $(12 \times 3!!) \times \sqrt{4} = (5 - 6 + 7)! \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$
▶ $12^3 \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 = 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9)$
▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7)! \times 6! \times (5 - 4) = 3!! \times (2 + 1 + 0)!$
▶ $(9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! = 4! \times (3 \times 2)! \times 1$

• **17280:**

▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times (7! + 6!) = (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! = (5! + 4!) \times (3 + 2)! \times 1$

▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times (7! + 6!) = (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! = 5 + 4! \times 3!! - (2 + 1)! + 0!$

▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times (7! + 6!) = (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! = 54 \times (32 \times 10)$

• **17280:**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 = (-6 + 5! - 4!) \times 3! \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$
▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 = 6 \times 5! \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1$
▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 = \sqrt{6!/5} + 4! \times 3!! - 2 - 10$

• **17281**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 + 6 - 5 = 4! \times (3 \times 2)! + 1$

• **17283**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8!/7 + 6 - 5) = 4! \times 3!! + 2 + 1$

• **17285**

$$\triangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) \times (7! + 6!) + 5 = 4! \times 3!! + (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• **17286**

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 + 6!/5! = 4! \times 3!! + (2 + 1)!$$
$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 + 6 = 5 + 4! \times (3 \times 2)! + 1$$

• **17292**

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 + \sqrt{6!/5} = 4! \times 3!! + 2 + 10$$

• **17298**

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!/7 + 6) = (5! \times 4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **17303**

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!/7 + 6) + 5 = 4! \times ((3 \times 2)! + 1) - 0!$$

• **17304**

$$\triangleright (1 + (2 \times 3)!) \times 4! = (5! \times 6 + 7! + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$
$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! + 6 \times 5!) = 4! \times ((3 \times 2)! + 1)$$

• **17304:**

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! + 6!) = \sqrt{5! + 4!} \times (3!! \times 2 + 1 + 0!)$$
$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! + 6!) = 5! + (-4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1 + 0)!)$$

• **17328**

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5) = 4! \times (3!! + 2 \times 1)$$

• **17376**

• **17376:**

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! + 6!) + 5! = (4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1 + 0)!)$$
$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! + 6!) + 5! = 4! \times (3!! + 2 + 1 + 0)!)$$

• **17400**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8! / (7! / 6!) + 5! = 4! \times (3! + (2 + 1)!! - 0!)$

• **17424**

▶ $((1 + 2)! + 3!!) \times 4! = 5! + (6! + 7! + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! + 6!) + 5! = 4! \times (3! + (2 + 1)!!)$

• **17448**

▶ $(1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4! + 5! = (6! + 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5!) = 4! \times (3!! + (2 + 1)! + 0!)$

• **17448:**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7 + 6!) = 5! + 4! \times (3!! + 2 \times 1)$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7 + 6!) = 5! + (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1 + 0)!$

• **17472**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times (-7 + 6!) + 5!) = 4! \times (3!! - 2 + 10)$

• **17527**

▶ $(1 + 2)!! + (3 + 4)^5 = 6! + 7^{8 - \sqrt{9}}$

• **17568**

▶ $(12 + 3!!) \times 4! = 5! + (6! + 7) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

• **17640**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) / 6 = 5! \times (4 + 3) \times 21$

• **17760**

• **17760:**

▶ $(9 \times 8 + 76) \times 5! = 4! \times (3!! + 2 \times 10)$

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) / 6 + 5! = 4! \times ((3 \times 2)! - 10)$

• **17808**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 \times (7 + 6!) + 5!) = 4! \times (3!! + 21 + 0!)$

• **17856**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right) \times 7! + 6^5 = (4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• **18000**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 + 6! = (5! + 4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 + 6 \times 5! = 4! \times 3!! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3!! \times 4! = 5 \times 6! \times (7 + 8)/\sqrt{9}$$

• **18432**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right)^7 \times 6!/5 = (4! - 3!) \times 2^{10}$$

• **18720**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3! + 4 \times 5) = 6! \times 78/\sqrt{9}$$

• **19440**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3 + 4!) = (5! + 6 \times 7) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6!/5 = (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!/7 + 6!) = 54 \times 3!!/2 \times 1$$

• **19683**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)^{3\sqrt{4}} = \sqrt{((5 + 67)/8)^9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times 3^{4+5} = \sqrt{(-6 + 7 + 8)^9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^{8+7-6}} = \sqrt{(5 + 4)^{3^2} \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^{-8 \times 7 + 65}} = (4! + 3)^{2+1}$$

• **20160**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3)! \times 4 = (56/7)! / \left(8 - (\sqrt{9})!\right)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 \times 5! \times 4 = (3! + 2)! / (1 + 0)!$$

• **20160:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7!/6 = 5! \times 4!/3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7!/6 = 5! \times 4 \times (32 + 10)$$

• **20160:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7! - 6! \times 5) = 4 \times (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7! - 6! \times 5) = (4 + 3)! \times 2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **20480**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7)^6 \times 5 = 4^{3!} / 2 \times 10$$

• **20736**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!/7) \times 6/5 = (4! \times 3!)^2 \times 1$$

• **20737**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3!)^4 = 5^6 + 7! + 8 \times 9$$

• **21570**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7 \right) \times 6 \times 5 = (4! + 3!) \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• **21599**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5 = (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• **21600**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3! + 4!) = 5 \times 6! \times (7 + 8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times 3!! \times \sqrt{4} \times 5 = (-6! + 7!) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7! - 6!) = 5!/4 \times (3 \times 2)! \times 1 = 5 \times 432 \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 - 7) \times 6 \times 5 = (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• **21600:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7! - 6! \times 5) = 4 \times (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7! - 6! \times 5) = (4 + 3)! \times 2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **21601**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5 = (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• **21630**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 = (4! + 3!) \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **22320**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (1+2)! \times (3!!+4!) \times 5 = 6! \times (7+8 \times \sqrt{9}) \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times 8+7) \times 6! = (\sqrt{5^4}+3!) \times (2+1)!! \\ &\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7+6) \times 5! = 4! \times (3!!+210) \end{aligned}$$

• **22680**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8!+7!)/6 = (5!-4 \times 3) \times 210$$

• **23040**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 \times (-7+6+5) = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times \sqrt{2^{10}} \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9}-8+7+6) \times 5! \times 4! = 3!! \times \sqrt{2^{10}} \end{aligned}$$

• **24480**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times 34 = (-5 \times 6!+7!) \times (8+9) \\ &\blacktriangleright (1+2)! \times 34 \times 5! = 6 \times 7! - 8 \times \sqrt{9}!! \\ &\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7! - 6! = 5 \times (4+3)! - (2+1)!! \end{aligned}$$

• **24576**

• **24576:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8^{-7+6+5} = 4^{3!} \times (2+1)! \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8^{-7+6+5} = 4 \times 3! \times 2^{10} \end{aligned}$$

• **24720**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 + (7!+6) \times 5 = 4! \times (3!+2^{10})$$

• **25170**

$$\blacktriangleright -(1+2)! + (3+4)! \times 5 = (-6+7!) \times (8-\sqrt{9})$$

• **25170:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times (7! - 6) = 5 \times ((4+3)! - (2+1)!) \\ &\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times (7! - 6) = \left((5+\sqrt{4})! - 3! \right) \times ((2+1)! - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **25200**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6! \times 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6! \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! \times 210$$

• **25200:**

$$\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)! + (3 + 4)! \times 5 + 6 = 7! \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 2 + 34) \times 5! \times 6 = 7! \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

• **25200:**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 \times 6! = 5 \times (4 + 3)! \times (2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 \times 6! = 5 \times 4 \times 3! \times 210$$

• **25200:**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! = (6! + 5!) \times (4 + 3!) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! = 6^5 + 4! \times (3!! + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! = 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)! - (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! = 6! + 5! \times (-\sqrt{4} \times 3 + 210)$$

• **25206**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + (3 + 4)! \times 5 = 6 + 7! \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! + 6 = 5 \times (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!$$

• **25230**

$$\blacktriangleright ((1 + 2)! + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 = (6 + 7!) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

• **25230:**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7! + 6) = 5 \times ((4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7! + 6) = \left(\sqrt{5\sqrt{4}}\right) \times (3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0!))!$$

• **25920**

▶ $(1+2)!! \times 3!^{\sqrt{4}} = 5! \times (-6+78) \times \sqrt{9}$
▶ $(12-3) \times 4! \times 5! = 6! + 7! \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$

• **25920:**

▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7! + 6! = 5 \times 4! \times 3!^{2+1}$
▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7! + 6! = 5 \times 4! \times (3! + 210)$

• **26244**

▶ $\sqrt{9^8} \times (-7+6+5) = 4 \times 3^{-2+10}$

• **27000**

▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times (8+7) \times (-6!+5!) = (4!+3!)^{2+1}$

• **27648**

• **27648:**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7!+6!)/5 = 4!^3 \times 2 \times 1$
▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7!+6!)/5 = (4!+3) \times 2^{10}$

• **28800**

▶ $1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times 4 \times 5 = (6!+7!) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$
▶ $(9-8+7) \times 6! \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times 2 \times 10$

• **28800:**

▶ $(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8-7!}}) \times 6! = 5! \times (4+3)!/21$
▶ $(-\sqrt{9}+8) \times (7!+6!) = 5! \times (4+3)!/21$
 $= (5!^{\sqrt{4}} - 3!!/2) \times (1+0!)$

• **29512**

▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7! \times 6 = (5!+4^{3!}) \times ((2+1)!+0!)$

• **29520**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! \times 8 - 7 \right) \times 6! = \left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right)! \times 3! - (2 + 1)!!$$

• **29520:**

$$\blacktriangleright 123 \times \sqrt{4} \times 5! = 6 \times \left(7! - \left(8 - \sqrt{9} \right)! \right)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 123 \times \sqrt{4} \times 5! = 6! \times \left(-7 + 8 \times \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! \right)$$

• **29808**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 6 = (5! + 4!) \times (-3 + 210)$$

• **30120**

$$\blacktriangleright - \left(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \right)! + 7! \times 6 = 5! \times (4 \times 3 \times 21 - 0!)$$

• **30192**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 - 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5) \times 6 = (7! - 8) \times \sqrt{9}!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! \times (-8 + 7!) = 6 \times \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right)! - 3^2 + 1 \right)$$

• **30198**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! \times (-8 + 7!) + 6 = \left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) \times 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• **30204**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right)! \times (7! - 6) = \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right)! - 3! \right) \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **30210**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times ((3 + 4)! - 5) = 6 \times (7! - 8 + \sqrt{9})$$

• **30210**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7!) \times 6 = (-5 + (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **30216**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! \times 6 = \left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right)! \times 3! - (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• **30222**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + 7!}}} \right) \times 6 = \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right)! - 3 \right) \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **30223**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 + 7! \times 6 = \left((5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3 \right) \times (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• **30228**

$$\blacktriangleright -12 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + (5))! = 6 \times (7! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!) \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (-8 + 7! + 6) = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! - 2 - 10$$

• **30234**

$$\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)! + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 \times (7! + 8 - 9)$$

• **30234**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7!) \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! - (2 + 1)!$$

• **30237**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7! \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! - 2 - 1$$

• **30238**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 \times 7! - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **30238:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! - 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! \times 6 = (5!^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!!) \times 2 - 1 - 0!$$

• **30239**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 - 2 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 \times 7! + 8 - 9$$

• **30239**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! - 2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7!) \times 6 + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times 21 - 0!$$

• **30240**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (-3 + 4!) \times 5! = 6 \times 7! \times (-8 + 9) \\ \blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7! \times 6 = 5! \times 4 \times 3 \times 21$$

• 30240:

- ▶ $(1+2)! \times (3+4)! = 5! + 6 \times 7! - (8 - \sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(1+2)! \times (3+4)! = 5 \times 6 \times 7! / (8 - \sqrt{9})$
- ▶ $(1+2)! \times (3+4)! = 5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 + \sqrt{9}$

• 30240:

- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)! \times 7! = (6+5!) \times (4+3)! / 21$
- ▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)! \times 7! = (-6+54) \times 3 \times 210$

• 30240:

- ▶ $-\left(-\sqrt{9}+8\right)! + 7! \times 6 + 5! = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times 21$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7! \times 6 + 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times 21$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 \times 7 \times \sqrt{6!} \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times 21$
 $= 4! \times 3! \times 210$

• 30240:

- ▶ $\left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) + 7! \times 6 + 5 + 4 = 3! \times ((2+1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 \times \sqrt{4} = 3! \times ((2+1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5! + 4! = 3! \times ((2+1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $-\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! - (8-7!) \times 6 + 54 = 3! \times ((2+1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7!) \times 6 + 5! + 4! = 3! \times ((2+1)! + 0)!$

• 30241

- ▶ $-1 + 2 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 \times 7! - 8 + 9$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5! = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times 21 + 0!$

• **30242**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 \times 7! + 8 - (\sqrt{9})! \\ &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5! = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! \times 21 + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **30242:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! \times 6 = (5!^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!!) \times 2 + 1 + 0! \\ &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! + 2 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **30243**

• **30243:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7! \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! + 2 + 1 \\ &\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7! \times 6 = 5 + \sqrt{4} \times (3!! \times 21 - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **30245**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3 + 4)! + 5 = 6 \times 7! + 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• **30245:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! \times 6 = 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times 21 \\ &\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7! \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! + (2 + 1)! - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• **30246**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 \times (7! - 8 + 9) \\ &\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7!) \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! + (2 + 1)! \end{aligned}$$

• **30249**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}} \right) + 7! \times 6 = 5 + 4 + 3! \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **30252**

▶ $12 + 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 \times (7! + 8 - \sqrt{9}!)$
▶ $(-\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! + 2 + 10$

• **30257**

▶ $9 + 8 + 7! \times 6 = ((5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3) \times (2 + 1)! - 0!$

• **30258**

• **30258:**

▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8 + 7!}}} + 7!} \right) \times 6 = ((5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3) \times (2 + 1)!$
▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8 + 7!}}} + 7!} \right) \times 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!)$

• **30264**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5! = 4! + 3! \times ((2 + 1)! + 0)!)$
▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! + (2 + 1 + 0)!)$

• **30270**

▶ $(1 + 2)! \times ((3 + 4)! + 5) = 6 \times (7! + 8 - \sqrt{9})$
▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7!) \times 6 = (5 + (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)!$

• **30276**

▶ $\left(\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} + 7!} \right) + 7! \right) \times 6 = ((5 + 4!) \times 3!)^2 \times 1$

• **30288**

▶ $(1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5) \times 6 = (7! + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• **30288:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7!) = 6 \times (5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1)$
▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7!) = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$

• **30294**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + (8 + 7!) \times 6 = 54 + 3! \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **30360**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times (3 + 4)! + 5! = 6 \times 7! + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7! \times 6 = (5! + (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **30384**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7!) \times 6 = 5! + 4! + 3! \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **30672**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 6 = (5! + 4!) \times (3 + 210)$$

• **30917**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! - (8 - 7!) \times 6 + 5 = 43 \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• **30960**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! \times ((3 + 4)! + 5!) = 6 \times (7! + (8 - \sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5 = 43 \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7!) \times 6 = 5! \times 43 \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **31003**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7!) + 6! + 5 = 43 \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **31008**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + (8 + 7!) \times 6 = 5 + 43 \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **31104**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7) \times 6^5 = 4! \times 3!^{2+1+0!}$$

• **31680**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 \times 7 - \sqrt{6!/5}) = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **32400**

$$\blacktriangleright 1^2 \times 3!! \times 45 = 6! \times (7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7) \times 6! = (5! / \sqrt{4} \times 3)^2 \times 1$$

• **32768**

$$\blacktriangleright (98/7 - 6)^5 = \sqrt{4^{-3!+21}} = \sqrt{4^{3+2+10}}$$

• **34224**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (-7 + 6!) = (-5! + 4! \times (3!! - 2)) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **34320**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8!/7! \times (6! - 5) = 4! \times (3!! \times 2 - 10)$$

• **34464**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (-7 + 6! + 5) = 4! \times (3!! - 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **34512**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (-8 + 7! + 6 \times 5!) = 4! \times (3!! \times 2 - 1 - 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})!! - 8 + 7!) \times 6 = (5! - 4! \times 3) \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• **34524**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 \times 6 = (5! \times 4! - 3) \times (2 + 10)$$

• **34542**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8!/7) \times 6 = 5 + 4! \times (3!! \times 2 - 1) + 0!$$

• **34551**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4! - 5) = (-6! + 7!) \times 8 - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8!/7 \times 6 = (-5 + 4! \times 3!!) \times 2 + 1$$

• **34556**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! - 7! - 6! + 5 = (4! \times 3!! - 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **34559**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4! = 5 - 6! - 7! + 8! - (\sqrt{9})! = 5 - 6 - 7! + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• **34559:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8!/7 - 6 + 5 = 4! \times 3!! \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8!/7 \times 6 + 5 = 4! \times 3!! \times 2 - 1$$

• **34560**

▶ $12 \times 3!! \times 4 = (5! + 6 - 78) \times \sqrt{9}!!$

▶ $12^3 \times 4 \times 5 = 6! / (7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}!!$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! / 7 = 6! \times (54 - 3 - 2 - 1)$

• **34560:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5)! = 4! \times 3!! \times 2 \times 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7 - 6 + 5)! = 6 \times 5 \times 4!^3 / (2 + 10)$

• **34560:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8! / 7! \times 6 = 5! \times 4! \times 3! \times 2 \times 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8! / 7! \times 6 = 5! \times 4 \times 3! \times (+2 + 10)$

• **34562**

• **34562:**

▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! / 7 \times 6 + 5 = 4! \times 3!! \times 2 + 1 + 0!$

▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7! - 6! + 5 = 4! \times 3!! \times 2 + 1 + 0!$

• **34563**

▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! / 7 \times 6 = 5 + 4! \times 3!! \times 2 - 1 - 0!$

• **34566**

▶ $1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4! + 5 = 6 - 7! + 8! - \sqrt{9}!!$

• **34566:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! / 7 + 6 = 5 + 4! \times 3!! \times 2 + 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! / 7 + 6 = ((5! - 4! - 3) \times 2)^{1+0!}$

• **34569**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4! + 5) = (-6! + 7!) \times 8 + 9$$

• **34569:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8!/7 \times 6 = (5 + 4! \times 3!!) \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8!/7 \times 6 = 5 + (4! \times 3!! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **34578**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8!/7) \times 6 = -5 + 4! \times (3!! \times 2 + 1) - 0!$$

• **34583**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8!/7) \times 6 + 5 = 4! \times (3!! \times 2 + 1) - 0!$$

• **34608**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7! \right) \times 6!/5! = 4! \times (3!! \times 2 + 1 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7! + 6!) = (54 - 3!) \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **34656**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7 + 6! - 5) = 4! \times (3!! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **34800**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / (8 + 7) \times (6! + 5) = 4! \times (3!! \times 2 + 10)$$

• **34896**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7 + 6!) = (5! + 4! \times (3!! + 2)) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **35280**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 2^3) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 - 7! + 8! - \sqrt{9}!$$

• **35280:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8!/7 + 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8!/7 + 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})!/3 \times 21$$

• **36000**

▶ $(1+2)!! \times (3!+4) \times 5 = 6! \times (7 \times 8 - \sqrt{9!})$

• **36000:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times (8+7 \times 6) = 5^{\sqrt{4}} \times 3!! \times 2 \times 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times (8+7 \times 6) = \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}}\right) \times (3 \times 2)! \times 10$

• **36720**

▶ $(1+2)!! \times (3!+45) = 6! - 7! + 8! + \sqrt{9!!}$

• **36864**

▶ $9 \times 8^{-7+6+5} = (4! \times (3!+2))^{1+0!}$

• **38160**

• **38160:**

▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7) \times 6! = ((54 \times 3!!) - (2+1)!!)$

▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7) \times 6! = 5! \times (-4! + 3!) + (-2+10)!$

• **38880**

▶ $\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}}\right) \times (7! - 6!) = 54 \times (3 \times 2)! \times 1$

• **39327**

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! + \sqrt{4} + 5 = 6! + 7 + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!!$

• **39366**

• **39366:**

▶ $\sqrt{9^{8!/7!}} \times 6 = 54 \times 3^{(2+1)!}$

▶ $\sqrt{9^{8!/7!}} \times 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})^{3^2} \times (1+0!)$

• **39600**

- ▶ $-(1+2)!! + (3! + \sqrt{4})! = 5! \times (-6 + 7 \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$
- ▶ $1 \times (2^3)! - (\sqrt{4+5})!! = 6! \times (7 + 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$
- ▶ $12 \times 3!! \times 4 \times (-5 + 6) + 7! = 8! - (\sqrt{9})!!$

• **39600:**

- ▶ $(1+2)!! \times 3! \times (4+5) + 6! = 7! \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})!! = 7! \times 8 - \sqrt{9}!!$
- ▶ $1 \times (2 + \sqrt{3^4}) \times 5 \times 6! = 7! \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})!! = 7! \times 8 - \sqrt{9}!!$

• **39600:**

- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! = 6! \times (54 + 3 - 2) \times 1$
- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! = (\sqrt{4^3})! - (2 + 1)!!$

• **39600:**

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 7!/6 + 5! \times (\sqrt{4} + 321)$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 7 + 6! + 54 \times 3!! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! = 6! \times (5 \times (4 + 3) + 2 \times 10)$

• **39601**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 - 6! + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! - (2 + 1)!! + 0!$

• **39607**

- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! - (\sqrt{4+5})!! + 6 = 7 + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7 = 6! + 54 \times 3!! + (2 + 1)! + 0!$

• **39624**

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + (-7 + 6 + 5)! = 4! - 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **40200**

- ▶ $(98/7 - 6)! = 5! + (\sqrt{4^3})! - ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$

• 40200:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7!/6 + 5 \times 4! = (3! + 2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7!/6 + 5 \times 4! = 5! \times (-4! + 3!!/2 - 1)$$

• 40237

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7 + 6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! \times 1$$

• 40263

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times (7! - 6) = (5 - 4!) \times 3 + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 40299

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times 7! - \sqrt{6!/5} = (\sqrt{4^3})! - 21$$

• 40310

• 40310:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times (7! - 6) + 5 + 4! = (3! + 2)! - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4! = (3! + 2)! - 10$$

• 40311

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4! - 5) + 6! + 7! = 8! - 9$$

• 40311:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! = 7! \times 6 + (-5 + (4 + 3)!) \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! = 7! + 6! - (5 - 4! \times 3!!) \times 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! = 7 \times 6 - 54 + 3 + (-2 + 10)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! = 7 + 6!/5! + (\sqrt{4^3})! - 21 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! = 7 + 6 - 5\sqrt{4} + 3 + (-2 + 10)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! = 7 - 6 \times (5 - 4) + (3! + 2)! - 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! = 7 - \sqrt{6!/5} - 4 + (3! + 2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! = \sqrt{76 + 5} - 4! + 3! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **40311:**

- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! = (6 - 5)^4 + (3! + 2)! - 10$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! = 6 + 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! - 21 + 0!$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! = 6 - \sqrt{5\sqrt{4}} \times 3 + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! = \sqrt{6!/5} - 4! + 3 + (-2 + 10)!$

• **40313**

▶ $-12 + (3! + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 6 - 7 + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!$

• **40313:**

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 + 6 = -5 - \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 + 6 = 5 + (4!/3)! - 2 - 10$

• **40314**

▶ $-(1 + 2)! + (3! + \sqrt{4})! = (\sqrt{56/7 \times 8})! - (\sqrt{9})!$

▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! = (6 - 5)^4 \times (-3! + (-2 + 10)!)$

• **40314:**

- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! - 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 = 8! - (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) - 6 + 7! = 8! - (\sqrt{9})!$

• **40314:**

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7!/6! - \sqrt{5! + 4!} + (3! + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7! + 6! - 5 + 4! \times 3!! \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7 + 6 + 5 - 4! + (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7 + 6 + 5 - 4! + (3^2 - 1)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7 + 6 - 5 \times 4 + (3! + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = (7 - 6)^5 - 4 - 3 + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7!/6! - 5 - 4!/3 + (-2 + 10)!$

• **40316**

▶ $-9 + 8! \times (7 - 6) + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! - 2 - 1 - 0!$

• **40317**

▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! + 6 = 5 + (4!/3)! + 2 - 10$

• **40317:**

▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! = (6 - 5) \times (-4 + (3! + 2)! + 1)$
▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! = 6! - 5 + \sqrt{4} - 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **40317:**

▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7 + 6 + 5 + (4!/3)! - 21$
▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7! + 6! - 5 + 4! \times 3!! \times 2 + 1 + 0!$
▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7 \times (6 - 5) - (4 + 3!) + (-2 + 10)!$
▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7 \times (6 - 5) + (-65 + 4^{3 \times 2}) \times 10$
▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7 + 6 + 5 - 4! + 3 + (-2 + 10)!$

• **40318**

▶ $-1 - 2 + (3! + \sqrt{4})! - 5 + 6 = 7 + 8! - 9$
▶ $9 + 8! - 7!/6! \times 5 + 4! = (3! + 2)! - 1 - 0!$

• **40318:**

▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7 + 6! + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! - 2 \times 1$
▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 + 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! - 2 \times 1$

• **40318:**

▶ $-9 + 8! + 7 = 6 - 5 + (4!/3)! - 2 - 1$
▶ $-9 + 8! + 7 = 6 - 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! - 2 - 1$
▶ $-9 + 8! + 7 = 6 - 5 - 4 + (3! + 2)! + 1$
▶ $-9 + 8! + 7 = \sqrt{6!/5} - 4 + (3! + 2)! - 10$
▶ $-9 + 8! + 7 = 6! - (\sqrt{5 + 4})!! + (3! + 2)! - 1 - 0!$
▶ $-9 + 8! + 7 = 6 \times 5! - \sqrt{4} - 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$
▶ $-9 + 8! + 7 = 6 \times 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! - \sqrt{2^{10}}$

• **40319**

▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 - \sqrt{6!/5} + 4! = (3! + 2!) - 1$

• **40319:**

▶ $-1 + (2^3)! = 4 + 5 + 6 - 7 + 8! - 9$

▶ $-1 + (2^3)! = \sqrt{4^5} - 6 \times 7 + 8! + 9$

▶ $-1 + (2^3)! = \sqrt{4 + 5!!} + 6 - 7 + 8! - \sqrt{9!!}$

• **40319:**

▶ $(9 - 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! - 2 + 1$

▶ $(9 - 8 + 7)! - 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{43 + 21})! - 0!$

• **40320**

• **40320:**

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! = 4! - 5!/6 - 7 + 8! + \sqrt{9}$

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! = 4 - (-5 + 6)^7 + 8! - \sqrt{9}$

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! = 4 \times 5! \times (67 + 8 + 9)$

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! = 4 + 5 + 6! \times 7 \times 8 - 9$

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! = 45 - 6 \times 7 + 8! - \sqrt{9}$

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! = \sqrt{4! + 5!} - 6 + 7! \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! = \sqrt{4} \times 5 + 6 - 7 + 8! - 9$

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! = \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6! - 7 + 8! - \sqrt{9!!}$

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! = \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 - 7 + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!$

▶ $1 \times (2^3)! = \sqrt{4} - 5 - 6 + 7! \times 8 + 9$

• **40320:**

▶ $(12/3 + 4)! = (-5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 + 9)!$

▶ $(12/3 + 4)! = 56 \times (7 + 8 - 9)!$

▶ $(12/3 + 4)! = 5 - 6 + 7 + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!$

• 40320:

- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7)! = (6 - 5) \times (\sqrt{43 + 21})!$
- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7)! = (6! + 5!) \times \sqrt{4} \times (3 + 21)$
- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7)! = (6 - 5 + 4 + 3)! \times (2 - 1)$
- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7)! = 6 - 5 + (4!/3)! - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7)! = 6 - 5 - \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! + 1$

• 40320:

- ▶ $(98/7 - 6)! = (54/(3 \times 2) - 1)!$
- ▶ $(98/7 - 6)! = 5 - 4 + (3! + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $(98/7 - 6)! = 5 - 4 + (3! + 2)! \times 1 - 0!$

• 40320:

- ▶ $(98/7 - 6)! \times (5 - 4) = (3^2 - 1)! = (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! - 6 + \sqrt{5! + 4!} = (3^2 - 1)! = (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! \times (7 - 6) - 5 + \sqrt{4} = (3^2 - 1)! = (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7)! + 6! - (5 - \sqrt{4})!! = (3^2 - 1)! = (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7! - 6) + 54 = (3^2 - 1)! = (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 + 6 + 5 + \sqrt{4} = (3^2 - 1)! = (3! + 2)! \times 1$

• 40320:

- ▶ $9 + 8! - 7 \times 6 + 5!/4 + 3 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9 + 8! - 7 - 6 + 5 - 4 + 3 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times (7! + 6) + (5 - 4!) \times 3 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 7! - 6! - 5 - 4 + 3!! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times 7! - 6 - 5 - 4 + 3! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-9 + 8! + 76 + 5 - 4! \times 3 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-9 + 8! - 7! + 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! - 6! + (-5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! - 6! + 5 + 4 + 3!! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 - 6! + 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3!! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7)! - 6! + 5! \times \sqrt{4} \times 3 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6! + (5 + 4) \times 3!! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! - 6 \times 5 + 4! + 3 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4 \times 3!! = (-2 + 10)!$

• 40320:

- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7) \times 6^5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $((\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! + (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7! / 6 - 5) + 4! + 3! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7! - 6) + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! - 6! + (5 - \sqrt{4})!! - 3! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 + 65 - 4^3 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 \times 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times 3! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! - 6 - (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + 3! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 \times 7 + 6! / 5 - 4! \times 3! = (-2 + 10)!$

• 40320:

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7!/6! - 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 + 3!! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7!/6! + 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7 + 6! - 5 + 4 \times 3 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7 \times 6 + 5 + 43 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7 - 6 \times 5 + 43 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - (-7 + 6 + 5)! + 4! + 3!! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7 \times 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! = (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! - 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + 3! = (-2 + 10)!$

• 40321

• 40321:

- ▶ $-1 + (2^3)! + \sqrt{4} = (56/7)! - 8 + 9 = 5 + 6 - 7 + 8! - \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $1 + (2 + 3 \times \sqrt{4})! = (56/7)! - 8 + 9 = 5 + 6 - 7 + 8! - \sqrt{9}$

• 40321:

- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! + 4 + 5 + 6 = 7 + 8! + 9$
- ▶ $-1 + 2 + ((3 + 45)/6)! = 7 + 8! - (\sqrt{9})! = 7 + 8! + 9$

• 40321:

- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! = 4! - 5!/6 + 7! \times 8 - \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! = 4 + 5 - 6 + 7 + 8! - 9$
- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! = \sqrt{4} + (56/7)! + 8 - 9$
- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! = \sqrt{4} + 5 - 6 + (7 - 8 + 9)!$

• 40321:

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 - 4 - 3! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 = 6 - 5 + (\sqrt{43 + 21})!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 = 6 - 5 + \sqrt{43 + 21}!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 = 65 - 4^3 + (-2 + 10)!$

• 40321:

- ▶ $(9 - 8 + 7)! + 6 - 5 = (4!/3)! + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 + 6 + 5 = (4!/3)! + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times (7! - 6 + 5) = (4!/3)! + 2 - 1$
 $= (\sqrt{4^3})! + 2 - 1$
 $= \sqrt{4} + (3^2 - 1)! - 0!$

• 40321:

- ▶ $9 - 8 + (7 + (6 - 5)^4)! = (3! + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7 - 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4})!! = (3! + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $-9 + 8! - \sqrt{76 + 5!} + 4! = (3! + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $-9 + 8! \times (7 - 6) + 5 \times \sqrt{4} = (3! + 2)! + 1$
 $= (3^2 - 1)! + 0!$

• 40321:

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7!/6! = ((5 - 4 + 3) \times 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7!/6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} - 3! + (-2 + 10)!$

• 40322

- ▶ $1 \times (2^3)! + \sqrt{4} = 5 + 6 + 7! \times 8 - 9$
- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! - 4 + 5 = 6 - 7 + 8! + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! - 6 + 5 = 4 + (3! + 2)! - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9 + (8!/7)! - 6 - 5 + 4 = (3! + 2)! + 1 + 0!$

• 40322:

- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! + 6 + 5 = (4!/3)! + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! + 6 + 5 = \sqrt{4} + (3^2 - 1)!$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! + 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! + 2 \times 1$

• 40322:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 + 6 = (-5 + 4 + 3^2)! + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 + 6 = 5 - 4 + (3! + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 + 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! - 2 - 1$

• 40323

- ▶ $-1 + (2^3)! + 4 = 5 - 6 + 7 + 8! - \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $1 \times (2^3)! - \sqrt{4} + 5 = 6 + 7! \times 8 - \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! + \sqrt{4} \times (-5 + 6) = 7! \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $1 \times (2^3)! + 4 \times (5 - 6) + 7 = 8! + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! \times (7 - 6) = 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! - 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! \times (7 - 6)^5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! + 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8 \times (7! - 6 + 5) + \sqrt{4} = 3 + (-2 + 10)!$

• 40323:

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7 - 6 + 5 - 4 + (3! + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! = \sqrt{76 + 5} - 6 + 5 - 4 + (3! + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7 + 6 - 5 \times \sqrt{4} + (3^2 - 1)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! = \sqrt{76 + 5} + (\sqrt{4^3})! - (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7 + 6 + (5 + 4 - 3 + 2)! - 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7 + 6! - 5 + (4!/3)! - (2 + 1)!! + 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! = \sqrt{76 + 5} + 4 + (3! + 2)! - 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7! + 6! + 5 + 4! \times 3!! \times 2 - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7! + 6 \times (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! = 7 + 6 - 5 + (\sqrt{\sqrt{4^3}})! - (2 + 1)! + 0!$

• **40323:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! = (6 - 5) \times (4 + (3! + 2)! - 1)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! = 6 + 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! + 2 - 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! = 6! - (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + 3 + (-2 + 10)!$

• **40324**

- ▶ $1 \times (2^3)! + 4 = 5!/6 - 7 + 8! - 9$
- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! - \sqrt{4} + 5 = 6 + 7 + 8! - 9$
- ▶ $-1 + (2^3)! + 4 - 5 + 6 = 7 + 8! - \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $-9 + 8! + 7 + 6 = 5 - \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! + 1$

• **40324:**

- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = 6 - 5 + (4!/3)! + 2 + 1$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = 6 - 5 + 4 + (3! + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = (6 - 5) \times 4 + (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = (6 - 5) \text{ times } 4 + (3^2 - 1)!$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 - 4 - 3 + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = 6! + 5 + (4!/3)! - (2 + 1)!! - 0!$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = 6! + 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! - (2 + 1)!! - 0!$

• **40325**

- ▶ $(12/3 + 4)! + 5 = 6 - 7 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! + 4 = 5 + 6 + 7! \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$

• **40325:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 + 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{43 + 21})!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 + 6 = 5 + (4 + 3)! \times (-2 + 10)$

• **40325:**

- ▶ $(98/7 - 6)! + 5 = 4 + (3! + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $(98/7 - 6)! + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! + (2 + 1)! - 0!$

• **40326**

- ▶ $(1+2)! + (3! + \sqrt{4})! = (\sqrt{56/7 \times 8})! + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $-1 + (2^3)! + \sqrt{4} + 5 = 6 + (7 - 8 + 9)!$
- ▶ $-1 + (2^3)! - 4 + 5 + 6 = 7! \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = (7-6)^5 \times (\sqrt{4^3})! + (2+1)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7! / 6 + 5 - 4) = 3! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **40326:**

- ▶ $1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)! + 5 + 6 \times 7! = 8! + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $1 - 2 + ((3 + 45) / 6)! + 7 = 8! + (\sqrt{9})! = 8! + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) + 6 + 7! = 8! + (\sqrt{9})!$

• **40326:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7 - 6 + 5 + (\sqrt{43 + 21})!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7! / 6! + ((5 - 4 + 3) \times 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7! / 6! + (5 - 4) \times ((3! + 2)! - 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7 + 6! - (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + (3! + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7! + 6 - (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7 + 6! - 5 + 4 - 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 76 - 5! / \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! - 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = (7 - 6)^5 \times -4 + (3! + 2)! + 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7! + 6! + (5 + 4! \times 3!! - 2) \times (1 + 0!)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7 + 6 + 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! - 2 - 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7! \times 6! / 5! + \sqrt{4} \times (3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)!)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! = 7 \times 6! - (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **40326:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! = 6 \times (5! \times (4! + 32) + 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! = (6 - 5)^4 \times 3! + (-2 + 10)!$

• 40326:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)! + 6 = 5 + (4!/3)! + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)! + 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{43 + 21})! + 0!$$

• 40327

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! + \sqrt{4} + 5 = 6 + 7 + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 + 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! + (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

• 40328

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! - 7 + 6 = 5 + (4!/3)! + 2 + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! - 7 + 6!/5! = (\sqrt{4^3})! - 2 + 10$$

• 40328:

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2^3)! + 4 + 5 = 6 - 7 + 8! + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2^3)! - 4 + 5 = 6 - 7 + 8! + \sqrt{9}$$

• 40329

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! - \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 = 7! \times 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2^3)! + \sqrt{4} \times 5 = 6! \times 7 \times 8 + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4! + 5) + 6! + 7! = 8! + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7! = (6!/5! + \sqrt{4})! + 3 \times (2 + 1) = 6 + 5 + (4!/3)! - 2 \times 1$$

• **40329:**

- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7 + 6 - 5 + (4!/3)! + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7 + 6 - 5 + (-4! + 32)! + 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + (3! + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7 + 6!/5! - 4 + (3^2 - 1)!$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7! + 6! + (5 + 4! \times 3!!) \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = (7 - 6) \times 5 + 4 + (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7! \times 6 + (5 + (4 + 3)!) \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 76 + 5 - 4! \times 3 + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = (7 - 6) \times 5 + (4!/3)! + 2 + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7! \times 6 + 5 + ((4 + 3)! + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7! + 6! + (5 + 4! \times 3!!) \times 2 \times 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7! + 6 - (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7 + 6! - (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + (3! + 2)! + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7 + 6 \times 5! + \sqrt{4} - 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9 + 8! = 7 - 6 + 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2 \times 1)! + 0!$

• **40330**

- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! - \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 = 7 + 8! + \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! + 6 + 5 + \sqrt{4} = (3! + 2)! + 10$

• **40330:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 + (4!/3)! - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = (-6 + 5)^4 \times (3! + 2)! + 10$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = 6! + 5 \times \sqrt{4} - 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 \times \sqrt{4} - 3! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **40332**

- ▶ $12 + (3! + \sqrt{4})! = 5 - 6 + 7 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $1 \times (2^3)! + \sqrt{4! + 5!} = 6 + 7! \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! + 6 = \sqrt{5! + 4!} + (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 - 6 + 5 = 4 \times 3 + (-2 + 10)!$

• 40333

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! + \sqrt{4} + 5 + 6 = 7 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})!$$

• 40333:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7!/6! = \sqrt{5! + 4!} + (3! + 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7!/6! = 5 + 4!/3 + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 40333:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 + (4!/3)! + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! + 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 = 6 - 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 3! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 40334

• 40334:

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! - 7 + 6 \times 5 = 4 + (3! + 2)! + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! + 6 + 5 = 4 + (3! + 2)! + 10$$

• 40335

• 40335:

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7! + 6 = 5 + (-4! + 32)! + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7! + 6 = 5 + 4 + 3! + (-2 + 10)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7! + 6 = (\sqrt{5\sqrt{4}}) \times 3 + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 40336

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2^3)! + 4 + 5 + 6 = 7 + 8! + 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 + 6 = 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 40336:

- ▶ $9 + 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 + 4 + (3! + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8! + 7 = \sqrt{6!/5} + 4 + (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9 + 8! + 7 = 6! / (5 \times 4!) + (3! + 2)! + 10$
- ▶ $9 + 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3 + (-2 + 10)!$

• 40338

▶ $9 + 8! + \sqrt{76 + 5} = 4! - 3! + (-2 + 10)!$

• 40339

- ▶ $-1 + (2^3)! + 4 \times 5 = 6 + 7 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times (7! + 6) = 5 + 4! + (3! + 2)! - 10$

• 40339:

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 + 6 = 5 \times 4 + (3! + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 + 6 = 5^{\sqrt{4}} - 3! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 + 6 = 5 + 4 + (3! + 2)! + 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 + 6 = 5 + 4! + (3! + 2)! - 10$

• 40340

▶ $9 + 8 \times 7! + 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! + 21 - 0!$

• 40341

• 40341:

- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! + 6 \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + 21$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 + 6 + 5 = (4!/3)! + 21 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! + 21$
 $= (\sqrt{4^3})! + 21$

• 40342

- ▶ $9 + 8! + 7 + 6 = 5 \times 4 + (3! + 2)! + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 + \sqrt{6!/5} = (\sqrt{4^3})! + 21 + 0!$

• **40343**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2^3)! + 4! = 5!/6 + 7! \times 8 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! + \sqrt{76 + 5!} = 4! + (3! + 2)! - 1$$

• **40344**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! + 4! = 5 + 6 + 7 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! + 6 \times 5 = 4! + (3^2 - 1)!$$

• **40345**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 + \sqrt{6!/5} = 4! + (3! + 2)! + 1$$

• **40346**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 + 6 \times 5 = 4! + (3! + 2)! + 1 + 0!$$

• **40347**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! + 7 + 6 + 5 = 4! + 3 + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **40350**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7!/6 + 5) = 4! + 3! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **40352**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! - 7 + 6 \times 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! + \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **40353**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2^3)! + \sqrt{4^5} = 6 \times 7 + 8! - 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! + 7 \times 6 = 5!/4 + 3 + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **40356**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 \times 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times 3! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **40359**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 \times (7! + 6) = 5 + 4! + (3! + 2)! + 10$$

• **40362**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7! + 6) = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **40363**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 + 6 \times 5 = 43 + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 40365

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! + 45 = 6 \times 7 + 8! + \sqrt{9}$$

• 40368

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 \times 6 = 5 + 43 + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 40371

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! + 7 \times 6 = 54 - 3 + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 40374

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times (7! + 6) = 54 + (3! + 2)! \times 1$$

• 40390

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 76 = 5! / \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! + 10$$

• 40440

$$\blacktriangleright (98/7 - 6)! + 5! = (\sqrt{4^3})! + ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• 40400:

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7!/6 = 5! + (\sqrt{4} + 3 \times 2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7!/6 = 5 \times 4! + (3! + 2)! + 1 - 0!$$

• 40464

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 \times 7 + 6!/5 = 4! \times 3! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 40960

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right)^{7+6} \times 5 = 4^{3 \times 2} \times 10$$

• 41037

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! + 6! = (5 - \sqrt{4})!! - 3 + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 41038

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! + 7 + 6! = (\sqrt{5+4})!! + (3! + 2)! - 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! + 7 + 6 \times 5! + \sqrt{4} = 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **41039**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2^3)! + (\sqrt{4+5})!! = 6! - 7 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **41039:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 + 6! = (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + (3! + 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7 + 6! = (-5 + 4!) \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• **41040**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + (3! + \sqrt{4})! = 5! \times (6 + 7 \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3 \times (4! - 5) = 6! + (7 - 8 + 9)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 - 2 + 3!) \times (4! - 5) \times 6! = 7! \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! = 6! \times 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! + (2 + 1)!!$$

• **41040:**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! \times 4 \times \sqrt{5^6} + 7! = 8! + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! - \sqrt{4} - 5 + 6! + 7 = 8! + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• **41040:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)! + 6! = (-5 + 4!) \times 3!! \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)! + 6! = (5!^{\sqrt{4}} - 3!!) \times (2 \times 1 + 0!)$$

• **41040:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! = (-6 + 5!) \times 4! \times (-3! + 2!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! = 6! \times (5 - 4!) \times (-3! + 2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! = \sqrt{6! \times 5} + (4^{3!} + 2) \times 10$$

• **41040:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = (-7 + 6 + 5)! - 4! + 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 7! \times (6 - 5 + 4) + 3!! \times (21 + 0!)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 7! + (6! - 5 \times 4!) \times 3 \times 2 \times 10$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 7! + 6! \times \sqrt{5^4} \times (3 - 2 + 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 7! + 6! + (54 - 3) \times (2 + 1)!!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 7! + 6! - 5 \times (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 7! + 6 \times 5! - (4 + 3)! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 7 + 6! - 5 + (4!/3)! - 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 7 + 6! - 5 - \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! = 76 + (5 \times 4^{3!} + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$

• **41040:**

- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! + 6! + 5 + 4 = 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 + 6! + 5 \times \sqrt{4} = 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! + 6! - 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! - 7!/6! + 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **41041**

▶ $1 + (2^3)! + (\sqrt{4+5})!! = 6! + 7 + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!$

• **41041:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 + 6! + 5 = (4!/3)! + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7 + 6! + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$

• **41042**

- ▶ $9 + 8! - 7 + 6! = \sqrt{5+4}!! + (3! + 2)! + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $9 + 8! - 7 + 6 \times 5! = \sqrt{4} + 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **41043**

▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! + 6! = (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + 3 + (-2 + 10)!$

• **41044**

$$2 \blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 + 6 \times 5! = 4 + 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **41044:**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 + 6! = 5 + \left(\sqrt{4^3}\right)! + (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7 + 6! = 5 + (4!/3)! + (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• **41046**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8 \times 7! + 6 = 5 + (4!/3)! + (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• **41047**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + (3! + \sqrt{4})! + 5 + 6! = 7 + 8! + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!!$$

• **41047**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8! + 7!/6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **41047:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8! + 7 = 6! + 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8! + 7 = 6 + \left(5 - \sqrt{4}\right)!! + (3! + 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8! + 7 = 6! + 5 - 4 + 3! + (-2 + 10)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8! + 7 = 6 + (-5 + 4!) \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• **41049**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8 \times 7! + 6! = \left(5 - \sqrt{4}\right)^{3!} + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **41050**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + (8! + 7 + 6!) = 5 \times \sqrt{4} + 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **41064**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8! + (-7 + 6 + 5)! = 4! + 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **41154**

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8! + 7!/6 = (-5 + 4!)^3 \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **41472**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7! - 6!)/5 = 4!^3 \times (2 + 1)$

• **41760**

▶ $1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times (4! + 5) = 6! + 7! \times 8 + (\sqrt{9})!!$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! + 6! = (5! - 4) \times 3!!/2 \times 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! + 6 \times 5! = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **41880**

• **41880:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7!/6 = 5! \times ((-4! + 3!!)/2 + 1)$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7!/6 = 5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **42480**

▶ $(-12 + 3!!)/\sqrt{4} \times 5! = 6! \times (7 \times 8 + \sqrt{9})$

• **42480:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7) \times 6! = (5! - \sqrt{4}) \times 3!!/2 \times 1$

▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7) \times 6! = 5! \times (4! - 3!) + (-2 + 10)!$

• **43200**

▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7) \times 6! \times 5 = 4 \times 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **43926**

▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! = 6 + 5 \times (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **44640**

▶ $12 \times (3!! + 4!) \times 5 = (6 + 7 \times 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!!$

• **44640:**

▶ $(12 + 3!!)/\sqrt{4} \times 5! + 6! = 7! + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!!$

▶ $1 \times 2 \times (3!! + (4)!) \times 5 \times 6 = 7! + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!!$

• **44640:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \right) \times 6! = (5! + 4) \times 3!! / 2 \times 1 \\ &\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7 \right) \times 6! = (5! + 4) \times 3!! / 2 + 1 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• **44640:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! = (6 \times 5! + 4!) \times 3 \times 2 \times 10 \\ &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! = 6! \times \sqrt{(5! + 4) \times (32 - 1)} \\ &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! = 6! + 5! / \sqrt{4} \times 3!! + (2 + 1)!! \end{aligned}$$

• **45288**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (-8 + 7!) = (6 + 5) \times (4^{3!} + 21) + 0!$$

• **45306**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times (7! - 6) = (5 + 4) \times (-3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0!))$$

• **45351**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! + 7! = (6! + (5!)^{\sqrt{4}} - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

• **45354**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)! + 3!! / \sqrt{4} \times (5! + 6) = 7! + 8! - (\sqrt{9})! \\ &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3! + (-2 + 10)! \end{aligned}$$

• **45357**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + 3!! / \sqrt{4} \times (5! + 6) = 7! + 8! - \sqrt{9}$$

• **45357:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7! = (6! + 5!^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\ &\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7! = 6! / (5! \times \sqrt{4}) \times (3!! \times 21 - 0!) \\ &\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7! = 6 + (5 + 4) \times ((3 \times 2 + 1)! - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **45360**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3)! \times (4 + 5) = (6 - 7 + 8)! \times 9$$

• 45360:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7! + 6 &= (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3^2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)! &= (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3^2 \times 1 \\ &= (\sqrt{5+4})!! \times (3 \times 21) \end{aligned}$$

• 45360:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 7! &= (6 + 54 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!! \\ \blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times 7! &= 6! \times (5 + 4) \times (-3!/2 + 10) \end{aligned}$$

• 45363

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + 3!! / \sqrt{4} \times (5! + 6) = 7! + 8! + \sqrt{9}$$

• 45363:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! + 7! &= (6! + 5!^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! + 7! &= 6 + \sqrt{5+4} \times (3!! \times 21 - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• 45366

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3!! / \sqrt{4} \times (5! + 6) &= (7! + 8!) + (\sqrt{9})! \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7! &= 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3^2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 \times 6! &= (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3! + (-2 + 10)! \end{aligned}$$

• 45369

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! + 7 \times 6! = (5 \times 43 - 2)^{1+0!}$$

• 45369:

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9 + 8! + 7! &= ((6! + 5!) / 4 + 3)^2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + 8! + 7! &= (6^{\sqrt{5+4}} - 3)^2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + 8! + 7! &= 6! - (5!)^{\sqrt{4}} + (3!/2)^{10} \\ \blacktriangleright 9 + 8! + 7! &= 6 + (5 + (\sqrt{4}))! + 3 + (-2 + 10)! \end{aligned}$$

• **45414**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) \times (7! + 6) = (5 + 4) \times (3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0!))$$

• **45432**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7!) = (6 + 5^4) \times (3 \times 2)! / 10$$

• **45927**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} \times 7 = (6! + 5 + 4) \times 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} \times 7! / 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3^{-2+10}$$

• **46079**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8! - 7 + 6! \times 5! = 4^3 \times (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• **46080**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times \sqrt{4^5} = 6! \times 7 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{3!} \times 4! \times 5 \times 6 = 7! + 8! + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5! = 4^3 \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• **46080:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7 \times 6! = 5! \times (4! + 3!! / 2 \times 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7 \times 6! = 5! \times 4 \times 3 \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **46080:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! = 6! \times (-5 + 4 + 3) \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! = 6 \times 5! + (4 + 3)! + (-2 + 10)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! = 6 - 5 + (\sqrt{4})^{3!} \times (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• **46081**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! - 8! + 7 + 6! \times 5! = 4^3 \times (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• **46086**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7! + 6! = 5 + (\sqrt{4})^{3!} \times (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• **46655**

▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7)^6 - 5 + 4 = 3!^{(2+1)!} - 0!$

• **46656**

▶ $(12 \times 3)^{\sqrt{4+5}} = 6^{7+8-9}$

▶ $(1 + 2)!^{3 \times \sqrt{4}} = (5 + (-6 + 7)^8)^{(\sqrt{9})!}$

• **46656**

▶ $(9 - 8 - 7)^6 = (5 + 4 - 3)^{(2+1)!}$

▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6^5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{(2+1)!}$

• **46656:**

▶ $(1 + 2)!^{3!} = (4 \times 5! + 6) \times (7 + 89)$

▶ $(1 + 2)!^{3!} = 4! \times (5!/6 + 7) \times 8 \times 9$

▶ $(1 + 2)!^{3!} = 4 \times (5! + 6 \times 7) \times 8 \times 9$

• **46656:**

▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7)^6 \times (5 - 4) = 3!^{(2+1)!}$

▶ $\sqrt{9^8} \times 7 + 6! + 5 + 4 = 3!^{(2+1)!}$

• **46657**

• **46657:**

▶ $(9 - 8)^7 + 6^{(\sqrt{5+4})!} = 3!^{(2+1)!} + 0!$

▶ $\sqrt{9^8} \times 7 + 6! + 5 \times \sqrt{4} = 3!^{(2+1)!} + 0!$

• **46661**

▶ $(-9 + 8 + 7)^6 + 5 = 4 + 3!^{(2+1)!} + 0!$

• **46680**

▶ $(9 \times 8 - 7) \times 6! - 5! = 4! + 3!^{(2+1)!}$

• 46800

▶ $(1 + 2)!^{3!} + 4! + 5! = 6! \times (7 \times 8 + 9)$

• 46800:

▶ $(9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6! = 5! + 4! + 3!^{(2+1)!}$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! + 6! = 5! + 4! + 3!^{(2+1)!}$

• 47040

▶ $((1 + 2)!! + (3 + \sqrt{4})!) \times 56 = 7 \times 8! / (\sqrt{9})!$

• 47520

• 47520:

▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7! - 6!) = (5! / \sqrt{4} + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!!$

▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8) \times (7! - 6!) = \sqrt{5 + 4} \times 3!! \times (21 + 0!)$

• 48960

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times (-8 + 76) = 5! \times 4! \times (-3 + 2 \times 10)$

• 50400

▶ $1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4)! \times 5 = 6! \times 7! / (8 \times 9)$

▶ $98 / 7 \times 6! \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3 + 2)! \times 10$

• 51768

▶ $9 \times (-8 + 7! + 6 \times 5!) = 4! \times 3 \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$

▶ $9 \times (-8 + 7! + 6!) = \sqrt{5! + 4!} \times 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$

• 51840

▶ $(1 + 2)!! \times 3 \times 4! = (5 - 6 + 7)! \times 8 \times 9$

▶ $12^3 / 4 \times 5! = 6! \times (78 - (\sqrt{9})!)$

• 51840:

▶ $9 \times 8 \times (7! / 6 - 5!) = 4! \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!!$

▶ $9 \times 8 \times (7! / 6 - 5!) = (4! \times 3)^2 \times 10$

• **51840:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7! \times 6! = 5! \times 4! \times 3! \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7! \times 6! = 5! \times 432 \times 1$$

• **51840:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7 = 6! \times (5! - 4! - 3 - 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7 = 6 \times 5! \times 4 \times (-3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7 = 6! + 5! \times \sqrt{4} \times (3 + 210)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7 = -6 + 5 + 4! \times 3!! \times (2 + 1) + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7 = 6 - 5 + 4! \times 3!! \times (2 + 1) - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7 = 6 - 5 + 4! \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• **51846**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7 + 6 = 5 + 4! \times 3 \times (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• **51912**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7! + 6 \times 5!) = 4! \times 3 \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 7! + 6!) = \sqrt{5! + 4!} \times 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **52488**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} \times (7 + 6 - 5) = 4! \times 3^{(2+1)!+0!}$$

• **52920**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! - 7!)/6 = 5! \times (4! - 3) \times 21$$

• **53280**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} - 7) \times 6! = (5! + 4!) \times (3!!/2 + 10)$$

• **54720**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! - 6! = 5!^{\sqrt{4}} + (3! + 2)! \times 1$$

• **55440**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3 \times 4! + 5) = 6! \times 78 - (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 55440:

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times (3^4 - 5) + 6! = 7! \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! + (3^4 - 5) \times 6! = 7! \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

• 55440:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times (3! \times 2 - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7 \times 6! = 5! \times (4! - 3) \times (21 + 0!)$$

• 55440:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! = (6! + (5!/4)^3) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! = (6 + 5) \times 4 \times 3! \times 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! = 6!/5 + 4!^3 \times 2 \times (1 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! = 6! + (5!^{\sqrt{4}} - 3!!) \times (2 + 1 + 0!)$$

• 56160

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 - 2 + 3^4) \times 5! \times 6 = 78 \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 87) \times 6! = 5! \times 4 \times (-3 + ((2+1)! - 0!))$$

• 56880

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times 8 + 7) \times 6! = (5! \times 4 - 3!) \times ((2+1)! - 0!)$$

• 57120

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + (2+3)!) \times 4 \times 5! = 6 \times (7! + 8!/9)$$

• 57600

$$\blacktriangleright ((1+2)!!/3)^{\sqrt{4}} = (-5! + 6!) \times (7 + 89)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right) \times (7! + 6!) \times 5 = 4 \times 3!! \times 2 \times 10$$

• 58320

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times 3^4 = 5! \times (6! - 78 \times \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! \times 3^4 \times 5! = 6! \times (78 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (87 - 6) = (5! \times 4 + 3!) \times ((2+1)! - 0!)$$

• **59040**

$$\blacktriangleright 123 \times 4 \times 5! = 6! \times (-7 + 89)$$

• **59049**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 \times (8 - 7)^6)^5 = (4 - 3 + 2)^{10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9^{-8+7+6} = (5 + 4)^{3+2 \times 1}$$

• **60479**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! \times \sqrt{6!/5} = 4 \times 3!! \times 21 - 0!$$

• **60480**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 + 4)! = 5! \times 6 \times (78 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3 \times 4 - 5)! = 6! \times (78 + (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 87) \times 6 \times 5! = 4 \times 3!! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7!/6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! \times 2 \times 1$$

• **60481**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7! \times \sqrt{6!/5} = 4 \times 3!! \times 21 + 0!$$

• **61920**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 87 \times 6! = 5! \times 43 \times (2 + 10)$$

• **62640**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (4! + 5) = 6! \times (78 + 9)$$

• **62640:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 87 = (-6! + 5!/4 \times 3!!) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 87 = 6 \times (5! - 4) \times 3^2 \times 10$$

• **63360**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 23) \times 4! \times 5! = (6! + 7!) \times (8 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! \times 87 + 6) \times 5! = 4 \times 3!! \times (21 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 87 \times 6! = 5! \times 4 \times 3! \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **64800**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times 45 = 6! \times (7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **64800:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 87) \times 6! = 5!/4 \times 3!! \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 87) \times 6! = 54 \times (3 + 2)! \times 10$$

• **65520**

$$\blacktriangleright (98 - 7) \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times (3! \times 2 + 1)$$

• **65526**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + 7 \times 6! \times 5 = 4^{3!+2} - 10$$

• **66960**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 87 \right) \times 6! = (5! - 4! - 3) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• **68040**

• **68040:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7!/6 = 5! \times (4! + 3) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \right) \times 7!/6 = 54 \times 3! \times 210$$

• **69120**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2 \times 3)! \times (-4! + 5!) = 6! \times (7 + 89)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6! = 5! \times 4! \times (3 + 21)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 87) \times 6 \times 5! = 4!^3 / 2 \times 10$$

• **69840**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + 3!! \times (-4! + 5!) = 6 \times 7! + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! / 8 + 7 \right) \times 6! = 5 \times 4!^3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

• **70560**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 + 3^4) \times (5! + 6!) = 7! \times \left(8 + (\sqrt{9})! \right)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times (-3! + 21 - 0!)$$

• 70560:

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times 7! = 6! + (5! - 4!) \times 3!! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times 7! = (6 + 5 - 4)! \times (3! - 2 + 10)$$

• 71280

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3 - 4! + 5!) = 6! + 7! \times \left(8 + (\sqrt{9})! \right)$$

• 71280

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! \times 6 = (5! - 4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• 73440

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3! - 4! + 5!) = (-6! + 7!) \times (8 + 9)$$

• 73440:

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (7! - 6!) = (5! - 4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times (7! - 6!) = (5! + 4!) \times (3!! - 210)$$

• 74880

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + (2 + 3)^4) \times 5! = (6 + 7) \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 \times (7 + 6) = 5! \times 4! \times (3^{2+1} - 0!)$$

• 75600

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3) \times ((\sqrt{4} + 5))! = 6! \times 7! / (8 \times (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• 75600:

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + 7) \times 6! = 5 \times (4 + 3)! \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + 7) \times 6! = 5 \times 4! \times 3 \times 210$$

• 77040

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 87 + 6!) \times 5! = 4! \times 3210$$

• **77405**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9}+8\right)^7 - 6! = 5^{4+3} - (2+1)!!$$

• **78119**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9}+8\right)^7 - 6 = 5^{4+3} - (2+1)!$$

• **78124**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9}+8\right)^7 - 6 + 5 = 6! + 5^{4+3} - (2+1)!! - 0!$$

• **78125**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9}+8\right)^7 \times (6-5) = \left(\sqrt{4}+3\right)^{(2+1)!+0!}$$

• **78125:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9}+8\right)^{7!/6!} = 5^{4+3} \times (2-1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9}+8\right)^{7!/6!} = 5^{4+3} - 2 + 1 + 0!$$

• **78131**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9}+8\right)^7 + 6 = 5^{4+3} + (2+1)!$$

• **78845**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9}+8\right)^7 + 6! = 5^{4+3} + (2+1)!!$$

• **79200**

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8! \times (7!/6! - 5) = \sqrt{4} \times (-3!! + (-2+10)!)!$$

• **80628**

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8! \times (7!/6! - 5) = \sqrt{4} \times (-3! + (-2+10)!)!$$

• **80632**

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! - 8 - 7! + 6! \times 5! = (-4 + (3! + 2)!) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **80634**

$$\blacktriangleright -\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! - 8!/7 + 6! \times 5! = \sqrt{4} \times (-3 + (-2+10)!)!$$

• **80637**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8!/7 + 6! \times 5! = \sqrt{4} \times ((3! + 2)! - 1) - 0!$$

• **80640**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! \times \sqrt{4} = 5! \times (678 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times (3!/\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 \times 7! \times 8/\sqrt{9}$$

• **80640:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7! + 6!) = \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4 + 3}} \right)! \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7! + 6!) = 5! \times (4! - 3) \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **80640:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7! + 6 \times 5!) = \left(\sqrt{4^3} \right)! \times 2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 \right) \times (7! + 6 \times 5!) = \sqrt{4} \times (3^2 - 1)!$$

• **80643**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8!/7 + 6! \times 5! = \sqrt{4} \times ((3! + 2)! + 1) + 0!$$

• **80646**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! + (7 + 6 - 5)! = \sqrt{4} \times (3 + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **80648**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7! + 6! \times 5! = (4 + (3! + 2)!) \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **80652**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8! \right) \times (7!/6! - 5) = \sqrt{4} \times (3! + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **81360**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (-3 - 4 + 5!) = 6! \times (-7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((-\sqrt{9} + 8)! - 7 \right) \times 6! = (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• **82080**

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8-7) \times (-6+5!) = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + (-2+10)!)!$$

• **82320**

$$\triangleright 98 \times 7!/6 = 5! \times (-\sqrt{4} + 3!! - \sqrt{2^{10}})$$

• **82944**

$$\triangleright 9 \times 8 \times (7! + 6!)/5 = 4!^3 \times (2+1)!$$

• **83520**

$$\triangleright (-9-8-7+6!) \times 5! = (-4! + 3!!) \times ((2+1)! - 0)!$$

• **84960**

• **84960:**

$$\triangleright (9+8) \times 7! - 6! = (5! - \sqrt{4}) \times 3!! \times (2-1)$$

$$\triangleright (9+8) \times 7! - 6! = 5! \times (-4! + 3!! + 2 + 10)$$

• **85560**

$$\triangleright (-1-2+3!!-4) \times 5! = (6! - 7) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\triangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times (-7 + 6!) = 5! \times (-4 + 3!! - 2 - 1)$$

• **85680**

$$\triangleright ((1+2)!! - 3!) \times 4! \times 5 = 6! \times 7 \times (8+9)$$

$$\triangleright (9+8) \times 7! = 6! \times (5! - 4 + 3) \times (2-1)$$

$$\triangleright (9+8) \times 7 \times 6! = 5! \times (-4 + 3!! - 2) \times 1 \times 0!$$

• **85680:**

$$\triangleright 1 \times (2 \times 3)! \times (-\sqrt{4} + 5!) + 6! = 7! \times (8+9)$$

$$\triangleright (123-4) \times 5! \times 6 = 7! \times (8+9)$$

• **85920**

$$\triangleright (-\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5! = (-4 + 3!!) \times ((2+1)! - 0)!$$

• **86160**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5! = (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• **86280**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• **86399**

$$\blacktriangleright -(9 - 8)^7 + 6! \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! \times (2 + 1)!! - 0!$$

• **86400**

$$\blacktriangleright ((1 + 23)/4)! \times 5! = 6! + 7! \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3 + \sqrt{4})! = 5! \times 6! \times (-7 + 8)^9$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5! + \sqrt{4} = 3!! \times ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• **86400:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \right)! \times 6 \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7 \right)! \times 6 \times 5! = 4! \times 3!! / 2 \times 10$$

• **86400:**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 - 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5! + 4! = 3!! \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5! + 4 = 3!! \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• **86400:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7! + 6! = 5! \times (4 + 3!! - 2 - 1 - 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7! + 6! = 5!^{\sqrt{4}} \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

• **86401**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8)^7! + 6! \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! \times (2 + 1)!! + 0!$$

• **86402**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6! \times 5! = \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• **86404**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8 - 7 + 6! \times 5! = 4 + 3!! \times ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• **86424**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 + (7! + 6!) \times 5) = 4! + 3!! \times ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• **86520**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7! + 6! + 5! = (\sqrt{4} + 3)! \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **86640**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• **86880**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8} + 7 + 6!}}} } \right) \times 5! = (4 + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• **87240**

$$\blacktriangleright ((1 + 2)^{3!} - \sqrt{4}) \times 5! = (6! + 7) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times (7 + 6!) = 5! \times (4 + 3!! + 2 + 1)$$

• **87360**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! + (3!! + \sqrt{4}) \times 5! = (6 + 7) \times 8! / (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **89280**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5! = (4! + 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$$

• **90720**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times 3! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = (-6 \times 7! + 8!) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 + 76) \times 5! = (4! - 3!) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$$

• **90720:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! - 7! \times 6) = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! - 7! \times 6) = (5! + 4!) \times 3 \times 210$$

• **91440**

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright (1+2)!! \times (3+4+5!) &&= 6! \times (7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!) \\ &\triangleright ((-\sqrt{9}+8)! + 7) \times 6! = (5! + 4 + 3) \times (2+1)!! \end{aligned}$$

• **92160**

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8!/7! + 6! \times 5! = 4 \times 3!! \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **92160:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright (- (\sqrt{9})! + 8)^7 \times 6! = 5! \times 4! \times 32 \times 1 \\ &\triangleright (- (\sqrt{9})! + 8)^7 \times 6! = 5! \times 4^3 \times (2+10) \end{aligned}$$

• **93312**

$$\triangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8+7) \times 6^5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!^{(2+1)!}$$

• **94080**

$$\triangleright 1 \times (2^3)!/(4!) \times 56 = 7 \times 8!/ \sqrt{9}$$

• **97200**

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright (1+2) \times 3!! \times 45 = 6! \times (7+8) \times 9 \\ &\triangleright 9 \times (8+7) \times 6! = 5 \times (4!+3) \times (2+1)!! \end{aligned}$$

• **97920**

$$\triangleright (9+8) \times (7!+6!) = 5! \times 4 \times (-3!+210)$$

• **98304**

$$\triangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times (7-6))^5 = 4^{3!} \times (2+1+0)!$$

4.6 Six Digits Numbers

• **100800**

• **100800:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\triangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8)! \times 7!/6 = 5!^{\sqrt{4}} \times (3 \times 2 + 1) \\ &\triangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8)! \times 7!/6 = 5 \times (4!/3)!/2 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **100800:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9!/8 + 7! \times (6 + 5) &= (4 + 3!)^{(2+1)!-0!} \\ \blacktriangleright (9 + (8 - 7)^6)^5 &= (4 + 3!)^{(2+1)!-0!} \\ &= (4 + 3)! \times 2 \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

• **103536**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (-8 + 7 + 6!)/5 = 4! \times 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! - 0!)$$

• **103680**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3! \times 4! &= (-5! \times 6 + 7!) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright 12^3/\sqrt{4} \times 5! &= (-6! + 7!) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• **103680**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 \times (7 + 6 + 5) &= 4! \times 3!! \times (2 + 1)! \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8!/7 \times 6 &= 5! \times 4 \times 3!^{2+1} \end{aligned}$$

• **103824**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7 \right) \times 6!/5 = 4! \times 3! \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• **104976**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \times (7 + 6) \right) / 5 = (4! - 3!)^{2+1+0!}$$

• **105120**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) = 6! + (5! + 4!) \times ((3 \times 2)! + 10)$$

• **105839**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) = 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)! \times 21 - 0!$$

• **105840**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3 + 4! + 5!) &= (-6! \times 7 + 8!) \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright (12 + 3 \times 45) \times 6! &= (-7! + 8!) \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7 \right) \times 6!/5 &= (4 + 3)! \times 21 \end{aligned}$$

• **105840:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) &= \left(6! + \left(\sqrt{5\sqrt{4}} \right)! \right) \times 3! \times 21 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) &= 6! \times (-5 + 4 \times 3) \times 21 \end{aligned}$$

• **105840:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7 \times 6!) = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3!! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7 \times 6!) = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3 \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **105846**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) + 6 = 5 + (4 + 3)! \times 21 + 0!$$

• **106560**

• **106560:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) + 6! = 5! \times 4! \times (3!^2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) + 6! = 5! \times 4! \times (3!^2 \times 1 + 0!)$$

• **107520**

$$\blacktriangleright (9! + 8! \times 7) / 6 = 5 \times (4! - 3) \times 2^{10}$$

• **108000**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3! + 4!) \times 5 = (6! - 7! + 8!) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7! + 6!) = \left(5! / \sqrt{4}\right)^3 / 2 \times 1$$

• **110592**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! / (8 + 7) + 6! \times 5! = 4!^3 \times (-2 + 10)$$

• **110880**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 23) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 \times (7! + 8! / \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right) \times 7! \times (6 + 5) = (4 + 3)! \times (21 + 0!)$$

• **112896**

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (7! + 6!) / 5 = (-4! + 3!! / 2)^{1+0!}$$

• **115200**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7 \times 6! = 5! \times 4 \times 3!! / (2 + 1)$$

• **115920**

• **115920:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7! = (6! + 5!^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (3^2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7! = 6! \times (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3 + 21 - 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7! = 6! + 5! \times (-4^3 + 2^{10})$$

• **116640**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3^4 \times 5! = 6! - 7! + 8! \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **116640:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7! + 6! = 54 \times 3!! \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7! + 6! = (-5! + 4 \times 3)^2 \times 10$$

• **116929**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9!/8!})!! + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} - (2 + 1)!!$$

• **117625**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} - 2 \times (1 + 0)!$$

• **117643**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9!/8!})! + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} - (2 + 1)!$$

• **117646**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9!/8!} + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} - 2 - 1$$

• **117647**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} - 2 \times 1$$

• **117648**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7^{6!/5!} = (4 + 3)^{(2+1)!} - 0!$$

• **117648:**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3 \times 2} - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} - 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

• **117649**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3)^{(\sqrt{4+5})!} = (6 - 7 + 8)^{(\sqrt{9})!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3 \times 2} \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7^6 + 5! = (4 + 3)^{(2+1)!}$$

• **117650**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7^{6!/5!} = (4 + 3)^{(2+1)!} + 0!$$

• **117650:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3 \times 2} + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} + 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

• **117651**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} + 2 \times 1$$

• **117652**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9!/8!} + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} + 2 + 1$$

• **117654**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + 7^6 = 5 + (4 + 3)^{(2+1)!}$$

• **117655**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9!/8!!} + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} + (2 + 1)!$$

• **117673**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} + (2 \times (1 + 0!))!$$

• **117769**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)! + 7^6 = 5! + (4 + 3)^{(2+1)!}$$

• **118098**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} \times (7 + 6 + 5) = \sqrt{4} \times (3!/2)^{10}$$

• **118369**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})!! + 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} + (2 + 1)!!$$

• **118800**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7! - 6!) = \sqrt{5 + 4} \times (-3!! + (-2 + 10)!)!$$

• **120816**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7! - 6) = ((5 + \sqrt{4})! - 3!) \times (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! - 6!/5 = 4! \times (-3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!)!$$

• **120888**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7 - 65 = 4! \times (-3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!)!$$

• **120939**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!/6!) = (5 + 4)!/3 - 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7) = (6! + 5!) \times 4! \times 3! - 21$$

• **120942**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7! - 6) = (5 - \sqrt{4}) \times (-3! + (-2 + 10)!)!$$

• **120945**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times ((3! + \sqrt{4})! + 5) = 6 + (-7 + 8!) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7) + 6 = (-5 + (4!/3)!) \times (2 + 1)$$

• **120953**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7!/6! = (5 + 4)!/3 - (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• **120957**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + (2^3)!) \times \sqrt{4 + 5} = (6 - 7 + 8!) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7 + 6) = (5 + 4)!/3 - 2 - 1$$

• **120959**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -1 + (2^3)! \times (-\sqrt{4} + 5) &= 6 - 7 + 8! \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7 + 6 &= (5 + 4)! / 3 - 2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! - 6 + 5 &= (\sqrt{4^3})! \times (2 + 1) - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• **120960**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2 \times 3)! \times 4! &= (-5 + 6) \times 7! \times 8 \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright (1 + 23) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! &= (-6 + 7) \times 8! \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright (123 + 45) \times 6! &= 7! \times 8 \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5! &= (\sqrt{4^3})! \times (2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

• **120960:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9! / \sqrt{8 + 7 - 6} &= (5 + 4)! / 3 \times (2 - 1) \\ \blacktriangleright 9! / \sqrt{8 + 7 - 6} &= (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! \times (2 + 1 + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **120960:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9! / 8 + 7! \times 6 \times 5 / \sqrt{4} &= 3 \times (-2 + 10)! \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7! - 6 + 5) + 4! &= 3 \times (-2 + 10)! \end{aligned}$$

• **120960:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! / 3 \times 4 \times 5! + 6! + 7! &= 8! \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright 1 \times 23 \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6! \times 7 &= 8! \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright -1 + (\sqrt{2^3})! \times (-\sqrt{4} + 5) - 6 + 7 &= 8! \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (-3! + (4 + 5)! / 6) + 6 + 7 &= 8! \times \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

• **120960:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! &= 7! / 6 + 5! \times ((4 + 3!)^{2+1} + 0!) \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! &= 7! + 6! + (5!^{\sqrt{4}}) \times (3^2 - 1) \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! &= 7 - 6 + ((5 + 4)! - 3!) / (2 + 1) + 0! \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! &= 7 - 6 + ((5 + 4)! - 3!) / (2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

• **120960:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! = 6! + (5 + 4)! / 3 - (2 + 1)!!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! = 6 \times 5! \times 4! \times (3 \times 2 + 1)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! = 6 \times 5! \times 4 \times (32 + 10)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! = 6 + (5 + 4)! / 3 - (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! = 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4}) \times ((3! + 2)! - 1 - 0!)$

• **120962**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8! + \sqrt{-7 + 6 + 5} = \sqrt{4} + 3 \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **120963**

▶ $(1 + (2^3)!) \times (-\sqrt{4} + 5) = (-6 + 7 + 8!) \times \sqrt{9}$

• **120963:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7 - 6) = (5 + 4)! / 3 + 2 + 1$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7 - 6) = (5 + 4)! / 3 + 2 \times 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7 - 6) = 5 - \sqrt{4} + 3 \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **120964**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7 + 6 + 5 = 4 + 3 \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **120966**

• **120966:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! + 6 = (5 + 4)! / 3 + (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! + 6 = (\sqrt{5 + 4})! + 3 \times (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! + 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! \times (2 + 1) + 0!$

• **120967**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7! / 6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3 \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **120967:**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2^3)! \times (-\sqrt{4} + 5) + 6 = 7 + 8! \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (\sqrt{2^3})! \times (-\sqrt{4} + 5) + 6 = 7 + 8! \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **120967:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7 = 6 + (5 + 4)! / 3 + 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7 = 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4}) \times (3! + 2)! + 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7 = (6! + 5!) \times 4! \times 3! + (2 + 1)! + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7 = 6 + (5 + 4)! / 3 + 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 - 4 + 3 \times (-2 + 10)!$$

• **120978**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7! + 6) = (5 - \sqrt{4}) \times (3! + (-2 + 10)!)!$$

• **120981**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times ((3! + \sqrt{4})! + 5) + 6 = (7 + 8!) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7! / 6!) = (5 + 4)! / 3 + 21$$

• **120981:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7) = (6! + 5!) \times 4! \times 3! + 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7) = 6 + (5 + (4! / 3)!) \times (2 + 1)$$

• **120984**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7 + 6 - 5) = 4! + 3 \times (-2 + 10)!$$

• **121032**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7 + 65 = 4! \times (3 + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)!)$$

• **121104**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7! + 6! / 5!) = 4! \times (3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0!)!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7! + 6) = ((5! - 4) \times 3)^2 \times 1$$

• 121680

• 121680:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! + 6! = (5 + 4)!/3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! + 6! = 5! \times (-4 - 3! + 2^{10})$$

• 121800

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7!/6 = (5! + 4! \times 3!!) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• 123120

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 \times 7! + 6!) = 5! \times (\sqrt{4} + 32^{1+0!})$$

• 123480

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7!/6) = 5! \times (\sqrt{4} + 3 + 2^{10})$$

• 125280

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7!/6) = (5 + 4!) \times 3!! \times (2 + 1)!$$

• 126000

$$\blacktriangleright (1^2 + 34) \times 5 \times 6! = 7! + 8! \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + (-2 + 3!))! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6! \times 7 + 8! \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7! = 6! + (5 + 4!) \times 3!! \times (2 + 1)!$$

• 126000:

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7 \times 6! = \sqrt{5^4} \times (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7 \times 6! = 5 \times (4 + 3)! \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• 126720

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7! + 6! = 5 \times 4! \times 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• 126736

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! + 7 + 6! \times 5! = (-4 + 3!!/2)^{1+0!}$$

• **129600**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times 3!!/4 &= 5 \times 6! + 7! + 8! \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright 9!/(8 \times 7 \times 6) \times 5! &= \left((\sqrt{4} \times 3)!!/2 \right)^{1+0!} \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8+7) \times 6 \times 5! \times 4 &= (3!!/2)^{1+0!} \end{aligned}$$

• **133920**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7! - 6!) = (5! + 4!) \times (3!! + 210)$$

• **136080**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3^4 \times (5! + 6!) &= (7! + 8!) \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! - 7 \times 6! \times 5) &= (4! + 3) \times ((2+1)! + 0!)! \end{aligned}$$

• **136080:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7!) + 6! &= (5+4) \times 3!! \times 21 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7 \times 6!) &= (5+4) \times 3!! \times 21 \\ &= (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times (3! + 21) \\ &= (-5 + 4!) \times (3 \times 2)! \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

• **136080:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7!) &= (6+5-4)! \times \sqrt{3^{(2+1)!}} \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7!) &= 6! \times \sqrt{5+4} \times 3 \times 21 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7!) &= 6! + 5! \sqrt{4} + 3 \times (-2+10)! \end{aligned}$$

• **138240**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times 3! \times \sqrt{4^5} &= (6! + 7! + 8!) \times \sqrt{9} \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7! + 6 \times 5!) &= 4! \times 3!! \times (-2+10) \end{aligned}$$

• **138240:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7! + 6!) &= 5 \times 4!^3 \times 2 \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times (7! + 6!) &= 5! \times 4! \times 3! \times (-2+10) \end{aligned}$$

• **139968**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2) \times 3!^{(\sqrt{4+5})!} = 6^7 / (8 - (\sqrt{9})!)$$

• **141120**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! \times 7/6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times (3! + 21 + 0!)$$

• **144000**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9} - 8) \times (7! + 6!) \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} + 3)!^2 \times 10$$

• **145152**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! / (8 + 7) \times 6 = (5 + 4)! / (3 + 2) \times (1 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! \times 6/5 = 4 \times (3^2)! / 10$$

• **146160**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7 \times 6! \times 5 = (-4! + 3!!) \times 210$$

• **150780**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (-8 + 7! - 6) \times 5 = (-\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times 210$$

• **151198**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! \times 6 \times 5 = -\sqrt{4} + 3!! \times 210$$

• **151200**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)! \times (3+4)! \times 5 = 6 \times 7! \times (8 - \sqrt{9})$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9-8) \times 7! \times 6 \times 5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times 210$$

• **151200:**

$$\blacktriangleright (98 + 7) \times 6 \times 5! \times \sqrt{4} = 3!! \times 210$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! \times 6 \times 5 + 4! = 3!! \times 210$$

• **151200:**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! \times 6 = 5 \times (4 + 3)! \times (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! \times 6 = (5 - 4) \times 3!! \times 210$$

• **151202**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! \times 6 \times 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3!! \times 210$$

• **151224**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! \times 6 \times 5 = 4! + 3!! \times 210$$

• **151620**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! \right) \times 6 \times 5 = ((\sqrt{4}) + 3!!) \times 210$$

• **153360**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9+8!+7!} \times 6! = (\sqrt{5+4})!! \times (3+210)$$

• **157464**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} \times (-7+6+5)! = 4! \times 3^{-2+10}$$

• **158400**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \times (-7+6+5) = 4 \times (-3!! + (-2+10)!)$$

• **161256**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8! \times (-7+6+5) = 4 \times (-3! + (-2+10)!)$$

• **161268**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8!) \times (-7+6+5) = 4 \times (-3 + (-2+10)!)$$

• **161275**

$$\blacktriangleright -9! + 8! \times (7+6) - 5 = 4 \times ((3!+2)! - 1) - 0!$$

• **161277**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8! \times (-7+6+5) = 4 \times ((3!+2)! - 1) + 0!$$

• **161280**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2 \times 3)! \times \sqrt{4^5} = (6+7) \times 8! - 9!$$

• **161280:**

$$\blacktriangleright -9! + 8! \times (7+6) = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9! + 8! \times (7+6) = (5 - 4 + 3) \times (-2 + 10)!$$

• **161280:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + (7 + 6 - 5)! = 4 \times (3^2 - 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + (7 + 6 - 5)! = (4 + 3)! \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **161283**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + 8! \times (-7 + 6 + 5) = 4 \times ((3! + 2)! + 1) - 0!$$

• **161292**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8!) \times (-7 + 6 + 5) = 4 \times (3 + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **161304**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})! + 8! \right) \times (-7 + 6 + 5) = 4 \times (3! + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **164160**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \right) \times (-7 + 6 + 5) = 4 \times (3!! + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **168480**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (-3! + \sqrt{4} \times 5!) = 6! \times 78 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **172800**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-\sqrt{9} + 8 \right)! \times (7! - 6! \times 5) = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times ((2 + 1)! - 0)!)$$

• **172800**

• **172800:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{(9! + 8!)/7} \times 6! = 5! \times \sqrt{4} \times (3 \times 2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{(9! + 8!)/7} \times 6! = 5! \times 4! \times 3 \times 2 \times 10$$

• **181392**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{9} \right)! \times (-8 + 7! \times 6) = (-5! + 4! + (3^2)!)/(1 + 0!)$$

• **181440**

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3)!/\sqrt{4} = (5!/6 \times 7! - 8!) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9!/(8 - 7 + 6 - 5) = (4 + 3 + 2)!/(1 + 0!)$$

• **181440:**

▶ $9!/(8!/7! - 6) = (5 + 4)!/(3 - 2 + 1)$

▶ $9!/(8!/7! - 6) = (5 - 4) \times (3^2)!/(1 + 0!)$

• **181440:**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (-8 + 7! \times \sqrt{6!/5}) + 4! = (3^2)!/(1 + 0!)$

▶ $(9! - 8)/(7!/6! - 5) + 4 = (3^2)!/(1 + 0!)$

▶ $9!/(8 - 7 + (6 - 5)^4) = (3^2)!/(1 + 0!)$

• **181444**

▶ $(9! + 8)/(7!/6! - 5) = 4 + (3^2)!/(1 + 0!)$

• **181464**

▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8 + 7! \times \sqrt{6!/5}) = 4! + (3^2)!/(1 + 0!)$

• **181488**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8 + 7! \times 6) = (5! - 4! + (3^2)!)/(1 + 0!)$

• **186624**

▶ $(9 + 8 + 7) \times 6^5 = 4 \times 3!^{(2+1)!} = 432^{1+0!}$

• **201600**

▶ $9! - 8! \times (-7 + 6 + 5) = (\sqrt{4^3})!/2 \times 10$

• **207360**

▶ $12 \times 3!! \times 4! = (5 \times 6! + 7!) \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$

▶ $12^3 \times 4! \times 5 = (-6! + 7!) \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$

▶ $(\sqrt{9}) \times 8 \times (7! + 6! \times 5) = 4! \times 3!! \times (2 + 10)$

• **207360:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8!/7 \times 6 = 5 \times 4!^3 \times (2 + 1)$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8!/7 \times 6 = 5! \times 4! \times 3! \times (2 + 10)$

• **211680**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8! - 7! \times 6(5 + \sqrt{4}) \times 3! \times ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$$

• **211680:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! - 7!) = (6! + 5!) \times 4 \times 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! - 7!) = (6 + 5 - 4)! \times (32 + 10)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! - 7!) = 6! + \left(5!/\sqrt{4}\right)^3 - ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$$

• **216000**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3!!/4 + 5!) = (6! - 7! + 8!) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **216000:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! - 7! + 6!) = (5 \times 4 \times 3)^{2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! - 7! + 6!) = (5!/4)^3 \times (-2 + 10)$$

• **216720**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8! - 7 \times 6! \times 5 = 43 \times ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$$

• **230400**

$$\blacktriangleright (9!/(8!/7!) + 6!) \times 5 = (4 \times (3 + 2)!)^{1+0!}$$

• **235298**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right) \times 7^6 = \left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)^{3!} \times 2 \times 1$$

• **236880**

• **236880:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8! - 7! = 6! \times (5 \times (4^3 + 2) - 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8! - 7! = 6! \times (5 + 4 + 321 - 0!)$$

• **237600**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7! - 6!) = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (-3!! + (-2 + 10)!)!$$

• **241200**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! \times 6 = (-5! + (\sqrt{4^3})!) \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **241824**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8! - 7) \times 6 = -5! + 4! + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$$

• **241860**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7) \times 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times ((3! + 2)! - 10)$$

• **241878**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright ((1 \times 2^3)! - \sqrt{4} - 5) \times 6 &= (-7 + 8!) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! - 7) &= 6 \times (-5 - \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)!) \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **241884**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7! - 6) = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (-3! + (-2 + 10)!)!$$

• **241902**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7!) \times 6 = (\sqrt{5 + 4})! \times (-3 + (-2 + 10)!)!$$

• **241908**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8! + 7) \times 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times ((3! + 2)! - 1 - 0!)$$

• **241914**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + (2^3)!) \times (\sqrt{4 + 5})! = 6 \times 7! \times 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **241917**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! \times 6 = 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$$

• **241919**

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8! - 7) \times 6 + 5 = (\sqrt{4^3})! \times (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• **241919:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8! - 7 + 6 = (5 + 4)! / 3 \times 2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8! - 7 + 6 = (5 + 4)! / 3 \times 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

• **241920**

- ▶ $(1+2)! \times (3! + \sqrt{4})! = ((56/7)! + 8!) \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $((1+2)!! + 3!^4) \times 5! = 6 \times (7-8+9)!$
- ▶ $(9-8+7)! \times 6 = (5+4)!/3 \times 2 \times 1$

• **241920:**

- ▶ $(1+2)! \times ((3! + \sqrt{4})! - 5!) + 6! = 7! \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $1 \times (2^3)! \times (-4! + 5 \times 6) = 7! \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• **241920:**

- ▶ $(9-8+7)! \times 6!/5! = (\sqrt{4^3})! \times (2+1)!$
- ▶ $(9-8+7)! \times 6!/5! = \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times (-2+10)!$

• **241920:**

- ▶ $(12 \times (3+4!) + 5) \times 6! + 7! = 8! \times (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $-1 + ((2^3)! + 4 - 5) \times 6 + 7 = 8! \times (\sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $-1 + (2+3)! \times (\sqrt{4+5})! - 6 + 7 = 8! \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• **241920:**

- ▶ $(-9 + 8 \times 7!) \times 6 + 54 = 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(-9 + 87 + 6) \times 5! \times 4! = 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-9 + 8 \times 7! \times 6 + 5 + 4 = 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8! - 7) \times 6!/5! + 4! = 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! - 7!/6! + 5 + \sqrt{4} = 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8! - 7!/6) + (5 + \sqrt{4})! = 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! \times 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4})!! = 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **241920:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7! = 6 \times (-5 + 4 + (3! + 2)! + 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7! = 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times ((3! + 2)! - 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7! = 6 - (5 - \sqrt{4})! + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **241920:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! = 7!/6! - 5 - \sqrt{4} + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! = 7 - 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3! + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! = 7 - 6 - 5 + 4 + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **241922**

▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! \times 6 + 5 = \sqrt{4} + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **241923**

▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7! \times 6 = 5 - \sqrt{4} + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **241924**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! - 7 + 6 + 5 = 4 + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **241926**

▶ $(1 + (2^3)!) \times (\sqrt{4+5})! = 6 + 7! \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• **241926:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7! + 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times ((3! + 2)! + 1)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! + 8 \times 7! \times 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times ((3! + 2)! + 1)$
 $= 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! \times (2 + 1)! + 0!$

• **241927**

- ▶ $1 + (2^3)! \times (-\sqrt{4} + 5) + 6$
- ▶ $1 + (2 + 3!)! \times (\sqrt{4+5})! + 6 = 7 + 8! \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• **241927:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! + 7!/6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! + 7 = 6 + (5 + 4)!/3 \times 2 \times 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! + 7 = 6 + (5 + 4)!/3 \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! + 7 = 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3! + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 - 4 + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **241929**

▶ $9 + 8 \times 7! \times 6 = 5 + 4 + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **241932**

▶ $(9 + 8! - 7) \times 6 = (\sqrt{5 + 4})! \times ((3! + 2)! + 1 + 0!)$

• **241938**

▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8 \times 7!) \times 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3 + (-2 + 10)!)$

• **241944**

▶ $(-9 + 8! - 7) \times 6 + 5! = 4! + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **241956**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8 \times 7! + 6) = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3! + (-2 + 10)!)$

• **241962**

▶ $1 \times (2 + (3! + \sqrt{4})! + 5) \times 6 = (7 + 8!) \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• **241962:**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8! + 7) = 6 \times (5 + \sqrt{4} + (3^2 - 1)!)$
- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times (8! + 7) = 6 + (\sqrt{5 + 4})! \times (3! + (-2 + 10)!)$

• **241974**

▶ $(9 + 8 \times 7!) \times 6 = 54 + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **241980**

▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8! + 7) \times 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times ((3! + 2)! + 10)$

• **242016**

▶ $(9 + 8! + 7) \times 6 = 5! - 4! + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **242208**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7! + 6!/5!) = (-4! + 3!!)^2 / (1 + 0!)$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7! + 6) = ((5! - 4) \times 3)^2 \times (1 + 0!)$

• **242640**

▶ $(1 + 2)! \times ((3! + \sqrt{4})! + 5!) = 6! + 7! \times 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!$

• **246940:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! \times 6 = (5! + (\sqrt{4^3})!) \times (2 + 1)!$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! + 8 \times 7! \times 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **246960**

▶ $(-1 \times 2 + 345) \times 6! = 7! + 8! \times (\sqrt{9})!$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! + 7 \times 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})^3 \times (2 + 1)!!$

• **246960:**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! + 7! = (6 + 5 - 4)^3 \times (2 + 1)!!$

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8! + 7!! = (6 + 5 - 4)! + 3! \times (-2 + 10)!$

• **248832**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7! + 6!/5) = (\sqrt{4} \times 3!)^{(2+1)!-0!}$

• **259200**

▶ $(1 + 2)!! \times 3!! / \sqrt{4} = 5! \times 6! \times (-7 + 8) \times \sqrt{9}$

▶ $12 \times 3!! / 4 \times 5! = 6! \times 7! / (8 + (\sqrt{9})!)$

▶ $9 \times 8! / 7! \times 6! \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3!! / 2)^{1+0!}$

• **259200:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7! + 6 \times 5! \times 4! &= 3!!^2 / (1 + 0!) \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times 8! / 7! \times 6! \times 5! / 4! &= 3!!^2 / (1 + 0!) \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (-8! / 7! + 6! \times 5!) + 4! &= 3!!^2 / (1 + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **259224**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! / 7! + 6! \times 5!) = 4! + 3!!^2 / (1 + 0!)$$

• **262088**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 - 7! / 6 \times 5! = (4 + 3!!)^2 / (1 + 0!)$$

• **262142**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + (8! / 7!)^6 + 5 = 4^{3^2} - 1 - 0!$$

• **262143**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + (8! / 7!)^6 + 5 = 4^{3^2} - 1$$

• **262144**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2^{-3!+4!} &= (-5 - 6 + 7 + 8)^9 \\ \blacktriangleright (12/3)^{4+5} &= (-6 + 7) \times 8^{(\sqrt{9})!} \\ \blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)^{6!/5!} &= 4^{3^2} \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **262144:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -1 + (-2 + 3!)^{4+5} - 6 + 7 &= 8^{(\sqrt{9})!} \\ \blacktriangleright -1 + 2^{-3!+4!} + (-5 + 6)^7 &= 8^{(\sqrt{9})!} \end{aligned}$$

• **262144:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)^6 &= (5! / 4! + 3)^{(2+1)!} \\ \blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)^6 &= (\sqrt{5\sqrt{4}} + 3)^{(2+1)!} \end{aligned}$$

• **262145**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2^{-3!+4!} = (-5 + 6)^7 + 8^{(\sqrt{9})!}$$

• **262146**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + (8!/7!)^6 + 5 = 4^{3^2} + 1 + 0!$$

• **262147**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} + (8!/7!)^6 = 5 + 4^{3^2} - 1 - 0!$$

• **262150**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + (8!/7!)^6 = 5 + 4^{3^2} + 1$$

• **262151**

• **262151:**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (2^{3!})^{-\sqrt{4}+5} + 6 = 7 + 8^{(\sqrt{9})!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + (-2 + 3!)^{4+5} + 6 = 7 + 8^{(\sqrt{9})!}$$

• **267840**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times 3!! \times (4 + 5!) = 6 \times (7! + 8! - (\sqrt{9})!!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! + 7! - 6!) = (5! + 4) \times 3!! \times (2 + 1)$$

• **272106**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8! + 7!) \times 6 = 54 \times ((3 \times 2 + 1)! - 0!)$$

• **272160**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2^3) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! \times 6 = (7! + 8!) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! / (8!/7!) \times 6 = 54 \times (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! + 7!) = 6^5 \times (\sqrt{4} + 32 + 1) = 6! \times 54/3 \times 21$$

• **272214**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8! + 7!) \times 6 = 54 \times ((3 \times 2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **276480**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!! \times \sqrt{4^5} = 6 \times (7! + 8! + (\sqrt{9})!!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9! - 8!) / 7 \times 6 = 5! \times 4!^3 / (2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times (7! + 6 \times 5!) = 4!^3 \times 2 \times 10$$

• **277200**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8!) \times 7!/6! = (-5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3!!) \times 210$$

• **277200:**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8!) \times 7 = 6! \times (\sqrt{5^4} + 3!!/2 \times 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8!) \times 7 = 6! \times ((5! + \sqrt{4} + 3!) \times (2 + 1) + 0!)$$

• **279847**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 23^4 + 5 = 6^7 - 89$$

• **279934**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2 + 3!^{\sqrt{4}+5} = 6^7 - 8 + (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **279935**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 \times 3)^{\sqrt{4}+5} = 6^7 + 8 - 9$$

• **279936**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!^{3+4} = 5! + 6^7 - (8 - \sqrt{9})! = -5 + 6^7 + 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• **279936**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!^{8-7+6} = (\sqrt{5+4})!^{3!} \times (2+1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (8! + 7!) + 6^5 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)^{(2+1)!+0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 - 7) \times 6^5 \times 4 = 3!^{(2+1)!+0!}$$

• **279936:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})!^7 = 6! - (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + 3!^{(2+1)!+0!}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})!^7 = 6^5 \times (4 + 32) \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})!^7 = 6^5 \times 4 \times 3^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})!^7 = 6 + (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3!^{(2+1)!} - 0!)$$

• **279938**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!^{\sqrt{4}+5} = 6^7 + 8 - (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **279941**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!^{3+4} + 5 = 6^7 + 8 - \sqrt{9}$$

• **279942**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})!^7 + 6 = (5 - \sqrt{4})! \times (3!^{(2+1)!} + 0!)$$

• **279960**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 23^4 + 5! = 6^7 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **280056**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!^{3+4} + 5! = 6^7 + (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})!^7 + 6! = (5 - \sqrt{4})!! + 3!^{(2+1)!+0!}$$

• **282198**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9})! + 8! \times (7!/6!) = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (-3! + (-2 + 10)!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9})! + 8! \times 7 = (6 + 5 - 4) \times (-3! + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **282219**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8!) \times 7!/6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (-3 + (-2 + 10)!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8!) \times 7 = (6 + 5 - 4) \times (-3 + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **282234**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9}! + 8! \times 7!/6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times ((3! + 2)! - 1) + 0!$$

• **282237**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + (3+4)! \times 56 = 7 \times 8! - \sqrt{9}$$

• **282240**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^{3\sqrt{4}} + 5!) \times 6! = 7! \times 8! / (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• **282240:**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) = 6 \times 7 \times 8! / (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2+3)! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) = 6 + 7 \times 8! - (\sqrt{9})!$$
$$= 6! + 7 \times 8! - (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• **282240:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \times 7 + 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3! + 2)! \times 1 \\ &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! + 8! \times 7 + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3! + 2)! \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **282243**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 56 = 7 \times 8! + \sqrt{9}$$

• **282246**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) + 6 = 7 \times 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! \times 7! / 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times ((3! + 2)! + 1) - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• **282246:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! \times 7 = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3! + 2)! \times 1 \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! \times 7 = 6 + (5! - \sqrt{4^{3!}}) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0)! \end{aligned}$$

• **282261**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8!) \times 7! / 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3 + (-2 + 10)!) \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8!) \times 7 = (6 + 5 - 4) \times (3 + (-2 + 10)!) \end{aligned}$$

• **282282**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8!) \times 7! / 6! = (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3! + (-2 + 10)!) \\ &\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! + 8!) \times 7 = (6 + 5 - 4) \times (3! + (-2 + 10)!) \end{aligned}$$

• **282960**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2 + 3)! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5) + 6! = 7 \times 8! + (\sqrt{9})!! \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \times 7 = 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times (3! + 2)! \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **287280**

• **287280:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})!! + 8!) \times 7 = (-6 + \sqrt{5^4}) \times 3!! \times 21 \\ &\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})!! + 8!) \times 7 = (-6! + 5! \times (\sqrt{4} + 3)!) \times 21 \end{aligned}$$

• **288000**

$$\triangleright ((1+2)!!/3)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 = 6! + 7 \times (8! + (\sqrt{9})!!)$$

$$\triangleright ((\sqrt{9})!! + 8!) \times 7 + 6! = 5 \times 4 \times (3+2)!^{1+0!}$$

• **290304**

$$\triangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times 8 \times 7! \times 6/5 = 4!^3 \times 21$$

• **302400**

$$\triangleright (9!/8 + 7!) \times 6 = 5! \times 4 \times 3 \times 210$$

$$\triangleright 9 \times 8 \times 7!/6 \times 5 = \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \times 210$$

• **311040**

$$\triangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 \times 5! = (-6! + 7!) \times 8 \times 9$$

• **311040:**

$$\triangleright 9 \times 8!/7 \times 6 = (5! + 4!) \times 3!! \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\triangleright 9 \times 8!/7 \times 6 = 54 \times 3!! \times (-2 + 10)$$

• **316800**

$$\triangleright 9!/8 \times 7 - 6! = 5! \times 4! \times ((3+2)! - 10)$$

• **317520**

$$\triangleright (1+2) \times (3+4!+5!) \times 6! = (-7! + 8!) \times 9$$

$$\triangleright (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = (-6! \times 7 + 8!) \times 9$$

$$\triangleright 9!/8 \times 7!/6! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3 \times 21$$

• **317520:**

$$\triangleright 9!/8 \times 7 = (65 - \sqrt{4}) \times (3! + 2 - 1)!$$

$$\triangleright 9!/8 \times 7 = (6 + 5!) \times 4 \times 3 \times 210$$

• **322559**

$$\triangleright -1 - (2^3)! + (4+5)! = 6 - 7 - 8! + 9!$$

• **322560**

- ▶ $1 \times 2 \times 3!! \times 4 \times 56 = (6 - 7) \times 8! + 9!$
- ▶ $(9! - 8 \times 7!) \times (6 - 5) = (\sqrt{4^3})! \times (-2 + 10)$

• **322560:**

- ▶ $(9! - 8!) \times (7 - 6) = (5 + 4)! - (3! + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $(9! - 8!) \times (7 - 6) = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times (3! + 2)^{1+0!}$

• **322567**

• **322567:**

- ▶ $1 - (2^3)! + (4 + 5)! + 6 = 7 - 8! + 9!$
- ▶ $1 + 2^{3!} \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! + 6 = 7 - 8! + 9!$

• **324000**

- ▶ $9 \times (8! - 7! + 6!) = (5! / \sqrt{4} \times 3)^2 \times 10$

• **327600**

- ▶ $(1 + 2^{3!}) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 7! - 8! + 9!$
- ▶ $(-1 + 23 \times 4) \times 5 \times 6! = 6! \times 7 - 8! + 9!$

• **331776**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9} \times 8)^{-7+6+5} = 4!^{3+2-1}$

• **332640**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9} + 8) \times 7! \times 6 = (5!^{\sqrt{4}} + 3!!) \times (21 + 0!)$

• **345600**

- ▶ $(9 + 87) \times 6! \times 5 = 4! \times 3!! \times 2 \times 10$

• **345600:**

- ▶ $(9! + 8!) / 7 \times 6 = 5! \times 4 \times (3 \times 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $(9! + 8!) / 7 \times 6 = (5! - 4!) \times 3!! \times ((2 + 1)! - 0!)$

• **349920**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times (7! - 6!) = 5! \times 4 \times 3^{(2+1)!}$$

• **352800**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! - 8! + 7! \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})!/3 \times 210$$

• **352947**

• **352947:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9!/8!} \times 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9!/8!} \times 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} \times 2 \times 1 - 0!$$

• **356400**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 \times 7! - 6!) = (5 + 4) \times (-3!! + (-2 + 10)!!)$$

• **358560**

$$\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)!! \times 3! + (4 + 5)! = 6! - 7! + 8! \times 9$$

• **362808**

$$\blacktriangleright -12 \times 3! + (4 + 5)! = 6 - 78 + 9!$$

• **362817**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! - 7!/6!) = (5 + 4)! - 3 \times 21$$

• **362873**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8! - 7 = -6 \times 5 + 4! + (3^2)! - 1$$

• **362877**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + (\sqrt{3^4})! = \sqrt{5 \times 6!} + (-7 + 8!) \times 9$$

• **362879**

$$\blacktriangleright (9! - 8 + 7) \times (6 - 5) = (4 + 3 + 2)! - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + 4! = (3^2)! - 1$$

• **362880**

- ▶ $(12 \times 3/4)! = (-5 + 6)^{78} \times 9!$
- ▶ $1^{23} \times (4 + 5)! = 6! \times 7 \times 8 \times 9$
- ▶ $(12 - 3)! \times (\sqrt{4} + 5 - 6) = 7! \times 8 \times 9$

• **362880:**

- ▶ $9 \times 8! \times (7 - 6) = (54/(3 \times 2))! \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! \times (7 - 6) = (5 - 4) \times (3^2)! \times 1$

• **362880:**

- ▶ $9 \times (8 \times 7! - 6) + 54 = (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 = (3^2)! \times 1$

• **362880:**

- ▶ $-1 - 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5)! + 6 + 7 = 8! \times 9$
- ▶ $(123 \times 4 + 5) \times 6! + 7! = 8! \times 9$
- ▶ $-(1 + 2)! + (3^{\sqrt{4}})! + 5 - 6 + 7 = 8! \times 9$
- ▶ $(12 - 3)! + 4 - 5 - 6 + 7 = 8! \times 9$

• **362880:**

- ▶ $(12 - 3)! = (-4 + 5)^{678} \times 9!$
- ▶ $(12 - 3)! = 4 + 5 + (6 - 7 + 8!) \times 9$
- ▶ $(12 - 3)! = 4 - 5 - 6 + 7 + 8! \times 9$
- ▶ $(12 - 3)! = \sqrt{4} + 5 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 9!$

• 362880:

- ▶ $-(1+2)!! + (\sqrt{3^4})! + 5! \times 6 \times (-7+8) = 9!$
- ▶ $(12-3)! + 4 - \sqrt{5 \times 6!} + 7 \times 8 = 9!$
- ▶ $-1 - (2 \times 3)! + (4+5)! + 6! - 7 + 8 = 9!$
- ▶ $-1 - (2^3)! + (4+5)! - 6 + 7 + 8! = 9!$
- ▶ $-1 \times (2 \times 3)! + (4+5)! + 6! \times (-7+8) = 9!$
- ▶ $1 \times (2^3)! \times 4 + 5 \times 6! \times 7 \times 8 = 9!$
- ▶ $-1 \times (2^3)! + (4+5)! + 7! \times 8 = 9!$
- ▶ $-1 \times (2+3)! + (4+5)! + (6+7-8)! = 9!$
- ▶ $-1 \times 2^3 + (4+5)! + (-6+7) \times 8 = 9!$
- ▶ $-1 \times 2 - 3 + (4+5)! + 6 + 7 - 8 = 9!$
- ▶ $-1^2 \times 3 + (4+5)! + \sqrt{-6+7+8} = 9!$
- ▶ $-1 + (2+3+4)! + (-5+6)^{78} = 9!$
- ▶ $-12 \times 3! + (4+5)! - 6 + 78 = 9!$
- ▶ $1 - 2^3 + (4+5)! + 6 - 7 + 8 = 9!$
- ▶ $-12 + (\sqrt{3^4})! + 5 + 6 - 7 + 8 = 9!$
- ▶ $-1 - 2 + (\sqrt{3^4})! + \sqrt{(5+67)/8} = 9!$
- ▶ $-1 - 2 - 3 + (4+5)! + 6 \times (-7+8) = 9!$
- ▶ $(12-3)! - 4! + (5 - (-6+7)^8)! = 9!$
- ▶ $(12-3)! - 4 - 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 = 9!$
- ▶ $(12-3)! - \sqrt{4} - 5 + 6 - 7 + 8 = 9!$

• 362880:

- ▶ $9! = (8 + 7) \times 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3^2 \times 10$
- ▶ $9! = (-8 + 7 + 6)! - 5! + (-4 \times 3 + 21)!$
- ▶ $9! = (-8 + 7 + 6)! - 5! + (4 + 3 + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! = (8 - 7)^6 + 5 + 4 + (3^2)! - 10$
- ▶ $9! = (8 - 7 + 6)! - (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! = (8 - 7 + 6)! - (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (-3 + 2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9! = 8!/7! \times 6 + (5 + 4)! - (3! - 2)! \times (1 + 0!)$
- ▶ $9! = 8!/7! + 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3! \times 2 - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8!/7! - 6! + (5 + 4)! + 3!! + 2 - 10$
- ▶ $9! = 8!/7! - 6 + (5 + 4)! + 3! + 2 - 10$
- ▶ $9! = 8!/7! - 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3 + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8!/7! - 6 + (5 - 4) \times (3^2)! - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8!/7 \times 6 + 5! \times 4! \times (-3! + ((2 + 1)! - 0!))$
- ▶ $9! = 8!/7 - 6! - (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3! + 2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $9! = 8! + 7 - 6 + (5 + 4)! - (3! + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8! - 7! + 6! \times (-5! + (4 \times 3!)^2 - 1)$
- ▶ $9! = 8! - 7! + 65 \times 4 \times 3! \times 210$
- ▶ $9! = 8! - 7 \times 6! + (5! + \sqrt{4} \times 3!!) \times 210$
- ▶ $9! = 8! - 7 + 6 + (5 + 4)! - (3! + 2)! + 1$

• 362880:

- ▶ $9! = 8 \times (7 + 6) + (-5 + 4! \times 3!!) \times 21 + 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times (7 - 6) - (5 + 4) + (3^2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times (7 - 6) + (5 + 4)! - \sqrt{32 \times (1 + 0)!}$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7!/6! - 54 + (3^2)! - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7!/6 + 5! \times 4 \times (3!! + 21 + 0!)$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7! + (6! + 5!) \times 4! \times (-3! + 21 + 0!)$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7! + (6! + 5!) \times \sqrt{4^{3!}} \times (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7! + 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! - (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7! + 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3! - (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7! - 6! + (5 + 4)! + 3!! - (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7! - 6 + (5 + 4)! + 3! - (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7 + (6 - 5!)/\sqrt{4} + (3^2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7 + 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3 \times 21 + 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5 - 4! + (3^2)! - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7 - 6 \times 5 - 4! + (3^2)! - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times 7 - 6 - 5!/\sqrt{4} + (3^2)! + 10$
- ▶ $9! = 8 \times \sqrt{\sqrt{76 + 5} - 4!} + (3^2)! \times 1$

• 362880:

- ▶ $9! = 8 + 7!/6! + (5 + 4)! + 3! - 21$
- ▶ $9! = 8 + 7!/6! + (5 + 4)! - 3 - 2 - 10$
- ▶ $9! = 8 + 7! - 6 - (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3^2)! - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 + 7 + 6 - 5 \times 4 + (3^2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8 + 7 - 6 + (5 + 4)! + 3 - 2 - 10$
- ▶ $9! = 8 + 7 - 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3^2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7! / (6 \times 5 \times 4!) + (3^2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7 + (6 + \sqrt{5 + 4})! - 3 + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7 + (6 - 5)^4 + (3^2)! - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7 + 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! - 2 \times 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7 + 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7 + 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3 \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 - \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! - 10$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7 + 6 + \sqrt{5 + 4} + (3^2)! - 10$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7 + 6 - 5 + (4 + 3 + 2)! - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7 + 6 - 5 - \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! = 8 - 7 - 6 / \sqrt{5 + 4} + (3^2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9! = 87 - 6 + (5 + 4)! - \sqrt{3^{-2+10}}$
- ▶ $9! = 87 - 65 - 4! + (3^2)! + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $9! = \sqrt{8 + 7 - 6} - \sqrt{5 + 4} + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! = \sqrt{8 + 7 - 6} - \sqrt{5 + 4} + (-3 + 2 + 10)!$

• 362880:

- ▶ $9! \times (8 - 7) = 9 \times 8 \times 7! = 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3 \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9! \times (8 - 7) = 9 \times 8 \times 7! = 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! \times (2 - 1)$
- ▶ $9! \times (8 - 7) = 9 \times 8 \times 7! = (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 \times 2 - 1)!$
- ▶ $9! \times (8 - 7) = 9 \times 8 \times 7! = (6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! \times (8 - 7) = 9 \times 8 \times 7! = (6 + \sqrt{5 + 4})! \times (3 - 2 \times 1)$
- ▶ $9! \times (8 - 7) = 9 \times 8 \times 7! = (6 + 5 - 4)! \times 3! \times (2 + 10)$

• **362880:**

- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7! - 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! \times (2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7 + 6 - \sqrt{5! + 4!} + (3^2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7 - 6 \times 5 + 4! + (3^2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7 - 6 + (5 - 4) \times (3^2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7 - 6 + (54 / (3 \times 2))! - 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7 + 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3! \times 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7! - 6! \times (5 + \sqrt{4}) + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = (7 - 6) \times (54 / (3 \times 2))! \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = (7 - 6) \times (5 - 4) \times (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7 \times 6 + (5 + 4)! - 32 - 10$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7 + 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7 + 6 - 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! - 10$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = \sqrt{76 + 5!} - 4 + (3^2)! - 10$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7! / 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3!! - ((2 + 1)! - 0)!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7! - 6 + (5 + 4)! + 3! - ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7! + 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3! - ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7! + 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! \times (-2 + 10)$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! = 7! + 6! + 5! \times (4! + 3!!) \times 2 \times (1 + 0)!$

• **362881**

- ▶ $1^{23} + (4 + 5)! = (-6 + 7)^8 + 9!$
- ▶ $1 + (2 + 3 + 4)! = (-5 + 6)^{78} + 9!$
- ▶ $9 - 8 + (\sqrt{76 + 5})! = (4 + 3 + 2)! + 1$

• **362881:**

- ▶ $9! + 8 + 7 + 6 - 5 \times 4 = (3^2)! + 1$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} + 8! \times \sqrt{76 + 5} + 4 = (3^2)! + 1$

• **362882**

- ▶ $(12 - 3)! + \sqrt{4} = 5 \times 6 / (7 + 8) + 9!$

• **362882:**

- ▶ $9 \times (8! - 7) + 65 = \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times (8! - 7) + 65 = 4 + (3^2)! - 1 - 0!$

• **362883**

- ▶ $1 + 2 + (3 \times \sqrt{4+5})! = \sqrt{-6+7+8} + 9!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9+8!} \times \sqrt{76+5} = 4 + (3^2)! - 1$

• **362883:**

- ▶ $1 + 2 + (3^{\sqrt{4}})! = 5! + (-6 - 7 + 8!) \times 9$
- ▶ $1 + 2 + (3^{\sqrt{4}})! = \sqrt{(5+67)/8} + 9!$

• **362883:**

- ▶ $9! + \sqrt{8+7-6} = \sqrt{5+4} + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! + \sqrt{8+7-6} = \sqrt{5+4} + (-3+2+10)!$

• **362883:**

- ▶ $9 \times (8! - 7 - 6) + 5! = 4 + (3^2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9 \times (8! - 7 - 6) + 5! = \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! + 1$

• **362884**

• **362884:**

- ▶ $(12-3)! + 4 = 5 - (6-7)^8 + 9!$
- ▶ $(12-3)! + 4 = 5 + 6 - 7 + 8! \times 9$

• **362885**

- ▶ $(12 \times 3/4)! + 5 = 6 + 7 - 8 + 9!$
- ▶ $9! + 8 + 7 = 6 + 5 + 4 + (3^2)! \times 1$

• **362885:**

- ▶ $9! - 8 + 7 + 6 = (5+4)! + 3 + 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9! - 8 + 7 + 6 = 5 + (4+3+2)! \times 1$

• **362886**

- ▶ $(1+2)! + (3^{\sqrt{4}})! = 5 - 6 + 7 + 8! \times 9$
- ▶ $12 - 3! + (4+5)! = 6 + 7! \times 8 \times 9$
- ▶ $9! - 8 + \sqrt{76+5!} = 4 + (3^2)! + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8 \times 7! + 6 = (5+4)! + 3 \times 2 \times 1$

• **362887**

- ▶ $(12-3)! + (\sqrt{4}+5) = 6 - 7 + 8 + 9!$
- ▶ $(12-3)! - 4 + 5 + 6 = 7 + 8! \times 9$

• **362887:**

- ▶ $9! + 8 - 7 + 6 = (5+4)! + 3 \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8 - 7 + 6 = 5 + (4+3+2)! + 1 + 0!$

• **362887:**

- ▶ $9 \times 8! + 7 = 6! + (5+4)! - 3!! + (2+1)! + 0!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! + 7 = 6 \times 5 - 4! + (3^2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! + 7 = 6 + (5+4)! + 3 - 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! + 7 = 6 + (54/(3 \times 2))! + 1$

• **362888**

• **362888:**

- ▶ $1 \times 2^3 + (4+5)! \times (-6+7) = 8 + 9!$
- ▶ $1 - (2 \times 3)! + (4+5)! + 6! + 7 = 8 + 9!$
- ▶ $1^{23} + (-\sqrt{4}+5+6)! + 7 = 8 + 9!$

• **362888:**

- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 + (6 - 5)^4 + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 + 6!/5! - 4 + (3^2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 + 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! + 2 - 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 + 6 - 5 + (4 + 3 + 2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 + 6 - \sqrt{\sqrt{5^4}} + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 - 6 + 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = \sqrt{\sqrt{76 + 5}} + 4 + (3^2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = (7 - 6) \times 5 + 4 + (3^2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 - (6 - 5)^4 + (3^2)! + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 \times 6!/5! - 4! + (3^2)! - 10$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 \times 6 + (5 + 4)! - 32 - 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 + 6 + (5 + 4)! + 3 + 2 - 10$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 + 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! + 2 \times 1 - 0!$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7 + 6 + \sqrt{5^{\sqrt{4}}} + (3^2)! - 10$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = 7! + 6 - (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3^2)! + 1 + 0!$
- ▶ $9! + 8 = (7 - 6) \times (5 + 4)! + \sqrt{32 \times (1 + 0!)}$

• **362888:**

- ▶ $9! + 8!/7! = 6 + 5 - 4 + (3^2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8!/7! = 6 + (5 + 4)! + 3 - 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8!/7! = 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! - 2 + 10$
- ▶ $9! + 8!/7! = 6 + (5 - 4) \times (3^2)! + 1 + 0!$

• **362889**

▶ $12 - 3 + (4 + 5)! = (-6 + 7 + 8)! + 9$

• **362890**

▶ $9! - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 = (4 + 3 + 2)! + 10$

• **362890:**

- ▶ $(9! + 8) \times (7 - 6)^5 + \sqrt{4} = (3^2)! + 10$
- ▶ $-9! + 8 + 7! \times 6!/5 + \sqrt{4} = (3^2)! + 10$

• **362892**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 12 + (\sqrt{3^4})! &= 5 + 6 - 7 + 8 + 9! \\ \blacktriangleright 9! + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 &= \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• **362893**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 + 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5)! &= 6 + 7 + 8! \times 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times 8! + 7 + 6 &= \sqrt{5! + 4!} + (3^2)! + 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **362894**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8! + \sqrt{76 + 5!} = 4! + (3^2)! - 10$$

• **362894:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9! + 8! / 7! + 6 &= (5 + 4)! + 3! - 2 + 10 \\ \blacktriangleright 9! + 8! / 7! + 6 &= (5 + 4)! - 3! + 21 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

• **362895**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (12 - 3)! + 4 + 5 + 6 &= 7 + 8 + 9! \\ \blacktriangleright 9! + 8 + 7! / 6! &= (5 + 4)! - 3! + 21 = (5 + 4)! + 3 + 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

• **362895:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 9! + 8 + 7 &= 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3 + 2 + 10 \\ \blacktriangleright 9! + 8 + 7 &= 6 + 5 + 4 + (3^2)! \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9! + 8 + 7 &= 6 + 5 + 4 + (3^2)! \\ \blacktriangleright 9! + 8 + 7 &= 6 + 5 + 4 + (-3 + 2 + 10)! \end{aligned}$$

• **362901**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 + 7 + 6 = 5 \times 4 + (3^2)! + 1$$

• **362904**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (12 - 3)! + 4! &= 5! / (6 + 7 - 8) + 9! \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + (\sqrt{76 + 5!})! &= 4! + (3^2)! \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **362905**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + (-8 + 7 + 6) \times 5 = 4! + (3^2)! + 1$$

• **362906**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 = 4! + (3^2)! + 1 + 0!$$

• **362914**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! - 8 + 7 \times 6! / 5! = 4! + (3^2)! + 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! - 8 + 7 \times 6 = (5 + 4)! + 32 + 1 + 0!$$

• **362922**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8! + 7 \times 6 = (5 + 4)! + 32 + 10$$

• **362928**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8! / (7! / 6) = (5 + 4)! + (3! - 2)! \times (1 + 0!)$$

• **362934**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8 \times 7! + 6) = 54 + (3^2)! \times 1$$

• **362936**

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3)! - 4 + \sqrt{5 \times 6!} = 7 \times 8 + 9!$$

• **362936**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 \times 7! / 6! = 54 + (3^2)! + 1 + 0!$$

• **362936:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 \times 7 = \sqrt{6! \times 5} - 4 + (3^2)! \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 \times 7 = 6 \times 5 + 4! + (3^2)! + 1 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 \times 7 = 6 + 5! / \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! - 10$$

• **362942**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 \times 7 + 6 = 5! / \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! + 1 + 0!$$

• **362943**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) + (\sqrt{3^4})! + \sqrt{5 \times 6!} = (7 + 8!) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! + 7! / 6!) = (5 + 4)! + 3 \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! + 7) = 65 - \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! \times 1$$

• **362958**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3! + (4 + 5)! + 6 = 78 + 9!$$

• **362967**

• **362967:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 87 = 65 + 4! + (3^2)! - 1 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 87 = 6 + (5 + 4)! + \sqrt{3^{-2+10}}$$

• **362970**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + (8 + 7) \times 6 = (5 + 4)! + 3^2 \times 10$$

• **362984**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 \times (7 + 6) = (5 + 4! \times 3!!) \times 21 - 0!$$

• **362997**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 - 2 + (3^{\sqrt{4}})! + 5! = (6 + 7 + 8!) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! + 7 + 6) = 5! - \sqrt{4} + (3^2)! - 1$$

• **363000**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2 + 3 + 4)! + 5! = (6 + 7 - 8)! + 9!$$

• **363000:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + (-8 + 7 + 6)! = 5! + 4! \times 3!! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + (-8 + 7 + 6)! = 5! + (4 + 3 + 2)! \times 1$$

• **363592**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! - 8!/7! + 6! = (5 + 4)! + 3!! + 2 - 10$$

• **363593**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8! - 7 + 6! = (5 + 4)! + 3!! - (2 + 1)! - 0!$$

• **363599**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5)! = 6! + 7 - 8 + 9!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! - 8 + 7 + 6! = (5 + 4)! + 3!! - 2 + 1$$

• **363600**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright ((1+2) \times 3)! + (\sqrt{4+5})!! = 5! \times 6 \times (-7+8) + 9! \\ &\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! + (\sqrt{3^4})! = 6! \times (-7+8^{\sqrt{9}}) \\ &\blacktriangleright 9! \times (8-7) + 6! = (5+4)! - 3!! \times (-2+1) \end{aligned}$$

• **363601**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)! + (4+5)! = 6! - 7 + 8 + 9! \\ &\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 - 7 + 6! = (5+4)! + 3!! + 2 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **363607**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8! + 7 + 6! = (5+4)! + 3!! + (2+1)! + 0!$$

• **363608**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8!/7! + 6! = (5+4)! + 3!! - 2 + 10$$

• **363720**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8! + 7!/6 = (5+4)! + 3!! + ((2+1)! - 0)!$$

• **367918**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! - 8 + 7! + 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3^2)! - 1 - 0!$$

• **367920**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2 \times 3)! + (4+5)! = 6! \times 7 + 8! \times 9$$

• **367920:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times 3! + (4+5)! + 6! = 7! + 8! \times 9 \\ &\blacktriangleright (-1+2+3)^{-\sqrt{4+5}} \times 6! = 7! + 8! \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

• **367920:**

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright 9! + (8-7+6)! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3 + (2+1)!)! \\ &\blacktriangleright 9! + (8-7+6)! = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (-3+2+10)! \end{aligned}$$

• **367920:**

- ▶ $9 \times 8! + 7! = (6 + 5!) \times 4 \times ((3 \times 2)! + 10)$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! + 7! = 6! \times (5 + \sqrt{4}) + (3^2)! \times 1$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! + 7! = 6! + (5 + 4)! + 3! \times (2 + 1)!!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! + 7! = 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$
- ▶ $9 \times 8! + 7! = 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$

• **367926**

▶ $9 \times 8! + 7! + 6 = (5 + 4)! + 3! + ((2 + 1)! + 0)!$

• **367928**

▶ $9! + 8 + 7! = 6 + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3^2)! + 1 + 0!$

• **368640**

▶ $9 \times 8! + 7! + 6! = 5 \times 4! \times 3 \times 2^{10}$

• **368640:**

- ▶ $9! + 8!/7 = 6! + (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3! + 2 + 1)!$
- ▶ $9! + 8!/7 = 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2^{10}$

• **369360**

▶ $9! + 8!/7 + 6! = (5 + 4) \times (3!! + (-2 + 10)!)!$

• **371293**

▶ $(12 - 3 + 4)^5 = (6 + 7)^{8 - \sqrt{9}}$

• **373248**

- ▶ $(12 \times 3!)^{\sqrt{4+5}} = (-6 + 78)^{\sqrt{9}}$
- ▶ $(9 \times 8)^{\sqrt{\sqrt{76+5}}} = (4! \times 3)^{2+1}$

• **380160**

▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8!/7 \times (6 + 5) = 4! \times 3!! \times (21 + 0)!$

• **385200**

▶ $(-1 + 23) \times 4! \times 5! \times 6 + 7! = 8! + 9!$

• **388800**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times 3!! \times 45 = (-6! + 7!) / 8 \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• **388800:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 \times (7! - 6!) = 5!^{\sqrt{4}} \times 3^{2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! / 8 \times (7! - 6!) = 54 \times (3 \times 2)! \times 10$$

• **390625**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + (-2 + 3!))!^4 = 5^{(-6+78)/9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} - 8)^{7+6-5} = (\sqrt{4} + 3)^{-2+10}$$

• **393120**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8! + 7! \times 6 = (5 + 4)! + 3! \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **401760**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8! = 7 \times 6! - (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3! + 2)! \times 10$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! + 7! - 6!) = (-5! - 4! + (3! + 2)!) \times 10$$

• **402960**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 \times (7! - 6 \times 5) = (-4! + (3! + 2)!) \times 10$$

• **403160**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 \times (7 \times 6! - 5) = (-4 + (3! + 2)!) \times 10$$

• **403199**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + 2 \times (3! + \sqrt{4})! \times 5 = 6 - 7 + 8! + 9!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + (8! - 7 + 6) = (5 + 4)! + (3! + 2)! - 1$$

• **403200**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! + (4 + 5)! = 6! \times 7 \times 8 + 9!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! / \sqrt{4} \times 5! / 6 = 7! \times 8 + 9!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -1 + (\sqrt{2^3})! + (4 + 5)! - 6 + 7 = 8! + 9!$$

$$\blacktriangleright -9! + 8! \times (7 + \sqrt{6!/5}) = (4 + 3!) \times (-2 + 10)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9! - 8! \times 7) \times (6 - 5 + 4) = (3! + 2)! \times 10$$

• **403200:**

- ▶ $9! + 8! = 7 \times 6! + (5^4 + 3!)^2 - 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8! = 7! + (6 + 5^4)^{\sqrt{3!-2}} - 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8! = 7 - 6 + 5 \times \sqrt{4} \times (3! + 2)! - 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8! = (7 - 6) \times 5 \times (4!/3)! \times 2 \times 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8! = (-7 + 6 + 5)! - 4! + (3! + 2)! \times 10$
- ▶ $9! + 8! = 7!/6! - (5 + \sqrt{4}) + (3! + 2)! \times 10$
- ▶ $9! + 8! = 7!/6! - 5 - \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! \times 10$
- ▶ $9! + 8! = 7! + (-6 + 5!) \times 4 + (3! + 2)! \times 10$
- ▶ $9! + 8! = 7 - (6 + 5 - 4) + (3! + 2)! \times 10$
- ▶ $9! + 8! = (7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 - 3 + 2)! \times 10$

• **403200:**

- ▶ $9! + 8 \times 7! = 6! \times (5 + \sqrt{4})! / (3! + 2 + 1)$
- ▶ $9! + 8 \times 7! = 6! + (5 + 4)! - 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$
- ▶ $9! + 8 \times 7! = 6 \times 5 \times 4^3 \times 210$
- ▶ $9! + 8 \times 7! = 6 + (5 + 4)! - 3! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **403204**

▶ $9! + 8! - 7 + 6 + 5 = 4 + (3! + 2)! \times 10$

• **403206**

▶ $9! + 8 \times 7! + 6 = (5 + 4)! + 3! + (-2 + 10)!$

• **403207**

▶ $1 + (2^3)! + (4 + 5)! + 6 = 7 + 8! + 9!$
▶ $9! + 8! + 7!/6! = 5 + \sqrt{4} + (3! + 2)! \times 10$

• **403207:**

- ▶ $9! + 8! + 7 = 6 + (5 + 4)! + (3! + 2)! + 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 \times (4!/3)! \times 2 + 1$
- ▶ $9! + 8! + 7 = 6 + 5 - 4 + (3! + 2)! \times 10$

• **403224**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8! + (-7 + 6 + 5)! = 4! + (3! + 2)! \times 10$$

• **403240**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8! + 7! / (6 + 5!) = (4 + (3! + 2)!) \times 10$$

• **403440**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 \times (7! + 6 \times 5) = (4! + (3! + 2)!) \times 10$$

• **403920**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8 \times 7! + 6! = (5 + 4)! + 3!! + (-2 + 10)!$$

• **408240**

$$\blacktriangleright (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4 + 5) \times 6! = (7! + 8!) \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! + 7 \times 6!) = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + (3! + 2)! \times 10$$

• **408240:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! + 7!) = (6! + 5!^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 3^{2+1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times (8! + 7!) = 6 \times 54 \times 3! \times 210$$

• **414720**

$$\blacktriangleright 12^3 \times \sqrt{4} \times 5! = (6! + 7!) \times 8 \times 9$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (7! + 6 \times 5!) = 4! \times 3!! \times (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• **414720:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (7! + 6!) = (-5! - 4! + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9 \times 8 \times (7! + 6!) = (5! + 4!) \times 3!! \times (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• **423360**

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (7! - 6!) = (5 + 4)! / 3! \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **433440**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3!! + \sqrt{4} - 5!) = 6 \times 7! + 8! + 9!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8! + 7! \times 6 = (-5! + \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• **437760**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8 \times 76 = (-5 + 4!) \times 3!! \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **448560**

$$\blacktriangleright -(1 + 2)!! - 3!! \times (-4! + 5! - 6!) = 7! \times 89$$

• **449280**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3!! + 4! - 5!) = 6! + 7! \times 89$$

• **453600**

$$\blacktriangleright (12 + 3) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5)! \times 6 = 7!/8 \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (12 - 3)!/4 \times 5 = 6! \times 7/8 \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• **453600**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 \times 7 \times 6! = 5!/4 \times 3!! \times 21$$

• **453600:**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 \times 7! = 6! \times (5^4 + 3 + 2 \times 1)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 \times 7! = 6 \times (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times (3 + 2 + 10)$$

• **454320**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!!/8 \times 7! + 6! = (5^4 + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• **466560**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}} \times (7! + 6!) = 5 \times \sqrt{4} \times 3!^{(2+1)!}$$

• **468750**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8)^7 \times 6 = 5^{4+3} \times (2 + 1)!$$

• **478080**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (-8 \times 7 + 6!) = (\sqrt{5 + 4})!! \times 3!! - (-2 + 10)!$$

• **483840**

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3!/\sqrt{4} + 5)! = 6 \times (-7 \times 8! + 9!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 12 \times (3! + \sqrt{4})! = (5 + 6 - 7) \times 8! \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9!/((8 + 7) \times 6) \times 5! = (\sqrt{4^3})! \times (2 + 10)$$

• **483840:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9! - 8! \times 7) \times 6 = (5! - 4!) \times (3 \times 2 + 1)!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9! - 8! \times 7) \times 6 = (5 + 4)! / 3 \times (2 + 1 + 0)!$$

• **491520**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8 - 7)^6 \times 5! = (4^{3!} \times ((2 + 1)! - 0)!)$$

• **493920**

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7! = (-6 \times 5 - 4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times 7 \times 6! = 5! \times (4^{3!} + 21 - 0!)$$

• **501264**

$$\blacktriangleright (-12 + 3!!)^{\sqrt{4}} = (-5 + 6! - 7)^{8 - (\sqrt{9})!}$$

• **512640**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! - 8! / 7! \right) \times 6! = \left(5 - \sqrt{4} \right)!! \times (3!! + 2 - 10)$$

• **513360**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9! / 8!!!} \times (-7 + 6!) = \left(-5 - \sqrt{4} + 3!! \right) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• **514080**

• **514800:**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times \left(3!! - \left(\sqrt{4 + 5} \right)! \right) = 6 \times 7! \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times \left(\left(3 \times \sqrt{4} \right)! - 5 \right) = (6 + 7) \times \left(8! - \left(\sqrt{9} \right)!! \right)$$

• **514800:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7! \times 6 = (5! - 4! + 3!) \times ((2 + 1)! + 0)!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 + 8) \times 7! \times 6 = \left(\sqrt{5 + 4} \right)!! \times (3!! - (2 + 1)!)$$

• **514800:**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right)!! + 8! \right) \times (7 + 6) = \left(-5! / 4! + 3!! \right) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right)!! + 8! \right) \times (7 + 6) = \left(-5 + \left(\sqrt{4} \times 3 \right)! \right) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• **515520**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times (3!!-4) &= 5! \times (-6!+7!-8 \times \sqrt{9}) \\ \blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} \times 8+7!-6!) \times 5! &= (-4+3!!) \times (2+1)!! \end{aligned}$$

• **515524**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times (2-3!!)^{\sqrt{4}} &= (5+6!-7)^{8-(\sqrt{9})!} \\ \blacktriangleright ((9-8) \times 7-6!-5)^{\sqrt{4}} &= (3!!-2)^{1+0!} \end{aligned}$$

• **516960**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})!! \times (-7+6!+5) = (-\sqrt{4}+3!!) \times (2+1)!!$$

• **517680**

$$\begin{aligned} &: -(1+2)!!+3!!^{\sqrt{4}} = 5! \times (6!+7-8) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\ \blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!!-8+7 \right) \times 6 \times 5! &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times ((2+1)!!-0!) \\ \blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!!-8+7 \right) \times 6 \times \left(\sqrt{5!^{\sqrt{4}}} \right) &= 3!! \times ((2+1)!!-0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **517680:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!!-8+7 \right) \times 6! &= (\sqrt{5+4})!! \times 3!! - (2+1)!! \\ \blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!!-8+7 \right) \times 6! &= 5! \times \sqrt{4} \times 3 \times ((2+1)!!-0!) \end{aligned}$$

• **518390**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!-8+(7!-6!) \times 5!+4 = 3!!^2-10$$

• **518394**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -(1+2)!+3!!^{\sqrt{4}} &= (5! \times 6!+7-8) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! \times (-8+7+6! \times 5!) &= 4+3!!^2-10 \end{aligned}$$

• **518398**

$$\blacktriangleright -1 \times 2+3!!^{\sqrt{4}} = 5! \times (-6!+7!)-8+(\sqrt{9})!$$

• **518399**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1-2+3!!^{\sqrt{4}} &= 5! \times (-6!+7!)+8-9 \\ \blacktriangleright -9+8+(7!-6!) \times 5! &= (\sqrt{4} \times 3)!^2-1 \end{aligned}$$

• **518399:**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5 \times 4! = 3!!^2 - 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} - 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5! + 4 = 3!!^2 - 1$$

• **518400**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2 + 3)! \times (\sqrt{4 + 5})!! = 6!^{7-8+\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2 \times 3)!^{\sqrt{4}} = 5! \times 6 \times (7 + 8 - 9)!$$

• **518400:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9!}/8!!! \times (-7 + 6!) + (5 + \sqrt{4})! = 3!!^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} \times 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5! + 4! = 3!!^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (7! - 6!) \times 5 \times 4! = 3!!^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5! + \sqrt{4} = 3!!^2 \times 1$$

• **518400:**

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times 6! = (5 + 4 - 3)! \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (-9 + 8 + 7)! \times 6! = 5! \times 432 \times 10$$

• **518400:**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3!! = 4! \times 5 \times 6! \times (7 + 8 - 9)$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3!! = 4! + 5! \times (-6! + 7!) - 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3!! = (\sqrt{4 + 5})!! + (6! + 7 - 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• **518400:**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (7! - 6!) \times 5! = (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (7! - 6!) \times 5! = (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)!^2 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (7! - 6!) \times 5! = (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! \times 5! = \sqrt{4} + 3!!^2 - 1 - 0!$$

• **518401**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 + (2 \times 3)!^{\sqrt{4}} &= 5! \times (-6! + 7!) - 8 + 9 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5! &= \sqrt{4} + 3!!^2 - 1 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)!^2 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **518401:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright - \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + (7! - 6!) \times 5! + 4 &= 3!!^2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5! + \sqrt{4} &= 3!!^2 + 1 \\ \blacktriangleright 9 - 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5 \times 4! &= 3!!^2 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **518402**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 + 3!!^{\sqrt{4}} &= 5! \times (-6! + 7!) + 8 - (\sqrt{9})! \\ \blacktriangleright - (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5! &= \sqrt{4} + 3!!^2 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

• **518402:**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (9 - 8) \times (7! - 6!) \times 5! + \sqrt{4} &= 3!!^2 + 1 + 0! \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5! + 4 &= 3!!^2 + 1 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

• **518403**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right) + (7! - 6!) \times 5! = 4 + 3!!^2 - 1$$

• **518405**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5! = 4 + 3!!^2 + 1$$

• **518406**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)! + 3!!^{\sqrt{4}} = (5! \times 6! - 7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

• **518406**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{9^8}}} \right)! + (7! - 6!) \times 5! = -4 + 3!!^2 + 10$$

• 518414

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5! = 4 + 3!!^2 + 10$$

• 518424

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3!! + 4! = 5! \times (-6! + 7!) + 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8 + (7! - 6!) \times 5! = 4! + 3!!^2 \times 1$$

• 519120

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times 3!!^{\sqrt{4}} = 5! \times (6! - 7 + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5! \times \sqrt{4} = 3!! \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 - 7) \times 6 \times 5! = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times ((2 + 1)!! + 0!)$$

• 519120:

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 - 7 + 6!) = (\sqrt{5 + 4})!! \times 3!! + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 - 7 + 6!) = (\sqrt{5 + 4})!! + 3!!^2 + 1 - 0!$$

• 519840

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})!! \times (7 + 6! - 5) = (\sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• 521280

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3!! + 4) = (5 + 6! + 7 - 8) \times (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 521280

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (-8 + 7 + 6! + 5) = (4 + 3!!) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

• 521284

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2 + 3!!)^{\sqrt{4}} = (-5 + 6! + 7)^{8 - (\sqrt{9})!}$$

• 521284

$$\blacktriangleright ((\sqrt{9})! - 8 - 7!/6 + 5!)^{\sqrt{4}} = (3!! + 2)^{1 + 0!}$$

• 523440

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2)!! \times (3!! + \sqrt{4} + 5) = (6 + 7) \times 8! - (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 523440

• 523440:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \times (7+6) = (5 + \sqrt{4})! + 3!!^2 \times 1 \\ &\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \times (7+6) = (5 + \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \times (2+1)!! \end{aligned}$$

• 524151

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8! \times (7+6) = (-5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} \times ((2+1)!! - 0!)$$

• 524160

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8!/7! + 6!) = (5 + 4!/3) \times (-2 + 10)!$$

• 524166

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! + 8! \times (7 + 6!/5!) = (4 + 3!!)^2 - 10$$

• 524174

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! \times (7+6) + 5 = (4 + 3!!)^2 - 1 - 0!$$

• 524288

$$\blacktriangleright \left(-(\sqrt{9})! + 8\right)^{7+\sqrt{6!/5}} = \sqrt{4^{\sqrt{3!!/2+1}}} = \sqrt{4^{3^2+10}}$$

• 524289

$$\blacktriangleright 9 + 8! \times (7+6) + 5! = \sqrt{4^{\sqrt{3!!/2+1}}} + 0!$$

• 524880

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)^{3!} \times (\sqrt{4+5})!! = (6+7) \times 8! + (\sqrt{9})!!$$

• 524880:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \times (7+6) = (\sqrt{5+4})!! \times 3^{(2+1)!} \\ &\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! + 8! \times (7+6) = \sqrt{(5+4)^{3!}} \times (2+1)!! \end{aligned}$$

• 529200

• 529200:

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7\right) \times 6! = 5 \times (4+3)! \times 21 \\ &\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8 + 7\right) \times 6! = 5! \times (4! - 3) \times 210 \end{aligned}$$

• **531441**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (12-3)^{(\sqrt{4+5})!} &= (-6+7+8)^{(\sqrt{9})!} \\ \blacktriangleright (9 \times (8-7))^6 &= (5+4)^{3 \times 2} \times 1 \\ \blacktriangleright \sqrt{9^8} \times (76+5) &= (4!+3)^{2+1+0!} \\ \blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})^{-8-7+\sqrt{6!+5+4}} &= 3^{2+10} \end{aligned}$$

• **535680**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times (3!!+4!) &= 5 \times (-6!+7!) \times 8+9! \\ \blacktriangleright 9!+8!/7 \times 6 \times 5 &= (4!+3!!) \times (2+1)!! \end{aligned}$$

• **535824**

$$\blacktriangleright (12+3!!)^{\sqrt{4}} = (5+6!+7)^{8-(\sqrt{9})!}$$

• **552960**

$$\blacktriangleright \left((\sqrt{9})!! + 8! + 7! \right) \times \sqrt{6!/5} = 4! \times 3!! \times \sqrt{2^{10}}$$

• **558720**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times (8 \times 7 + 6!) = (\sqrt{5+4})!! \times 3!! + (-2+10)!$$

• **559872**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright 1 \times 2 \times 3!^{\sqrt{4+5}} &= 6^7 \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!) \\ \blacktriangleright 9 \times 8!/7! \times 6^5 &= \sqrt{4} \times 3!^{(2+1)!+0!} \end{aligned}$$

• **564480**

$$\blacktriangleright 98 \times (7!+6!) = (5+\sqrt{4}) \times (3!+2)! \times (1+0!)$$

• **574560**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + (8! - 7!) \times = (5! - \sqrt{4} \times 3) \times ((2+1)! + 0)!$$

• **588245**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8) \times 7^6 = 5 \times (4+3)^{(2+1)!}$$

• **589680**

$$\blacktriangleright 9!/8 \times (7+6) = (5+\sqrt{4})! \times (-3 + ((2+1)! - 0)!)!$$

• **604080**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright -(1+2)! + (3+4)! \times 5! &= (-6+7!) \times (8-\sqrt{9})! \\ \blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9}+8)! \times (7! - 6) &= 5! \times ((4+3)! - (2+1)!) \end{aligned}$$

• **604800**

- ▶ $1^2 \times (3+4)! \times 5! = 6! \times 7 \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7 \times 6! \times 5 = 4 \times 3!! \times 210$

• **604800:**

- ▶ $-(1+2)! + (3+4)! \times 5! + 6 = 7! \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $1 \times (2^3)! \times (4+5+6) = 7! \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$

• **604800:**

- ▶ $9! + 8 \times 7! \times 6 = 5 \times (4!/3)! \times (2+1)$
- ▶ $9! + 8 \times 7! \times 6 = 5 \times 4! \times (3 \times 2 + 1)!$

• **604800:**

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 7! = 6! \times 5! \times (4+3) \times (2-1)$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 7! = 6! \times 5 \times 4!/3 \times 21$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 7! = 6 + 5! \times (4+3)! - (2+1)!$

• **604806**

- ▶ $(1+2)! + (3+4)! \times 5! = 6 + 7! \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$
- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times 7! + 6 = 5! \times (4+3)! + (2+1)!$

• **605520**

- ▶ $(1+2)!! + (3+4)! \times 5! = 6! + 7! \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$

• **605520**

- ▶ $(-\sqrt{9} + 8)! \times (7! + 6) = 5! \times ((4+3)! + (2+1)!)$

• **635040**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times (8! - 7!) \times 6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})! \times 3! \times 21$

• **645120**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! / 45 \times 6! = 7 \times 8! + 9!$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8! \times 7! / 6! = (5! + \sqrt{4^3}) \times ((2+1)! + 0)!$$

• **645120:**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8! \times 7 = (6! + 5!) \times 4! \times 32 \times 1$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8! \times 7 = (6 + 5!) \times \sqrt{4^{3^2}} \times 10$$

• **691200**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! / 3 \times 4! \times 5! = (6! + 7!) \times (8 - \sqrt{9})!$$

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})!! \times 8! / (7 \times 6) = 5! \times 4 \times 3!! \times 2 \times 1$$

• **695520**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} \times 8! - 7!) \times 6 = (5! + 4! - 3!) \times ((2+1)! + 0)!$$

• **705894**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9!/8!})! \times 7^6 = (5 + \sqrt{4})^{3!} \times (2+1)!$$

• **710640**

$$\blacktriangleright 987 \times 6! = (5! + 4! - 3) \times ((2+1)! + 0)!$$

• **725712**

$$\blacktriangleright -(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5 = (-4! + (3^2)!) \times (1+0)!$$

• **725752**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! - 8 + (\sqrt{76+5})! = (-4 + (3^2)!) \times (1+0)!$$

• **725757**

$$\blacktriangleright -\sqrt{9} + 8! \times (7+6+5) = \sqrt{4} \times ((3^2)! - 1) - 0!$$

• **725758**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5 = \sqrt{4} \times ((3^2)! - 1)$$

• **725759**

$$\blacktriangleright -9 + 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3^2)! - 1$$

• **725760**

- ▶ $(12 - 3)! \times \sqrt{4} = ((5 + 67)/8)! + 9!$
- ▶ $(12 - 3)! + (4 + 5)! = 6 \times 7! \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$
- ▶ $9! + 8! \times \sqrt{76 + 5} = \sqrt{4} \times (3^2)! \times 1 = 4 \times (3^2)! / (1 + 0!)$

• **725760:**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! \times 6 = (5 + 4)! \times (3 - 2 + 1)$
- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 \times 7! \times 6 = (5 - 4) \times (3^2)! \times (1 + 0!)$

• **725760:**

- ▶ $9! \times (8 - 7 + (6 - 5)^4) = (3^2)! \times (1 + 0!)$
- ▶ $-\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5 + 4! = (3^2)! \times (1 + 0!)$

• **725761**

- ▶ $9 - 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5 = \sqrt{4} \times (3^2)! + 1$

• **725762**

- ▶ $-(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5 = \sqrt{4} \times ((3^2)! + 1)$

• **725763**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} + 8! \times (7 + 6 + 5) = \sqrt{4} \times ((3^2)! + 1) + 0!$

• **725768**

- ▶ $9! + 8 + (\sqrt{76 + 5})! = (4 + (3^2)!) \times (1 + 0!)$

• **725784**

- ▶ $\sqrt{9} \times 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5 = 4! + (3^2)! \times (1 + 0!)$

• **725808**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})! \times 8 + 7! \times 6! / 5 = (4! + (3^2)!) \times (1 + 0!)$

• **737280**

- ▶ $(\sqrt{9})!! \times 8! / 7! \times (6 + 5! + \sqrt{4}) = 3!! \times 2^{10}$
- ▶ $9! + 8! / 7 \times 65 = (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times 2^{10}$

• **756000**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! + 7! \times 6 = 5 \times (\sqrt{4} \times 3)! \times 210$$

• **806400**

$$\blacktriangleright (9 - 8 + 7)! / 6 \times 5! = \sqrt{4} \times (3! + 2)! \times 10$$

• **816480**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times (8! + 7!) \times 6 = 54 \times 3!! \times 21$$

• **846720**

$$\blacktriangleright (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)! \times 56 = 7 \times 8! \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **846720:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! \times 7! / 6! = \left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^4 + 3}} \right)! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! \times 7! / 6! = (5 + 4)! / 3 \times ((2 + 1)! + 0!)$$

• **846720:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! \times 7 = (6 - 5) \times (\sqrt{4^3})! \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! \times 7 = 6! \times (5! - 4^3) \times 21$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! \times 7 = 6 - 5 + (4! / 3)! \times 21 - 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! \times 7 = 6 - 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! \times 21 - 0!$$

• **846726**

• **846726:**

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! \times 7 + 6 = 5 + (\sqrt{4^3})! \times 21 + 0!$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! \times 7 + 6 = 5 + (4! / 3)! \times 21 + 0!$$

• **887040**

$$\blacktriangleright (9! - 8! \times 7) \times (6 + 5) = (\sqrt{4^3})! \times (21 + 0!)$$

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + 8! \times (7 + 6) = (\sqrt{5^4 - 3}) \times (-2 + 10)!$$

• **933120**

$$\blacktriangleright (1+2)!! \times 3!^4 = 5! \times 6! + 7 \times 8! \times \sqrt{9}$$

• **950400**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8!/7!) \times 6! \times 5! = 4! \times (-3!! + (-2+10)!)$$

• **967440**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + (-8 + 7! + 6) \times 5! = 4! \times ((3! + 2)! - 10)$$

• **967536**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8!) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! = 4! \times (-3! + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **967608**

$$\blacktriangleright (-\sqrt{9} + 8!) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! = 4! \times (-3 + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **967680**

$$\blacktriangleright 1 \times (2^3)! \times 4! = (56/7)! \times 8 \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \sqrt{9} \times 8! \times (7 + 6 - 5) = 4! \times (3^2 - 1)!$$

• **967752**

$$\blacktriangleright (\sqrt{9} + 8!) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! = 4! \times (3 + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **967824**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)! + 8!\right) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! = 4! \times (3! + (-2 + 10)!)$$

• **967920**

$$\blacktriangleright 9! + (8 + 7! - 6) \times 5! = 4! \times ((3! + 2)! + 10)$$

• **984960**

$$\blacktriangleright \left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!! + 8!\right) \times (-7 + 6 + 5)! = 4! \times (3!! + (-2 + 10)!)$$

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